

**PATTERNS OF KNOWING IN WOUND MANAGEMENT AMONGST SPECIALIST
AND GENERALIST NURSES: A REFLEXIVE THEMATIC ANALYSIS**

LYNN ANNE WELSH

**Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the University of
the West of Scotland for the award of Professional Doctorate in Nursing**

December 2021

Acknowledgements

The work for this study was completed throughout the period between 2016 and 2021; years that proved to be extremely trying professionally and personally. During this time, I moved jobs, lost my mother and mother-in-law within a period of one month and like the rest of the world, experienced living through a pandemic for the first time. A number of people deserve thanks for helping through the process of completion for what has proven to be an enormously challenging piece of work for me. I couldn't have done it without any of them.

I wish to thank my lead academic supervisor Dr Joanne Lusher for her ongoing support, knowledge, expertise and exceptional feedback and feed-forward along the way. This was most appreciated during the many times I felt I had lost my way and needed guidance for getting back on track. Your talent for seeing potential structure and clarity in the drafts when all I could see was chaos was exactly what I needed and your belief in the study during the times when I felt like giving up kept me moving forward. Thanks for reining me in and for not giving me too hard a time for going astray in the first place. I also wish to thank Professors Moira Lewitt and Jean Rankin for their professional and academic expertise and valued support during the correction stage.

Without professional and financial support from my then employer UWS, I would have struggled to fund my study and I am most grateful for both their generosity and their belief in me. I wish to thank my line manager and a number of my colleagues in higher education, healthcare and industry; who did everything they could to support me: from granting study leave, to providing invaluable literature and information, to simply listening to gripes about my latest hurdle.

Thanks to the many clinical experts working within the field of wound management, tissue viability and district nursing who I look up to with such well-deserved admiration. As leaders in the field, you have provided me with a great deal of food for thought and inspiration about what I consider to be a fascinating topic and I certainly couldn't have hoped to achieve any of this without you leading the way. You are my professional role models.

Last but by no means least, I want to thank my immediate and extended family and friends, whose support, well-wishes and pride have propped me up at every step of the way. Special love and gratitude to Mark, Tony, and Ciara, who have made so many enormous sacrifices on my behalf and lived through each one of the highs and lows with me from day one. You three are my world and without you, completing this work would not have meant a fraction of as much.

Author Statement

I declare that this thesis is my own work and has not been previously submitted for another comparable award.

Lead Academic Supervisor

Personal details withheld.

Abstract

Background: Wounds comprise a significant and growing burden both in the United Kingdom (UK) and globally. Positive wound management outcomes rely upon high quality evidence; effective knowledge transfer to the practice setting and education and skill of clinicians delivering care. However, limitations have been identified in the quality and range of available evidence supporting wound management; and education at pre-registration, post registration and continuing professional development (CPD) levels. Ineffective and varied practices have been highlighted, with poor application of evidence and a culture of ritualistic practice continuing to prevail. Very little is known about the nature of nurses' knowledge in the context of wound management or the impact of the limitations in evidence and education on clinical and educational outcomes.

Aim: The purpose of this study was to gain a rich and detailed understanding of the origins and nature of knowledge in generalist and specialist nurses with a key role in the delivery of wound management.

Methods: A reflexive thematic analysis (RTA) with five wound management specialists and five wound management generalist nurses was conducted using qualitative data from semi-structured interviews. Chinn and Kramer's *patterns of knowing* (2015) was applied as a conceptual framework from which to explore nursing knowledge in the context of wound management.

Results: Seven main themes and sixteen sub-themes were generated from the data: *the bigger picture; the smaller picture; it all comes together at the bedside; show me the evidence; industry: a political football; do good not harm; the power isn't ours; and I'm not that creative...but.*

Conclusions: The knowledge that nurses apply in wound management is multidimensional, contextual and highly integrated; with components that are unique from nursing knowledge in the wider sense. It develops most commonly in the practice setting in the direct presence of a wound. Although the *Patterns of Knowing* in wound management are well integrated, they are not equally represented and the types of knowledge that nurses demonstrate is not consistently aligned with those that they value. Minor distinctions were found between wound management specialist and generalists; however specific traits were identified in the knowledge development of those working in a community role. Industry represents a unique influencing factor in the context of wound management knowledge formation.

Table of Contents

Author Statement....	3
Abstract....	4
Chapter 1: Introduction and Background.....	9
Chapter 2: A narrative review of existing literature on knowledge in wound management...36	
Chapter 3: Methodological, theoretical and conceptual frameworks....	56
Chapter 4: Methods....	73
Chapter 5: Results....	87
Chapter 6: Discussion....	108
Chapter 7: Conclusions and recommendations for research and practice....	133
References....	145

Appendices

List of Appendices....	163
Appendix 1: Table of Studies....	165
Appendix 2: UWS Research Approval Letter....	169
Appendix 3: Participant Information Sheet Specialist Nurses...170	
Appendix 4: Participant Information Sheet Generalist Nurses....	173
Appendix 5: Data Management Plan (DMP)...176	
Appendix 6: Data Management: Electronic Folder Pathways.....	180
Appendix 7: Risk Assessment....	181
Appendix 8: Participant Consent Form Specialist Nurses....	183
Appendix 9: Participant Consent Form Generalist Nurses....	185
Appendix 10: Semi Structured Interview Schedule....	187
Appendix 11: Sample Interview Transcript Specialist Nurse....	192
Appendix 12: Sample Interview Transcript Generalist Nurse....	206

Appendix 13: Sample Initial Participant Code Sweep Chart (Data Analysis) Specialist Nurse....	217
Appendix 14: Sample Initial Participant Code Sweep Chart (Data Analysis) Generalist Nurse....	273
Appendix 15: Sample Individual Code Chart (Data Analysis) Specialist Nurse...	304
Appendix 16: Sample Individual Code Chart (Data Analysis) Generalist Nurse....	307
Appendix 17: Collated Code Chart (Data Analysis) Specialist Nurses....	312
Appendix 18: Collated Code Chart (Data Analysis) Generalist Nurses...	315
Appendix 19: Example Mind Map (Data Analysis)....	317
Appendix 20: Braun and Clarke's (2006) 15-Point Checklist for Thematic Analysis...	318
Appendix 21: Extracts from data- table of themes....	319
Appendix 22: Themes in the context of Chinn & Kramer's Patterns of Knowing....	323
Appendix 23: Dimensions for the development & utilisation of knowledge-examples from the context of wound management (adapted from Chinn & Kramer 2015)....	327

Tables and Figures

Tables

Table 1: Comparison of theoretical knowledge types...	32
Table 2: Dimensions for the development & utilisation of knowledge (Chinn & Kramer 2015)	70
Table 3: Participant clinical practice & education....	79
Table 4: Prevalence & frequency of links between themes & patterns of knowing....	104
Table 5: French & Ravens power types in the context of this study....	121
Table 6: Pattern consideration and demonstration...	125

Figures

Figure 1: Conceptual model of factors contributing to wound healing outcomes...	12
Figure 2: Multidisciplinary model of wound management...	15
Figure 3: Transforming Nursing Roles careers development pathways (CNOD 2018) ...	17

Figure 4: Chinn and Kramer's patterns of knowing in nursing....30

Figure 5: Search Strategy Algorithm...38

Figure 6: Diagram of ontological and epistemological stance of the study....61

Figure 7: Themes in order of dominance....88

Figure 8: Case Study: a pattern gone wild in wound management...106

Figure 9: Personal knowing in wound management...117

Figure 10: Chinn and Kramer's adapted patterns of knowing in wound management....124

Figure 11: Industry in wound management...132

List of publications associated with this study

Welsh, L. (2018) Wound care evidence, knowledge and education amongst nurses: a semi-systematic literature review. *International Wound Journal*. 15, pp. 53–61.

Welsh, L. Lusher J. (2020) A narrative review of specialist and generalist clinician's knowledge of wound management delivery. *Journal of Wound Care* (accepted for publication June 2021).

Welsh, L., Lusher, J. (2022) A reflexive thematic analysis of patterns of knowing in wound management amongst specialist and generalist nurses, *Nursing Forum*. Jan 2022

“Knowledge is the creation of an inventive mind, interacting with an inventive universe which itself is a part of what humans construe in the process of interaction”

Eisner 2002

Chapter 1 Introduction and background

Introduction

The purpose of this study was to gain a deeper appreciation of the origins and nature of knowledge in nurses with a key role in the delivery of clinical and educational wound management; an interest that was initially formed in the practice context. During practice as both a District Nurse (DN) and Tissue Viability Nurse (TVN), two roles in which wound management comprises a core component of practice, I experienced challenges accessing high quality evidence, education and continuing professional development (CPD); with the potential implications for practice becoming increasingly obvious over time. Since education packages at CPD level are often produced and delivered by representatives from wound management industry, access to CPD has historically relied heavily upon the formation of relationships between health boards and companies. Yet; for clinicians involved in the provision of wound care in the United Kingdom (UK), these relationships have presented a source of contention and confusion due to conflicting and somewhat inconsistent messages from National Health Service (NHS) management and a lack of clarity about industry roles, responsibilities and permissions for engagement. If it could therefore be proposed that there were recognised limitations in evidence, education and CPD, then the question of what impact this had on the knowledge of nurses involved in the delivery of wound management seemed a reasonable one to ask.

Although it has long been recognised that knowledge in nursing is multi-layered and more wide-ranging than that which arises from formal sources alone, the importance of the question seemed obvious to me as a researcher, since wounds present a significant and growing burden in relation to cost to health and social care service providers and to quality of life for those afflicted. If the development and application of nursing knowledge in wound management was affected by the quality of education and underpinning evidence, then a second question might be what impact this was having on clinical and educational practice. A key motivating factor for the topic was therefore my professional interest and insider's view of the wound management context from both specialist and generalist perspectives.

Background

Policy and practice in wound management

The presence of a wound has negative implications in terms of economic burden and patient quality of life (QoL); an impact that has been recognised throughout countries across the world (Hjort & Gottrup 2010; Guest et al. 2015; Guest et al. 2016; Guest et al. 2017; Jarbrink

et al. 2017; Fletcher et al. 2018; Nussbaum et al. 2018; Olsson et al. 2019). In the UK, studies by Guest et al. (2015; 2016) supported a cost of £4.5 to 5.1 billion pa for wounds and related comorbidities; an effect that is steadily worsening with changing demographics (Sibbald et al. 2011; Milne 2016; Lusher, Murray and Chapman-Jones 2017; Guest et al. 2017; Fletcher et al. 2018). More recent figures are proposed to be higher, with an expectation that wound care costs for individual UK health boards could increase by 37% over a five-year period (Guest et al. 2017). This has contributed to considerable financial cost to health and social care service providers; with mean UK costs of venous ulcers and diabetic foot ulcers proposed to be £7600 and £7800 respectively in 2015-16 (Fletcher et al. 2018; Guest et al. 2018a; Guest et al. 2018b). Economic costs incurred relate to a number of factors including hospital and facility costs; professional services, clinician time, overuse of antibiotics, equipment and lost productivity (Dowsett 2015; Brambilla et al. 2017; Murphy et al. 2020). Wounds also have detrimental effect on overall health and wellbeing of those afflicted including: physical impairment such as increased pain and decreased mobility; psychosocial wellbeing; for example, increased depression and anxiety and increased social isolation (Sibbald et al. 2011; Augustin et al. 2012; Brambilla et al. 2016; Lusher, et al., 2017; Murphy et al. 2020). This affects the ability of those living with a wound to carry out daily activities of living (Sibbald et al. 2011; Augustin et al. 2012; Brambilla et al. 2016), a consequence which increases in accordance with chronicity (Sibbald et al. 2011; Augustin et al. 2012; Lusher, et al. 2017; Fletcher et al. 2018). Wounds are historically categorised into acute and chronic subtypes, with the latter being the more problematic in terms of healing trajectory, QoL and economic cost (Purwins et al. 2010; Sibbald et al. 2011; Dowsett 2015; Brambilla et al. 2016). Examples of acute wounds include surgical incisions, traumatic wounds and blisters; while chronic wounds include pressure ulcers, leg ulcers and diabetic foot ulcers.

Although chronic wounds are often distinguished by prolonged healing rates; there is currently no universally agreed definition about specific timescales. Chronic wounds are generally accepted to be those of any origin that do not follow a normal sequence of events; with prolongation of healing occurring primarily at the inflammation stage and with acute wounds of any origin potentially becoming chronic (Frykberg and Banks 2015). More recently, the terms *hard-to-heal* and *slow-to-heal* wounds have been increasingly adopted by certain specialists who suggest they are preferable due to their recognition that barriers to wound healing can be overcome with the appropriate evidence-based treatment pathways (Dowsett 2015; Brambilla et al. 2016; Atkin et al. 2019; Murphy et al. 2020). For the purpose of this study, hard-to-heal wounds will therefore be used to define a wound with a prolonged rate of healing. Atkin et al. (2019) suggest that hard-to-heal wounds should be defined as

those which have not reduced by 40-50% with a good standard of care for a period of four to five weeks.

The increasing incidence, prevalence and complexity of hard-to-heal wounds has made them a growing priority on the current national health care agenda in the UK (Guest et al. 2015; NHS England 2016; NHS 2016; Guest et al. 2016; Guest et al. 2017; National Wound Care Strategy Programme (NWCSP) 2018; Atkin et al. 2019). This has been reflected in House of Lord's debates in 2016 and 2017 aimed at raising the profile of their impact and the growing presence of national campaigns and strategies to raise awareness and education about the prevention and treatment of particular wound types; for example, NHS Improvement's *Stop the Pressure* (NHS Improvement 2016) and the Tissue Viability Society's (TVS) *Legs Matter* coalition. In 2018, a National Wound Care Strategy Programme (NWCSP) was developed in England, with a directive to reduce variation and improve wound care through the implementation of a number of clinical and enabler work streams (NWCSP 2019). Despite recent progress, leaders in the field have recognised this as a long-awaited shift; with wounds being historically under financed and overlooked as an area of priority in comparison to other clinical specialities (Maylor 2012; Ousey et al. 2013a; Guest et al. 2015; NWCSP 2019). As of time of writing, the NWCSP has not expanded to include Scotland.

Elements determining wound outcomes are recognised to be multifactorial and linked to a number of intrinsic and extrinsic determinants which include: the presence of comorbidities, nutritional status, level of activity and psychological factors such as mood or motivation; as well as the availability and quality of underpinning evidence, effective transfer of evidence to practice and knowledge, and education and skill of clinicians delivering care (Hjort & Gottrup 2010; Upton and Soloweiej 2010; Guest et al. 2015; Lusher et al 2017; Fletcher et al. 2018; Gray et al. 2018; Nussbaum et al. 2018; Atkin et al. 2019; Olsson et al. 2019). **Figure 1** (p. 12) provides a diagrammatic representation of factors contributing to wound healing outcomes.

Figure 1: Conceptual model of factors contributing to wound healing outcomes (*those for primary consideration in this study are boxed)

Although any of these factors would in themselves represent a potential area of focus for a study, the importance of ensuring high quality evidence, education and clinician knowledge and skill cannot be overemphasized; with links between outcomes and clinician skill being widely acknowledged (Fletcher 2010; Sibbald et al. 2011; Guest et al. 2015; Harding et al. 2015; Vowden and Vowden 2016; Gray et al. 2017; Fletcher et al. 2018; Atkin et al. 2019). An interest in the potential impact of any proposed shortfalls in this capacity was a second motivation for its selection as an area of focus for this study.

Evidence, knowledge and education

The management of wounds is highly complex and it is expected that those involved in its delivery have the appropriate knowledge and skills (Probst et al. 2014; Guest et al. 2015; Powers et al. 2016). These include: knowledge pertaining to the anatomy and physiology of tissue repair and wound aetiology; knowledge of wider holistic factor affecting wound healing (i.e., comorbidities, psychological and social factors); knowledge of the main typologies of dressing products and their appropriate usage; and knowledge of national and local guidance, formulary processes and cost implications for clinical decision making in this capacity. Leaders in the field additionally propose that effective wound management practice requires the completion of specialist training; but point out that this is not widely or consistently evident (Fletcher 2010; Orsted et al. 2011; Ousey et al. 2013a; Guest et al. 2015a; Guest et al. 2015b; Ousey 2017; NWCSP 2019). Before the publication of the *Future Nurse: Standards of Proficiency for Registered Nurses*, the new standards for registered nurses by the NMC (2018), there had been no agreed competencies for wound management with the pre-registration nursing curriculum in the UK, which equated to roughly 1 x study day or less than 10 formal teaching hours (Maylor 2012). Given that wound management is common clinical activity for general nursing practice and comprises a key specialism for those working in particular clinical areas, this should be regarded as insufficient. Although the publication of the 2018 NMC standards has introduced proficiencies relating to nursing procedures that support skin integrity; these are not comprehensive and the degree to which they will impact upon clinician skill remains to be seen (Annex B NMC 2018). Since an increasing number of nurses are registered prescribers from one of three categories of Nursing and Midwifery Council (NMC) professional annotation, knowledge and skills pertaining to safe, evidence-based prescribing and adherence to formulary and protocol should also be considered integral to the provision of quality wound care; but it is not clear how prevalent and consistently applied this is in practice.

Whilst insufficient education in wound management is an important factor determining the effectiveness of quality of care and outcomes; limitations associated with the evidence base itself should also be noted as having an impact; for example; an overall shortage of original research exploring aspects of wound management from a nursing perspective, and the prevalence of those conducted and published with the support of industry (Langley and Parkinson 2008; Sharp 2010). This includes sponsorship for the production of studies and consensus documents; but also, dissemination in journals and conferences which are highly corporate in nature. Existing evidence that is proportionately produced by companies who develop, manufacture and supply wound management products and research is therefore conducted to some degree, for corporate interest (Langley and Parkinson 2008). This

reflects a growing shift towards a marketisation of health care research which; rather than being motivated by a sense of altruism, social responsibility and development of scientific knowledge, has become increasingly profit driven (Sharp 2010). It also presents potential issues relating to quality, ethical conduct and conflicts of interest; with unique concerns in the UK where mainstream health care is delivered by a publicly funded organisation (Pollock 2004). Although the focus of the present study is the UK setting and in particular Scotland; international literature supports that to varying degrees, issues and shortfalls surrounding wound management education and practice pervade at a global level (Orsted, Woodbury and Stevenson 2012; Lemon, Munsif and Sinha 2013; Guest et al. 2015a; Gray et al. 2018; Murphy et al. 2020). Wounds are managed by a number of clinicians in a range of settings; for example, consultants in specialist medicine such as vascular surgery and dermatology; and allied health professionals (AHPs) including podiatrists and orthotists (Orsted, Woodbury and Stevenson 2012; Ousey et al. 2013a; Ousey et al. 2015). Although it is recognised to be a multidisciplinary clinical specialty, for the most part wound management is a nurse-led discipline (Guest et al. 2015; Harding et al. 2015; Ousey et al. 2015; Vowden and Vowden 2016).

Successive changes to the health and social care policy agenda have led to an increasing decentralisation of care delivery and the burden of management of chronic conditions, including wounds, sitting predominately in the community setting (Heaslip 2013). A considerable proportion of community nursing time is taken up with wound management activity; with Hampton and Lindsay (2005) and Probst et al. (2014) suggesting this equates to 35-65% and Fletcher (2010) placing the figure between 50-60%. Much of this workload falls upon DNs who have an established role in leading community care. However, DNs have also been identified as a devalued professional group facing a number of inherent challenges which place them under an undue amount of pressure that affects their ability to carry out regular workload activities to an optimum standard (Bowers & Pellet 2010; Heaslip 2013). A number of DN colleagues have reported anecdotally that their wound management knowledge is insufficient; and literature supports variation, poor application of evidence and ineffective practices in wound management (Guest et al. 2015; Harding et al. 2015; Vowden and Vowden 2016; Gray et al. 2018; Fletcher et al. 2019). Guest et al. (2015) highlighted the particular difficulties for nurses working in the community setting to effectively diagnose and manage wounds and appropriately access specialist support. This may be related in part, to the failure of the District Nursing Specialist Practitioner Qualification (SPQDN) programme, the Nursing Midwifery Council's (NMC) professionally accredited programme of education for DNs in the UK, to include standardised competencies or minimum curriculum requirements for wound management. Although many shortfalls pertaining to wound management practice

reflect issues for the wider nursing profession rather than being particular to DNs; unique challenges identified within the group may be argued to compound these (Drew 2011; Longstaff 2013; Heaslip 2014; King's Fund 2016; Royal College of Nursing (RCN) 2016; McComiskey 2017). The unique role of DNs and community nurses in delivering wound management forms the key rationale for selecting them as the most appropriate generalist group from which to consider the impact of aforementioned issues with knowledge, evidence and education in this area of practice.

Wound management specialists

Within the UK, the TVN is recognised as the key clinician responsible for the delivery of specialist wound management education and the provision of clinical support to generalist clinicians (Maylor 2012). Although initially a speciality led by medical, surgical and bioengineering disciplines (White 2008); tissue viability has become primarily nursing-led and largely involves the provision of clinical and educational support to clinical nursing teams. However, as tissue viability services operate within a multi-disciplinary model of care, a number of additional clinical specialities may also be involved in the delivery of wound management. **Figure 2** (p. 15) provides diagrammatic representation of the multidisciplinary model of wound management.

Figure 2: Multidisciplinary model of wound management

Although the TVN is regarded as a specialist practitioner, there has been a historic lack of role definition and standardisation at regional and national levels; as well as a reported overall lack of priority for tissue viability as a clinical specialty (White 2008; Maylor 2012; Ousey 2017). This has been due to the historic absence of a role-specific governing body, as well as poorly defined partnerships with the medical profession since nursing has not traditionally adopted medical models of clinical assessment and management (White 2008; Ousey et al. 2013a). Ousey et al. (2013a) point out that doctors receive minimal wound management education within their undergraduate curriculum; therefore, not valuing its clinical importance. This is supported by Fletcher (2010) who shares concerns over insufficient levels of education in tissue repair for medical students. Wound management has also been historically linked to the absence of a strong evidence base and educational underpinning, (White 2008; Sharp 2010; Orsted, Woodbury and Stevenson 2012; Ousey et al. 2013a; Ousey 2017). Although discussion around the TVN role has mainly focused upon clinical knowledge and skills, the role continues to evolve and includes core functions such as education, service organisation and delivery, leadership and management, research, quality improvement and business modelling and planning (White 2008; Holloway 2019; Ousey and Lindsay 2019).

The absence of professionally regulated or nationally agreed levels of wound management education and competence affects generalist nurses but has additional implications for specialist roles such as the TVN; which currently has no universal requirement for educational preparation and skill; and no nationally agreed job description in the UK (Maylor 2012). In the UK, post-graduate specialised degree level programmes in tissue viability accept applicants from a range of clinical professions; however, although a number of TVNs are likely to have higher degrees, completion is not a consistent pre-requisite for those fulfilling TVN roles. Whilst a number of TVNs are likely to have higher degrees, this is in contrast to countries such as the United States (US) and Canada; where those fulfilling specialist roles in wound management are required to undergo structured education and assessment in order to become accredited with one of a number of independent regulatory bodies. Accreditation must also be maintained on an ongoing basis through continued demonstration of skill through re-assessment and payment of a registration fee (Masturzo et al. 2013). At practice level, defined educational criteria have been defined in professional competency and capability frameworks outlining criteria and skills required to support wound management. In the UK, the first of these was developed by the National Association of Tissue Viability Nurses Scotland (NATVNS) which identified both clinical skills and broader competency requirements to fulfil the TVN role which could be measured against the framework (Finnie and Wilson 2003). In 2016, Tissue Viability Leading Change (TVLC), a

collaborative group of leaders from academia, healthcare and industry, developed an updated competency framework consisting of ten core competencies enabling practitioners working in a range of levels within wound management to self-asses knowledge and skills against standards and regulations (Ousey 2016b).

An additional overarching factor that has significant implications for the TVN role are the current developments in the national policy agenda in relation to the delivery of care and frameworks outlining the preparation of nurses to effectively meet these. In Scotland, the integration of health and social care has led to the blurring of traditional professional boundaries and a growing shift towards more multidisciplinary approaches of delivery centred on prevention, person and community-centeredness and the reduction of health inequalities (Chief Nursing Officer’s Department (CNOD) 2017a). As depicted in **Figure 3** (p. 17) the CNO has devised an educational and career development pathways model in its drive to develop a nursing workforce that will have the appropriate skills to deliver this vision; with a particular focus on re-developed advanced nurse practitioner (ANP) roles (CNOD 2018).

Figure 3: Transforming Nursing Roles careers development pathways (CNOD 2018)

Although not professionally accredited, ANPs are proposed to have advanced knowledge and skills ranging across four accepted pillars of advanced practice: clinical practice, facilitation of learning, leadership and evidence and research development. These are garnered through the mandatory completion of a master’s level degree in an accepted ANP

programme (CNOD 2018). The skill set of the ANP is grounded in medical models of systems-focused assessment and treatment and include independent prescribing capabilities. This represents a shift from the historically holistic models of nursing within which the holistically skilled nursing specialist is considered to be the most senior clinician (Chinn and Kramer 2015). Current TVN preparation does not clearly align to advancing practice curriculums based on systems-models. In addition, those who have been in practice prior to the move of nursing to an all-graduate profession may have secured senior roles based on clinical experience and unaccredited or pre-graduate level education alone. This lack of standardisation arguably places the role of the TVN, a specialist in the more traditional model of nursing, in a questionable position as a clinical leader and expert does not align clearly with concepts of expertise and advanced practice within more contemporary career and education frameworks.

The development of nursing roles and increasing move towards advancing practice rooted in the scientific-technical model is not confined to specialist and senior clinical roles. Within the newly published *Standards of Proficiency for Registered Nurses* (NMC 2018); the NMC has outlined future pre-registration curriculums embedding more medically-based skills including pharmacological knowledge and structured assessment to prepare nurses for advanced roles earlier in the career trajectory. From 2023, the first newly qualified nurses graduating from pre-registration programmes approved on the new standards will have skills and educational preparation that may supersede those of many clinicians in specialist roles which remain aligned to older career pathway models.

Although it may be proposed that contextual inconsistencies and evolving policy changes have a de-stabilising effect on the role of the TVN, they maintain a high degree of influence at professional level. As members of high-profile formulary development and procurement steering groups for NHS organisations, they act as key negotiators with NHS procurement and representatives of industry. TVNs and other wound management specialists frequently work closely alongside industry in the development of research publications and consensus documents, where their names are routinely added as authors to establish academic and clinical credibility which can be in exchange for financial remuneration. These are disseminated at conferences that are highly corporate in nature; therefore, suggesting that TVNs have a powerful role in the formation of evidence. Although codes of conduct for both the pharmaceutical industry and individual NHS boards attempt to control any conflicts of interest to a large extent (Association of British Healthcare Industries (ABHI) 2009; NHS Greater Glasgow and Clyde (NHSGGC) 2016; Association of British Pharmaceutical Industries (ABPI) 2019), there is considerable potential for TVNs to have personal company

preferences and relationships with individual representatives; which increases scope for engagement in practices that could be construed as ethically questionable.

Despite recognition of limitations in the development of evidence supporting tissue viability as a speciality and the known challenges associated with the role itself; little is known about the perceived impact of shortfalls and their influence on the nature of knowledge wound management specialists' access and utilise to shape their practice. This has been identified as a gap in the current evidence base.

Wound management generalists

As the TVN is considered to lead specialist wound management practice, the DN is the leading clinician in the planning, implementation and evaluation of nursing care in the community; of which wound management comprises a considerable proportion (Hampton and Lindsay 2005; Fletcher 2010; Probst et al. 2014; RCN 2016). In order to fulfil the DN role, candidates must undertake a recordable specialist DN (SPQDN) qualification, which distinguishes them from Community Staff Nurses (CSNs), who comprise wider community nursing teams and who require no such specialist qualification. A key difference between the DN and CSN roles is therefore the former's overall responsibility for caseload and operational management, primary assessment and team leadership. Despite this distinction, there remains public and professional confusion surrounding the distinctions between the DN and CSN roles; with the term *DN* often being used to refer to any general nurse practicing within a community setting (RCN 2016). This may be partly due to the perceived similarities in clinical components of the roles for which there is often no clear differential. In Scotland, DN programmes of education are delivered at post-graduate level and increasingly incorporate advanced skills content such as systematic clinical assessment and independent prescribing; however, there are variations with other parts of the UK where SPQDN programmes are offered at undergraduate level. Although DNs are not currently considered to be advanced practitioners within the new careers framework and are placed on NHS *Agenda for Change* pay scales below clinicians employed in ANP roles; the increasing expectation that they have advanced clinical and prescribing skills has contributed to a growing lack of clarity in relation to competence, remuneration, career frameworks and the future of the role itself. This is reflected in the CNOD's career development pathways model in which DNs are placed below both ANPs and specialists in terms of levels of expertise and seniority (CNOD 2018) (see **Figure 3**; p.17). Despite the *specialist* title of the SPQDN qualification and necessity to undertake an educational qualification at post-graduate level in many parts of the UK, DNs are widely considered to be generalist clinicians by nature. Within the confines of wound management practice, they are also regarded as having less

expertise than the TVN who does not formally and consistently require a particular qualification or academic pre-requisite to fulfil the specialist role. This adds to the lack of clarity about specific clinical roles and their context within current nursing career frameworks.

DNs spend a proportionate amount of time engaged in wound management practice; yet, a number of factors may impact upon their ability to deliver to high quality care in this respect. In addition to outlined challenges surrounding wound management in the generic sense and those related to the lack of standardised wound management education on the SPQDN curriculum, are those associated with the wider health care policy agenda for DN practice and the role itself. In the UK, the ongoing service redesign and shifting balance of health care delivery from acute to community sectors, has led to increased workload and complexity of care, in terms of patient population, level of intervention required and caseloads which are increasingly spread across wider geographical areas (Bowers & Pellet 2010). These developments, in combination with an ageing DN workforce and challenges in recruitment and retention, have contributed to an overall decrease in staffing numbers and growing pressure to perform more task-based, efficiency-driven care (Heaslip 2014; Dickson et al. 2016; RCN 2016; McComiskey 2017). The gradual shift away from traditional holistic models of nursing education and move towards the medical model of care delivery have also led to a recent decline in uptake in DN education programmes and prioritisation of the more medically-focused ANP role at government and service development levels (Dickson et al. 2016; RCN 2016; Scottish Government 2016; CNOD 2018). This low strategic priority has left a sense of uncertainty and lack of direction within the profession; an oversight which has been exemplified in the failure of the NMC to prioritise review of the significantly outdated 2001 DN standards which no longer reflect the graduate attributable skills and level of knowledge required to fulfil the current role (United Kingdom Central Council for Nursing and Midwifery (UKCC) 2001). As of October 2021, updated standards for community nurse education are in development and consultation stages but have not yet been published. Since professional regulation supporting both DN practice and wound management is therefore questionable, DN ability to carry out wound management is arguably compounded.

Despite evidence supporting pressure for the role reaching crisis point (Heaslip 2014; King's Fund 2016; RCN 2016; McComiskey 2017); DNs have long been devalued by the public and other healthcare professions and the challenges they face are not new (Dickson et al. 2016; RCN 2016). This may be due in part to the invisible and hidden nature of DN work and the ongoing failure of the profession to articulate its unique skill set and knowledge base (Longstaff 2013; Heaslip 2014). As such, DNs continue to suffer from low professional image and perceived oppression from service developers and professional colleagues (Longstaff 2013; Heaslip 2014; King's Fund 2016; RCN 2016) factors which increasingly impact on their

ability to carry out clinical duties to an optimal standard (Drew 2011; Longstaff 2013; Heaslip 2014; King's Fund 2016; RCN 2016; McComiskey 2017).

Although there have been studies considering DNs' unique knowledge in relation to its specialist role; very little is currently known about the quality of knowledge DNs apply specifically in wound management practice and the implications of wider and role-specific challenges on this. A limited understanding of the nature of wound management knowledge in the contexts of both specialist and generalist practice have therefore been identified as gaps here.

Since an in-depth exploration of the knowledge applied in this context will be a primary aim of the study, a wider conceptualisation the nature of knowledge will now be considered.

Conceptualisations of knowledge

Theoretical debates about the nature of knowledge have ensued since the ancient Greek writings of Aristotle, Plato and Socrates (Eisner 2002).

Aristotle outlined four predominant categories of knowledge which included: *episteme* (true and certain universal knowledge); *phronesis* (practical wisdom); *techne* (craftsmanship); and *doxa* (commonly held values, attitudes and beliefs). A number of theorists have adapted Aristotle's knowledge domains over the centuries and the underpinnings share similarities with many contemporary frameworks which attempt to define knowledge (Carper 1978; Barnett 1997; Eisner 2002; Chin and Kramer 2015; Ullman 2015). For example, Aristotle's *episteme*, which he identified as universal, certain and deliberative knowledge reflects the realist/positivist concept proposing that knowledge exists consistently and objectively out-with the perceptions of the individual mind (Garrett and Cutting 2014). His concepts of *techne*, *phronesis* and *doxa* are examples of knowledge types that are garnered through practical-based experience and interaction with others; reflecting the epistemological stance of relativist/interpretivist and constructivist views (Eraut 2004; Eraut 2007). However, a recognised limitation of historical conceptualisations of knowledge is their limited consideration of the relationships between the different knowledge types (Nonaka and Takeuchi 1995; Eraut 2000; 2004; 2007; Nonaka and Toyama 2007).

Eraut's (2000; 2004; 2007) more contemporary consideration of knowledge proposes that it can be divided into formal, explicit (codified) and informal tacit (personal) varieties; the former referring to scientific evidence, theory and knowledge gained through structured education; and the latter referring to experiential learning gleaned in practice settings. Eraut (2004; 2007) adds that whilst formal knowledge is most commonly developed when learning

is intentional; informal learning can be episodic; occurring when an individual is not intending to learn (i.e., picking up habits or practice from colleagues). Despite similarities to Aristotle's episteme and links to positivism and realism, Eraut (2000) argues that formal knowledge should still be regarded as having a contextual element since its formation requires integration with more tacit types; adding that codified knowledge varies across different settings. Thus, it might be reasoned that the nature and relationships between Aristotle and Eisner's knowledge types are not clear cut and definitive. Indeed, Eisner (2002) argues that true episteme is an unrealistic concept; since *truth* is a conception of knowledge containing ideas, values and opinions which are socially constructed. Nygaard and Belluigi (2011) add that all knowledge creation is contextualised and value-laden since it is embedded into each individual's distinct learning process. Roxa and Martensson (2011) also support the contextual nature of knowledge and suggest that knowledge construction relies upon social interaction and the formation of relationships.

In addition to a proposed ability to think; Eisner (2002) considers the concept of knowledge in relation to *feeling*; which might be perceived to align to Aristotle's concepts of *doxa* and *phronesis*; representing the quality of an individual's attitudes and capacity for wisdom. This idea is articulated in the contemporary notion of emotional intelligence which outlines capabilities including: *self-awareness*, *self-management*, *social awareness* and *relationship management* as key indicators; and which is increasingly regarded to be as vital a component of professional practice as more appropriate intellectual indicators in disciplines such as nursing and teaching (Bass 1998). Finally, Eraut (2002) discusses *artistry* as a distinct knowledge type; which relies upon both thinking and feeling abilities and represents aesthetic skills including creativity and imagination. Within the context of education, Eisner (2002) interpreted *artistry* as an effective use tone, language, timing, aesthetics and execution to improve knowledge transmission and exchange; consequently, enhancing the learner experience (Eisner 2002). Nevertheless, it might also be argued, that rather than being an accumulation of knowledge, skills and experience, *artistry* is an intuitive and distinct ability to creatively connect and communicate externally and is therefore, related more to ability to communicate than to *know*.

Ullman (2015) further supports the multidimensional conceptualisation of knowledge; proposing that it is an umbrella term for philosophical epistemology which can be divided into 6 sub-types: a priori-reasoning ability (what can be derived from the world without directly experiencing it); a posteriori reasoning ability (using inductive reasoning or past experiences to form knowledge); explicit knowledge (formal, reliable and easily communicated knowledge); tacit knowledge (difficult to communicate through any medium; acquired beyond theory; experiential); propositional knowledge (descriptive or declarative-knowing that or

knowing how); and non-propositional knowledge (procedural-knowing how to) which is acquired by *doing*. This conceptualisation moves beyond the traditional focus upon definitions of knowledge that reflect theoretical and empirical types and capture knowledge formed in action, rather than that contained within the academic setting. Although not profession or discipline-specific, models such as Ullman's (2015) may be more reflective of those that are rooted in practice and may therefore align with the multidimensional models that seek to define nursing knowledge. Indeed, informal, contextual types of knowledge have been recognised to have particular importance in practice-based professions such as nursing where a large proportion of knowledge is formed through experiential-based learning (Carper 1978; Benner 1982; Kennedy 2004; Chinn and Kramer 2015).

Barnett (1997) also recognises the complex nature of knowledge; suggesting that whilst knowledge in the simplest form results from the education of an individual; the highest forms of criticality are holistic in nature. These are proposed to occur in three domains: *structured knowledge, knowledge of the self; and knowledge of the world*. The view of knowledge in action is supported by Bailin et al. (1999) who points to the traditional tendency to distinguish and divide educational goals into three main categories: *knowledge, skills and attributes*. Although theoretical typologies include a wide range of knowledge types; many theorists concur that definitions and distinctions between each type are not clear cut or definitive (Barnett 1997; Eraut 2000; Pahor et al. 2015). Barnett (1997) proposes that categorisations of knowledge can be both generic and specific and that the ability to link and synthesise different types is therefore in itself an important skill in knowledge formation; an observation that is shared by a number of authors (Eraut 2000; Nonaka & Toyama 2007; Pahor et al. 2015). Eraut (2000) argues that the process of integration of different knowledge types can vary across contexts, leading to the creation of new *personal* knowledge; whilst Nonaka & Toyama (2007) point out that knowing in practice requires an ability to link knowledge and personal values; forming a synthesis between objectivity (positivism) and subjectivity (relativism). This further supports the notion that knowledge types, the relationships between them and the paradigms that shape them, are not consistently discrete.

Conceptualisations of knowledge by critical theorists support its role in fulfilling particular interests for powerful individuals, systems and institutions that create societal inequalities (Habermas 1972; Green and Earle 2010; Sharp 2010; Cohen et al. 2018). Eagleton (1991) argues that critical theory aims to identify and question the legitimacy of the false consciousness which renders certain groups powerless; whilst exposing knowledge and behaviours of institutions and ideologies with dominant, repressive and illegitimate components. Critical pedagogists such as Freire (1973) and Giroux (2017) support that structured education systems serve to recreate dominant ideologies and are fundamentally

narrative rather than transformative since teachers decide what *true* knowledge is and students are regarded as empty receptacles in which knowledge is deposited. From this perspective, knowledge formation is an intentional act of cognition which leads to a transformation of consciousness through ongoing cycles of critical action and reflection (i.e., praxis). Barnett (1997) adds that transformative criticality is the highest form since it is concerned with morality and a quest for the greater good; as well as independence of thought and action. As such, Giroux (2017) concludes that education and knowledge development are always political acts.

Historical consideration of knowledge in nursing

Much has been written on the typologies of knowledge supporting nursing practice and its historic development within the profession (Carper 1978; Benner 1982; Garrett and Cutting 2014; Chinn and Kramer 2015; Pahor et al. 2015; Williams and Burke 2015; Davis and Maisano 2016; Lockwood and Hopp 2016; Voldbjerg et al. 2016). Questions abound about the perceived uniqueness of nursing knowledge and whether it has a distinct evidence base; or borrows on those from more elite, established professions such as science, medicine and the social sciences (Aktar-Danesh et al. 2013; Ayala et al. 2014; Chinn and Kramer 2015; Pahor et al. 2015; Shearer 2015). In order to understand nursing knowledge, it is therefore necessary to consider it within the context of the historic evolution of the profession itself.

From as early as Florence Nightingale, nursing has been proposed as having a unique knowledge set; one which has included a range of knowledge types; but which is primarily rooted in the Eastern philosophy of holism (Fawcett and DeSanto-Madeya 2013). Unlike the medical model which deduces individuals and associated frameworks of assessment to different anatomical and physiological systems, holism regards each individual as being more than equal to the sum of their parts which cannot be deduced to a series of systems. The individual; rather than the particular system for examination, has therefore been traditionally placed at the centre of any assessment process in nursing (Fawcett and DeSanto-Madeya 2013). Despite a recognition of the value of holism, Florence Nightingale also recognised the range of knowledge types required to practice nursing and importantly, the existence of a unique nursing science. Although innovative, Nightingale's view of nursing was of its context and reflective of the inferior social position of women at that time. Between 1900 and 1950, significant changes pervaded in nursing which impacted upon knowledge formation and its professional evolution. In the US, this was articulated as healthcare services developing as capitalist, for-profit systems in which the scientific, medical model began to prevail; and medicine establishing its position as the dominant healthcare profession; in the US and beyond (Friedson 1970; McInnes and Lawson-Brown 2007; Cooke

and Philbin 2008; Ayala et al 2014; Birdin 2014; Khalili et al. 2014). Whilst nurses in Nightingale's time were predominantly females from middle-classes, during this second phase, nursing became increasingly regarded as a semi-profession for working-class females who were trained within an apprenticeship model in which physician's orders were followed (Ayala et al 2014; Khalili et al. 2014). Accordingly, nurses were regarded as a source of inexpensive labour; were *trained* rather than *educated* and excluded from access to scientific based knowledge (Ayala et al, 2014). With the introduction of university-based education in the 1950s and 1960s, a shift occurred through which the profession attempted to align with scientific models of knowledge; mainly driven by an attempt to gain academic and professional legitimacy from the medical profession and wider society (Cooke and Philbin 2008; Denny 2010; Greene and Earle 2010; Ayala et al. 2014). This resulted in a growing focus upon empiric sources of knowledge and a movement towards higher education in nursing; trends which continue in the current context. Nevertheless, throughout this evolutionary shift, nursing's holistic origins also persisted and into the 1970s and 1980s, a number of theoretical frameworks of nursing knowledge and processes rooted in the social sciences developed in recognition that nursing was inherently value-laden and did not clearly fit with the objectivity demanded by the scientific approach (Carper 1978; Benner 1982; Neuman 1995; Orem 2001; Roy 2009).

Debates on typologies of knowledge in nursing are often centred on its perceived professional legitimacy and continued exclusion from true professional status by the more established professions. The debates centre on two main arguments; those relating to gender and the historic origins of nursing in a female domestic caring role; and those highlighting its comparatively inferior level of education (Denny 2010; Ayala et al. 2014). Despite academisation in recent years and subsequent move from the apprenticeship model to all-graduate status; nursing continues in its struggle to overcome the horizontal elitism and dominance of the scientific, medical model and move beyond status as a semi or subordinate profession (Denny 2010; Keeling and Templeman 2012; Ayala et al. 2014; Fantahun et al. 2014). Although proponents of this argument continue to point to nursing's lack of unique evidence base and inferior education; the functionalist view proposes that professionalism, rather than being based on specific traits of members, should be viewed as an ideology linked to class identification and monopoly of social and political power (Martimianakis et al. 2009; Aktar-Danesh et al. 2013; Khalili et al. 2014). As such, professions are established to reproduce and maintain power amongst a privileged elite, a group which excludes nurses since they historically lack political control and autonomy (Aktar-Danesh et al. 2013; Ayala et al. 2014; Fantahun et al. 2014).

The functionalist view was first considered in the context of health care in a seminal study by Friedson (1970) who argued that as the dominant health care profession, doctors attempt to subordinate other groups through social closure and denying outsiders, including nurse's access to specialist knowledge (Denny 2010). Ayala et al. (2014) argue that academisation has done little to redistribute power to nurses, since institutions of higher education are themselves, instruments of social reproduction and replication which stabilise inequalities and factors contributing to medical and male dominance of power; a view that is supported by critical theorists such as Giroux (2017). Greene and Earle (2010) add that this is partly due to the perceived inferiority of holistic models to scientific and technical models. Denny (2010) points out that the emphasis placed on scientific and technical knowledge devalues alternative knowledge types associated with nursing (i.e., caring) which are considered "dirty" work; whilst Greene and Earle (2010) add that emotional labour, despite demanding a high level of skill, remains professionally unrecognised. From a critical theoretical perspective, Giroux (2017) associates this with a pervading culture of positivism which infiltrates most structural organisations and institutions, including education and health care. Proponents of the feminist argument would add that the basis of scientific knowledge is objectivity which is considered to be a male trait; one which women, the majority of whom make up the nursing profession, have been traditionally perceived to be theoretically incapable (Letherby 2010). Crenshaw (1989) adds that the perceived value of knowledge constructs remain rooted in inequality; with gender representing one of a number of oppressive factors (others include race, social class and religion) and those that are hailed as superior continuing to be highly Eurocentric. Denny (2010) points out that advanced nursing roles, which tend to be highly technical, removed from basic care and therefore masculine, bring nursing under greater control by medicine since the medical profession defines their terms.

Proponents of the critical pedagogical argument support that the theoretical knowledge generated by dominant professions passes on existing cultural standards which therefore remain the most highly valued in society (Friedson 1973; Johnson 2010; Giroux 2017). Friedson (1970) argues that subordinate professions often strive to adopt characteristics of more dominant ones as is the case with expanded nursing roles which are often doctor- led. Proposed examples in Scotland include the increasing drive towards ANP and non-medical prescribing agendas motivated by reductions in junior doctors' hours and cost; and the implementation of the 2017 General Medical Services (GMS) contracts which have devolved a number of work streams from GPs to nurses and AHPs. These developments have been viewed with contention by some non-medical professionals as examples of shifting workload from the most powerful group rather than reducing it and serving the medical profession

rather than the service users it proposes to benefit (Scottish Government 2016; Scottish Government 2017; Glasgow City Integrated Joint Board 2019). From a functionalist perspective it might also be proposed that DNs are considered to be less technical and therefore less knowledgeable than their nursing colleagues working in more acute settings. This view has also pervaded in the field of wound management which continues to be overlooked and undervalued by the medical profession due to shortfall in its evidence base and its being the historic domain of nurses (Guest et al. 2015; Harding et al. 2015; Vowden and Vowden 2016).

Whilst medicine continues to be the key source of professional dominance over the nursing profession (McInnes and Lawson-Brown 2007; Johnson 2008; Ayala et al. 2014) those involved in wound management practice may be faced with additional sources of oppression. For generalists such as the DN, this can include TVNs and other specialists who continue to exercise a degree of control over a range of wound management practices including education, formulary development and engagement with industry (Maylor 2012; Ousey 2017). Due to the corporate domination of both evidence and education in wound management, industry should also be recognised as a potential source of power and control over nurses; since much of that produced is developed for marketable aim (Langley and Parkinson 2009). The resulting commodification of wound management evidence and education should therefore be rigorously questioned and challenged; since as Giroux (2017) argues, education should be about teaching consciousness and encouraging social agency rather than consumerism. An additional source of control and influence are NHS health boards and service providers at large. As a primarily public organisation, most notably in Scotland, the NHS is accountable for the responsible and equitable use of resources and in order to manage this effectively and transparently, strict processes of governance outline procurement, formulary and prescribing practices. This includes the utilisation of cost models through which health care is shaped and driven by service need, highly structured processes for formulary development and systematic monitoring and reporting of clinician formulary adherence. In an attempt to prevent and manage potential conflicts of interest and avoid ethical misconduct, interaction between NHS staff and representatives from industry is tightly controlled; all of which have been reported to have a restrictive effect on wound management education and CPD by some clinicians (Ousey 2017). Many restrictions on nursing knowledge development may not always be recognised by nurses themselves; since Giroux (2017) proposes, systems of control in power models are often invisible and set up to restrict rather than facilitate consciousness.

Conceptual models of nursing knowledge

Throughout the development of the profession, a number of models and frameworks have arisen in attempt to define nurse knowledge. Despite variations, most concur on the multidimensional nature of knowledge; and in particular, the importance of that which is experiential, practice-based and linked to clinical decision-making (Carper 1978; Benner 1982; Kennedy 2004; Chinn and Kramer 2015). Since models specific to nursing also overlap and reflect some of the more generic conceptualisations of knowledge (Barnett 1997; Bailin et al 1999; Eraut 2000; Eisner 2002; Eraut 2004; Eraut 2007; Ullman 2019), the necessity to regard nursing knowledge as distinct and unique has been questioned (Garrett and Cutting 2014). However, nursing's historical origin as a practice-based profession within which knowledge is primarily linked to concepts such as caring, compassion and personal values, have made its knowledge base more problematic to define than those rooted in more formal academic sources and its unique challenges should be recognised in this capacity (Green and Earle 2010; Aktar-Danesh et al.2013; Ayala et al. 2014; Pahor et al. 2015; Shearer 2015; Springer and Clinton 2015). Williams and Burke (2015) point out that during pre-registration education, nursing identity and knowledge is developed not in the traditional academic sense; but rather, through a complex professional socialisation process which includes learning and knowing; and also *doing* and *speaking*. This is supported by Voldbjerg et al. (2016) who add that nursing knowledge development relies upon knowing and doing; and Shearer (2015) who suggests the nursing knowledge formation contains a personal aspect which is developed through an ongoing process of self-reflection. This may be more attributable to competence; which has been ascribed as a combination of knowledge, skills, attitudes and behaviours (World Health Organisation (WHO), aligning to Aristotle's *techne*, *phronesis* and *doxa* and Eraut's codified, implicit, personal knowledge (Eraut 2000; 2004; 2007; Cowan et al. 2005; Bradshaw and Merriman, 2008; Smith 2012). Within the context of nursing there is continued debate over definitions of competence and in turn, the most effective means for its evaluation. Similarly, are definitions for capability, which is regarded as a holistic integration of knowledge, skills and personal qualities that can be applied effectively in different contexts (Cowan et al. 2005; Calman 2006). Stage models such as Benner's (1982) determine that competence and capability may improve over time and the ongoing evaluation of both underpins performance evaluation for significant proportions of nursing practice and education, including the pre-registration nursing curriculum in the UK. However, the effectiveness of evaluation processes themselves; particularly those leading to certification have also been questioned since there is significant variation in implementation of practice across clinical areas (Calman 2006; Wade 2008; Smith 2012). Within nursing practice, a common method of evaluation is through the application of structured competency and capability frameworks; examples of which include those for specific clinical skills (i.e., Doppler ultrasound) and specific clinical areas of practice

(i.e., tissue viability). Yet, a continued critique of competence and capability-based assessment, is its practical-based application and assessment, which align more to the apprentice and training model that nursing has sought to distance itself from (Croxon and Maginnis 2009; Jacobs 2018; Jayasekara et al. 2018; Mulkeen et al. 2019; Tayler and Flaherty 2020).

A number of theorists further point out that nursing knowledge is not a static concept and is determined largely by context (Richie and Lewis 2009; Cioffi 2012; Pahor et al. 2015; Davis and Maisano 2016; Lockwood and Hopp 2016; Voldbjerg et al. 2016). Lockwood and Hopp (2016) maintain that nursing is an adaptable and diverse profession constituting a variety of knowledge types that vary with local contexts; whilst Springer and Clinton (2015) recognise the multiple representations of nursing knowledge which are created and sustained through complex interaction between individuals, social structures and the specific practice setting. Since it is a broad ranging profession with a large number of specialities and associated skill sets, many theorists propose that nursing knowledge, rather than being a one size fits all, should therefore be considered highly diverse and context-specific (Richie and Lewis 2009; Cioffi 2012; Pahor Domanjko et al. 2015; Davis and Maisano 2016; Lockwood and Hopp 2016; Voldbjerg et al. 2016).

Several of the theoretical models of nursing knowledge are recognised to be products of their historical time and context; for example, the post-modernist movement of the 1970s and 1980s when multiple forms of knowledge began to be regarded as legitimate as those originating from scientific and empiric models (Garrett and Cutting 2014). During this period, seminal models of nursing knowledge such as Carper's *Fundamental Patterns of Knowing* (1978) and Benner's *Novice to Expert* (1982) emerged; and despite being their age, have generally remained accepted as the epistemological basis of nurses' knowing to the present day (Garrett and Cutting 2014; Davis and Maisano 2016; Lockwood and Hopp 2016). Benner's (1982) model outlines five stages of professional practice and skills advancement in nursing (*novice, advanced beginner, competent, proficient and expert*) and is widely considered to remain applicable within contemporary practice (Davis and Maisano 2016). Stage models such as Benner's; however, are not without their critics and have been recognised to overlook the widely contextual factors which impact upon practice-based professions such as nursing (Dall'Alba and Sandberg 2006; Lockwood and Hopp 2016). Davis and Maisano (2016) add that stage models fail to capture nurses' *real-world* knowledge (i.e., ability to prioritise tasks or utilize past experiences) which are more difficult to define than formal knowledge types. This has been attributed to their focus upon the acquisition and stages of knowledge formation over time; rather than an in-depth contemplation of constituents comprising knowledge itself; a view which is supported by

Pahor et al. (2015) who argue that nursing is professional socialisation process which is complex; combining a range of knowledge types that do not develop in a straightforward linear fashion. As such, the integration of different knowledge types is regarded in itself as a key indicator of complexity which cannot be captured by dimensions or stages that are defined purely vertically and horizontally (Pahor et al. 2015); a view that is shared by wider conceptualisations of knowledge out with nursing (Eraut 2000; Nonaka & Toyama 2007). Carper's seminal *Fundamental Patterns of Knowing* (1978) remains one of the most recognised theoretical models of nursing knowledge, outlining: *empirical, ethical, personal* and *aesthetic* knowledge types as the epistemological basis of nursing; with Chinn and Kramer (2015) later re-developing the model and adding a fifth pattern, *emancipatory knowing*. **Figure 4** (p. 30) provides diagrammatic representation of Chinn and Kramer's (2015) patterns of knowing.

Figure 4: Chinn and Kramer's patterns of knowing (reproduced with permission from Elsevier)

Whilst accepting Carper's (1978) four fundamental patterns of nurse knowing as it's basis, Chinn and Kramer (2015) introduced *emancipatory knowing*; to encourage reflection upon inequalities and injustice inherent in social and political systems and a call for action to re-address these through a process called *emancipatory praxis*. Despite being a more recent addition to the model, emancipatory knowing and commitment to social justice have been recognised as being reflective of very early philosophies of nursing practice (Fawcett and DeSanto-Madeya 2013; Chinn and Kramer 2015). Chinn and Kramer (2015) support that within the framework of Carper's fundamentals, emancipatory knowing, rather than being a separate entity, is woven through each pattern; hence its central position in the diagrammatic representation. This supports the seminal critical pedagogical theories of Freire (1973) and more contemporary thinkers such as Giroux (2017) who propose that

knowledge production should lead to an emergence of consciousness. This might suggest that emancipatory knowing not only contains elements of each of the remaining patterns which are integral in shaping consciousness; but takes precedence over them as a result of its core function. Like many of the theorists attempting to capture the nature of nursing knowledge (Dall’Alba and Sandberg 2006;Richie and Lewis 2009; Cioffi 2012; Davis and Maisano 2016; Lockwood and Hopp 2016; Voldbjerg et al. 2016; Shearer 2015); Chinn and Kramer (2015) also recognise the *action* and *doing* components of knowledge (i.e. competence); and distinguish between *knowledge* (a combination of ontology and interaction); and *knowing*, which they argue cannot be fully expressed in formal knowledge alone; instead, relying upon more tacit and contextual forms of expression.

Although nursing has historically relied upon formal knowledge types (i.e., those deriving from research and theory); the importance of more tacit experiential knowledge has continually been recognised by numerous nursing knowledge models, including Benner (1982), Carper (1978) and Chinn and Kramer (2015); as well as by conceptual models underpinning the nursing process (Neuman 1995; Orem 2001; Roy 2009) (Cioffi 2012; Voldbjerg et al. 2016). One such example of tacit knowledge is the concept of intuition which has been defined as the experience of feeling before understanding (Panksepp 1998) and linked to emotional awareness and interpretation at subconscious levels rather than to analytical decision making (Shirley and Langan-Fox 1996; Price et al. 2017). Smith (2006) describes three dimensions of intuition including: physical awareness, emotional awareness, and making connections. Intuition has been proposed to represent a complex decision-making process that advances with level of experience (Benner and Tanner 1987; Holm and Severinsson 2016; Ruzska et al. 2020); however, Price et al. (2017) also found intuition to be a source of knowledge in novice nurses. A systematic review by Holm and Severinsson (2016) identified intuition to be increasingly recognised as a legitimate form of knowledge in nursing; albeit one that is not consistently acknowledged or defined (Appleton and Cowley 2003). As a result, its validity continues to be questioned by a number of critics (Lamond & Thompson, 2000; Holm and Severinsson 2016).

Despite practice-based, personal learning being hailed by nurse theorists as being as important as more formal types of knowing; it has been recognised that nurse educators have not yet established ways to ensure that doing-based knowledge is made explicit and formal (Cioffi 2012; Davis and Maisano 2016; Lockwood and Hopp 2016). An understanding of informal, implicit knowledge types should be of particular relevance for wound management specialists such as TVNs for whom competence is poorly and inconsistently defined (Maylor 2012) and wound management generalists such as DNs, whose practice is by nature invisible, complex and linked to contextual factors (Drew 2011). Although DNs

have been previously recognised as having a unique, role-specific knowledge base (Kennedy 2004; Burke 2014; Bain 2015); their level of expertise continues to be poorly understood by other professional groups (Drew 2011; Heaslip 2014; RCN 2016) and there is a dearth of evidence pertaining specifically to their knowledge in the context of wound management. Knowledge specific to clinicians practicing wound management is also poorly defined and in recognition of this, Maylor (2012) suggested the implementation of a specific novice to expert continuum with clear benchmarks for roles practice ranging from specialist (i.e., TVNs) to basic skills (i.e., Healthcare Assistants). However, as per previous critique of stage models such as Benner (1982) and proposals within the Transforming Nursing Roles careers development pathways (CNOD 2018) (refer to **Figure 3** (p. 17), knowledge that is defined in a linear construct may fail to capture the complexity and tacit nature of knowledge in wound management.

Table 1 (p. 32) compares generic theoretical frameworks of knowledge with those specific to nursing.

Table 1: Comparison of theoretical knowledge types

Type	Aristotle	Eisner (2002)	Carper (1978)	Chinn & Kramer (2015)	Eraut (2000)	Barnett (1997)
	Episteme	Episteme	Empiric	Empiric	Codified Formal & Explicit	Knowledge (cognition, reasoning, functioning)
	Doxa	Doxa	Ethical	Ethical	Codified and Personal	Self (personal) Interactive (with world & society)
				Emancipatory	Formal & Explicit or Informal & Tacit	
	Phronesis	Phronesis	Personal	Personal	Personal Informal & Tacit	

	Techne	Techne	Aesthetic	Aesthetic	Informal & Tacit	
--	--------	--------	-----------	-----------	---------------------	--

Positionality

My own professional and personal experiences and insider's view while practising as a TVN and DN delivering wound care were the starting points for this study because I experienced a number of the identified challenges first hand. In my recent role as an educator in a Higher Education Institution (HEI), a keen interest in formal and informal knowledge formation and the theoretical models supporting nursing knowledge were forged. The question of how challenges encountered at practice level may link to theoretical models of knowledge formation, as well as to overarching social and organisational factors became more pressing; and the context of wound management projected to be a typical and interesting point from which to explore any suggested links. For example, I began to recognise wound management being historically over-looked and under-valued due to its status as a nurse-led profession. Theoretical associations between wider factors impacting on wound management practice were gradually forged and the development of an understanding of more tacit knowledge forms that potentially shape this area of practice became of growing interest. As part of this, a comparative overview of some of the theoretical models and conceptual frameworks that were proposed to underpin nursing knowledge and practice followed. I considered clinicians practicing as specialists and generalists in the field of wound management to be in unique and optimal positions to provide insight into the nature of knowledge development, which contributed to the rationale for their selection as the study participants. Although the study is not comparative in the purest sense of the word, I believed it would be of value to explore the nature of wound management knowledge from both specialist and generalist perspectives whilst considering any potential similarities and distinctions that may present between the two groups.

Prior to qualifying as a nurse, I completed a social sciences degree which fuelled an interest in sociological theories such as post-structuralism and critical theory. A curiosity about links between social injustice and knowledge and power within different health and social care professions resulted; which contributed to a wider critical consideration of the impact of social and organisational factors on nursing practice. It is my belief that nursing knowledge in wound management has not been subject to any comprehensive examination to date because those who are implicated and affected are situated at practice level and are as such, not routinely provided with research skills and opportunities to do so. On the other hand, those who are equipped with research expertise and means may not regard it to be of

sufficient importance to be the topic for study since they have not routinely experienced the problem at practice level. In essence, wound management knowledge has not been researched extensively because like many facets of nursing knowledge, it has been historically undervalued. For this reason, I am of the belief that the Professional Doctorate (DProf), which identifies problems at practice rather than theoretical level, was a more suitable academic programme from which to approach the topic than the typically more deductive, theoretically-driven PhD. Having now returned to the NHS in a management role within community nursing, my professional identity and knowledge have come full circle which feels like confirmation that the DProf was the right choice. I believe I am best placed to see the actualisation and articulation of the topics and findings from the study at practice level and in that sense, it feels like I am “home”.

Relevance of Study and Community of Practice

It is anticipated that the study will add to the evidence base underpinning wound management with a potential to influence educational and practice outcomes; most typically but not exclusively amongst the nursing profession. I envision that the research will be of interest to a number of professional peer groups who can be regarded as forming a community of practice at local, national and global levels. These include: academic colleagues, NHS and clinical colleagues, health and social care policy-makers and importantly, representatives from industry. Leaders and researchers in the field of wound management should find this study to be of particular interest but just as importantly, are those carrying out wound management at practice level. Clinical colleagues would include those with expertise similar to the researcher and study participants (i.e., wound management, DNs and TVNs) and clinicians with comparable wider theoretical interests. The study would also be of relevance to policy makers and developers involved in the process of professional regulation and the development of protocols and national guidelines.

It is projected that the research will be of relevance to academic colleagues with similar teaching and research interests from a range of schools and areas of practice; most notably, those from Schools of Health and Life Sciences. It is anticipated that the results of the study will make a positive contribution to wound management curriculum development; including those within pre-registration nursing programmes. Equally, academics from the Schools of Education and Social Sciences with interests in education, knowledge formation and the impact of wider influencing factors on practice may also find the study to be of relevance. Fellow researchers with interest and experience in particular methodologies and methods; for example, qualitative approaches and reflexive thematic analysis (RTA) should also find aspects of the study to be of interest. It is also hoped that the findings of the study will be of

significance to private organisations and industry with corporate interests in wound management (i.e., those who produce products and original research) since they play a considerable and influential role in this area of practice.

Finally, it is hoped that the identification and articulation of less formal knowledge types applied in the context of wound management will contribute to their recognition as legitimate and sophisticated forms of knowledge that represent highly complex and skilled clinical practice. In doing so, it is also expected that clinicians delivering wound management will be encouraged to critically reflect and validate the knowledge they apply in the context of their own practice.

Summary

This chapter provided an introduction and background to the context of current wound management practice in the UK setting. Wounds represent a significant and increasing burden to health and social care service providers and to those afflicted. Wound management outcomes are linked to a range of factors, including the knowledge and skill of clinicians providing care; however, significant shortfalls have been identified in a number of factors influencing clinicians' knowledge. These include limitations in the evidence base supporting wound management as well as the questionable role of wound management industry in evidence and knowledge production which presents proposed methodological and ethical issues. In addition, nurses have faced challenges accessing sufficient wound management education at pre-registration, post-graduate and CPD levels. Challenges inherent to the clinical roles of both specialist and generalist nurses delivering wound management have also been highlighted as limiting wound management knowledge, education and professional development as a highly valued clinical area of practice and speciality.

Although nursing knowledge in the wider sense is recognised to be multi-layered and complex, it is not known how influencing factors and shortfalls specific to the context of wound management impact upon the knowledge of specialist and generalist nurses in this clinical area. Previous studies have highlighted shortfalls but the nature of the knowledge applied in this context has not been examined in depth. This study aims create a new understanding of this issue and address the gap in the current evidence base by gaining a rich and detailed understanding of the origin and nature of the knowledge of clinicians delivering wound management in both specialist and generalist roles. Chapter 2 provides a narrative review of the existing literature to set the context for the study.

Chapter 2: A narrative review of existing literature on knowledge in wound management

Introduction

Hart (2001) states that an analytical understanding of literature is an important pre-requisite for all research; whilst Trafford and Leshem (2008) maintain that literature reviews hold both intellectual and methodological value for those undertaking doctoral level study. Aveyard (2019) proposes that a comprehensive and systematic approach ensures the identification of relevant literature, while also addressing and shaping the research question. Although a systematic process is integral for assuring quality and was utilised here, it is accepted that systematic reviews by their strictest definition are out with the capabilities of an independent student researcher (Aveyard and Sharp 2013).

Due to the shortage of original research on the topic which was highlighted in the background chapter of this study, a narrative review was considered to provide the most comprehensive and realistic picture of wound management knowledge; whilst ensuring that a sufficient range of relevant literature could be captured. Broad areas that informed the search strategy included: nurses' knowledge and competence in wound management, evidence in wound management, education in wound management, the TVN role, TVN knowledge, the influence of the DN role on DN/CSN knowledge development in wound management and the influence and role of industry in wound management.

Search strategy

The review consisted of a number of systematic searches of the literature which were conducted in the period between September 2017 and August 2021. Searches were carried out using relevant electronic databases and search engines including: CINAHL, Medline (including PubMed), Science Direct, Cochrane, EMBASE and Google Scholar. Key words and Medical Subject Heading (MeSH) terms including: district and/or community nurs\$, nurs\$, wound\$, education, evidence, tissue viability, tissue viability nurse\$, know\$ power, intuition, competency and pharmaceutical industry were used both singularly and in various combinations with truncations to capture all noun and verb endings. Original limits were set for database searches for English language with inclusion dates 2009-2019 to ensure that level of literature was contemporary yet sufficient, as well as being manageable for a study by a single researcher. However, in recognition of an overall dearth of original research on the subject and the importance of capturing the historical context of the TVN and DN role in wound management knowledge development, dates were expanded to range from 1991-2019. Original research studies of all designs were included to ensure alignment with

traditional hierarchies of evidence across qualitative and quantitative paradigms (Argyrous 2011). To ensure a pragmatic approach which highlighted and summarised evidence trends covering a wide date range, review papers were also included. Since they constitute a sizeable proportion of the evidence base supporting wound management and are recognised to be of variable methodological quality, small scale/individual case studies were excluded. Saved searches were re-run on a monthly basis until August 2020 to ensure any key contemporary literature was captured. A number of additional hand and online library searches were also carried out to source relevant grey and supplementary literature including policy, professional frameworks, consensus and guidance documents and text books to support the background and discussion content and offer a broader perspective of the literature. However, these were not included in the formal review component or literature table. Inclusion and exclusion criteria have been summarised below:

Inclusion criteria: original research studies of all design including surveys; review papers; English language; date range between 1991-2019

Exclusion criteria: non-wound related (i.e., stoma care, skin lesions), non-English language, out with date range of 1991-2019, evaluation of specific product or technology, audit and evaluation of specific tools, patient experience; studies with sponsorship by industry; individual patient/small scale case studies

Although considered robust in methodological terms, an identified shortfall of PRISMA and Cochrane search strategies is that their strict criteria for inclusion may limit the ability to capture relevant material; for example, valuable literature containing more qualitative content. Neither was employed here for this reason; however, an adapted version of the PRISMA model was utilised to ensure a systematic process was followed (Refer to **Figure 5** p. 38). For an overview of studies included in the review, refer to **Appendix 1**, p. 165.

In order to ensure a structured approach to methodological critique and quality appraisal; Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (CASP) tools specific to particular methodologies were used as frameworks for original research studies included in the review (Centre of Research Dissemination 2009; CASP 2018). An adapted tool by Wooliams et al. (2009) was used for appraisal of more general studies; for example, surveys that did not follow more traditional research design.

Figure 5: Search Strategy Algorithm

An overview of knowledge, evidence and education in the wider context of wound management:

The literature revealed that the evidence base underpinning wound management has inherent and significant limitations; both in terms of scope and availability of research and education, but also in the methodological quality of existing studies. A number of shortfalls in knowledge, evidence and education pertaining to wound management in the wider sense were identified, an overview of which is provided below:

- domination of studies adopting post-positivist quantitative, descriptive approaches which were not of high quality in methodological terms (i.e., surveys and questionnaires employing simple, descriptive statistical analysis);
- no evidence at Randomised Controlled Trial (RCT) level;
- a shortage of studies adopting interpretive and constructivist approaches exploring in-depth, rich, contextual aspects in wound management;

- shortfalls in the application of evidence-based practice (EBP) including inconsistent application of guidelines and poor links between academia and practice;
- inadequate wound management knowledge amongst nurses from a range of clinical areas; and within specific wound management practices (i.e., pressure ulcers, leg ulcers, etc.)
- inadequate wound management knowledge amongst nurses within specific aspects of wound management (i.e., wound cleansing, wound infection, wound bed preparation, etc.)
- the prevalence of historic and ritualistic practice and utilisation of experiential knowledge over referral to formal evidence; particularly in generalist nurses
- Inconsistent links between theoretical knowledge, competence and clinical decision making
- shortfalls in structured wound management education at pre-registration, post-registration and continuing professional development (CPD) levels for nurses;
- A lack of standardisation in the preparation and education of wound management specialists globally.
- An inconsistent approach for the role and education of the TVN in the in the UK.
- a considerable reliance upon industry for the development of wound management evidence and education;
- An uncritical and accepting attitude towards industry relationship by nurses

Despite the continued dominance of the scientific and technical model in wider health care research (Denny 2010) and increasing prevalence of studies adopting this paradigm, methodological limitations were evident in a number of the studies of quantitative design which were reviewed. For example, no Randomised Controlled Trial (RCT) level studies, which are considered to be high on the traditional hierarchy of evidence, were sourced with the majority of studies adopting a post-positivist approach. A large proportion adopted basic quantitative design; for example, surveys and questionnaires employing descriptive statistical analysis. Whilst post-positivist studies may increase generalisability when compared to those adopting qualitative design, they may also limit the capture of reality and experience (Polit and Beck 2017). A shortage of high-quality qualitative literature generating rich descriptive and contextual data relating to wound management was also identified;

meaning that studies supporting wound management were of limited scope and range overall. While a scarcity of evidence which is high on the traditional hierarchy may be the most noteworthy limitation of the evidence base supporting wound management, the shortage of studies applying a qualitative approach should also be highlighted here since nursing is a practice-based profession which relies on context. As such, quantitative experimental studies may be considered too far removed from the clinical context to fully capture wound management practice (Polit and Beck 2017).

In terms of quality assurance, methodological quality was found to be limited in a number of studies; several of which were initiated opportunistically at conference proceedings. This makes assurance that rigorous methodological design; for example, in relation to ethical considerations, difficult to verify. A number of the quantitative studies failed to clarify whether validated data collation tools were utilised for example, and sample sizes in many of those reviewed were also relatively small. There was also a high incidence of participant dropout rates in several studies; which is likely to have impacted upon reliability of findings (Cunningham et al. 2013; Polit and Beck 2017). Of those studies adopting a quantitative approach, not all carried out power calculations in relation to sampling; therefore, affecting overall strength of data and transferability (Cunningham et al. 2013). Similarly, it was unknown in certain studies whether participants were previously known to researchers and potential for researcher effect was not acknowledged or explicitly addressed. This presented potential ethical implications which were not consistently articulated. Finally, several relied upon self-reported data and for a number of those reviewed, systematic collation and analysis was not explicit. Several of the included studies acknowledged the deficit in the quality of wound care research and made recommendations about the requirement to adopt a more robust approach to evidence formation. Yet; deficits in the evidence base were widely attributed to the overall dearth of studies, rather than to the methodological quality of those conducted.

Shortfalls and limitations in wound management knowledge in the wider sense were highlighted in a number of studies (Edwards et al. 2005; McClusky and McCarthy 2012; Ashton and Price 2013; Gillespie et al. 2014; Zarachi et al. 2014; Ferriera et al. 2016; Gonzaga deFaria et al. 2016; Gray et al. 2019; Kielo et al. 2019a; Kielo et al. 2019b; Kielo et al. 2019c). Particular evidence deficits were identified within individual nursing specialities including paediatrics and neonates (Dugdall and Watson 2009), mental health (Stephen-Haynes and Greenwood 2011) and palliative care (Willis and Sutton 2013; Gillespie et al. 2014); as well as in particular areas of practice such as leg ulcers (Haram et al. 2003; Hjelm et al. 2003; Barratt et al. 2009; Thompson and Adderley 2014; Ylonen et al. 2014; Adderley and Thompson 2015), pressure ulcers (Lamond and Farnell 1998; Miyazaki et al. 2010;

Samuiwiwo 2010; Beeckman et al. 2011; Moore and Clarke 2011; Cullen and Moore 2013; Tubaishat et al. 2013; Qaddumi and Khawaldeh 2014; Samuiwiwo and Dowding 2014; Hossein et al. 2015; Simonetti et al. 2015; Pieper et al. 2016; Etafa et al. 2018; Cardoso et al. 2019) and foot ulcers (Haram et al. 2003). Shortfalls in specific aspects of wound management; for example, wound bed assessment and preparation were also highlighted (Kennedy and Arundel 1998a; Kennedy and Arudel 1998b; Haram et al. 2003; Beeckman et al. 2011; Cook 2011; Friman et al. 2011; Deeth and Grothier 2016; Hughes 2016; Ousey et al. 2016a); along with insufficient understanding of dressing types (Haram et al. 2003; Dugdall and Watson 2009; Barratt et al. 2009; Cowman et al. 2011; Innes-Walker and Edwards 2013; Gillespie et al. 2014; Gray et al. 2019). In generic aspects of wound management, Zarchi et al. (2014) identified a knowledge of investigations as being lesser than that pertaining to therapy and treatment; while Stephen-Haynes and Greenwood (2011) found shortfalls in both prevention and provision of clinical care for mental health nurses.

Links between knowledge and attitudes were considered by a number of studies, most frequently in relation to the pressure ulcer prevention. While some found clear links between the attitudes of clinicians and the development of wound management knowledge in the more generic sense (Dugdall and Watson 2009; Etafa et al. 2018); other studies found links to be more tenuous (Cullen and Moore 2013; Tubaishat et al. 2013; Simonetti et al. 2015; Kielo et al. 2019a; 2019b; 2019c). An additional shortfall in the range of evidence was that a large number of studies were carried out in the acute setting; which limited the generalisability of findings to other clinical areas; and more significantly, left the community setting, where most wound management practice in the UK takes place, insufficiently researched (Cook 2011; Logan 2015).

The next section will explore particular themes identified in the literature in further detail.

Application of clinical evidence to practice

The application of evidence to practice was found to be limited in a number of studies (Lamond and Farnell 1998; Dugdall & Watson 2009; Miyazaki et al. 2010; Beeckman et al. 2011; McCluskey and McCarthy 2012; Ashton and Price 2013; Ferriera et al. 2014; Gillespie et al. 2014; Samuiwiwo and Dowding 2014; Ylonen et al. 2014; Gillespie et al. 2015; Logan 2015; Simonetti et al. 2015; Gonzaga de Faria et al. 2016; Gray et al. 2019). This revealed an existing gap between theoretical knowledge and practice that was notable in specific areas of wound management practice (i.e. pressure ulcer and leg ulcer management) (Miyazaki et al. 2010; Cullen and Moore 2013; Qaddumi and Khawaldeh 2014; Simonetti et al. 2015; Pieper et al. 2016) and with knowledge and skills in the generic sense (i.e. wound assessment) (Miyazaki et al. 2010; Gillespie et al. 2014; Qaddumi and Khawaldeh 2014;

Thompson and Adderley 2014; Adderley and Thompson 2015). Time and resource challenges prevented many clinicians from reviewing research evidence which had a negative impact on the application of evidence (Friman et al. 2011; Tubaishat et al. 2013; Etafa et al 2018; Gray et al. 2019); while poor partnerships and integration between academic institutions and clinical sectors adversely affected links between evidence and practice (Dugdall and Watson 2008; Ousey et al. 2013a; Gonzaga de Faria 2016; Gray et al. 2019). A positive correlation between application of evidence and knowledge was found in some studies (Dugdall and Watson 2009; Simonetti et al. 2015); with positive clinician attitude found to improve levels of evidence application (Samuiriwo 2010; Etafa et al. 2018; Kielo et al. 2019a; 2019b; 2019c). Miyazaki et al. (2010) found that both educational and individual factors accounted for level of knowledge and application of clinical guidelines; whilst Simonetti et al. (2015) acknowledged a positive attitude towards clinical guidelines to be a contributing factor to clinician compliance in their utilisation. Ashton and Price (2013) found that whilst generalist clinicians routinely referred to other colleagues and experience in practice to guide practice, specialist clinicians were more likely to utilise evidence from formal sources such as journals.

Although clinical guidelines remain one of the most utilised sources of formal evidence by clinicians in practice, the review found that clinicians did not always apply or adhere to recommendations by guidelines and protocols or in certain cases, demonstrate an awareness of their existence (Ferreira et al. 2014; Gillespie et al. 2014; Samuiriwo and Dowding 2014; Gonzaga de Faria et al. 2016). This was recognised in relation to generic wound management (Cowman et al. 2011; Innes-Walker and Edwards 2013; Logan 2015; Ferreira et al. 2014; Gonzaga de Faria et al. 2016) but also to specific skills such as debridement (Ousey et al. 2016a) and particular areas of practice such as pressure ulcers (Miyazaki et al. 2010; Cullen and Moore 2014; Qaddumi and Khawaldeh 2014; Simonetti et al. 2015; Pieper et al. 2016) and leg ulcers (Thompson and Adderley 2014; Ylonen et al. 2014; Adderley and Thompson 2015). A descriptive- explorative study carried out by Miyazaki et al. (2010) in Brazil, used Pieper's Pressure Ulcer Knowledge Test (PUKT), a validated tool based on international guidelines, to measure participant knowledge in pressure ulcer prevention (PUP). Participants included nurses, nursing technicians/auxiliaries with PUP found to be insufficient in all groups; and the percentage of correct answers as: 79.4% (nurses) and 73.6% in technicians/auxiliaries. It was recognised that at the time of the study, there were no national guidelines for PUP in Brazil; suggesting that findings cannot be assumed to be transferrable to countries such as the UK where national guidelines are in place. Since the study was carried out in an acute setting, it may

additionally fail to reflect the knowledge and skills of clinicians working in community roles where the majority of wound management in the UK is carried out.

Inconsistent application of evidence also revealed the frequent utilisation of knowledge from less formal sources, for example; that gained from personal experience and from clinical colleagues and specialists (Kennedy and Arundel 1998a; Kennedy and Arundel 1998b; Haram et al. 2003; Edwards et al. 2005; Ashton and Price 2013; Gillespie et al. 2014; Qaddumi and Khawaldeh 2014; Samuirwo and Dowding 2014; Gillespie et al. 2015; Gonzaga de Faria et al. 2016; Gray et al. 2019). Prevalence of ritualistic practice in wound management was also identified here (Dugdall and Watson 2009; Mizazaki et al. 2010; Beeckman et al. 2011; McCluskey and McCarthy 2012; Ashton and Price 2013; Ferriera et al. 2014; Gillespie et al. 2014; Qaddum and Khawaldeh 2014; Gonzaga de Faria et al. 2016; Hughes 2016).

Links between knowledge and competence

Relationships between knowledge and competence were explored by several studies with mixed findings. In contrast to the majority of studies reviewed, McClusky and McCarthy (2012) found nurses' wound management knowledge to be good overall and positively affected by education; with competence found to be improved more visibly by experience. This was echoed by Cullen and Moore (2013) who found student nurses' positive attitudes to wound management to be linked to competency but not knowledge. In other studies, links between level of knowledge and length of experience were not identified (Qaddumi and Khawaldeh 2014; Zarachi et al. 2014). Ousey et al. (2016a) found discrepancies between knowledge and practice in the area of debridement. While nurses were found to understand its importance in the theoretical sense, they did not report to feeling competent in practice. Studies by Kielo et al (2019a; 2019b; 2019c) comparing wound management knowledge and competence in student nurses and podiatrists found a positive correlation between knowledge and competence. Whilst both disciplines recognised their own competence to be limited; those with more time spent training in practice, scored higher in a knowledge test; thus, identifying positive links between the two. These findings were supported by McClusky and McCarthy (2012) who added that when regularly updated, links between knowledge and competence improved. Meanwhile, Allison (1995) found that theoretical knowledge made a positive contribution to practice, but only when applied on an ongoing basis; therefore, reinforcing a perceived link between knowledge and competence with frequency and regularity of clinical application.

Clinical decision making

Clinical decision making and reasoning in wound management were considered by a number of studies. Many clinical guidelines for wound management identify the importance of utilising clinical judgement when selecting wound management products (Madden 2012); however, studies reviewed here found that it varied significantly (Lamond and Farnell 1998; Barratt et al. 2009; Samuiriwo and Dowding 2014; Logan 2015). Research by Thompson and Adderley (2014) and Adderley and Thompson (2015) exploring decision-making within leg ulcer management found it to be inconsistent and complex; whilst Logan (2015) added that for community nurses, it was individualised and context specific. These findings were supported by Hallett et al. (2014) and Gillespie et al. (2015) who found clinical decision-making to be a personalised and highly intuitive process; yet a study by Hjelm et al. (2003) comparing community nurses in the UK and Sweden found the ability to holistically integrate knowledge to be insufficient overall; but somewhat better in Swedish nurses. The ability to integrate formal and informal knowledge types holistically in clinical decision making was also explored in an Australian study by Gillespie et al. (2015) who found that nurses' practice-based knowledge was developed and relatively balanced with that derived from evidence. Nonetheless, knowledge in this area was more weighted towards intuitive practice. Wider factors were identified components of nurses' decision making in wound management; for example, cost and the need of the patient, demonstrating a holistic approach to knowledge formation.

Of the few studies specifically considering the knowledge of both generalists and specialists, specialists' clinical decision making was found to be more accurate and of better quality but still lacking overall (Lamond and Farnell 1998; Edwards et al. 2005; Ashton and Price 2013; Thompson and Adderley 2014; Adderley and Thompson 2015). Clinicians from both groups were found to utilise knowledge from experiential and personal sources, but specialists more frequently referred to formal sources of evidence (Ashton and Price 2013). Only three studies considered the role of the medical professional in relation to wound management knowledge development; two within the community/primary care context and one in the acute setting. Innes-Walker and Edwards (2013) and Friman et al. (2011) found GPs knowledge to be insufficient; with the latter attributing this to a lack of interest and apathy towards wound management as an area of practice. In contrast, Ashton and Price (2013) found that within specialist wound management practice in a hospital setting, medical staff dominated clinical decision making. Although this was the only study that considered the power of the medical profession as an influencing factor in the context of clinical decision making, a study by Radcliffe (2000) acknowledged the power imbalance between the value given to the opinions of doctors and those of nurses across wider clinical areas.

A small number of studies explored the role and nature of intuition in knowledge development and clinical decision-making within wound management. Although it was not the primary focus of exploration; Hallett et al. (2014), Gillespie et al. (2015) and Logan (2015) identified intuitive practice as underpinning most clinical decision-making in this capacity; with the majority regarding intuition as being correlated with an ability to draw on practice learning and experience (Kennedy and Arundel 1998a; Kennedy and Arundel 1998b; Hallett et al 2014; Gillespie et al. 2015; Logan 2015). Hallett et al. (2014), pointed out that although intuitive in nature, clinical decision-making in wound management was also a form of complex diagnostic reasoning. However, Lamond and Farnell (1998) concluded that more research into decision making in this context was required.

Wound management education and training

All studies exploring wound management education found it to be insufficient for nurses at various levels of practice (Dugdall & Watson 2009; Cowman et al. 2011; Moore and Clarke 2011; McCluskey and McCarthy 2012; Innes-Walker and Edwards 2013; Ousey et al. 2013b; Cullen and Moore 2013; Stephen-Haynes 2013; Gillespie et al. 2014; Ferriera et al. 2014; Quaddum and Khawaldeh 2014; Romero-Collado et al. 2014; Gonzaga de Faria et al. 2016; Pieper et al. 2016). Studies exploring undergraduate nursing education found that student nurses felt insufficiently prepared both in wider wound management and in particular areas of practice (i.e., pressure ulcer prevention and chronic wounds) (Cowman et al. 2011; Moore and Clarke 2011; Innes-Walker and Edwards 2013; Ousey et al. 2013b; Stephen -Haynes 2013; Romero-Collado et al 2014; Hossein et al. 2015; Pieper et al. 2016; Kielo et al. 2019a; Kielo et al 2019b; Kielo et al 2019c). Pre-registration nursing curriculums in a number of countries were reported to be inadequate; in terms of quantity of practice hours and experience (Allison 1995; Ousey et al. 2013b; Stephen-Haynes 2013; Pieper et al. 2016) and overall content. In the UK, this was attributed to a reported failure to prioritise wound management as speciality (Dugdall and Watson 2009; Ousey et al. 2013b). This has contributed to poor links between theory and practice and the failure of to meet overall wound management competencies identified in several studies (Allison 1995; Moore and Clarke 2011; Ousey et al. 2013b; Romero-Collado et al. 2014; Pieper et al. 2016).

While both theory and practice were determined to be equally important by some (Kielo et al. 2019a; 2019b; 2019c); other studies highlighted the unique importance of practice experience in the development of wound management knowledge and competence (Allison 1995; Ousey et al. 2013b; Simonetti et al. 2015; Pieper et al. 2016; Kielo et al. 2019a; Kielo et al. 2019b; Kielo et al. 2019c). A grounded theory study by Samuirio (2010) found that direct experience with caring for a pressure ulcer in practice was the key factor in changing

nurses' value of pressure ulcer prevention; not education. This was supported by McClusky and McCarthy (2012) who found number of wounds treated per week increased competence but not necessarily knowledge. Studies by Kielo et al. (2019a; 2019b; 2019c) comparing wound management competence in student nurses and podiatrists found podiatrists to have more competence in practice. Only Holloway (2017) considered the impact of postgraduate studies in wound management and found some evidence of its positive impact on practice; however, this was in relation to a particular individual curriculum in a single identified education facility which may not be transferrable in the wider educational context. However, non-specified wound management education was found to improve knowledge in other studies (Dugdall and Watson 2009). An Australian training needs analysis of clinicians practicing in wound management found multiple learning needs amongst practitioners from a range of backgrounds but identified those of clinicians working in primary care (i.e., GPs; community nurses) to be the greatest (Innes-Walker and Edwards 2013). Learning needs were also found to vary with context; with the largest identified gaps relating to basic wound management skills including assessment, prevention and diagnosis. Although the study mirrored findings of conducted in the UK, it cannot be assumed that it is transferrable due to international differences in models of health care delivery and demographics. Nevertheless, the identification of particular learning needs amongst clinicians in primary care may be of some consideration to the UK context given that this is where most wound management is carried out. This was reinforced by Ousey et al. (2013b) who maintained that more nurse education was needed in the UK.

In addition to formal education, CPD (i.e., training undertaken at in-house study days, conferences and education sessions) was also explored. Edwards et al. (2005) and Qaddumi and Khawaldeh (2014) found that most nurses' wound management knowledge arose mainly from non-accredited learning with Gray et al. (2019) adding that much of this was delivered by the pharmaceutical industry. In the UK, nurses stated that they obtained most of their education in-house; often from TVNs or representatives from industry; meaning that a standardised, evaluated approach could not be assured and potential for conflicts of interest and marketable aims of companies could not be adequately controlled or eliminated (Madden 2012; Ousey et al. 2013b). Although Dugdall and Watson (2009) found unaccredited training to have a positive impact on level of knowledge; Ashton and Price (2013) and Efata et al. (2018); found wound management training to be inadequate overall; with constraints including time, lack of available resources and attitudes identified as influencing factors on quality and access to education and PDP (Ashton and Price 2013; Tubaishat et al. 2013; Gray et al. 2019).

Specialist nurses (TVNs)

While certain domains of wound management have traditionally fallen under the remit of the medical profession (i.e., dermatology, plastic surgery and vascular surgery); tissue viability education within undergraduate medical education was found to be minimal and practice in this area continued to be widely associated with nursing (Cowman et al. 2011; Ousey et al. 2013b; Ousey et al. 2015). An additional factor emerging from the literature revealed challenges associated with the wider aspects of tissue viability as a clinical speciality and variations in TVN education and standards of practice, both in the UK and internationally (Flanagan 1998a; Flanagan 1998b; Fox 2001; Dutton et al. 2014; Ousey et al. 2015). Two seminal literature reviews by Flanagan (1998a; 1998b) and Fox (2001) explored the role of the TVN in the UK; with Flanagan (1998a; 1998b) determining it to be less regulated and consistent than international equivalents due to a chaotic historic development nationally. The findings of this review have attributed this to two key causes: a misinterpretation of the original UKCC (1994) model of specialist practice; and a subsequent failure to align indicators of specialist practice to explicitly defined specialist roles. This has led to a persisting lack of role standardisation and consensus in relation to education and regulation (Fox 2001) and competence (Dutton et al. 2014; Ousey et al. 2015). As a result, professional organisations and employing institutions had been historically left to develop local standards for the TV specialist role which has led to considerable variation (Flanagan 1998a; 1998b). Flanagan additionally found the terms specialist and advanced practice were used interchangeably despite their distinctions; a confusion that continues, even though the review projected that the TV specialist role should gain further consistency and clarity over time. Fox (2001) found that there were several working titles for the role. Although Flanagan (1998a; 1998b) found role instability to increase stress amongst TV specialists, the literature also highlighted the positive aspects attributed to it. A survey by Ousey et al. (2015) examining the role found all clinical respondents to have access to a TV service; with TVNs enjoying professional and strategic power as gatekeepers of specialist knowledge and service provision (Ousey et al. 2015). Evidence from this study also supported a link between specialist TV nurses and positive outcomes which included improved healing and a decreased prevalence of pressure ulcers. Unlike comparable specialities, the TVN role has not been the focus of any sufficient economic evaluation using key performance indicators (Ousey et al. 2013b; Ousey et al. 2015). In contrast to the North American counterpart, specialist education for TVNs remains unregulated and/or unregistered with a professional regulatory body. These factors, along with failure to deliver high quality research output, have contributed to its establishment as a reported under resourced 'Cinderella service'

(Stephen-Haynes and Greenwood 2011; Ousey et al. 2013b; Ousey et al 2015). Ousey et al. (2015) added that TVNs' links with the development of research remain weak.

A study by Holloway (2017) exploring the effect of post-graduate study in advanced tissue repair on clinical practice in wound management reported positive links between the two; suggesting that education is an important indicator of specialist practice. An Australian phenomenological analysis of an advanced practice nursing (APN) framework found the model to be effective in the context of a professional development programme for TV nurses; however, implementation of the accepted domains was inconsistent and variable in practice (Upton et al. 2015). Although carried out in Australia, the APN domains align closely to the equivalent of the UK model and therefore findings may be transferrable to some degree.

Generalist nurses (DNs and CSNs)

Although several of the reviewed papers focused on the acute setting (Dugdall and Watson 2009; Mizazaki et al. 2010; McCluskey & McCarthy 2012; Innes-Walker and Edwards 2013; Ferriera et al. 2014; Gillespie et al. 2014; Qaddum and Khawaldeh 2014; Gonzaga de Faria et al. 2016), a number also explored wound management in the community setting. The findings identified similar issues as nursing in the wider sense in the UK and further afield; yet a number of studies also highlighted shortfalls and challenges that were particular to DN and community nurses (Kennedy and Arundel 1998a; Kennedy and Arundel 1998b; Davies et al. 1999; Haram et al. 2003; Hjelm et al. 2003; Barrett et al. 2009; Cook 2011; Friman et al. 2011; Willis and Sutton 2013; Adderley and Thompson 2014; Hallett et al. 2014; Logan 2015; Thompson and Adderley 2015; Gray et al. 2019).

Wound assessment was found to be limited; with Cook (2011) and Adderley and Thompson (2015) identifying that community nurses failed to utilise structured assessment tools and Kennedy and Arundel (1998a;1998b) revealing a combination of observation and experience as the most commonly applied method for assessing wounds in practice. Hallett et al. (2014) found community nurses to draw on a range of information sources to guide clinical decision making in the context of wound management; but as a largely intuitive process. Logan (2015) supported the importance of intuition in this capacity, but pointed to number of specific shortfalls which contributed to variability in community nurses' practice; including a lack of knowledge about specific treatments, contextual uncertainties and an inability to interpret clinical information. Although consideration of wider holistic factors is arguably a key ability required to deliver effective wound management in a community setting, Hjelm et al. (2003) found community nurses in Sweden and the UK to pay insufficient attention to them in practice.

Within the scope of leg ulcer management Haram et al. (2003); found an overall lack of knowledge in the diagnosis, assessment, treatment and use of products. A survey of Irish community nurses by Barratt et al. (2009), identified specific deficiencies including an insufficient understanding and use of Doppler, lack of awareness of the principles of Laplaces' Law and an inappropriate use of primary dressings in leg ulcer management. A judgement analysis of by Adderley & Thompson (2014) found variability in overall performance accuracy in both diagnosis and treatment of venous leg ulceration in community nurses. The need for additional education to support practice was recognised in this context (Davies et al. 1999). Although community nurses reported their leg ulcer knowledge to be regularly updated in some cases, this was not consistently reflected in practice (Barratt et al. 2009) and colleagues and experience were identified as the main sources of knowledge (Haram et al. 2003; Gray et al. 2019). However, some good practice was also highlighted in relation to the utilisation of current leg ulcer guidelines (Barratt et al. 2009).

Willis and Sutton (2013) identified particular challenges in knowledge development in relation to palliative wounds amongst DNs and proposed the need for an interactive educational programme to meet specific educational demands. Since leg ulcers and palliative wounds are likely to remain as core functions for DNs for the foreseeable future, knowledge gaps in these areas should be regarded as particularly concerning. This was supported by Cook (2011) who identified the requirement for more comprehensive wound management education for community nurses. The pharmaceutical industry was also revealed as a key source of wound management education for community nurses (Gray et al. 2019).

Friman et al. (2011) identified a lack of priority and interest in wound management on the part of GPs, the health care professional with whom DNs work most closely as a key barrier to development of it as a speciality. Although carried out in Sweden, the generic working relationships within the community sector are structurally similar to those in the UK; and therefore transferable. Additional barriers were also highlighted; including organisational shortcomings such as lack of resources (i.e., dressings, equipment etc.) and insufficient time. Gray et al. (2019) added financial and work pressures and variation in application of research and evidence as barriers. The role-specific challenges associated with the wider health care policy agenda for DN practice which were discussed in the background chapter, should also be considered as barriers impacting on the context of wound management practice in the community.

Industry in wound management

The impact and influence of industry and its role in the development of wound management evidence and knowledge was also considered in the review. A study by Madden (2012), applying an observational case study approach at a national educational conference, found evidence supporting wound management to be highly corporate in nature, and focusing on the dissemination and marketing of technological product innovation rather than the formal evidence supporting holistic assessment and underlying conditions contributing to the development of wounds. Since wound management products are categorised as medical devices rather than medicinal products, companies are not permitted to advertise directly to patients and marketing is targeted directly at clinicians. In addition to advertising in clinical journals, this was found to include high-contact with clinicians attending educational conferences and forging key relationships with TVNs (Dumville et al. 2009; Madden 2012). Dumville et al. (2009) found that a large proportion of advertisements in clinical journals were related to medical devices including wound management products, with most failing to include citations to support product claims with evidence, which were as such, misleading to readers. Ashmore et al. (2007) concurred; adding that greater examination of the influence of journal advertising on clinicians was required. Dumville et al. (2008) found that the publication of wound research in clinical and scientific journals was less likely than in other specialities; while Madden (2012) added that the content of debate at wound management conferences focused on quality of technological innovation rather than underlying conditions or methodological quality of research presented. Although the focus remained on innovation, its links to outcomes for wound healing remain unsubstantiated. Quality was also questioned; as Madden (2012) upheld that variation rather than true innovation dominated. Finally, discussions about RCTs and systematic reviews revealed a negative view by many conference participants; who regarded them as being too removed from clinical practice and having a restrictive effect on wound management research which prompted calls to remove their application in this context. The development of the AGREE (Appraisal of Guidelines, Research and Evaluation) guideline-rating system (2001), which developed in recognition of the limited objectivity of industry-sponsored consensus documents in wound management was also considered as restrictive. Madden (2012) concluded that, with no alternative for clinicians, conferences were more akin to trade fairs than academic conferences; which positioned wound management as more of a corporate science than a genuine clinical speciality. Although benefits from engagement between industry and health care were also perceived (i.e., information-sharing about new products, exposure to experts and dissemination of research findings) (Kessenich and Westbrook 1999), the potential cost implications and conflict of interest were considered downsides.

As gatekeepers for the dissemination of wound management research and education, clinician's views and understanding of relationships with industry were also of importance here and were a focus for exploration by several studies (Kessenich and Westbrook 1999; Monaghan et al. 2003; Ashmore et al. 2007; Crigger et al. 2009). All those reviewed determined that nurses largely viewed the role of industry uncritically, regarding it as beneficial and having educational value. An American study by Monaghan et al. (2003) comparing student nurses, doctors and pharmacists found that although all took this primarily uncritical view of industry, student nurses and doctors interacted more closely with industry representatives than student pharmacists. A correlation between level of participation and critical awareness was also found; with an increase in industry engagement leading to a less-critical view. The study found the relationship between clinicians to be based on a "gift mentality"; whereby level of self-interest and consensus from other engaged clinicians were revealed as factors that shaped views and level of participation. While some found nurses to be largely unaware of an existing conflict of interest with industry engagement (Monaghan et al. 2003; Ashmore et al. 2007; Crigger et al. 2009); Monaghan et al. (2003) and Madden (2012), revealed that although sensitive to this potential in others, many nurses considered themselves to be above influence. Monaghan et al. (2003) identified a scale of ethical acceptability which determined certain activities (i.e., sponsored trips) as unacceptable, and others (i.e., educational conferences) as appropriate and presenting minimal conflict of interest. This was partly attributed to the lack of education about industry engagement received in the undergraduate curriculums of clinicians such as nurses and doctors; leading to its recommendation by the authors. Although it was conducted in the US, findings should be transferrable to the UK where similar lack of education in industry engagement have also been identified.

Although potential for ethical misconduct has been acknowledged; views on clinician links with industry remain mixed and it has been proposed by some wound management experts that links between health service providers and industry have a positive impact upon research and practice development which should be maintained (Ousey et al. 2013a; Ousey et al. 2015). To support this stance, an exemplar has been made of the key institution of academic and research excellence in wound management in the UK, which continues to forge ties with industry and attract international students from a range of clinical health care professions. Whilst many health care managers have become increasingly reluctant to permit clinician engagement with industry in light of these concerns, Ousey et al. (2015) argue that codes of conduct for both industry partners and clinicians employed by the National Health Service (NHS) should ensure governance and ethical conduct and links with industry should be facilitated rather than restricted. One notable benefit is that industry can

freely access the research teams, equipment, facilities and financial resources necessary to conduct quality studies and as such, partnership with the NHS should be perceived as mutually beneficial to both parties. Nonetheless, the shortage of original, independent research dictates that nurses are left little choice but to rely heavily upon evidence that is placed lower on the traditional hierarchy; with wound management continuing to be largely shaped by expert opinion and consensus documents (Madden 2003; Gillespie et al. 2014).

The power of specific clinical roles should also be considered in this context; for example, the TVN, who represents the key stakeholder in formulary development, practice and education and with whom industry representatives endeavour to influence and forge relationships with (Madden 2012). A study by Radcliffe (2000) also considered power in relation to the opinions of the traditionally male doctor and female nurse and the associated cultural implications (Radcliffe 2000); whilst Madden (2012) pointed to the recent lobbying to prevent additional regulation in pharmaceutical industry in this context as evidence of the government's economic dependence and strategic power over ongoing developments. Madden (2012) also identified an increasing recognition that industry has been in a position of having too much historic power in this context (Health Committee 2005).

Typologies of knowledge supporting nursing practice have been widely discussed (Carper 1978; Benner 1982; Garrett and Cutting 2014; Chinn and Kramer 2015; Pahor et al. 2015; Williams and Burke 2015; Davis and Maisano 2016; Lockwood and Hopp 2016; Voldbjerg et al. 2016). Within District Nursing, unique knowledge has also been recognised. A seminal study by Kennedy (2004) identified six types of DN knowledge including getting to know the patient in their own setting; getting to know carers; knowing what needs to be done now; knowing what may happen in the future; knowing/recognising knowledge deficits and knowing community resources and services. Although the study is several years old and not entirely reflective of contemporary DN practice, the findings remain of interest in highlighting the particularly tacit components of DN knowledge. However, the observational design dictates that findings were drawn from a narrow window of data and are therefore likely to offer only limited insight into DN knowledge. Emancipatory knowing was also notably absent from this knowledge set. Kennedy's findings were supported by a more recent study by Bain (2015) exploring the unique knowing in DN practice, which proposed that DN knowledge remains particularly challenging to examine because of its hidden nature and inherent links to local structures and context.

Summary

This literature review revealed several limitations in the existing knowledge and evidence underpinning specialist and generalist wound management practice. This included a

prevalence of ritualistic practice, educational deficits in wound management at pre and post registration and CPD levels and shortfalls relating to the quality and nature of the evidence base itself. The influential role of industry in knowledge development; proposing potential conflicts of interest and an evidence base that is disproportionately corporate in nature, was found to be a contributing factor in this respect. Links between knowledge and practice were found to be inconsistent, with variations in the application of clinical guidelines and links between theory and practice. Poor role definition and inconsistency have left the TVN, the key clinician involved in the provision of specialist wound management poorly defined and represented compared to similar specialties. Unique challenges pertaining to the DN role have also negatively impacted upon their perceived ability to carry out duties, including wound management to a sufficient standard.

Much of the reviewed literature focused on levels of wound management knowledge; as well as the generic and specific deficits in evidence and education which have been widely identified. However, the quality and nature of this knowledge has not been explored in any sufficient depth. Whilst previous work has been carried out exploring the nature of knowledge in the wider context of nursing and within DN practice; there is insufficient in-depth understanding of the knowledge that either specialist or generalist nurses utilise within wound management practice or how the challenges and shortfalls which have been identified impact upon its development and utilisation. This is notable for formal evidence but also for informal knowledge types (i.e., experiential knowledge learned through practice and colleagues) which have been recognised as having particular importance in practice-based professions such as nursing. Informal knowledge may have additional and unique implications for both wound management specialists such as TVNs and community nurses such as DNs since they are to a sufficient degree, lone workers whose work is somewhat hidden and might be of particular relevance for DN practice due its unique complexity. Although a limited number of studies have explored both specialist and generalist nurses as participants, these have been in relation to specific shortfalls and aspects of wound management knowledge (i.e., venous leg ulcers) and no previous study has made substantial comparisons between specialists and generalist nurses or explored the relationships between profession-specific challenges and the nature of knowledge development comprehensively.

A limited number of studies have also highlighted the impact of industry on evidence formation and clinician education; however; no previous study has explored its impact in-the context of wound management practice and knowledge development in-depth. The main scholarly feature of this study was the creation of a new understanding of an existing issue, the nature of knowledge in specialist and generalist nurses delivering wound management.

By bringing together this available literature on clinicians' knowledge of wound management, it has become apparent that further research is vital to gain a more comprehensive appreciation of the nature of knowledge within the wider context since little is understood about the knowledge that specialist or generalist nurses utilise within wound management practice or how challenges impact on knowledge development and transference. This is notably the case for informal knowledge types (i.e., experiential knowledge learned through practice and colleagues) which have particular importance in practice-based professions such as nursing. Informal knowledge may have unique implications for both wound management specialists (TVNs) and community nurses (DNs). As such, a multidimensional model, capturing the decidedly complex and somewhat hidden nature of knowledge of specialist and generalist nurses practicing in wound management should be comprehensively studied. Future research should consider methods for obtaining a richer understanding of the origins and nature of knowledge among clinicians who play a key role in the delivery of clinical or educational wound management and consider methods for obtaining a richer understanding of the origins and nature of knowledge among clinicians who play a key role in the delivery of clinical or educational wound management. Based on this pooled information, it is proposed that future work is steered toward:

- unravelling patterns of knowing for both specialist and generalist nurses who play key roles in the delivery of clinical and/or educational wound management;
- exploring how this might impact the current wound management context; • drawing comparisons between TVNs and DNs/CSNs;
- identifying any dominant patterns of knowing and the factors that contribute to this;
- addressing the implications of this for wound management practice and education.

Aim of the present study

The aim of the present study was to gain a detailed and rich understanding of the origins and nature of knowledge in specialist and generalist nurses with a key role in the delivery of clinical or educational wound management. The research questions were:

- What are the patterns of knowing for specialist and generalist nurses with key roles in the delivery of clinical and/or educational wound management and how has this been affected by the current wound management context?
- Do any particular pattern(s) dominate and if so, what factors have contributed to this?

- What comparisons can be made between specialist and generalist nurses?
- What are implications of these findings for wound management practice and education?

Chapter 3 Methodological, theoretical and conceptual frameworks

Introduction

In order to address the study's aims, a qualitative approach was adopted utilising Chinn and Kramer's *Patterns of Knowing* (2015) as a conceptual framework from which to explore and compare types of knowledge in the context of wound management practice. Prior to discussing the methods applied, this chapter explores the theoretical and conceptual frameworks underpinning the methodological approach.

Theoretical framework

There is much debate about the nature and application of theory in research and no consistent definition of a theoretical framework exists. Whilst some researchers consider theory to be situated at a generalised level out with the confines of methodology (i.e., "grand" theory) (Huff 2009); others regard paradigms, ontology and epistemology as theoretical perspectives which form the assumptions that guide and underpin studies (Biesta Allan and Edwards 2011; Hammersley 2012; Anfara & Mertz 2015). Still others debate whether there is a requirement for theory in research at all; and it is accepted that this will be to some degree, dependent upon the design and nature of the study (Avis 2003; Anfara 2008). Braun and Clarke (2019) argue that the presence of theory in qualitative approaches is inevitable and what distinguishes studies from being purely descriptive. A seminal work by Kerlinger (1970) defined theory as forming the relationship between elements, components, concepts and constructs which describe, explain and predict. Theoretical frameworks have also been defined as empiric theories of psychological and/or social processes from which phenomena can be explored and understood (Anfara 2008). Although some authors use the terms *theoretical framework* and *conceptual framework* interchangeably (Anfara 2008); others argue that there are key distinctions between them; maintaining that whilst theoretical frameworks explain at high levels of abstraction; conceptual frameworks are concerned with key concepts within a particular piece of research (Cohen, Manion & Morrison 2018).

In studies adopting interpretivist and constructivist approaches, theory is often embedded in ideological or epistemological assumptions; therefore, serving as a lens through which exploration and understanding of a topic can be facilitated (Clarke et al. 2019). From this perspective, theoretical frameworks infiltrate almost every aspect of a study; since the researcher brings pre-existing experiences, beliefs and knowledge to the study which shape the aims; and act as a construct around data and the relationships that exists between them (Anfara and Mertz 2015). The theoretical framework applied in this study was therefore rooted in its qualitative approach and more specifically, the spectrum between post-

structuralism and interpretivism/constructivism rather than in a particular methodological design. This supports Braun and Clarke's (2006; 2012; 2013) conceptualisation of Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA) as having its theoretical framework situated at level of paradigm, ontology or epistemology. With this in mind, Braun and Clarke's RTA was selected as the research method for the study (Braun and Clarke 2006; 2012; 2013).

Paradigms

According to seminal work by Burrell and Morgan (1979), the starting point for all research inquiry is the critical consideration of the researcher's conception of social reality, which is based upon 4 key assumptions: ontological, epistemological, the perceived relationship between humans and their environment; and methodological assumptions. When considered in totality, these principles form a paradigm, which Shepherd and Challenger (2013) refer to as a framework or model upon which personal reality is based. In the context of research activity, a seminal work by Kuhn (1962) referred to paradigms as accepted models, patterns and belief systems based on a particular world view which determine how knowledge should be investigated. Yet, views on types and categories of paradigms are wide ranging and continue to be disputed (Cohen et al. 2018). It is increasingly proposed by some that selection of research paradigm and methodology need not align with ontological and epistemological beliefs and should instead, be fit for purpose in answering the proposed research question (Avis 2003; Denscombe 2014). Others maintain that different paradigms have unique and incompatible ontological and epistemological assumptions which are not interchangeable (Shepherd and Challenger 2013). As models for viewing reality, it is commonly argued that paradigms determine and should therefore underpin methodological approach as means to ensure epistemic reflexivity (Shepherd and Challenger 2013). This is supported by Hammersley (2013) who points to the incommensurability of different paradigms; maintaining that they can never be compatible since they contain distinct and contrasting assumptions about the world

At one end of the philosophical spectrum is the positivist paradigm, which takes a top-down approach to knowledge formation, upholding that it is universal and therefore consistent and replicable (Garrett and Cutting 2014). Positivism is based upon an epistemological belief that true empirical knowledge must separate theory from evidence of the senses; with rigorous processes of verification, objectivity and reproducibility applied to determine truth (Avis 2003). This is the basis of scientific experimentation and studies of quantitative design in which data collection is highly controlled and analysis typically based on numerical or statistical measurements. Constructivism or interpretivism at the other end of the scale, takes a bottom up, inductive approach; sustaining that knowledge is subjective,

individualised and socially constructed. This underpins qualitative methodology (Gray 2014). Since qualitative investigations focus upon constructional aspects of social behaviour and practices, data collection is commonly conducted within a natural, interactive setting and analysis focuses upon individual thoughts, ideas, feelings and experiences. The objectivity and detachment required in scientific investigation is considered to be incompatible with the achievement of qualitative aims since the paradigm is founded on distinct ontological and epistemological assumptions which support a subjective insider view (Avis 2003). Due to this subjectivity, qualitative research is accepted to be highly sensitive to the researcher's personal attitudes and perspectives which makes reliability problematic to attain (Gobo 2011). Zhou and Hall (2018) argue that true objectivity, distance and generalisability are unattainable since an individual researcher's ideas are shaped by both their own thoughts and by those proceeding them, meaning that knowledge always contains a personal dimension. Gobo (2011) further proposes that replicability and generalisation in qualitative studies is achievable with precise research design. Seminal works by Quine (1953), Davidson (2001;1984) and Rorty (1991) question the positivist notion of knowledge and truth as being objective and non-epistemic; advising that they hinge on individual beliefs in order to *know* them; which makes them co-created, epistemic concepts in themselves (Avis 2003). Quine (1953) proposed that the verification of truth by evidence of the senses can therefore not be reduced to any single determinant of empirical content, since it is always shaped by comparative sensory experience and must be viewed within the wider context in which it is situated. Avis (2003) argues that in this construct, reality is as much created as it is discovered. Within the context of RTA, Braun and Clarke use a comparative analogy of the generation of data and themes as either analytic input (i.e., buried treasure) or analytic output which is created at the intersection of what the researcher brings to the data itself (Braun and Clarke 2006; 2012; 2013).

In acknowledging that sensory experience cannot be separated from mind-dependent reality and theory, Quine (1953) concluded that simple reductionism is therefore not an adequate foundation for positivist epistemology and instead, offers a holistic, pragmatic epistemological view in which verification is considered within the sum total of an individual's experience and beliefs (Quine 1953; Avis 2003). Quine's epistemology reflects a third paradigm rooted in pragmatism, which recognises elements of both positivist and interpretivist thought, and combines verification through empirical sensory evidence with individual and social interpretations (Avis 2003). Rather than aligning to pure epistemological and philosophical origins, proponents of pragmatism support a transdisciplinary approach; one in which different research methods are likened to flexible toolkits and suitability for answering the research question takes precedence (Snape and Spencer 2009). Quine's

(1953) pragmatic holism, accounts that all empiric evidence is situated within the conceptual schemes of the individual belief systems in which it is co-created which is perceived here to sit somewhere on the philosophical spectrum, between critical realism and interpretivism (refer to **Figure 6**, p.61). However, other supporters of pragmatic approaches uphold that that selection of research method should be separated from epistemological stance or and altogether atheoretical. Pragmatism is the main foundation for studies of mixed methods design, which take an integrative, complementary view of paradigms; and combine objective and subjective views of reality that are driven by desired results and fitness for purpose rather than pure ontological allegiance (Cohen et al. 2018; Zhou and Hall 2018). There is considerable debate around the validity of mixing research methods; with some authors arguing that it should be limited to methods and approaches within the same paradigm to ensure analytic accountability and clarity of aim (Snape and Spencer 2009).

From the critical theorist's perspective, those who argue for an integrative or pluralistic view; point to the positivist and scientific paradigm's historic domination of research activity as the true motivation for separating them in order to maintain power and control (Greene and Earle 2010; Ayala et al. 2014; Donomeyer 2014; Giroux 2017). Donomeyer (2014) argues that this is less about true quality differential and more about political power and funding issues. In certain cases, the call for an integrative or pluralist view of paradigms may therefore be viewed as an attempt to promote and validate those founded in post-positivism as equally viable and legitimate; while challenging the elitism that underpins the realist approach and professions that are shaped by it (Donomeyer 2014; Cohen et al. 2018; Zhou and Hall 2018).

Although the critical theorists' view is supported in relation to the elitist nature of research and domination of the positivist paradigm, the position here is that paradigms are founded upon distinct and opposing beliefs and that alignment of methodology to ontological and epistemological beliefs is fundamental to ensuring integrity of the study. In this case, individual alignment accepts that elements of both positivist and interpretivist paradigms may co-exist on a spectrum, forming a holistic view of knowledge and reality in line with Quine's pragmatic holism (1953). It is also accepted that fitness for purpose in meeting the study's aim should hold as much weight as philosophical stance. A post-positivist, pragmatic, qualitative approach was therefore adopted.

Interpretivist/constructivist approaches

Naturalistic and interpretivist approaches hold that reality is a product of personal cognition that cannot exist out with the individual perception. From this perspective, reality cannot exist objectively since it relies upon human consciousness for interpretation at both individual and

societal levels and is unique and relative to each person (Sullivan 2010; Polit and Beck 2017). As such, context plays a key role in the formation of reality. The ontological and epistemological stance of this study would conceptualise knowledge as being unique, individual and dependent upon contextual relationships, subsequently supporting the qualitative perspective with which it is underpinned. Since the study was driven by an interest in exploring a range of knowledge types and the relationships between them; individual interpretations and contextual factors were regarded to be of key importance in defining knowledge and an interpretivist/constructivist approach was regarded to be the most suited in achieving this aim. However, fitness for purpose in the chosen method was also considered in conjunction with alignment to epistemological stance.

Tacit knowledge types were worthy of attention here since they have been previously linked to nursing as a practice-based profession (Richie and Lewis 2009; Cioffi 2012; Pahor et al. 2015; Williams and Burke 2015; Davis and Maisano 2016; Voldbjerg et al. 2016); and to unique challenges that have been attributed to specific clinical groups delivering wound management (Kennedy 2004; Jorgenson et al. 2010; Cook 2011; Friman et al. 2011; Stephen-Haynes and Greenwood 2011; Ousey et al. 2013b; Willis and Sutton 2013; Mahoney 2014; Adderley and Thompson 2015; Bain 2015; Ousey et al. 2015). Informal knowledge was also of interest since the shortfalls in structured education and formal evidence identified in the literature review were proposed to present unique pressures which affect the nature and extent to which it is utilised (Dugdall and Watson 2009; Maylor 2012; Ferriera et al. 2014; Gillespie et al. 2014; Gonzaga DeFaria et al. 2016). Finally, the identification of wider factors that influence patterns of knowing in wound management practice (i.e.-organisational and power relationships) was also an aim. It would have seemed one-sided and contradictory to have approached this from an empirical perspective alone; since the positivist paradigm and scientific approach have been recognised as agents of power which have utilised dominant ideologies as a means to control knowledge formation and maintain it's perceived superiority (Greene and Earle 2010; Ayala et al. 2014; Chinn & Kramer 2015; Giroux 2017). The rationale for the selection of paradigm and qualitative methodology can therefore be summarised as a pragmatic combination of epistemological and ontological stance, researcher positionality and fitness for purpose in answering the research questions.

For diagrammatic representation of the theoretical stance refer to **Figure 6** (p. 61)

Figure 6: Diagram of ontological and epistemological stance of the study

Reflexivity and theoretical stance.

In fulfilling both generalist and specialist wound management roles, I brought pre-existing ideas about how knowledge is shaped from an experiential perspective and ideas about the importance of informal knowledge in the practice setting. For example, many of my own memorable learning situations have occurred by observing colleagues and picking up particular skills and behaviours that I feel could not have been learned from theoretical and academic sources. Since informal knowledge is something I value, I recognise that my personal interpretations of participant responses will influence my analysis and I am at risk of imposing and validating my own beliefs. My experience as an educator has led me to increasingly question pedagogical approaches and limitations in current wound management education and how appropriate it is in the preparation of nurses to fulfil this clinical function. It has also enabled me to consider my prior clinical experiences from a more theoretical perspective. This includes considerations about access and availability of education, and the curriculum itself. Importantly it also includes my generic experiences as a member of the nursing profession and the power imbalances I have personally felt in relation to other professions; most notably, medicine.

The experience of having an insider’s view, yet maintaining a balance between immersion and researcher distance can introduce a tension for researchers conducting qualitative studies (Freshwater 2007). This was a key consideration of my ongoing reflexivity along with writing style, use of language and voice.

While an objective third-person *etic* voice is traditionally associated with quantitative research and seeks to maintain a prescriptive distance, the subjective *emic* voice brings familiarity through the constructive perspective of the researcher’s experience (Bansal and

Corley 2012; Zhou and Hall 2018). Although advocates of alignment of study design with philosophical origin support that academic writing style should also maintain ontological consistency, those supporting a pragmatic view, propose the complementarity of combining first and third voices as an effective means to balance the shortcomings of each, whilst offering a more comprehensive picture (Onwuegbuzie and Johnson 2006; Zhou and Hall 2018). This dualistic approach was believed to complement the flexibility and sense of co-creation of RTA as a method. Seminal works by Bakhtin (1981;1986) offer a theoretical underpinning for using mixed voices in academic writing in *heteroglossia*; which proposes that written language is not tied to a single view and instead, conveys a sense of multiplicity of perspectives, contexts, and realities. Zhou and Hall (2018) further argue that even in quantitative studies where data generated is numbers and statistics and the aim is objectivity, it is impossible to remove the personal dimension and experiences of the author. Bakhtin supports that mixing first and third person in scholarly writing allows authors to validate their own voices in the context of those of other authors (Bakhtin 1981;Bakhtin 1986; Greene 2007). Within this study, where previous authors' work is being considered and the goal is to convey an objective formal stance, a third person voice will mainly be used. When I am introducing my personal perspective as an insider of the subject in discussion, I will write in first person.

Consideration of alternative qualitative methods

The term *qualitative research* embodies a range of approaches which have been traditionally perceived to produce findings which are neither quantifiable nor statistical in nature (Snape and Spencer 2010). The common features attributed to studies of qualitative design mirror the aims of this study; for example: gaining an in-depth understanding of participants' social worlds, perspectives and experiences; collating rich detailed descriptive data; and presenting findings which interpret social meaning (Snape and Spencer 2010). Although qualitative research has been criticised for its overall questionable quality and lack of clearly defined methodological criteria (Hammersley 2013); quantitative research, traditionally considered to be the most generalisable and therefore superior approach; would have overlooked the more complex, contextual factors related to the aims; ignoring components of practice that are value dependent and of considerable relevance here (Donomeyer 2014; Chinn and Kramer 2015). This is supported by Polit and Beck (2017) who point out that studies that maintain scientific objectivity may not capture reality or experience within nursing research as an inherently social and practice-based discipline. In its disregard for context in the formation of new evidence, it was considered to an unsuitable framework for this study since it is fundamentally unable to answer certain questions; for example, those pertaining to

participants' socially constructed ideas and experiences about their wound management knowledge and practice (Habermas 1972; Hammersley 2013; Donomeyer 2014).

Although it was clear from the outset that a qualitative design would be most closely aligned to the study's aims; a number of potential methods were explored in the early stages. Since shortfalls in wound management were first identified during clinical practice as a DN and later, a TVN; action research was initially considered. It was envisioned that clinicians delivering wound management could be involved as co-researchers in a number of action research cycles intended to make positive changes to practice; the outcomes of which would directly result in improvements at clinical level. With further examination, it became evident that the shortfalls that manifested at practice level did not all originate there; and were the result of much larger social, political and organisational structures shaping health care service delivery, nursing and wound management. Although action research would have been useful in promoting self-reflection and calling to attention potential social injustices within wound management practice, it was considered to be too direct and focused to address these broader issues effectively. The implementation of any proposed changes that would have reasonable impact was therefore assessed to be out with the capabilities and scope of a study of this scale. Finally, action research is typically associated with critical realist and constructionist approaches and this did not align as clearly to this study's theoretical framework as alternative methods.

As the impact of social injustices pervading in health care and familiarity with the various sociological theories which attempt to account for them grew; an interest in the concept of power was heightened, as did the notion that knowledge formation serves to maintain intellectual, financial and professional control in particular groups (Habermas 1972). An examination of the wider oppressive forces and structures impacting upon wound management practice from the critical perspective became an area of further investigation and this formed the methodological basis for the initial research proposal for this study. Due to its shared emancipatory interests and associations with action research, critical ethnography was also explored as a method at this stage. This approach would have supported a detailed description of any cultural components within wound management practice and more specifically, facilitate comparisons between specialists and generalists as distinct cultural and professional groups. Since a key strength of ethnography is founded on the researcher's ability to combine roles of both participant and observer (Gray 2014); the advantage of having practised in both TVN and DN roles was a potential strength. However; ethnography is largely concerned with the understanding of behaviours, ritual and ceremonials (Gobo 2011) which, although of some interest in relation to knowledge development, was not the primary focus of the study. Furthermore, it typically involves

prolonged periods of fieldwork or participant observation to facilitate deep immersion within communities of practice. As the study was being undertaken as part of a professional doctorate alongside full-time employment, travel across the country to various “fields” would have been impractical for a single researcher which reflects the pragmatic considerations that determined choice of method. Critical ethnography has also been criticised for being more reflective of academic aims and interests than those embedded in true transformative social action (Gray 2014) and was therefore not concluded to be the most appropriate for answering the research questions

Next, case study was considered as a potential method for capturing the specificity of contextual factors that shape knowledge in wound management practice. Since case studies are historically conducted from the perspective of the interpretative paradigm (i.e., phenomenology, grounded theory, ethnography etc.); a descriptive case study using the narrative accounts of participants was explored as an approach. Following further exploration, a number of factors made this seem less fitting. Firstly, potential participants from both the specialist and generalist groups would comprise clinical staff from a range of health boards and locations across Scotland; presenting challenges for drawing clear boundaries around specific cases and making either a single or a multiple case study approach impractical. Secondly, the literature reported similar trends in the challenges associated with wound management knowledge and evidence across clinical settings globally and it was not a primary area of interest to compare individual health boards or regions as unique cases in this particular context. Finally, analytic generalisation through expansion and generation of theory which is typical of case study methodology (Yin 2014), did not fit with this study’s key aims.

Since participants’ experiences in relation to use of knowledge and evidence in wound management would likely form the basis of some of the data; phenomenology was also briefly considered as final option. This approach would have supported a detailed understanding of the constructs and cognitive processes underpinning knowledge development in this area of practice (Snape and Spencer 2009). The importance of subjective consciousness in the formation of certain knowledge types was of some interest, but it was not of primary concern; and the primacy of the phenomena of experience was not a perceived priority (Marshall and Rossman 2016). The exploration of lived experiences alone was therefore not considered to be the most suited to fulfil the research aims.

Given that the theoretical underpinning at ontological and epistemological levels was proposed to sit at the interpretivist/constructivist end of the spectrum coupled with pragmatic considerations, a mixed methods design might have offered a suitable approach. However,

there was no perceived methodological or analytic benefit of introducing quantitative data for answering the research questions, and consideration of mixed methods would have solely been for its sympathetic alignment with a pragmatic paradigm rather suitability and fitness for purpose. A mixed methods approach was therefore not considered to be a strong choice.

Following examination of the main qualitative traditions, it was accepted that a theoretical approach was not necessary at the level of method. From the pragmatic perspective Avis (2003) proposes that it is unnecessary and often counterproductive to assign a particular methodological theory to qualitative research; arguing that it dilutes critical reflection upon the relationship between theory and empirical evidence. Other authors argue that qualitative research has relied too heavily on the philosophical considerations of the traditional epistemological stances and associated methods (Seale 1999). This mirrors arguments that researchers' critical abilities are undermined by unnecessary attachment to tradition, and calls for a more levelled approach that effectively combines philosophy and pragmatism (Snape and Spencer 2009). Critical theorists further argue that the perceived requirement for assigning a conceptual scheme to qualitative studies originated in an attempt to escape hegemony and domination of the scientific approach to knowledge generation and should not be regarded as a true benchmark for quality (Rorty 1991; Donomeyer 2014).

The evidence base supporting nurses' knowledge and use of evidence in wound management is recognised to be universally limited; and studies focusing upon specialist practice even less prevalent (Dugdall and Watson 2009; Stephen-Haynes and Greenwood 2011; Maylor 2012; Ferriera et al. 2014; Gillespie et al. 2014; Ousey et al. 2015; Gonzaga DeFaria et al. 2016). The topic was recognised to be significantly under-researched area of practice. Although the interpretivist/constructivist interpretations of reality and knowledge are accepted here as the theoretical basis at ontological and epistemological levels, a generic, flexible, qualitative design was considered to be an appropriate starting point for a subject about which there was little known. This was reflective of the positionality, suitability for answering the research questions and forms the rationale for not committing to a particular conceptual scheme at the level of method.

Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA)

Thematic analysis is widely reported to have originated from Grounded Theory (Glaser and Strauss 1967; Rivas 2018); but it is increasingly recognised to have pre-dated this, tracing as far back as the 1930s (Clarke et al. 2019). It has been defined as a method for identifying, analysing and reporting patterns or themes in data, evolving originally from qualitative content analysis (Braun and Clarke 2006; Braun and Clarke 2012; Braun and Clarke 2013; Clarke et al. 2019). Joffe (2011) proposes that thematic analysis is being increasingly

recognised as a distinct research method in its own right; however, Braun and Clarke (2013) point out that rather than being a single method, thematic analysis is a broad term for a number of different approaches. A key distinguishing component of thematic analysis is its flexibility; since it is not consistently tied to a particular theoretical framework and can therefore be adopted and applied in a number of ways (Braun and Clarke 2006; Ayres 2008; Joffe 2011; Braun and Clarke 2012; Braun and Clarke 2013). RTA was perceived to complement the epistemological essence of interpretivist/constructivist multiple social realities; and its inherent flexibility supported a pragmatic approach.

Clarke et al. (2019) identify three main categories of thematic analysis: Coding Reliability Thematic Analysis; Codebook Thematic Analysis and Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA); which range from those that align to positivist and quantitative values (i.e., Coding Reliability), those which are underpinned by fully qualitative assumptions (i.e., RTA) and those that are situated in between (i.e., Codebook Thematic Analysis). RTA is recognised as being inductive, data driven and uniquely flexible. Clarke et al. (2019) argue that for this reason, it is more aligned to a method than a methodology since it does not have in-built theoretical assumptions. They are careful to point out that this does not mean RTA is atheoretical and purely descriptive; but that links to theory are situated at ontological and epistemological rather than methodological level. Braun and Clarke (2019) support that although RTA is theoretically flexible and embodies purely, qualitative values, these typically range from critical realist to experiential paradigms. It was selected as the appropriate method for this noted flexibility; since a structured theoretical approach would not be applied at methodological level in one of the traditional qualitative traditions. Secondly, it was selected for its embodiment of qualitative values and in particular, those shaped by the spectrum between post-structuralism and constructivism/interpretivism which fits closely with researcher positionality (Clarke et al 2019). Within the context of this study, RTA will therefore be considered as both the approach to data analysis and in the absence of theoretical approach, the method.

Braun and Clarke (2006; 2012; 2013) maintain that since RTA has no in-built theoretical conventions, it is imperative that the researcher's own assumptions are acknowledged and articulated throughout to ensure theoretical sensitivity (Clarke et al. 2019). Although they recommend ongoing reflexivity as a means to secure this (Braun and Clarke 2006; Braun and Clarke 2012; Braun and Clarke 2013; Clarke et al. 2019); it is acknowledged that reflexivity is an ongoing strive that is never fully realised rather than a complete insight. A large part of this involves the continued recognition that data is contextual, situated and co-created which renders the researcher's assumptions as playing a significant role in the analytic process. My own reflexivity was therefore considered as both a strength and a

potential limitation to the results of the study as I strove to maintain a balance between objective distance and insider's view point.

Since it was my clinical and professional experience that shaped the interest in this area of practice and determined the choice of subject matter, I acknowledge that I came to the study with a number of theoretical assumptions and pre-conceived notions about wound management practice. As both a former DN and TVN, I had an insider view of the shortfalls and challenges in wound management at practice level from the perspectives of both participant groups. These include an experiential and personal understanding of many of the issues raised here and personal experience with challenges that were specific to both roles. I had to acknowledge that I may be bringing my individual frustrations around the lack of clarity and inconsistencies about wound management industry and the possibility that I was encouraging participants to view this from my gaze. Sensitivity to the attitudes of the individual researcher is always a consideration with qualitative studies which makes replicability challenging (Avis 2003; Gobo 2011). Although replicability is not an aim of RTA studies, a precise and consistent research design was a key means of ensuring reliability (Gobo 2011); for example, using the same semi-structured interview schedule and approach to data collection and analysis for all participants while at the same time, recognising the impact of the individual realities and perspectives brought by each as a process of co-creation. Recruitment of participants from both specialist and generalist wound management practice and adoption of heterogenous sampling was also conceived to give a broader understanding of knowledge within different groups involved in the delivery of wound management, introducing an opportunity to compare and increase theoretical generalisability.

In fulfilling both generalist and specialist wound management roles, I also brought pre-existing ideas about how knowledge is shaped from an experiential perspective, as well as ideas about the importance of informal knowledge in the practice setting. For example, many of my own memorable learning situations have occurred by observing colleagues and picking up particular skills and behaviours. Since informal knowledge is something I value, I had to recognise my own interpretations of participant responses to ensure I was not imposing and validating my beliefs. My experience as an educator has led me to increasingly question pedagogical approaches and limitations in current wound management education and how appropriate it is in the preparation of nurses to fulfil this clinical function; but also consider my prior clinical experiences from a more theoretical perspective. This includes access and availability of education but also the curriculum itself. However; importantly it also includes my more generic experiences as a member of the nursing profession and the

power imbalances I have personally felt in relation to other professions; most notably, medicine.

My own ontological assumptions which I place on the spectrum between critical realism and interpretivism (refer to Chapter 3 **Figure 6**; p 61); also shape my perspective and I recognise my critical view of the culture of positivism in this respect. It was therefore important to acknowledge that I may be prone to looking for similar data to fulfil the study's aim and check this tendency which I did throughout the course of the study with the use of a reflexive research diary which I populated throughout; most regularly during the data collection and analysis stages.

Conceptual frameworks of knowledge

Cohen, Manion & Morrison's (2018) proposal that conceptual frameworks organise key concepts within the scope of an individual study was adopted in relation to the knowledge shaping wound management practice. Since there are a number of different frameworks attempting to conceptualise the complex nature of knowledge and its various typologies, the application of a specific model was considered vital to narrow the focus and frame some of the key points surrounding it in a way that fit the study's aims. Chinn and Kramer's *Patterns of Knowing* (2015), adapted from Carper's (1978) original *Fundamental Patterns of Knowing* (1978) was selected as the model from which to conceptualise and explore participants' knowledge in the context of wound management. The rationale for selecting Chinn and Kramer's (2015) model was threefold. Firstly, it continues to be regarded as one of the most comprehensive of those conceptualising nurses' knowledge and along with Carper (1978), is widely accepted to form the epistemological basis of nursing (Garrett & Cutting 2014). Although alternatives were considered, many of which overlapped with components of Chinn & Kramer's model, none of these were specific to nursing. This was regarded to be a limitation since it was of primary interest to identify components that could be viewed as unique both in the context of nursing as a practice-based profession and more specifically, within wound management. Secondly, the model captured the multidimensional nature of nursing knowledge; giving attention to those types which have been historically superseded by empiric, formal knowledge (Denny 2010; Green and Earle 2010; Ayala et al. 2014; Chinn and Kramer 2015). Since the review of the literature identified the formal evidence base supporting wound management as having considerable limitations, it was of key interest to explore whether this impacted upon the utilisation of other knowledge types. Finally, the emphasis the model placed on emancipatory knowing was deemed to be particularly pertinent; since many of the shortfalls in wound management practice rather than being isolated to practice level, may be proposed to link to wider organisational factors. As one of

the research questions specifically considered influential factors in the current wound management practice context, emancipatory knowing was considered to be worthy of particular attention within the aims of this study; due to its importance in ensuring the connectedness of all knowledge types. For this reason, Chinn and Kramer's (2015) revised patterns of knowing was considered to be more developed than Carper's (1978) original model and a better fit as the conceptual framework for knowledge.

Fundamental patterns of knowing: background and historical relevance

In recognising the multidimensional nature of nursing knowledge, Carper (1978) identified its origins in different sources; and as existing out with the confines of formal expressions and traditional definitions. Since this is dependent upon factors including personal values, social interaction and ontology, it was considered to be an ideal theoretical platform for a study adopting an interpretative/constructivist approach. Although the empiric pattern of knowing has been recognised as dominating the historical development of knowledge in nursing (Aktar-Danesh et al. 2014; Ayala et al. 2014; Garrett and Cutting 2014; Chinn and Kramer 2015), there has been a gradual shift and growing body of literature exploring types of knowledge that are reflective of the remaining patterns (Porter and O' Halloran 2009; Garrett and Cutting 2014; Pahor et al. 2015; Springer and Clinton 2015; Williams and Burke 2015 Davis and Maisano 2016; Voldbjerg et al. 2016). In recognising Carper's (1978) ideals, Chinn and Kramer (2015) accepted its basis; and added emancipatory knowing to the framework; proposing that the development and utilisation of knowledge in each of the patterns has five unique dimensions. **Table 2** (p.70) provides an overview of development and dimensions of knowledge for each pattern.

Table 2: Dimensions for the development & utilisation of knowledge (Chinn & Kramer 2015)

	Dimension	Emancipatory	Ethics	Personal	Aesthetics	Empirics
Generation & development of knowledge	Critical questions	Who benefits? What is wrong with this picture? What are the barriers to freedom? What changes are needed?	Is this right? Is this responsible?	Do I know what I do? Do I do what I know?	What does this mean? How is this significant?	What is this? How does it work?
	Creative processes	Critiquing Imagining	Clarifying Exploring	Opening Centring	Envisioning Rehearsing	Conceptualising Structuring
Examination & improvement of knowledge	Formal expressions	Action plans Manifestoes Critical analyses Visions for the future	Principles and codes	Personal stories Genuine self	Aesthetic criticism Works of art	Facts Models Formal descriptions Theories Thematic descriptions
	Authentication processes	Social equity Sustainability Empowerment Demystification	Dialogue Justification	Response Reflection	Appreciation Inspiration	Confirmation Validation
	Integrated expression in practice	Praxis	Moral and ethical comportment	Therapeutic use of the self	Transformative art/acts	Scientific competence

Reproduced with permission from Elsevier

Chinn and Kramer (2015) support that each dimension of the knowledge development process leads to the next. For example; critical questions that initiate the generation and development of knowledge in the emancipatory pattern include *what is wrong with this picture?* which prompt the creative processes of *critiquing* current standards and inequities

(i.e. prevailing hegemonies of power that should be addressed) which lead to the development of formal expressions of emancipatory knowing such as action plans; which are shared and subsequently authenticated (i.e. through processes to support social equity). The final stage of knowledge development is its integrated expression in practice. For emancipatory knowing this is *praxis*, which is defined as a process of reflection and action through which knowledge development leads to a transformation of consciousness, thereby overcoming oppression (Freire 1973). Whilst critical questions and creative processes initiate and generate knowledge, formal expressions, integrated practice and authentication processes represent expressions of knowledge that allow for its examination and improvement. Chinn and Kramer (2015) additionally propose that knowledge development occurs at three levels: individual level; collective level and at level of discipline. As the purpose of this study was to primarily to examine the existing knowledge utilised by wound management specialists and generalists rather than generate new wound management knowledge amongst participants, the latter three dimensions were of primary interest in this context and formed the basis of data collection and underpinning of the semi-structured interview schedule.

Chinn and Kramer (2015) propose that processes for developing knowledge are non-linear and interactive; with each of the patterns being integrated and complimentary to form whole knowledge. If any single pattern dominates or becomes removed from the overall knowledge context, an uncritical, narrow interpretation follows; resulting in a partial, unproductive use which they refer to as *patterns gone wild* (Chinn and Kramer 2015). The consequences for each *pattern gone wild* is unique to the pattern itself; for example, the removal of emancipatory knowing from the knowledge context may result in an extreme political or social stance; while removal of empirics can lead to control and manipulation which the authors point out, is ironically, the direct, formal aim of the scientific approach. Since the literature review for this particular study supported shortfalls and limitations in the formal scientific evidence base underpinning wound management practice (Jorgenson et al. 2010; Ousey et al. 2013a; Logan 2015; Ferriera et al. 2014; Gillespie et al. 2014; Gonzaga de Faria et al. 2016; Gray et al. 2017); a key area of interest was how this had impacted upon the utilisation of the patterns as a whole and whether a *patterns gone wild* situation had been established.

Summary

This chapter has provided an outline and rationale for the methodological, theoretical and conceptual frameworks underpinning the study's aims. In line with my ontological and epistemological stance as a researcher, a pragmatic qualitative approach, rooted in

interpretivism/constructivism was adopted; informing the theoretical framework of the study. Braun and Clarke's (2006; 2012; 2013) RTA was applied as the methodology and method and Chinn and Kramer's *Patterns of Knowing* (2015) was selected as the conceptual framework of nursing knowledge from which to consider the knowledge of specialist and generalist nurses involved in the delivery of wound management.

Chapter 4 Methods

Ethical considerations

It is accepted that those undertaking research activity should be aware of the basic ethical guidelines and underpinning theory and principles. In addition to formal regulation, the highly contextual and individual nature of ethical decision making must also be considered (Brooks et al. 2014). Throughout the research process, all guidelines were adhered to and all formal ethical approvals sought. In the first instance, this included institutional review from the University of the West of Scotland's (UWS) School of Health and Life Sciences review committee (refer to **Appendix 2** p. 169); followed by approvals through the Integrated Research Application System (IRAS) (IRAS Approval ID 262262), the national online ethics review system for studies involving the National Health Service (NHS). As the study was considered low risk; involving Higher Education Institution (HEI) and NHS staff but not service users, NHS Research Ethics Committee (REC) approval was not necessary; however, NHS Research and Development (R&D) approval and access permissions were required from the participants' employing health boards as well as NHS sites where data collection took place. This totalled 4 x NHS health boards and sites for which approval was granted. All remaining data collection took place on HEI premises. All correspondence with NHS R&D was retained by the researcher who duly notified NHSR&D of the study completion and submitted a final report to the relevant departments for each participating health board.

Informed consent

Autonomy, one of the four ethical principles, is an individual's right to self-determination; one which can only be over-ridden in exceptional circumstances (Beauchamp & Childress 2012). In the legal sense, autonomy is based upon one's capacity to make a decision (Dimond 2015) and researchers are duty bound to uphold and prevent interference with it. This is ensured through the provision of informed consent from participants. In order for consent to be valid, there must be three integral elements pre-existing elements (i.e., competence and voluntariness); information elements (i.e., disclosure and understanding of relevant information); and consent elements including agreement and authorisation of participation (Beauchamp and Childress 2012)

In the present study, informed consent was obtained from participants in written form prior to undertaking the study. All participants were provided with a participant information sheet (PIS) (refer to **Appendices 3** and **4** p.170 and 173) outlining the purpose, nature and processes of the study, including what was involved and how data would be used. As

participants were NHS or HEI employees, they were considered to have full capacity and no vulnerable groups were included. A two-week cooling off period was given to enable potential participants to fully consider whether they wished to participate. All potential participants were invited to ask questions and express any potential concerns and were clearly advised that they were under no obligation to participate. Those who did agree to participate were informed that they may withdraw at any stage of the study and would not have to provide a rationale. All participants consented to data being used for educational and dissemination purposes, including publication.

Anonymity and confidentiality

In order to uphold the ethical principles of beneficence and non-maleficence, all data and written information was anonymised to ensure confidentiality throughout the course of the study in adherence with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (2018). A data management plan (DMP) was developed using checklist principles of the Digital Curation Centre (DCC) to support the ethical integrity and management of data throughout the study (DCC 2013). (**Appendix 5** p. 176). Although there was no perceived methodological benefit or requirement to include participants' names, specific geographical location or additional identifying information; data generated using RTA is recognised as being highly individualised and contextualised and full confidentiality may be difficult to guarantee (Braun and Clarke 2006; 2012). Although participants' identity was known to the researcher, all data, documentation and written information relating to individual participants within the main body of the thesis was coded to ensure anonymity. Transcripts, written text and the researcher's hand written notes were reviewed repeatedly to ensure the removal of as much identifying content as possible.

Data management and storage

All data management was in line with *UWS Ethics Committee Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship* (www.uws.ac.uk/media/5544/guidelines-for-ethical-practice-in-research-and-scholarship-refreshed-september-2019.pdf). Raw data from interviews was recorded by the researcher using an encrypted hand-held audio-recorder and anonymised using participant codes to ensure confidentiality. Participants provided consent prior to recording and were advised that interviews could be stopped at any time. Although participants were not directly invited to view transcripts prior to data analysis, requests to do so would have been fully supported.

In RTA, data collation, management and analysis are recognised as being simultaneous processes with considerable overlap between phases which have significant interpretive and

analytical value (Braun and Clarke 2006). Since qualitative data are socially situated and dependent on context, it is important that the researcher becomes fully immersed so that a holistic understanding of all perspectives and interpretations of the situation can be facilitated (Cohen et al. 2018). Rich descriptive data, whilst providing a varied and rounded interpretation, typically generate a large volume of analytic material which can present organisational and procedural challenges for a single researcher. A systematic and accessible system of data organisation, categorisation and retrieval is therefore considered central for the integrity of the study. Although data management tools are recognised as being useful in this capacity, an additional layer of distance would have been created, which would have negatively impacted on the necessary process of co-creation between the raw data and researcher interpretation. The value of using a data management tool was therefore considered to be a pragmatic one only; and would have been to the potential detriment of the analytical process itself. A transcribing service was also not utilised for this reason and a systematic process for carrying out all stages of data management was developed by the researcher. Although the transcription, data management and storage processes were lengthy, the hands-on approach enabled intensive, long-term researcher involvement, immersion and probing necessary for sufficient analysis (Cohen et al. 2018).

Raw data from interviews was transferred from the audio recorder onto encrypted electronic files on a security and password-protected computer accessible only to the researcher. In order to support systematic collection, analysis and retrieval of data a clear electronic data management pathway was followed throughout the study. Sub folders were created for specialists and generalists, then further sub folders created for each participant categorised consistently and systematically (**Appendix 6** p.180). Hard printed copies were stored in a file folder in a locked cabinet in locked premises. Data was accessed and reviewed only by the researcher and academic supervisory team and stored on encrypted files. Upon study completion, the findings may be published in an academic journal and/or presented at relevant academic or professional conferences and shared for educational purposes; however, identifying information will be removed from any publication or education session. UWS policy does not outline explicit timescales for keeping data and it was outlined in the original de-brief submitted to HEI and IRAS ethics for approval that data would be destroyed 3 years post study. However, it is recognised that if any section of the completed thesis is submitted for publication, there may be specific requirements for keeping data for a prolonged period; in which case consent for any necessary longer data retention would be submitted.

Assessment and management of risk

The study was considered low risk to both participants and researcher. Adverse effects were anticipated to be minimal but may have potentially included time and intrusion associated with semi-structured interview participation. As participants were recruited based on their clinical expertise and involvement in wound management, this was an area of professional interest to them and they unanimously expressed that they enjoyed the opportunity to discuss, reflect upon and improve their practice in this respect. The subject matter and nature of the interviews did not bring up any sensitive or distressing topics; however, if participants were to have become distressed or uncomfortable, appropriate support would have been sought.

A field work risk assessment was carried out for interview settings out with the UWS Campus (refer to **Appendix 7** p.181). The academic supervisory team and/or named colleagues were informed where the researcher was at all times and provided with contact details should they have needed to make contact. A mobile phone was carried at all times and although there were no incidents, these would have been reported in accordance with local protocol.

As any interview settings out with UWS were NHS premises, local risk protocol was adhered to at all times. Since all data collection occurred within office hours, there was no lone working.

Participant identification and recruitment

A range of generalist and specialist clinicians are involved in the delivery of wound management but it is recognised to be a primarily nurse-led discipline (Cowman et al. 2011; Ousey et al. 2013b; Guest et al. 2015; Harding et al. 2015; Ousey et al. 2015; Vowden and Vowden 2016). It therefore followed that nurses would form the most appropriate participant group for this study. The literature review revealed that a lack of high-quality evidence pertaining to nurses' knowledge in the context of wound management and a richer understanding of this was perceived to contribute to filling an important gap in the evidence base. Wound management was considered by the researcher to be an ideal context from which to explore patterns of knowing since identified shortfalls in sources of formal knowledge (empiric knowing) may be proposed to contribute to nurses frequently utilising less formal knowledge types; for example, aesthetic knowing; than clinical areas in which the evidence base is more robust. In addition, an exploration of emancipatory knowing in the context of wound management practice and the impact of factors at organisational, structural and professional levels on evidence, education and practice were of primary interest.

Comparisons between nurses providing specialist and generalist wound management in this context was also an aim of this study. Those fulfilling specialist wound management roles (i.e., TVNS) and DN and CSNs, who are recognised to be the key clinicians involved in the provision of generalist wound management (Hampton and Lindsay 2005; Fletcher 2010; Moore 2010; Heaslip 2013; Probst et al. 2014; Logan 2015) were therefore selected as the specific nursing disciplines which would make up the participant group.

Wound management specialists were recruited through membership of a national professional group comprising clinical and educational wound management specialists from across Scotland. Wound management generalists were recruited from staff and students undertaking a professional community nursing qualification (Specialist Practitioner Qualification District Nurse (SPQDN) at a Scottish HEI. The rationale for not recruiting participants directly from health boards was three-fold. Firstly; both the professional group and the community nurse educational programme provided single points of access to participants who were based (or previously based) in a range of national health boards which may be proposed to increase theoretical generalisability. Secondly, it was recognised that participants in a clinical role may feel more removed from their place of employment and therefore more comfortable about discussing potential influencing factors that were of key interest for the study (i.e., wider social and political factors that may shape emancipatory knowing in wound management practice). The likelihood of generating more robust data was proposed to be increased with this approach to recruitment. Finally, it was anticipated that student DNs' participation may be proposed to support contribution to the development of the future wound management education curriculum itself.

Participants were identified through their professional group membership or their involvement in the PgD SPQDN Programme through gatekeeper access. The gatekeeper for specialist participants was the acting professional group chair and the gatekeeper for DNs was the PgD SPQDN Programme Leader. Through the gatekeepers, invitations to participate were circulated via email which outlined the study information including participant information sheets (PISs) (refer to **Appendices 3** and **4** p.170 and 173) and participant consent forms (refer to **Appendices 8** and **9** p.183 and 185). Potential participants were advised about time scales, level of involvement and were provided with details of how data might be used (i.e., for teaching or publication). Those who wished to participate were invited to contact the researcher directly using an accompanying contact email address and by completing the attached participant consent form.

Eligibility criteria

Those meeting eligibility criteria as participants in the study included: wound management specialists with active membership in the national professional group practising in a specialist clinical and/or educational wound management role; and wound management generalists practising as a DN or CSN in a clinical and/or educational capacity. The exclusion criteria included those who did not meet eligibility criteria outlined above.

Approach to sampling

Qualitative research typically supports the utilisation of small, purposefully selected samples (Polit and Beck 2017). Morgan (2008) proposes that since the goal of qualitative research is to gain a contextual understanding of specific phenomena rather than achieve statistical generalisability, sample sizes should be reflective of this aim. Snape and Spencer (2010) add that smaller samples enable the necessary close interactive contact between the researcher and participants throughout the data collection stage. Since the contextual and tacit components of knowledge were of notable interest in this study, a purposive approach to sampling was employed to ensure representativeness and comparability (Denscombe 2014).

Clarke et al. (2019) suggest that due to the flexible nature of RTA, there are no particular requirements or restrictions in relation to sample size which are dependent upon the specific research approach and selected methodology and methods. For interview studies which typically generate a large amount of data; it is proposed that for DProf level research, a sample of eight to ten participants is the suggested mid-range (Braun and Clarke 2013; Clarke et al. 2019). Based on this guidance, a total of between eight and twelve participants was initially considered to be representative of the population for examination which would enable exploration at a sufficient level of depth. The heterogeneous nature of the sample was an additional consideration since it would potentially produce a sizeable amount of data; which was found to be the case during the early stages of data collection in this study. In addition to ensuring methodological rigour, this brought pragmatic considerations in relation to the sample size. Gray (2014) indicates that including sub-samples with different perspectives on the issues for exploration can be proposed to increase generalisability in qualitative studies, therefore ensuring external validity. Following interviews with five wound management specialists and five wound management generalists, analysis of the data revealed that theoretical and data saturation had been reached and no further interviews were conducted. A purposive, non-probability sample of five wound management specialists and five wound management generalists formed the final participant group.

Since wound management knowledge and education were of importance in this study, educational preparation and background of participants was recorded at recruitment stage. Three of the five participants working within a specialist role had undergone formal education pertaining to wound management at degree level, with two of these completing a wound management qualification at master’s level. All five generalist participants had undergraduate degrees but only one had completed formal education specific to wound management. **Table 3** (p. 79) provides an overview of participant clinical and educational backgrounds.

Table 3: Participant clinical practice and education

Group A Wound Management Specialist Nurses	
Participant	Education
SP11 (Acute)	Undergraduate Degree; MSc Tissue Repair
S11 (Community)	Undergraduate Degree; MSc Tissue Repair
S12 (Acute)	Wound management CPD
S13 (Acute)	Undergraduate Degree; 3 x wound management modules (undergraduate level)
S14 (Acute & Community)	Undergraduate Degree; Wound management CPD
Group B Wound Management Generalist Nurses	
Participant	Education
GP11 (Community)	Undergraduate Degree; Wound management CPD prescriber; currently undertaking MSc level education
G11 (Community)	Undergraduate Degree; Leg Ulcer Module (undergraduate level); Wound management CPD; currently undertaking MSc level education
G12 (Community)	Undergraduate Degree; Wound Management CPD; prescriber; currently undertaking MSc level education
G13 (Community)	Undergraduate Degree; Wound Management CPD; currently undertaking MSc level education
G14 (Community)	Undergraduate Degree; Wound Management CPD; currently undertaking MSc level education

Data collection

Participants were invited to partake in semi-structured face to face interviews with the researcher on an individual basis (approximately 60-90 minutes length) during which Chinn and Kramer’s *Patterns of Knowing* (2015) was used to frame open ended questions relating

to current wound management knowledge and practice (refer to **Appendix 10** p.187). Seminal work by Cannell and Kahn (1968) defines the research interview as a conversation between two or more people in which data is collated through systematic description and explanation. Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018) suggest that a primary purpose of interviews is to understand, assess and evaluate a particular situation, which aligned well to the aims of the study. Interviews have been compared favourably with questionnaires as means of qualitative data collection due to extensive opportunities for eliciting rich descriptions of specific situations and unique participant experiences (Kvale 1996). Oppenheim (1992) adds that interviews have higher response rates than questionnaires and this offered additional pragmatic benefits for a single researcher. Although there are a range of interview types, semi-structured interviews were selected using standardised closed and open-ended questions to facilitate organisation and analysis of the data. Patton (1980) reports that a semi-structured design increases comparability of responses which was considered to be fitting for the heterogeneous approach to sampling. Focus group interviews were also initially considered as a method of data collection; however, this were rejected on several counts. Firstly, recruiting and organising a group interview from a sample that was spread across several regions would have presented practical challenges (Gray 2014). Secondly, group dynamics that impact upon focus groups may have resulted in one or two members dominating the discussion (Kitzinger 1994) with confidentiality difficult to maintain; both of which could affect participant responses and impact upon the reliability of the data (Kitzinger 1995). Finally, the study did not employ content analysis or ethnographic methods of data analysis with which focus groups are usually methodologically associated (Wilkinson 2011). Semi-structured interviews were therefore considered to be the most fitting method of data collection.

A standardised template of semi-structured interview questions was used for all participants. The same schedule was used for both specialists and generalist participants and included both closed and open-ended questions. The use of standardised questions is proposed to reduce researcher effect and bias and increase reliability (Patton 1980; Gray 2014), while open-ended questions allow for flexibility of response to gain an in-depth, rich understanding of participants' thought processes and beliefs. Gray (2014) proposes that open-ended questions, which encourage participants to expand and express themselves, also strengthen internal validity. Probes were presented as an opportunity for both the interviewer and participants to clarify and elaborate points (Gray 2014; Cohen et al. 2018). Smith and Osborn (2008) suggest that this approach allows flexibility of coverage of the topic area which gives the participant more control; whilst promoting a naturalness that may be limited

by the use of purely standardised wording. The interview schedule was structured and set out to cover broad areas first, for example:

- *Can you describe where you think the knowledge you apply to wound management comes from?*

Following a number of generic, overview questions, these funnelled from the general to the more specific:

- *Do you continue to access formal or structured wound management education? Who delivers it? Can you tell me about how strong you considered the evidence base supporting it to be?*
- *Can you give some examples from practice where you take a creative approach to wound management?*

Although questions were semi-structured, it was recognised that the interview process was iterative and could therefore be adapted and developed for each individual participant (Patton 1980; Gray 2014). This also supports the flexibility of approach that is favoured by Braun and Clarke's (2006; 2012; 2013) RTA as a research method.

Piloting

A pilot interview with one specialist and one generalist (DN) was carried out prior to commencement of data collection. Pilot work contributes to the validity of a study; however, in qualitative approaches, validity can be problematic since objectives are not always pre-decided and often arise inductively from the interview itself (Gray 2014). Following the pilot, the instrument of data collection was considered to be valid and no changes were made to the interview schedule. Data from the two pilot interviews was included in the final analysis. Interviews were recorded using an encrypted hand-held audio device and transcribed verbatim by the researcher. Hand held notes were kept available to compile and record particular points of interest and relevance including specific behaviours and body language.

Data analysis

Braun and Clarke's (2006; 2012; 2013) 6-phase approach to RTA was selected as both the applied method for the study and the specific method of data analysis. Although RTA can be applied to both inductive and deductive analysis, this study adopted an inductive, data driven process. Data analysis followed Braun and Clarke's (2006; 2012; 2013) 6 phases which have been outlined below:

1. Familiarisation with the data
2. Coding

3. Generating initial themes
4. Reviewing themes
5. Define and name themes
6. Write up and weave together analytic narrative

Braun and Clarke (2006; 2012; 2013) point out that all phases routinely overlap and do not occur in purely sequential order. Data analysis therefore followed a lengthy process of working through and re-visiting each phase in both chronological and non-chronological order.

Familiarisation with the data

During the first phase, raw data from the audio recordings of semi-structured interviews was transcribed verbatim and broadly categorised within each the five *patterns of knowing* on a case-by-case basis using the outline of the interview schedule as a framework (refer to **Appendix 11** p. 192 and **Appendix 12** p.206). A transcription tool was not used for this process so that sufficient researcher familiarisation and immersion in the data was facilitated during this key interpretative phase.

Data was collected and analysed separately within two distinct data sets: data for wound management specialists and data for wound management generalists. Throughout the data collation stage for each set, handwritten notes were taken in relation to patterns, ideas for coding and points of interest on an ongoing basis. Transcripts were read and re-read to ensure immersion in the data and patterns and points of interest were organised into initial codes based on richness and meaning of account (refer to **Appendix 13** p. 217 and **Appendix 14** p.273 for sample initial participant code sweep charts).

Coding

During the initial coding phase, succinct codes or labels that were considered to hold importance and relevance for answering the research questions were generated from raw data. Clarke et al. (2019) propose that unlike codebook approaches to thematic analysis in which coding is a highly structured processes utilising multiple coders, RTA is organic, subjective and highly interpretive. It is appropriate for a single coder to be used with no requirement to carry out inter-rater reliability testing, since reliability reflects quantitative values and is not a concern in this context (Braun and Clarke 2019). Although quantitative data such as frequency and prevalence of response are not routinely considered to be of particular value to qualitative studies (Pyett 2003), their potential to be indicators of dominance and therefore potential providers of key information relating to the nature of

wound management knowledge could not be ignored. Although recognised to be secondary to the qualitative aims of the study, prevalence was therefore noted and recorded during this stage. Following the generation of an initial code chart for each participant (refer to **Appendices 15** and **16** for sample individual code charts p. 304 and 307), all codes for the two the participant groups were collated and presented in distinct charts so that comparisons between specialist and generalist nurses could be made (refer to **Appendices 17** and **18** p. 312 and 315 for collated code charts).

Themes

Clarke et al. (2019) identify two main conceptualisations of themes: domain summary themes, in which all observations about a topic or piece of data are collated without a unifying factor; and fully realised themes, which are underpinned by a central concept capturing core, shared meaning that can be attached to the data. While domain summary themes are conceptualised as simple analytic input, fully realised themes are regarded as more complex analytic output, and their creation occurs at the intersection of the data and the analytic assumptions brought by the researcher. In RTA, fully realised themes can be regarded as being built and co-created rather than as pre-existing and being uncovered through the process of analysis (Clarke et al. 2019). It is therefore crucial that the researcher explicitly acknowledges assumptions to maintain theoretical sensitivity as themes are developed.

During these phases of the RTA, a list of coded data was collated from both data sets and clustered into broader patterns and themes. Mind maps (refer to **Appendix 19** p. 317) and tables were developed to explore and examine relationships and levels of themes which were organised into over-arching and sub-themes within each of the two data sets. Braun and Clarke (2006; 2012; 2013) support that development of themes from initial codes is a subjective and interpretive process involving considerable analytic work on the part of the researcher. A significant amount of time was therefore spent reviewing and refining themes to ensure accurate representation of the raw data. Initial themes were developed and named, but later revised a number of times during this phase. This was commonly guided by ongoing reflexivity and the content of my reflexive diary; in conjunction with findings from literature included in the review stage. Although RTA does not demand consensus with coding and themes, as a measure to ensure that they were clearly aligned with analytic claims and checked for viability in answering the research questions, each of these was reviewed and agreed by a peer prior to finalisation. In addition, Braun and Clarke's (2006) 15-point checklist of criteria for good thematic analysis was used to review the process (refer to **Appendix 20** p. 318). Themes were then defined and considered in order of perceived

dominance; which in the context of this study was attributed to data that was particularly rich, descriptive, meaningful and representative of frequently identified subject matter. Again, review of current literature in combination with my own reflexivity was key here.

Final themes were generated using Chinn and Kramer's *Patterns of Knowing* (2015) as a conceptual framework so that comparisons could be made between the data sets from both specialists and generalists.

Trustworthiness

The criteria for determining quality or trustworthiness in qualitative research is distinct from those in studies employing quantitative and experimental designs (Yin 2014; Nowell et al. 2017; Polit and Beck 2017). Qualitative data is typically rich and socially constructed and can bring an element of personal bias and subjectivity on the part of the researcher since ontological and epistemological perspectives are linked to personal experiences (Hugh-Jones 2010). Nowell et al. (2017) therefore highlight the importance of ensuring a rigorous and precise approach when conducting thematic analysis to ensure results are consistent and meaningful. One means of ensuring trustworthiness in qualitative research is assuring construct validity; in which constructs supporting specific issues for examination are considered consistently and systematically (Yin 2014). However; the construction of issues may vary considerably between participants and studies applying RTA since it is viewed as an intersection of the interpretations of the researcher with the data as a form of co-production (Braun and Clarke 2006; Braun and Clarke 2012; Braun and Clarke 2013). Lincoln and Guba's (1985) criteria for ensuring trustworthiness has been recommended as a useful tool for ensuring verification of thematic analysis and was applied during the course of this study (Nowell et al. 2017). Lincoln and Guba (1985) outline a six-point approach to ensuring trustworthiness including: credibility, transferability, dependability, confirmability, audit trails and reflexivity.

Credibility is determined through explicit alignment of participant views and experiences with the researcher's representations (Tobin and Begley 2004). This was addressed through prolonged engagement with participants during data collection and regular de-briefing throughout the research process (Lincoln and Guba 1985). In addition to monthly de-briefing meetings with a peer as a form of external checking, initial themes were also reviewed to ensure clarity of analytic claims. Transferability is the generalisability of and application of findings to the broader population and has been proposed to promote external validity in qualitative studies. This can be challenging to assure in studies applying an interpretivist/constructivist approach (Yin 2014; Polit and Beck 2017). Perakyla (2011) support that validity in the context of qualitative research therefore relates largely to the

assurance of truthfulness and transparency of analytic claims. Throughout the study, transferability was supported through the provision of rich, descriptive data from participant interviews so that researcher interpretations and analysis were explicit for those wishing to transfer findings to other contexts. The research process was clearly outlined and documented to ensure dependability and credibility of the study (Lincoln and Guba 1985; Tobin and Begley 2004) For example, code charts (refer to **Appendices 12-15** p.206-304) were used to demonstrate transparency and consistency in the coding process and clarity about generation of themes and findings (Lincoln and Guba 1985; Tobin and Begley 2004). Records of each stage of the research process were maintained (i.e., interview recordings, transcripts, field notes etc.) to support a clear audit trail which evidenced analytical decisions throughout the process.

Although RTA is not linked to a particular theoretical framework; Braun and Clarke (2019) argue that in order to maintain validity, it is important that the researcher recognises and clearly articulates their own theoretical assumptions; since decision-making in the research process is often value-laden and driven by these assumptions in conjunction with the underpinning theoretical framework (Braun and Clarke 2006; Braun and Clarke 2012; Braun and Clarke 2013; Clarke et al. 2019). Since researcher bias in interpreting the data should also be considered; ongoing reflexivity was an important means of ensuring reliability and validity in the data analysis process throughout the duration of this study (Perakyla 2011; Gray 2014). This was safeguarded through re-reading transcripts repeatedly to ensure themes were representative of participant response rather than imposing researcher beliefs on participants, maintaining an audit trail of the research process and keeping a reflective research diary to monitor activity and reflect on assumptions and analytical decisions.

While researcher distance and objectivity are regarded as marks of validity in quantitative approaches, in qualitative studies, insider information and contextual knowledge are often considered to strengthen the methodological approach since researcher interaction with the subject constitutes an important part of knowledge production (Sullivan 2010). In addition, the social and interactive elements dictate that the separation of the researcher-participant relationship to maintain objectivity is not necessarily beneficial since each participant brings their own agendas with response and participation (Hugh-Jones 2010). As a result, data is co-created rather than extracted and potential power relationships are of less consequence (Braun and Clarke 2006; Braun and Clarke 2012; Braun and Clarke 2013; Clarke et al. 2019). Although there were no pre-existing close personal or professional relationships between interviewer and participants, the potential for researcher effect was still considered since some of the participants were previously or loosely known to the researcher in a professional capacity either as a former DN, member of teaching staff, or through

professional group membership. This was managed by ensuring participant awareness and informed consent throughout the process and allowing their own beliefs and thoughts to emerge. Any potential for conflict of interest would have been managed on an individual basis. Had such a situation arisen, the decision would have been made to exclude any participants or data. Snape and Spencer (2009) state that continued reflection upon the researcher's position remains a key means of ensuring trustworthiness and aids in ensuring neutrality in qualitative work.

Summary

This chapter outlined the methods applied in conducting this study. This included an overview of the processes of ethical approval and risk management and the methodological approach including: participant recruitment, sampling, data collection and data analysis. Trustworthiness was considered; with ongoing reflexivity highlighted as a key means to assure this within the context of the study.

Chapter 5 Results

This chapter reports on the findings from the RTA of data from two participant groups. An introduction and overview of each theme is provided with sample extracts of interview data and tabulated themes. Following RTA of the semi-structured interview data using Braun and Clarke's 6 phase approach (2006), seven distinct themes were co-created from analysis of the data and the findings of the wider literature. Due to its highly subjective and organic nature, RTA does not demand consensus with coding and theme development and does not have concerns with reliability; however, as a measure to ensure that themes were clearly aligned with analytic claims, each of these was reviewed by two researchers prior to finalisation. During data analysis, this involved checking the themes across the entire dataset and ensuring that each was underpinned by a core concept or idea which the researcher developed from the findings. Names of themes were selected and defined on this basis; and considered in order of perceived dominance; which in the context of this study was ascribed to data that was particularly rich, descriptive and meaningful; and representative of frequently identified subject matter and responses attributed to the largest number of participants. **Figure 7** (p.88) presents the themes in order of perceived dominance.

Appendix 21 (p. 319) presents extracts from the data to support each of the themes.

Figure 7: Themes in order of dominance

Theme 1: *The bigger picture; the smaller picture*

Sub-theme: wound management knowledge comes from multiple sources

Theme 1 revealed the multifactorial and complex nature of wound management knowledge and its origin in multiple sources. This was observed by all participants, with the majority organising sources of knowledge into three over-arching categories: knowledge originating in formal or structured evidence and education; knowledge gained from others; and knowledge learned through their own experience in practice

“...I would say it’s come from multiple sources; I would say it’s come from years of experience in a range of different...um...settings I suppose...I mean I had xx years in xx...em...before I came into tissue viability and I’m xx odd years in tissue viability.....em...I also think that because I worked across community and hospital as well as in a specialist area it actually gives you a very broad range of wounds and experiences and different types of challenges that you come across” (S14)

While knowledge was determined to arise from multiple sources, more informal knowledge types; most notably those originating from experiential learning and from colleagues in practice were the most frequently reported and dominant amongst participants. More than any other type, experiential knowledge that developed over time was reported to form the largest basis of wound management in both participant groups, but most notably, in generalists who did not refer to more formal knowledge types (i.e., research literature) as frequently or as appraisingly as specialists. All participants expressed that much of their knowledge was also picked up from colleagues in practice; for example, peers, specialists, medical consultants and occasionally students. Participants from both groups concurred that formal and informal knowledge types had equally important parts to play in wound management. While a number referred to this in the implicit sense; others clearly stated the equal value of both:

“Emmm, probably from myself when you’re actually going out and you’ve got like an actual wound in front of you and you’ve got somebody there either teaching you or if you’ve met up with tissue viability it kind of gives you that extra knowledge because you’re seeing it first-hand rather than just slides or whatever so I’d say I had a really good experience” (G11)

Sub-themes: consideration and integration of wider holistic factors & wound management is individualised & contextualised

The central concept of this theme was two-fold. First, an acknowledgement of the level of complexity of wound management knowledge and ability to consider and integrate holistic

factors shaping it (i.e., the “bigger picture” of wound management knowledge). Second, an understanding of the individualised and contextualised nature (i.e., the “smaller picture”) of wound management knowledge. For many participants, knowledge associated with the bigger picture centred on wider components; including demographic factors, as well as larger generic issues that impacted on outcomes (i.e., time, resources, consistency of service delivery etc.). It also represented the ability to assess external and internal factors which some participants likened to an ability to “put pieces of a puzzle together”. Correlated but also notably distinct from this, was an ability to recognise unique contextual factors as being important in wound management; an understanding that there was no *one size fits all* and that each individual context had to be considered accordingly; for example, individual patient adherence, personal preferences in relation to dressings or treatments and localised barriers. Although these forms of knowledge were evident in both participant groups, consideration of both the wider holistic factors and the individualised nature of wound management knowledge were more predominantly expressed by those working in the primary care setting. This included all generalist participants but also those specialists practicing within a community role. Although participants working in an acute setting still considered holistic and individual factors in their practice and demonstrated a degree of this type of knowledge, they had more of a tendency to focus directly upon the wound in the *here and now*. Some participants working in the community identified and remarked on this tendency in relation to acute clinicians; including one specialist who had moved from the acute to community and reflected upon it in relation to personal experience:

“I used to refer discharges to the district nurse team and we’d discharge them on a Friday and say “could you go to them on Monday or Tuesday to renew this wound?” and I used to wrap the wound up to make sure it wasn’t going to leak to make absolutely sure it, you know, lasted the person until the nurse came on Tuesday and now having swapped over to this area which is very much an outpatient setting, I can reflect on that and say “how stupid was I? The patient couldn’t get a shower, they couldn’t get a shoe on, it made them less able to mobilise.....” (S12)

Sub-theme: personal motivation and passion drives wound management

A further component of this theme was the perceived importance of personal motivation and individual passion in driving the development of wound management knowledge and practice. Several participants highlighted that they had to actively seek new knowledge out for themselves; for example, finding sources of reading material or making requests to attend CPD and education sessions. There was additional recognition that wound management relied heavily upon the individual efforts of a minority who held a particular

interest to share knowledge with others, propelling it forward as an area of practice. In some cases, this was reported to be in a formal sense (i.e., taking on recognised specialist roles, undergoing specialist education etc.); yet, others who expressed a particular interest in wound management were recognised locally for their expertise and volunteered for roles in which they could develop this (i.e., being nominated to run leg ulcer clinics; undertaking TVN link roles). In most cases, there was recognition of an ongoing level of personal and individual inquiry in the formation of knowledge:

“I think that if you go out to seek the knowledge then you’ve got that personal interest to seek that knowledge and I’m quite happy to talk about that with any...or share it with staff who come to ask if.....that knowledge that came through your professional experience but also through an academic module then you’ve gone and learned more about that particular area and.....I think that that’s important that you’ve got to seek it out as well.....seek the knowledge out” (G12)

Almost all participants acknowledged the role of reflection in the development of wound management knowledge; most commonly, on an individual basis; and less routinely, in structured forms (i.e., with colleagues; either informally or during team meetings). All participants believed that they brought their authentic selves to their wound management practice and many felt that they also brought wound management practice and experience to other areas of their lives. To summarise, this theme revealed knowledge supporting wound management to be a highly complex, skilled type of knowledge that was contextual, situated and more representative of practice-based professions than strictly theoretical knowledge types. It represented an ability to consider both over-arching and individual factors and put pieces together to shape decision making and the importance of individual interest in knowledge formation.

Theme 2: *It all comes together at the bedside*

Sub-theme: wound management knowledge is well integrated

Theme 2 takes the multifactorial nature of wound management knowledge identified in Theme 1 and gives location to its development: the bedside. A number of the participants overtly recognised their own ability to integrate many different knowledge types together and identified this integration taking place most commonly at a practice level in the direct presence of wound. For those with educational components to their role, this also included during active teaching.

“I think for me.....I would do the reading; I would do the conferences and everything and it only really meshed and gelled together when you were actually doing it with your experience; when you were taking it to the bedside; you know the actual wound management or when you were teaching” (SP11)

Sub-theme: intuition is integrated knowledge at subconscious level that develops with experience

The concept of intuition was also dominant here; with a number of participants proposing its crucial role in knowledge formation and expression. Intuition was perceived by a number of participants to be a subtle but advanced knowledge type that often took place at subconscious level. For many, intuition was not regarded as simplistic or devoid of underpinning evidence and formality; rather, it was considered to be directly linked to level and depth of experience and skill, signifying advanced decision-making abilities. It was often perceived to be linked to ability to integrate different sources of information without always being aware of doing so. In addition, intuition was perceived to improve and develop over time and represent a particularly advanced form of knowledge integration.

“Emm...I think it has a big role to play in it. Yeah, intuition and experience go hand in hand that way. But it’s a learned intuition; you can look at something and just know or you get a bad feeling and think ‘I’m going to go back and see them again tomorrow because I don’t know if I trust what I’ve done or I trust that dressing or I’m just going to check that again tomorrow’ because something is just not sitting on you” (G14)

While Theme 1 identified the ability to consider and review the range of complexities in wound management knowledge development and application, Theme 2 centred on the next facet of ability: processing and integrating all of the components presented with them in a clinical situation. Integration of different constituents of knowledge was regarded by some participants as a distinct skill and many believed that it represented a degree of higher-level thinking and ability. Several also noted it to be a core component of wider nursing knowledge which, like intuition, improved with experience.

Theme 3: Show me the evidence

Sub-theme: limitations and barriers to the formal evidence & education in wound management

Theme 3 represented the formal, structured evidence base in wound management knowledge; comprising original research and theory, structured education at pre and post registration levels and policy and guidelines underpinning practice. Formal knowledge and

evidence were agreed to be highly valued but largely underdeveloped by all participants; however, specialists placed more emphasis upon both its importance and shortfalls in the context of wound management. Structured education was identified for its role in ensuring quality, depth and critical appraisal of knowledge. For specialists, it was also a means of securing professional respect.

“I think formal education is what has empowered me to be more confident and I think makes people respect you more than if you have a clinical qualification. Looking back, I think I can rationalise more since I’ve done my masters....you can rationalise better and you do think differently. And my colleagues have actually said to me “you do think differently XXXX; but it’s the education, that’s what helped I think” (S11)

Although the importance of formal education was recognised, limitations and shortfalls relating to both access and quality were widely identified by all participants. Wound management education was unanimously reported to be insufficient, most notably during pre-registration; but also, at post-registration and CPD levels. Limitations were found in relation to a number of factors including time, resources, lack of managerial support and increasing restrictions on engagement with wound management industry. All participants were in agreement that the lack of available formal education impacted negatively on knowledge formation and recognised the role of structured education as a means to improve wound management.

“I haven’t done any specific training other than the days that they put on, sort of wound management days. But actually, even in the latter bit, they weren’t particularly on wound management, they were more on how the formulary got made and it was more budget-related learning; you weren’t really getting any...(pause)... you know..the blurb ‘here’s a wound’. You could go to these days that were optional on the products but again, that was just if you were on duty that day or...if it suited patient-care wise. It wasn’t really a priority” (GP11)

Shortfalls in their own education were widely reported amongst generalists who frequently conveyed difficulties with access. Although specialists faced similar challenges, they were reported to a lesser degree. Many specialists recognised insufficient education to be detrimental in the wider sense, but they unanimously described their own wound management education to be adequate. This was in contrast to generalists who largely regarded their own wound management knowledge to be insufficient, despite there being little difference in overall education levels between the two groups. However, all specialist participants had more wound management-specific education than generalist participants.

Although structured education was widely valued, many participants regarded experiential knowledge as carrying just as much weight as more formal types. A number also conveyed that rather than being regularly accessed directly from the source, evidence was often passed on indirectly from colleagues. For those in specialist roles this was mostly other specialist colleagues, while for generalists this was either specialists such as TVNs or those practicing in Tissue Viability link nurse roles.

Sub-theme: guidelines, formularies, tools and protocols are a key source of evidence

Guidelines, protocols, formularies and structured assessment tools represented an additional source of formal knowledge and evidence and views on their effectiveness were mixed. Whilst some participants regarded them as a necessary form of practical assurance that an evidence-based approach was being utilised; they were also proposed to be a source of restriction on practice. Reported strengths of protocols included: perceived informability, assurance of ethical practice, assurance of responsible resource use and defence against pressure from colleagues to apply practice that wasn't evidence based. Proposed limitations included: inconsistent and overwhelming information, restriction on individual clinical judgement, lack of time to access; exclusion of front-line clinicians on development groups and industry sponsorship. Challenges with application to practice were also recognised by a number of participants.

“Because usually with the xxxx one (guideline) it does say “from such and such” or whatever; but I’ve never really looked at it that in depth because if you’re working, you’re kind of skimming and just taking the kind of points that you need from it really” (G11)

The formal evidence base was recognised as an important source of knowledge, most notably by specialists; who were more critically appraising of its strengths and limitations in the context of wound management. Although several generalists did refer to research and literature as important sources of knowledge, formal evidence was not considered in as much depth and methodological quality was not considered. Generalists who did critique its efficacy did so mainly in relation to links with industry rather than the nature of evidence base or research methodologies employed.

“I think in wound management there is always a lack of what people class a good evidence...you know your RCTs and sort of higher level of evidence....emmm.....a lot of the papers that come out they can be considered biased because they’re sponsored by companies. You have to look beyond that and the stuff the evidence you get that comes through that is by an independent person is much more valuable” (S13)

Many generalists reported time as a barrier to evidence engagement, with a number revealing that it often came second-hand via specialist colleagues.

“Emm.....I probably trust tissue viability.....maybe too much....if we ask them what is the best technique for..... wound cleansing is always a good one; should we cleanse a wound or should you not clean it or what should you clean it with?” (G13)

Theme 4: Industry: a political football

The relationship between healthcare providers and industry within the context of wound management was recognised to be contradictory, contentious and challenging by all participants. Theme 5 addressed this relationship and the influential role industry plays in wound management knowledge formation and practice. Three main areas of focus were identified: industry’s influence on the creation of the evidence base itself, the provision of product-based education; and the importance of maintaining ethical relationships between health care service providers and company representatives.

“Right.....it’s a bit of a political football.....now.....it wasn’t so much before.....we couldn’t have functioned without the wound care companies.....and the wound care companies couldn’t have functioned without us because TVNs were- and to a certain extent still do-function as gatekeepers... I think.....there was.....some people took probably more an ethical approach than others.....” (SP11)

Sub-theme: importance of industry role

Many participants conveyed that interaction between industry and health care service providers was increasingly regulated by health service managers and believed that this imposed unnecessary restrictions. Although the importance of ethical engagement with companies was clearly articulated, all participants expressed a sense of frustration about it and identified industry as having an important role in research development, education delivery and provision of product information. The majority believed that partnerships with industry should be encouraged and facilitated but identified that this had become increasingly difficult in clinical practice. As a result, many participants believed that wound management knowledge and education were becoming increasingly compromised

“Maybe reps aren’t the best people because maybe they’re trying to sell you something.....and.....we’re told not to organise reps; although recently I was trying to prescribe some XXXXX for a patient and I knew I was going to get the wrong ones and then I did get the wrong ones and then it’s a huge expense. So, I tried to organise the rep to come

to the team meeting to give us some training on prescribing basically because we know this is the best thing for the patient” (G13)

“I do think a lot of their (reps) information is ...can be very helpful because there’s always wee tricks or things with their products that they know inside out; so, I do think that it would have been beneficial a bit more if there was a bit of teaching from them and then-I don’t know; but if it’s on the formulary, there is some evidence behind it so I don’t know why they couldn’t like give us what they’re worth” (GP11)

Sub-theme: ethical engagement with industry & potential for bias

Although industry was valued by the majority of participants, there was recognition of the limitations associated with industry-supported evidence, mainly in relation to ensuring ethical conduct and reducing bias. However, almost all participants remarked that as autonomous practitioners, nurses should be regarded as competent to make their own decision and didn’t need institutional restrictions to engage ethically. A number also recognised the regulatory guidelines and codes of conduct that supported sound interaction with industry as being a form of insurance and protection against conflict of interest.

“I think they do have a role and I certainly miss that we don’t have that any more....I think that theytheir knowledge on their products is very good.....personally; but also, a lot of my colleagues and I feel we can make our own decision on the products; we wouldn’t be unduly influenced by one particular rep who’s nicer than the other....I’d like to think that we can make our clinical decision based on what that individual wound needs as opposed to what product we’ve been sold” (G12)

Of all of the themes, this one presented the most contradictory data. All but one participant agreed that the development of wound management knowledge relied heavily upon facilitating partnerships with industry, but there were mixed feelings about the extent to which companies should be involved in the development of evidence. There was also a belief, particularly amongst specialists; that the evidence base supporting wound management would be strengthened by more independent studies; which were regarded to be methodologically superior to those sponsored and supported by companies. Nationally visible experts and noted practitioners working in the field of wound management who were perceived to have close relationships with industry were also viewed with mixed feelings by some of the specialists.

“I do wonder if.....some people can be very positive and have influence that..... I do wonder if it’s the best influence, if that makes sense; not from a wound management point of

view, but I think that XXXX has got a lot of clout. I don't know her personally but I know she's very vocal and she's very..... I know she has a lot of influence there, but one thing I'm not sure about is how much she is influenced by companies" (S14).

Despite the mixed and often contradictory beliefs about the role of industry; the majority of participants were in agreement that wound management could not function without it.

Theme 5: *Do good not harm*

Sub-theme: *doing the right thing*

For all participants, the prospect of doing the right thing for the patient was a central concept that ran through all aspects of practice. Many used variations of the term *doing good not harm* to describe the ethical components of their wound management practice, which was articulated in a number of ways. These included: direct interaction with patients, adherence to protocol, formulary and guidelines and ethical engagement with industry. At the bedside this included an understanding of more generic ethical conduct such as giving the right information to patients, gaining consent, minimising pain and discomfort and ensuring cultural sensitivity.

"Yes. Doing the right thing or not doing any harm. And also helping them make the right decisions as well because they may actually choose not to go with what you have advised; they may choose to take a risk in something and choose something that's actually may do them good and it may not and I suppose it's giving them the ability to make that decision with the right level of information" (S14)

Taking a person-centred approach and meeting patient goals was also a recurrent topic within this theme.

"Yeah my goal is often to make the wound smaller or heal it. But I had a man with a spinal injury a tetraplegic type condition and I asked 'well what is your goal?' because he'd been on bed rest for months and months and months and he said 'my goal is to see my 12-year-old son playing football in the park' and I said 'well we can get you up for 2 hours on a Sunday to do that' (S11)

In the wider sense, participants related ethical knowledge to examples from practice including being accountable for ones' clinical actions, ensuring equity of service and one of the most frequently reported: adherence to formulary. For a few in specialist roles, it was also linked to ethical research conduct. Consideration of cost and responsible use of resources were also recounted to represent ethical knowledge by many participants. At the

level of the individual clinician, this included scale of product and dressing use and at wider level, service provision and equity of distribution. Almost all participants described wound management services in their area to be equitable on the whole and described patients as being able to access what they needed; with only one participant believing this not to be the case. Although it was acknowledged that some patients may get a bit more than others at times; this was perceived to be the exception and always in relation to proposed clinical need rather than any unethical factor.

“Absolutely; we’re talking about elderly people with paper thin skin here and they’re telling me its £££ per sachet of XXXX so I think they might try to be restrictive. This is local contract for NHSXXXX and its on contract, I’m not breaching contract. I might be incurring cost for them but am I convinced I am doing the best for the patient? Yeah I am” (S12)

Ethical engagement with industry was another topic widely acknowledged here and included appropriate conduct and recognition of potential bias in industry-supported research, evidence and product education.

Sub-theme: sound ethical practice but not widely considered in theory.

Although there was consistent consideration and demonstration of sound ethical practice amongst participants, this was not routinely in a theoretical sense. Despite being widely practiced, ethical conduct was not always formally considered. Many participants expressed that they felt ethically ill-prepared, having no knowledge of ethical guidance specific to wound management to support them. The exceptions were industry and health board-related codes of conduct which were the only identified sources of guidance mentioned by a number of participants in relation to ethical behaviour.

“I wouldn’t say I’ve been aware of any ethical guidelines; I have to be honestno I can’t say I’ve.....I’m thinking of a few years ago a surgeon wanted brown sugar and.....something to make a paste to go into a patient’s wound and you know.....that was notgoing to happen (laughs).....but that’s the kind of challenges.....I can’t think of any ethical guidelines that are sort of general for all wound management” (S13)

Theme 6: The power isn’t ours

Sub-theme: barriers to wound management knowledge development

Theme 6 represented the barriers that restricted wound management knowledge development and practice. There was recognition from many participants that most of these were directly or indirectly related to wider political and organisational factors that were often

perceived to be beyond the control of the participants themselves. These were represented by the extrinsic factors in the blue outer circle in **Figure 1** in Chapter 1 (p. 12) and included generic factors such as time, money, resource or skill; as well as more specific and localised barriers including lack of consistency between acute and primary care formularies and inconsistent service provision across different areas. Most barriers were recognised to arise from problems on the wider scale; for example, the prevalence of ritualistic practice in wound management which was widely identified and perceived to result from bigger barriers including: insufficient time and resources to access education and CPD; and low value placed on wound management as a speciality.

“I think wounds for a long time has been quite low profile and I think, you know cancer and heart disease and all these things have been really up there, but I think they’ve realised- especially chronic wounds, I think they’ve realised the impact that chronic wounds have on patients and life and budgets is huge. But yeah I think it has to be recognised at quite a high level for things to change and happen” (S14)

People were often presented as barriers to effective knowledge development and practice and these were reported to include fellow clinicians, colleagues, managers and patients, who could intentionally or unintentionally fail to engage with treatment pathways.

“I would say.....other staff being blinkered...with their.....‘this is what I want to use’. But I’ve always done it this way’. That kind of attitude. ‘But I like XXXX on everything’. You know that is blinkered and that is obstructive and it’s not always the best for the patient (laughs)” (G14)

Despite lengthy referral processes being cited as barriers to practice (i.e., several generalists reported that referrals to TV service took a long time), all participants reported that they had good relationships with colleagues from different clinical backgrounds. Any clashes in relation to wound management were reported to be at individual level rather than between particular professions. Many participants working in generalist roles (i.e., DNs or CSNs) presented the nature of the role and challenges specific to it as being obstructive. These mainly centred around the number of competing demands, lack of time and opportunity for wound management CPD; but also challenges inherent with working in the community setting; for example, not having access to proper equipment and supplies and being isolated from colleagues:

“I think in community it’s definitely time; you don’t have the time to spend as much ...em...time or even like that...read up on things.....time is a problem and also just the total variation of the job. You could be doing wound management one day...one visit and then the

next one you're in at a palliative care and the next minute you're in at a different task; so, you've got to know a bit of everything...the sort of variety that you have to cover in your day restricts the amount of time that you can up your game in one particular area unless it's your....like...love and passion" (GP11)

Specialist participants also identified distinct role-specific barriers; most notably the absence of a clear training structure and career trajectory for TVNs and the low profile of wound management as an area of clinical speciality.

Sub-theme: power in wound management

The concept of power and its relationship to the perceived barriers restricting wound management practice was also considered by a number of participants and this was often explored in the context of relationships with colleagues; for example, senior managers and other clinicians. Although participants reported positive relationships with clinical colleagues, organisational factors such as lengthy referral processes were highlighted as having a negative impact. At times management was perceived as being obstructive, for example, when restricting product use to local formulary, failing to support education and CPD and restricting interaction with industry. The notion that wound management knowledge development relied upon those individuals with particular passion to carry it forward was raised again in this context; often with the suggestion that shortfalls relating to organisational factors made it a necessary compensatory measure to develop and champion wound management as a speciality. There was an expressed sense of individuals having to go above and beyond; despite perceived lack of recognition, career progression or financial incentive.

"I think the motivation and support to learn in management- or your employer- is lacking; unless you're really motivated or driven. And actually, the career structure within our organisations and limits.....it doesn't encourage.....there's no career pathway for clinicians if you want to remain clinical and progress if you get to a Band 7. So, I've learned to cope with that, that it's about job satisfaction" (S11)

An additional point within this theme was in relation to the perceived value of wound management as a speciality. Most generalists perceived it to be held in high value as an area of practice compared to other areas of practice in the community (i.e., continence); yet, many participants practicing in a specialist role expressed that the opposite was true. Generalists viewed specialists such as TVNs as holding positions of influence and power within wound management practice; although many participants from the specialist groups did not share this observation about their own roles.

*“(Long pause).....The TVN should have.....**should** have the power. **Should**. I think I had the power; however informal it was.....in my clinical area. I think now that they’ve moved to larger teams, I think it’s not as high profile; it doesn’t have the same visibility.....”*
(SP11)

Despite being held in high regard by generalist participants, many specialists believed roles such as that of the TVN had decreased in value and influence over time. The role of the medical profession in wound management was also raised by a number of participants with some conflicting views being expressed. While many participants reported doctors as having an overall lack of interest and specific knowledge in wound management; some specialists reported being pressured to implement clinical interventions and treatment pathways dictated by senior medical staff on occasion. However, most described good partnerships with medical colleagues.

Theme 7: I’m not that creative...but

The concept of creativity as a component of wound management knowledge was one that resonated less obviously with participants than more structured forms of knowledge. Many explicitly identified themselves as being more scientific and logical than creative and appeared to find questions relating to creativity challenging to answer. Although many participants had to think carefully about applying creativity in their wound management knowledge development and practice; artistic expressions were clearly demonstrated on the whole; if not always immediately obvious to the participants themselves.

“I suppose I’m not a creative person in my normal life..emmm...but certainly in terms of wound care I would say myself and my colleagues can be quite creative...at times when we have to be. And that can be a challenge, so I mean it can be awkward to dress areas-VACs are the main ones I can think of, when you’ve got quite a complex VAC dressing and we often finish by saying we should get a Blue Peter badge” (S13)

Expressions of creativity focused around 3 main areas: creative therapeutic approaches creativity in forming & maintaining relationships and creativity in relation to the consideration of wider holistic factors in forming wound management practice. These have been represented as sub-themes below.

Sub-theme: creative therapeutic approaches

Creative therapeutic approaches related mainly to skill in dressing technique and application; for example, the ability to be adaptable and innovative with limited supplies or when treating

wounds that were problematic to dress because of location or nature of wound (i.e., using flesh-coloured dressings on the face or adapting dressings to fit to an elbow or knee).

“Eh, yes. I am very much an advocate for shapes and eh, yeah, I quite often say to patients this is what I learned on Blue Peter because you know quite a lot of dressings are square and.....yeah.....wounds come in all shapes and sizes and the dressings that are designed for heels and sacrum but you know, a scalp is not square, the side of a nose is not square, a fingertip is not square, so things have gotten better in terms of that so aesthetically, yes (S12)

Participants who were involved in delivering education mentioned creativity in relation to presentation and teaching activity, while other generic activities (i.e., developing newsletters) were also identified in this context. The majority of participants expressed an element of enjoyment associated with utilising creative skills in wound management; and the ability to dress a wound well was identified by some participants as an activity that was particularly rewarding.

“I think there’s an art to it; a beautiful bandage is an art. There’s nothing nicer in life than a nice bandage. And there’s nothing worse than one that looks horrific. Pet hate as well is not putting it on properly. You know, it’s on from the ankle to the mid-calf or one that’s pristine, there’s a beauty to it” (G14)

Sub-theme-creativity in forming & maintaining relationships:

Most participants referred to the use of communication as an example of creativity in their wound management practice; usually in the context of forming and maintaining relationships with colleagues, patients and carers. This included using humour, listening and sharing oneself as a means to build relationships; as well as using negotiation skills to “get the patient on board” with treatment plans. Most participants believed themselves to be authentic in sharing their true nature in their wound management practice; however, part of the creative knowing in this respect was knowing when to be “professional” and knowing when it was appropriate to let their “authentic self” show.

“You probably bring a bit of both because I think... if you don’t bring your true self, like building relationships, seeing what makes people tick- I think that’s a skill in itself. So, if you can’t do that, then you’re not going to treat the wound because you’re not going to really know what the patient needs or wants or feels or thinks.....” (G11)

Sub-theme: creativity in relation to the consideration of wider holistic factors in forming wound management practice

Ability to consider and integrate the wider holistic aspects shaping wound management (as explored in Theme 1) was also considered to demand a level of creative knowledge and skill in wound management practice; supporting existing literature which has been widely discussed here.

“Emmm....I think its looking at the holistic type approach where you’re looking at all the other reasons why this wound isn’t healing, what else is going on with the patient-their nutritional status; emm...their mobility all the different aspects of pressure that could be affecting as it as just opposed to it being a wound on its own” (G12)

Themes in the context of the conceptual framework: Chinn and Kramer’s patterns of knowing (2015).

Following consideration of initial findings, the themes generated from the present study were examined in the context of Chinn and Kramer’s *Patterns of Knowing* (2015). These have been outlined and presented in **Appendix 22** (p. 323). For many of the themes, there was substantial overlap within the framework; with several of these not presenting as distinguishable or clear cut within the bounds of each pattern. This potential for overlap and interrelationships between patterns has been addressed by Chinn & Kramer (2015), who propose that since *knowing* is more than can be defined and expressed formally with expressions of individual patterns alone, it would naturally follow that knowledge considered within the bounds of this framework would be highly integrated in nature (Chinn and Kramer 2015). Due to the subjective nature of RTA, it was also recognised that pre-existing researcher assumptions would shape many of the analytic claims and that codes, sub-themes and themes could have been interpreted and proposed to fit into several of Chinn and Kramer’s (2015) patterns in a number of different ways; further increasing the potential for overlap. In the context of this study, each of the themes was found by to be linked to more than one pattern; including a dominant or *core* pattern that most closely articulated it; and less dominant additional pattern(s) with which it could also be mapped. The exception was Theme 2, which focused upon the ability to integrate different types of knowledge in wound management and was therefore perceived to connect all of the themes rather than align to any particular one(s) individually.

The prevalence and frequency of links between themes and patterns were also recorded at this stage. Although quantitative data such as frequency and prevalence are not routinely considered to be relevant to qualitative studies (Pyett 2003), their potential to be indicators of dominance and therefore providers of key information relating to the nature of wound management knowledge were points of interest in the context of this study. Their potential significance was therefore analysed accordingly and presented in **Table 4** (p. 104).

Emancipatory knowing was the pattern that linked the biggest number of themes, supporting Chinn and Kramer’s (2015) suggestion that it runs through and shapes all remaining patterns rather than presenting distinctly. However; it was also a core pattern to only one theme, suggesting that emancipatory knowing was not as visibly valued or recognised by participants in comparison to empiric knowing; the latter being the only pattern that had core links to more than one theme. Aesthetic knowing, was of less perceived value and frequent expression amongst participants and had the least number of links to themes overall. Since empiric knowing was found to be the most highly valued pattern by participants, the number of core links to themes in this context may therefore be positively correlated to the level of which participants valued a particular type of knowledge.

Table 4: Prevalence & frequency of links between themes and patterns of knowing

Pattern of Knowing	Number of links to Theme	Core	Additional
Empiric	4	2	4
Ethical	4	1	3
Personal	4	1	3
Aesthetic	2	1	1
Emancipatory	6	1	5

Chinn and Kramer (2015) suggest that all patterns must be integrated and complementary or they become removed from the context as a whole. They further argue that the empiric pattern has been historically over-valued in nursing and therefore represents a *pattern gone wild*. Although empiric knowing was also found to be highly valued by participants within the context of wound management, its value was not consistently aligned to level of expression and articulation. This was partly attributed to associated shortfalls in formal evidence and education; which placed wound management specialists and generalists with little choice but to rely more heavily upon less formal sources of knowledge such as experiential learning than they may have done had more structured evidence and education of sufficient quality been more accessible. It resulted in personal knowing becoming the only pattern which identified as a *pattern gone wild* in the context of wound management; an illustrative overview of which is presented in **Figure 8** (p.106). However, this was more in relation to its

demonstration and expression since participants did not consistently and explicitly articulate its perceived value.

Figure 8: Case Study

Case Study: a *pattern gone wild* in wound management

“...I think that you have to have the science and you have to have the art side of it; you have to understand the psychology of the patient and the sociology, you know the family dynamics, the lifestyle issues, the work-life balance side of things and that not...its science but it’s not anything you can actually put down to figures and I think wounds are the same. I don’t think you can say....yes, we need the science, we absolutely need the science of why wounds heal, why they break down, the different aetiologies, we need that information. But actually, we can have all that information and we can address them and we can have a wound that’s still not healing. And that is actually where I think the bigger picture bit comes in and the art bit of it comes in and it’s like ‘right I’ve looked at all the science-y bits of it, but actually the patient has got religious reasons why they take the dressings off or why they wash that part of the body with that particular product?’ Have I looked at the family reasons why that patient doesn’t do anything because actually the family wait on them hand and foot because that’s their culture? Have I looked at they’re smoking and can’t give it up because they’ve got mental health issues and that’s their way of dealing with their mental health but actually its affecting their wound?”

“You can’t develop and learn without seeing other people’s skills as well. I mean I learned sharp debridement by watching plastic surgeons in theatre and watching the skills they had and the techniques and that was before there were courses in that. You know, there weren’t any courses, so you did it and were watched by a plastic surgeon and they said ‘yeah you can do it’ and that was you. So, you learn your skills by watching and observing and by asking questions; you know sometimes, I think we can observe and understand and not necessarily take on those skills; but know that that person is who we refer on to. So, for example, diabetic podiatrists, that is a skill in its own right you- know, the sharp debridement and the assessments they do. But to actually see those skills and understand makes you see ‘well that’s where we need to send people’ because although the guidelines say it, actually you’ve seen it and you can’t do that and that’s not a skill anyone can do”.

*“... I think they’re all important (slight hesitation)(pause)...I think... you do the reading (pause)..... and if it matches up with what you see in practice, you’re more likely to take it on board.....or be reassured that what you think and what you see is correct.....Ummmm... I think the really good, **really** experienced people take the knowledge and actually challenge what they see and do in practice and pick out the bits that match what they know. But...but, it’s the looking deeper in what’s actually going on and so I think the discussion with peers is really valuable...and I think that probably influences an awful lot of people.....”*

Chinn and Kramer (2015) propose that the layers of knowledge formation in each dimension occur at individual, collective and disciplinary levels in ordered phases (i.e. critical questions initiate creative processes through which knowledge is generated and formally expressed; then presented for formal authentication before finally, reaching the stage of integrated expression in practice). This conceptualisation was introduced in Chapter 3 **Table 2** (p. 70) and is presented in **Appendix 23** (p. 327) with adaptations of the original dimensions provided to illustrate examples of knowledge formation at each phase within the context of wound management. This consists of examples of formal expressions in practice for each pattern; many of which align closely to codes, themes and sub-themes and findings from the literature review (i.e. integration of wider holistic factors in wound management and referral to formularies and protocols). It also includes extracts of data which illustrate critical questions, creative processes, authentication processes and integrated expressions in practice that were provided by participants for each of the patterns of knowing. Cross-over and overlap between patterns was also evidenced here; for example, policy, protocols and guidelines were cited as formal expressions in practice for ethical, emancipatory and empiric knowing

Summary

Seven themes were constructed following a RTA of the interview data: *the bigger, picture; the smaller picture; it all comes together at the bedside; show me the evidence; industry: a political football; do good not harm; the power isn't ours; and I'm not that creative...but*. With the exception of Theme 4, which explored the influence of industry in wound management knowledge formation and to a lesser extent, Theme 3 which represented the formal evidence base and revealed unique expressions of the nature of knowledge in the context of wound management, all remaining themes were more generic and reflective of nursing practice in the wider sense with fewer facets that were distinct to wound management. The nature of wound management knowledge was found to be individualised and contextualised and developing predominantly through experience in the practice setting; with personal knowing found to be a *pattern gone wild* in this context. This was also reflective of findings of several studies included in the literature review, in which the evidence base supporting this area of practice was limited, leaving knowledge development in wound management to occur mainly in the practice setting.

Chapter 6 Discussion

This chapter presents a discussion of novel findings from the study in the context of current wound management practice. Chinn and Kramer's *Patterns of Knowing* (2015) will be used to frame findings within the context of current wound management practice; following which distinctions between wound management knowledge specialists and generalists will be explored. Study outcomes will then be considered within three categorisations: those that are generic to nursing; those which are generic to nursing but significantly shaped by the context of wound management and those that can be considered unique to wound management.

Empiric knowing in wound management

Empiric knowing was found to be highly valued by all participants but largely underdeveloped, particularly in relation to the quality and availability of research evidence and structured education. It was the most frequently referred-to patterns by participants; but the least dominant in shaping knowledge in this context. This mirrors findings from the preliminary literature review which identified shortfalls in wound management evidence and education at pre-registration, post-registration and CPD levels (Dugdall and Watson 2009; Cowman et al. 2011; Moore and Clarke 2011; McCluskey and McCarthy 2012; Innes-Walker and Edwards 2013; Ousey et al. 2013b; Cullen and Moore 2013; Stephen-Haynes 2013; Gillespie et al. 2014; Ferriera et al. 2014; Quaddum and Khawaldeh 2014; Romero-Collado et al. 2014; Gonzaga de Faria et al. 2016; Pieper et al. 2016). It contrasts with Chinn and Kramer's (2015) proposal that empiric knowing has been historically over-emphasised in nursing and it's proposed position as a *pattern gone wild* in the wider context of the profession. The results of this study therefore suggest that aspects of empiric knowing in wound management development should be considered distinguishable from other clinical areas of practice since they do not consistently reflect previous ideas about knowledge in the wider picture of nursing in this respect. Yet, despite claims of a historic over-emphasis of empiric knowing by Chinn and Kramer (2015), shortfalls in formal knowledge and evidence in the nursing profession have been commonly identified and the profession has been criticised for borrowing on the evidence base from professions such as medicine, science and the social and behavioural sciences in attempts to gain academic and professional legitimacy (Aktar-Danesh et al. 2013; Ayala et al. 2014; Chinn and Kramer 2015; Pahor et al. 2015; Shearer 2015). The recognition that nursing is shaped by multidimensional knowledge that is rooted in socialisation can be considered different; yet not inferior to formal knowledge types; adding to the questionable nature of this claim (Green and Earle 2010; Aktar-Danesh et al. 2013; Ayala et al. 2014; Pahor et al. 2015; Shearer 2015; Springer and Clinton 2015;

Williams and Burke 2015). The documented status of empiric knowing as a *pattern gone wild* in wider nursing might therefore be proposed to reflect aspiration, emphasis and value placed on scientific evidence by nurses rather than quality of expression and articulation; as it does in the context of wound management. This may be reflective of findings supporting the perceived superiority of academic, objective and technical knowledge, the traditional dominance of quantitative research evidence and the nursing professions's strive to embody it (Greene and Earle 2010; Ayala et al. 2014; Donomeyer 2014; Cohen et al. 2018). It therefore upholds arguments that the perceived superiority of positivism is rooted in power and elitism rather than being determinants of true quality (Donomeyer 2014; Giroux 2017).

Shortfalls and limitations in research evidence and application of protocols and guidelines aligning to empiric knowing were found to comprise some of the most significant barriers in wound management knowledge development which supports the findings of the preliminary literature review (Lamond and Farnell 1998; Dugdall & Watson 2009; Miyazaki et al. 2010; Beeckman et al. 2011; McCluskey and McCarthy 2012; Ashton and Price 2013; Ferriera et al. 2014; Gillespie et al. 2014; Samuiriwo and Dowding 2014; Ylonen et al. 2014; Gillespie et al. 2015; Logan 2015; Simonetti et al. 2015; Gonzaga de Faria et al. 2016; Gray et al. 2019). Several specialist participants highlighted particular shortfalls associated with the formal evidence base: most notably, that it did not include a sufficient number of scientific studies placed high on traditional evidence hierarchies which negatively impacted upon the quality of knowledge. However, although it was determined that studies adopting the positivist paradigm were important in relation to ensuring perceived scientific and professional legitimacy, it was also recognised by several specialists that experimental and quantitative studies were too de-contextualised and far removed from clinical practice to be meaningful; a finding that was also identified in the literature review (Habermas 1972; Madden 2012; Hammersley 2013; Donomeyer 2014; Polit and Beck 2017). Polit and Beck (2017) also question the suitability of the positivist approach in nursing, pointing out that methods of control and elimination of variables don't always transfer to the practice setting; therefore questioning their theoretical suitability in the context of wound management. This aligns to findings from wider literature and this study which have identified experiential and practice-based knowledge as the primary underpinning for wound management (Kennedy and Arundel 1998a; Kennedy and Arundel 1998b; Haram et al. 2003; Edwards et al. 2005; Ashton and Price 2013; Gillespie et al. 2014; Qaddumi and Khawaldeh 2014; Samuiriwo and Dowding 2014; Gillespie et al. 2015; Gonzaga de Faria et al. 2016; Gray et al. 2019). All participants in this study supported that experiential knowledge types were just as important as that learned from formal sources such as research evidence and education; findings that echo those from wider literature on nursing knowledge (Carper 1978; Benner 1982; Kennedy

2004; Richie and Lewis 2009; Cioffi 2012; Chinn and Kramer 2015; Pahor et al. 2015; Davis and Maisano 2016; Lockwood and Hopp 2016; Voldbjerg et al. 2016).

Identified challenges with application of guidelines were highlighted in this study and have been linked to ineffective knowledge transfer (KT) in wider nursing practice by previous studies (Cioffi 2012; Kilpatrick et al. 2015; Nickitas and Friedrickson 2015; Svavarsdottir et al. 2015; Kitson and Harvey 2016; Lockwood and Hopp 2016). In addition to recognition of the barriers between research and practice, are those between evidence, policy and administration (Moat et al. 2013; Kilpatrick et al. 2015). Svavarsdottir et al. (2015) propose that KT occurs in two stages: the creation stage and the action stage, maintaining that it must be effective at both; whilst Kilpatrick et al. (2015) uphold that due to limited understanding of the process of KT, only half of patients receive care that is consistent with evidence-based practice. Kilpatrick et al. (2015) add that like knowledge itself, KT is multidimensional and iterative, occurring at both levels of research evidence and cognitive, interpersonal levels. Lockwood and Hopp (2016) support KT as being process-driven, which leads to routine shortfalls between what nurses know and what they do; and significant variations that are dependent upon context. Cioffi (2012) argues that an ageing workforce and increasing number of experienced nurses leaving the profession have led to shift in the ratio of experience and a subsequent decline in expertise being passed from experienced nurses to those who are new to the profession. This is a development which should have a particular impact on tacit knowledge types, since Cioffi (2012) proposes they are best learned through experiential means; for example, storytelling and practical activity. It may have additional implications for DNs practicing wound management since it has been recognised as an ageing specialty (Heaslip 2014; McComiskey 2017).

The utilisation of guidelines as a key source of evidence for clinicians is also of consideration here; for example, those produced by National Institute of Care Excellence (NICE) and the Scottish Intercollegiate Guidelines Network (SIGN) which are widely adopted across the NHS as a means to standardise the management of particular conditions and ensure the application of evidence-based practice. Inconsistent application of guidelines was identified in this study, but limitations in the guideline development process should also be considered as an indicator of efficacy and quality of evidence. While processes for guideline development are highly standardised and employ strict criteria for hierarchies of evidence upon which recommendations are based, there is a continued preference for positivist/realist studies to underpin guidelines. As a result, evidence from the interpretivist/constructivist paradigm are routinely omitted and contextual factors (i.e., patient preference and clinician experience) are overlooked in evidence formation. This undermines the value of any knowledge that it is not purely scientific or technical in scope; thus, reinforcing the perceived

superiority of positivism (Donomeyer 2014). A second limitation pertains to the elitist approach of the guideline group selection process and inequitable representation of professions, which are selected based upon expertise within a specific clinical or scientific field. Guideline groups are disproportionately formed by members of the medical profession, yet the responsibility and expertise in wound management lies mainly with nurses. A particular example is *SIGN 120 Management of Chronic Venous Leg Ulcers* (SIGN 2010) for which only three of the sixteen development group members were nurses; despite the management of venous leg ulcers being overwhelmingly led by the profession in practice. This highlights the dominance of medicine as the most influential health care profession and the political and power dimensions which underpin health care and research development (Friedson 1970; McInnes and Lawson-Brown 2007; Johnson 2008; Denny 2010; Keeling & Templeman 2012; Ayala et al. 2014; Donomeyer 2014; Fantahun et al. 2014) and supports arguments that nurses should be more equally represented on guideline development groups relevant to wound management.

Industry was also identified as having a particularly influential role on the development of the evidence base and shaping the empiric pattern of knowing. Again, this was considered to decrease legitimacy and quality of evidence to some degree; suggesting that participants recognised the potential implications of the marketisation and commodification of research. It contrasted to some findings from the existing literature which attributed clinicians as having a largely uncritical attitude to the role and influence of industry (Kessenich and Westbrook 1999; Monaghan et al. 2003; Ashmore et al. 2007; Crigger et al. 2009; Madden 2012). Yet, industry was also considered to hold value in relation to the production of research and education by all participants and most believed its role should be facilitated in this respect. Only specialists in this study considered the importance of innovation in the context of wound management research; which highlights the differences between the two participant groups in relation to understanding and prioritisation of empiric evidence in this context. Yet notably, no specialist participants articulated a critical understanding of the nature and quality of innovation in recognition of Madden's (2012) proposal that product innovation replaces methodological research design as a marker of quality at wound management educational conferences.

The challenges around wound management education were reported to affect all levels of education across both specialist and generalist roles to varying degrees. A majority of nurses in the UK stated that they obtained most of their education in-house; which was routinely delivered by TVNs or representatives from industry. A standardised, evaluated approach can therefore not be assured and conflicts of interests and adequate control of the marketable aims of companies remain problematic to ensure (Maylor 2012). Ousey (2017)

anticipates that the situation will worsen with increasing cuts to CPD funding in NHS England; a development which is likely to affect other areas of the UK. This should be regarded as an additional contributing factor to the prevalence of ritualistic practice that has been commonly reported (Dugdall and Watson 2009; Mizazaki et al. 2010; McCluskey and McCarthy 2012; Ferriera et al. 2014; Gillespie et al. 2014; Qaddum and Khawaldeh 2014; Gonzaga de Faria et al. 2016).

Poor links between theoretical knowledge and practice were also identified in the context of wound management in the literature review for this study as well as by participants (Dugdall & Watson 2009; McCluskey & McCarthy 2012; Ferriera et al. 2014; Gillespie et al. 2014; Logan 2015; Gonzaga de Faria et al. 2016). Since wound management knowledge was found to be largely practice-based and contextual, it naturally follows that links with academic knowledge would be challenging to assure (Dugdall and Watson 2008; Ousey et al. 2013a; Gonzaga de Faria 2016; Gray et al. 2019). Literature supports that it has been historically problematic for educators to make *doing* based knowledge explicit and formal (Cioffi 2012; Davis and Maisano 2016; Lockwood and Hopp 2016); which can be considered an additional contributing factor impacting on knowledge development. Issues with access to structured education were also reported by participants; however, those who had completed formal wound management education reported on its perceived benefits on knowledge and competence. This barrier has also been reported in wider literature, mainly by those practicing in generalist roles (Ashton and Price 2013; Tubaishat et al. 2013; Gray et al. 2019). Yet, as the higher education sector moves towards globalisation (Ashwin et al. 2015); there is potential for some of these barriers to be overcome. For example, increased opportunities for distance and elearning and more collaborative, innovative approaches should be perceived as widening access and having a positive impact on empiric knowing. However, the corporatisation of a higher education sector that is increasingly based on economic modelling, may also present issues of quality and potential conflicts of interest since students are likened to consumers (Ashwin et al. 2015; Giroux 2017).

Participants' identification that wound management knowledge and evidence primarily develops in the practice setting reflects aspects of the apprentice model of education which dominated nursing prior to the move towards graduate level education (Denny 2010; Keeling and Templeman 2012; Ayala et al. 2014; Fantahun et al. 2014). Although the effectiveness of apprenticeship models of nurse education have been questioned by many nurse theorists for their academic integrity (Croxon and Maginnis 2009; Jacobs 2018; Jayasekara et al. 2018; Mulkeen et al. 2019; Taylor and Flaherty 2020); their popularity has increased in recent years in recognition of the practice-based nature of knowledge development in the profession. This has led to their re-introduction by the NMC in England 2017; the

implications of which on the development of the empiric evidence base remain to be seen. The findings of this study support knowledge and evidence being exchanged and transferred at practice; therefore clinical educator and links roles may be worthy of note as effective facilitators of this.

The findings of this study support the continued profile of wound management as a nursing-led speciality which predominantly utilises multidimensional practice-based knowledge types rooted in holism; rather than scientific, systems-based knowledge typical of ANP practice. On one hand this supports the profile of nursing as an adaptable and diverse profession utilising multiple forms of knowledge which are highly integrated and contextual (Springer and Clinton 2015; Gillespie et al. 2016; Lockwood and Hopp 2016). On the other, it has been recognised that nursing specialities such as tissue viability have faced a historic lack of role definition in the UK (Maylor 2012; Ousey et al. 2013b; Ousey et al. 2015) and do not clearly align with contemporary frameworks for educational and career pathways such as that outlined by the CNOD in Scotland (CNOD 2017a) (refer to Chapter 1 **Figure 3** p. 17). Although clinical decision making in wound management was recognised in this study to be complex, variable and often intuitive (Lamond and Farnell 1998; Barratt, Cassidy and Graham 2009; Thompson and Adderley 2014; Samuiriwo and Dowding 2014; Logan 2015), ANP models are increasingly favoured as models of contemporary nursing expertise which may contribute to the continued lack of value of specialist practice and perceived inferiority of the nursing evidence base (Denny 2010; Keeling and Templeman 2012; Ayala et al. 2014; Fantahun et al. 2014). However; advanced practice models have been successfully utilised in tissue viability practice out with the UK (Upton et al. 2015); offering scope for further development in this capacity. As the new pre-registration curriculum embeds (NMC 2018), development of advanced skills such as assessment and prescribing earlier in the career trajectory should support frameworks of nursing knowledge that increasingly utilise medical models, without losing the holistic forms of knowledge that have remained integral to nursing.

Contemporary competency and capability frameworks also offer scope to capture some of the more nuanced but measurable forms of knowledge, competence and skills supporting wound management. For example, the TVLC Framework identifies clinical skills along with wider cognitive abilities such as problem solving and critical thinking; therefore incorporating theoretical knowledge reflecting graduate attributes in combination with skill and behaviour-based dimensions (Ousey 2016b). This reflects the proposed strengths of practice based, integrated knowledge in line with definitions of capability which can be considered better rounded and reflective of nursing practice (Cowan et al. 2005; Calman 2006).

In recognition of the move towards advanced models, frameworks in this area of practice have also begun to incorporate knowledge reflective of contemporary career frameworks. In 2021, the NWCSP developed a *Core Capabilities Framework in England* for all disciplines working in wound management; outlining three tiers of knowledge: *general, independent with critical analysis and complex/autonomous*, which align with traditional stage models such as Benner's novice to expert (1982) (NWCSP 2021). The document outlines twelve capabilities within five key domains of practice, which identify an overlap between skills, knowledge and behaviours and reflect the multidimensional model of knowledge that has been a key finding of this study. The identified skills for those practicing in wound management range from assessment and care planning to provision of personalised care; to broader skills including those supporting effective leadership, management and education. Notably, advanced clinical skills such as assessment and diagnosis have also been included. Similar trends have been evident in other areas of the UK. In Northern Ireland, the Department of Health (DoH) has published a career framework for specialist nursing roles (DoH 2018) which outlines generic core specialist competencies based on the four pillars of practice; in addition to those specific to individual areas of practice; one of which includes tissue viability.

Contemporary competency and capability frameworks offer effective means of supporting a systematic and strategic approach to the assessment, measurement and development of wound management knowledge and skills in line with current practice. In addition to the development and articulation of knowledge itself, they offer clarity and consistency to support the continued development of the specialist role in the changing health care context. However; barriers to their implementation at organisational level (i.e. variation, local processes and resources) may result in changes and resulting role clarity for the TVN, taking time to embed. As yet, no similar frameworks exist in Scotland where this study took place and the lack of definition for the specialist role persists.

Certification, accreditation and professional regulation of those practicing as specialists are further considerations for the wound management career trajectory in the UK (Masturzo et al. 2013). However, it is important to note that certification is not necessarily a reliable indicator of quality in educational preparation. For example, the independent status of professional regulation bodies in the North American model may present conflicts of interest between educational, regulatory and organisational aims.

Ethical knowing in wound management

Ethical knowing was found to be highly developed and reflective of wider nursing practice but not notably distinguishable or unique to the field of wound management. Exceptions were in relation to the influential role of industry, the specific ethical considerations

associated with this and with formulary adherence. This somewhat contradicts the findings associated with empiric knowing and its proposed unique nature within wound management practice. As an integral component of nursing knowledge that is firmly embedded within the ethos and shared values of the profession itself, ethical knowing in wound management was found to for the most part, reflect that of the nursing as a whole. It was therefore identified as being a relatively dominant pattern overall. However; this was not in the theoretical or academic sense; but rather, in the day to day practice of wound management; upholding the practice-based nature of wound management knowledge development. Although participants clearly demonstrated ethical practice, they did not necessarily contemplate it explicitly; nor consistently believe that this was formally or theoretically articulated and supported in the specific context of wound management. This is reflective of findings linked to the empiric pattern of knowing in which weak links between academic and theoretical components of knowledge and those that are practice-based were identified; echoing those of wider literature review (Dugdall & Watson 2009; Jorgenson et al. 2010; Cioffi 2012; McCluskey & McCarthy 2012; Ferriera et al. 2014; Gillespie et al. 2014; Kilpatrick et al. 2015; Logan 2015; Nickitas and Friedrichson 2015; Svavarsdottir et al. 2015; Kitson and Harvey 2016; Lockwood and Hopp 2016; Gonzaga de Faria et al. 2016; Gray et al. 2017). Although participants did not identify wound-specific codes and guidelines relating to ethical conduct, they demonstrated accountability and autonomy in relation to ethics overall. This is supported by literature confirming that nurses demonstrate satisfactory adherence to ethical codes in the wider sense and that ethical conduct in practice is well-articulated (Ghobadifar and Mosalanejad 2013; Marzieh et al. 2015).

Personal knowing in wound management

Personal knowing revealed wound management knowledge to be individualised, contextualised and developing predominantly in the practice setting. Personal knowing was found to be the most dominant of the *Patterns of Knowing* in the context of wound management; with specific overemphases on experiential knowledge that developed over time and learning from colleagues in practice. The personal pattern was the most frequently and widely reported to be the key source of wound management knowledge in all participants; but most evidently amongst those working in a community role.

It was found to be the only *pattern gone wild* in the context of this study (refer to **Figure 8** p. 106); which was interpreted to result to a certain degree, from limitations and under-representation of other patterns in the context of this study; to some extent, aesthetic knowing; but most notably, to empiric knowing, for which it was construed, as a partial gap-filler which compensated for the underdevelopment of more legitimate knowledge types. This

supports the global prevalence of ritualistic practice in wound management that was identified both in wider literature (Mizazaki et al. 2010; McCluskey and McCarthy 2012; Ferriera et al. 2014; Qaddum and Khawaldeh 2014; Gonzaga de Faria et al. 2016) and by a number of the participants in this study. Problems with accessing formal evidence and education and additional barriers such as time, resources and those which were role-specific, left both generalists and specialists to rely upon less formal types of knowledge; for example, an increased dependence upon certain groups and individuals with particular interests and passion in the field to propel the development of knowledge forward. Many participants revealed formal evidence as being routinely transferred indirectly rather than through written or formal sources; which may account for weak links between academic and clinical practice that have been highlighted (Dugdall and Watson 2009; Jorgenson et al. 2010; McCluskey and McCarthy 2012; Ferriera et al. 2014; Gillespie et al. 2014; Logan 2015; Gonzaga de Faria et al. 2016; Gray et al. 2017). Yet, rather than being a consequence of these shortfalls alone; the dominance of the personal pattern was also considered to reflect the practice-based nature of wound management knowledge. This is supported by a number of authors who argue that the concept of knowledge formation occurring in an academic setting does not clearly represent practice-based professions such as nursing (Richie and Lewis 2009; Cioffi 2012; Chinn and Kramer 2015; Pahor et al. 2015; Davis and Maisano 2016; Lockwood and Hopp 2016; Voldbjerg et al. 2016). It also supports findings here highlighting the complex and intuitive nature of clinical decision making in wound management (Thompson and Adderley 2014; Adderley and Thompson 2015; Gillespie et al. 2015; Logan 2015).

In summary, nursing has been historically recognised as a practice-based profession in which knowledge formation largely takes place out with the academic setting (Denny 2010; Green and Earle 2010; Ayala et al. 2014; Chinn and Kramer 2015); however, the particular shortfalls associated with the formal evidence base and empiric pattern of knowing in wound management represent an imbalance between patterns which compounds this; creating unique implications in this context. This correlates with findings of studies which reported on the frequent utilisation of knowledge that is personal and context specific in wound management (Mizazaki et al. 2010; McCluskey and McCarthy 2012; Qaddum and Khawaldeh 2014; Pieper et al. 2016). **Figure 9** (p. 117) outlines diagrammatic representation of the unique factors attributing to personal knowing as a *pattern gone wild* in the context of wound management

Figure 9: Personal Knowing in wound management

Intuition was also identified in this context as a sophisticated, implicit form of knowledge and decision making which occurred at a subconscious level and which improved with level of experience. This interpretation mirrors broader literature in which it has been accepted as a legitimate form of decision making in the context of the wider nursing profession (Benner and Tanner 1987; Shirley and Langan-Fox 1996; Smith 2006; Holm and Severinsson 2016; Ruzska, Szevereny and Varga 2020); as well as that from the preliminary literature review in which it was found to underpin much clinical decision making in wound management (Kennedy and Arundel 1998a; Kennedy and Arundel 1998b; Hallet et al 2014; Gillespie et al. 2015; Logan 2015; Price et al. 2017). However, it remains challenging to define and articulate and remains undervalued as a legitimate form of knowledge.

Variations in the prevalence of particular sub-themes and codes were also notable in the personal pattern of knowing. For example, although experiential types of knowledge were widely represented, the concept of bringing oneself to wound management practice was much less dominant than remaining aspects. This exemplified what might be regarded as a *pattern within a pattern* in which representation of all components of an individual pattern

were not equal. Personal knowing was also recognised to be a key constituent in the formation of the personal values which underpinned ethical forms of knowledge; as well as a requirement to demonstrate certain aspects of aesthetic knowing. This represents infiltration, dominance and extensive overlap of personal knowing in comparison to other patterns (i.e. empiric) which were more definitively marked.

Aesthetic knowing in wound management

Aesthetic knowing was found to be the least recognised and valued of patterns in the context of wound management knowledge formation by participants. Although with lesser prevalence than other forms, it was clearly demonstrated; yet not as explicitly or contentedly acknowledged as being a key component of knowledge. This reflects perceptions about its perceived legitimacy in wider literature (Shirley and Langan-Fox 1996; Holm and Severinsson 2016; Price et al. 2017). Despite participants largely expressing that they did not feel creative or regard themselves to be so, aesthetic knowing was articulated in three key areas: creativity in therapeutic approaches; creativity in the formation and maintenance of interpersonal and professional relationships; and creative ability associated with the consideration and integration of wider holistic factors in the context of wound management. It was also expressed in relation to intuition, which was perceived by participants to demonstrate higher thinking abilities involving an element of creativity and the effective utilisation of subconscious forms of thinking (Benner and Tanner 1987; Lamond and Thomspn 2000; Holm and Severinsson 2016; Ruzska et al. 2020). This supports findings from broader literature about relationships between knowledge and competence, with the latter being accepted to represent more practical, experiential-based capabilities (Allison 1995; McClusky and McCarthy 2012; Qaddumi and Khawaldeh 2014; Zarachi et al. 2014; Ousey et al. 2016b; Kielo et al. 2019a; Kielo et al. 2019b; Kielo et al. 2019c). Literature reveals links between clinician attitudes, knowledge and skills; which should also be of interest here since a number of participants expressed enjoyment and satisfaction through the articulation of aesthetic knowing; which might therefore evidence positive attitudes impacting on level of skill (Dugdall and Watson 2009; Etafa et al. 2018).

Chinn and Kramer (2015) do not conceptualise an opposing interpretation of a *pattern gone wild*; however in the context of this study, aesthetic knowing was found to be more recessive than all remaining patterns in relation to the lower value that was attributed to it by participants and its less frequent articulation. Again, this was identified as demonstration of the nursing profession's historic pattern of attempting to align to the scientific model of more dominant professions such as medicine and appear more scientific (Denny 2010; Green and Earle 2010; Ayala et al. 2014; Chinn and Kramer 2015); supporting claims from critical

theorists that subordinate professions strive to emulate more dominant ones (Friedson 1970; Johnson 2010; Giroux 2017). Participants in this study were therefore concluded to regard aesthetic knowing as a lesser form of knowledge that did not warrant comparable consideration to empiric types; which is reflective of the nursing profession's failure to recognise the complexity and value of their own knowledge base and striving to emulate the scientific status quo (Denny 2010; Green and Earle 2010; Ayala et al. 2014). This echoes the increasing preference for advanced models of nursing knowledge that are rooted in medical systems-models of assessment and hailed as superior to traditional nursing knowledge (Fawcett and DeSanto-Madeya 2013; Chinn and Kramer 2015). Developments such as these, which are not consistently driven by the profession itself, therefore support that nurses may not consider contextual, practice-based knowledge to hold equal importance since they have been historically taught to believe this to be the case (Denny 2010; Keeling and Templeman 2012; Ayala et al. 2014; Fantahun et al. 2014).

Emancipatory knowing in wound management

Emancipatory knowing was construed to be one of the more broadly expressed patterns which ran through a number of themes. Yet; as with the ethical pattern of knowing, the emancipatory pattern reflected more generic concepts associated with wider nursing knowledge rather than being unique to wound management practice. Again, the key exception was in relation to the role of industry as a wider influential factor in wound management, and recognition of a need to challenge bias which was determined in the supporting literature to be variable amongst nurses (Kessenich and Westbrook 1999; Monaghan et al. 2003; Ashmore et al. 2007; Crigger et al. 2009; Madden 2012). An understanding of the power held by industry in relation to empiric knowledge development (Radcliffe 2000; Madden 2012); as well as that exerted by external sources (i.e. management) in controlling access to industry, also characterised forms of emancipatory knowing; although this was found to vary amongst participants. Existing literature supports that although nurses' express an awareness of the potential for conflict of interest in others, they believe themselves to be above influence (Madden 2012). This supports study findings that emancipatory praxis, although demonstrated and articulated to a degree, was not fully realised since there was recognition but not consistent action to redress this type of power imbalance.

The ability to consider wider holistic factors prior to making decisions in wound management also typified a degree of emancipatory knowing; reflecting Chinn & Kramer's (2015) proposal that emancipatory knowing moves through and feeds all remaining patterns rather than being a distinct entity. This has been widely highlighted as a particular strength and

characteristic of the nursing profession (Carper 1978; Benner 1982; Garrett and Cutting 2014; Pahor et al. 2015; Williams and Burke 2015; Davis and Maisano 2016; Lockwood and Hopp 2016; Voldbjerg et al. 2016); however, findings here about its quality in the wound management context were mixed (Hjelm et al. 2003; Hallett et al. 2014; Gillespie et al. 2015).

The most recognisable expression of emancipatory knowing was in relation to the critical awareness of barriers to the development of wound management knowledge and participants' recognition that they were linked to wider organisational factors that were often out with their own control. This included a critical understanding of the role of social power in the context of wound management and its relevance in shaping outcomes. A seminal work by French & Ravens (1959) examined the concept of social power as an ability to control and influence others, often without their consent. Five distinct types of power were identified and their expressions within the context of this study have been presented in **Table 5** (p.121). A potential for overlap was noted in many of the sources of power' for example, while healthcare managers were recognised to hold legitimate and coercive power over a number of aspects shaping wound management knowledge due to hierarchical roles (i.e. interaction with industry, compliance with formulary); they could also hold referent or expert power at individual level. While participants recognised sources of social power and associated barriers in wound management presented; they most commonly reported it to be out with their individual control. Within the literature review, only two studies considered power in this context. Ashton and Price (2013), who identified the power of the medical profession and its exerting influence and control in clinical decision making; and Radcliffe (2000), who revealed an overall power imbalance between the opinions of doctors and nurses in the wider sense; both of which were perceived to affect level of engagement and influence by industry (Madden 2012). Although some participants recognised this imbalance to certain degree, good relationships with the medical profession in practice were identified overall. While it was beyond the scope of this study to determine the extent to which the invisible nature of power has impacted on participants' views and understanding of the nature of these relationships, it might be construed to reflect subordinate professions' recognised attempts to emulate more dominant ones; further evidence that emancipatory praxis was not fully realised here (Friedson 1970; Chinn and Kramer 2015).

Table 5: French & Ravens power types in the context of this study

Type of Power	Characteristics	Application in context of this study
Reward Power	Leader/supervisor has ability to reward (i.e., pay, promotion, privileges etc)	Healthcare Service Managers; Senior colleagues; Industry
Coercive Power	Based on fear & capacity to punish	Healthcare Service Managers; Senior colleagues; Medical Profession; Specialists
Legitimate Power	Based in hierarchical role & position	Healthcare Service Managers; Senior colleagues; Medical Profession; Specialists
Referent Power	Perceived attractiveness, popularity, respect, esteem	Healthcare Service Managers; Medical Profession; Specialists; Industry; Colleagues
Expert Power	Specialist knowledge & expertise	Healthcare Service Managers; Senior Colleagues; Medical Profession; Specialists; Industry

Although an understanding of theoretical conceptualisations of emancipatory knowing was not typical amongst participants at political or societal levels, a critical understanding of both the barriers themselves and participants' own sense of powerlessness in relation to them was widely demonstrated at personal and role-specific levels. For example, specialists clearly articulated a critical understanding of the low value placed on the TVN role and demonstrated an ability to link this to the methodological shortfalls in the evidence base. Whilst generalists did not recognise this in relation to wound management specifically, they did display a critical consideration of factors impacting upon to the DN role overall which impacted indirectly on wound management practice. Chinn and Kramer (2015) maintain that whilst critical thinking can lead to emancipatory knowing, the two should not be considered interchangeable; since emancipatory knowing must move beyond personal reflection. The concept of *praxis*, the integrated expression of emancipatory knowing in practice, suggests that *having* emancipatory knowledge is not enough since it must coexist with ongoing critical

action and reflection at wider social and political levels (Habermas 1972; Freire 1973; Chinn and Kramer 2015). Although participants in this study recognised barriers and in some cases, power imbalances, they did not explicitly and consistently link these to the broader subordination and control of nursing by more dominant and autonomous sources (Friedson 1973; Johnson 2010). Therefore, whilst it is clear that barriers and power relationships influencing wound management knowledge and practice were critically reflected upon in the context of individual roles; the extent to which action was taken to overcome them was not as clear and participants were considered to articulate a degree of praxis that was not consistently fully realised as result.

Relationships between patterns in the context of wound management

Chinn & Kramer (2015) propose that all patterns of knowing should be fully integrated and complimentary. Where this has not been achieved, patterns have the potential to become distorted with only partial and narrow interpretations replacing fully realised ones; as in the case of *patterns gone wild*. The relationships between all patterns in the context of wound management were found to be closely connected; however, the extent of overlap between them was not consistent; with some patterns more visibly demarkated and blended than others. For example, while the empiric pattern displayed clearly defined boundaries, emancipatory, personal and ethical patterns were less definitive; which accounts for them being more frequently represented in multiple themes. Empiric knowing was the only pattern that had core links to more than one theme which was construed as a representation of the extent to which it was valued by participants. Although it was the most widely and explicitly referred to by participants, this was frequently in relation to the identification of its limitations and shortfalls in the context of wound management; reinforcing its position as a highly considered but poorly developed pattern. The over-development of personal knowledge may therefore be additionally regarded as a particular strength that is reflective of complex, hidden nature of wound management knowledge; rather than being purely attributed to the relationships between different patterns of knowing. The view of personal, informal types of knowledge as being of questionable quality and value is also one that should be viewed critically. Nevertheless, Chinn and Kramer (2015) maintain that without the balance of patterns working together, the danger of knowledge being limited and one-sided persists. If it can therefore be confirmed that the status of personal knowing as a *pattern gone wild* in the context of wound management is linked to relationships with shortfalls in empiric knowing, the potential impact of this should continue to be highlighted and addressed.

Both emancipatory and ethical knowing were represented in ways that did not support any distinctions between wound management and the wider nursing profession in relation to

knowledge development. Participants demonstrated a high level of ethical decision making and consideration; but did not articulate these to be unique to the wound management context. Again, the exception was in relation to industry; the role of which represented the requirement for those delivering wound management to have a high level of ethical consideration and contemplation. This was a similar case for emancipatory knowing; for which participants demonstrated a recognition of wider barriers to outcomes and their implications at practice level; but did not articulate much that was uniquely wound management-focused. Outcomes for these two patterns should therefore be perceived as generalisable to other areas of clinical practice and to wider nursing in general rather than being unique in this context.

Participants in this study largely reported their own wound management knowledge to be well-integrated, a process that most commonly took place in the practice setting in the direct presence of a wound or for those with an educational component to their role, when actively delivering education. Integration of different types of knowledge was considered by participants to improve with practice and experience which reflects existing literature on nursing knowledge (Carper 1978; Benner 1982; Garrett and Cutting 2014; Chinn and Kramer 2015; Pahor et al. 2015; Williams and Burke 2015; Davis and Maisano 2016; Lockwood and Hopp 2016; Voldbjerg et al. 2016). In one of its most advanced forms, this was expressed as intuition; which was alleged to represent a complex, hidden form of decision making taking place at the subconscious level and which is supported by previous literature on the subject (Benner and Tanner 1987; Kennedy and Arundel 1998a; Kennedy and Arundel 1998b; Hallett et al. 2014; Gillespie et al. 2015; Logan 2015; Holm and Severinsson 2016; Price et al. 2017; Ruszka et al. 2020). This was explored in discussions around relationships between knowledge and competence, as well as in clinical decision making; which determined mixed results. Despite an identified imbalance in the representation of individual patterns in the context of wound management and mixed findings from the literature review (Hjelm et al. 2003; Hallett et al. 2014; Gillespie et al. 2015) the ability to integrate different knowledge types was evidenced by all participants. This can be perceived to reflect the more multidimensional definitions which capture *doing* types of knowledge such as clinical decision making, competence and capability.

Conceptualisation of Chinn and Kramer's (2015) patterns of knowing in the context of wound management

When considered within the concept of patterns of knowing, the findings of this study also support the unique nature of wound management knowledge which distinguishes it from Chinn and Kramer's (2015) conceptualisation of nursing knowledge in the wider sense. An

adapted version of Chinn and Kramer's (2015) conceptual model (refer to Chapter 1 **Figure 4**; p. 30) is therefore being proposed to more accurately represent the *Patterns of Knowing* in the context of wound management knowledge development in **Figure 10** (p.124).

Figure 10: Chinn and Kramer's (2015) adapted patterns of knowing in wound Management (reproduced with permission from Elsevier)

The dominance of each pattern has been reflected by its size in relation to the remaining patterns. Sizes replicate the explicit demonstration of each pattern in combination with the perceived value of each knowledge type based on the results of the study. A comparative overview of the consideration and demonstration of each pattern has been outlined in **Table 6** (p.125). Ethical and emancipatory knowing were perceived to have somewhat normalised and largely equivalent representation in relation to the original conceptualisation of Chinn and Kramer's model (2015) (refer to Chapter 1 **Figure 4**; p 30) reflecting wider nursing knowledge; whilst empiric and aesthetic knowing were visibly less developed. Empiric knowing, despite being highly valued, was limited in its demonstration; whilst aesthetic knowing, whilst being of less consideration, was clearly demonstrated in action. Aesthetic knowing was the only pattern for which the presence of industry was not articulated to have an influential role in the explicit sense; but specific components of aesthetic knowing could be perceived as being applicable wound management practice in the generic sense and therefore to industry indirectly (i.e. creativity in relationships with others). Personal knowing and more specifically, experiential forms of knowledge (i.e. learning from colleagues, learning in practice), were the most dominant and widely represented; giving personal knowing its status as a *pattern gone wild*. The taupe coloured border surrounding the model

represents the presence and influence of industry in knowledge formation which impacts either directly or indirectly upon all *Patterns of Knowing* in the context of wound management.

Table 6: Pattern Consideration and Demonstration

Pattern of Knowing	Consideration	Demonstration
Empiric	High	Limited
Personal	Moderate	High
Ethical	Moderate	High
Aesthetic	Limited	Moderate
Emancipatory	Moderate	Moderate

Since it should be contended that different clinical roles may also dictate dominance and weaknesses of individual patterns, distinctions between wound management specialists and wound management generalists will now be considered.

Distinctions between wound management specialists and wound management generalists

Outcomes relating to an ability to integrate patterns of knowing did not reveal notable differences between the two groups with participant responses revealing minimal distinction. Both specialists and generalists professed ability to integrate different knowledge types and correspondingly recognised the importance of intuition as a complex, advanced form of knowledge. Although wider literature review supports intuition as developing in accordance with level of experience (Benner and Tanner 1987; Holm and Severinsson 2016; Ruzska et al. 2020) there was no notable distinction between specialists and generalists in this respect in the context of this study which supports findings from a study by Price et al. (2017) which determined intuition to be a contributing factor to decision-making in less experienced nurses.

Ethical forms of knowledge also failed to demonstrate any marked variances between the two groups for most outcomes; with one exception: the role of industry in wound management. Whilst both groups identified ethical engagement with companies as a key consideration in relation to influence; there were notable differences in industry relationships, with specialists articulating both a more intricate understanding of their role in this capacity and enjoying more autonomy and power in their interaction. Several participants from both

groups remarked that specialists such as TVNs acted as gatekeepers to industry and were permitted to engage more freely; a freedom which afforded a degree of power in relation to accessing knowledge. This suggests that despite findings in wider literature review in which there was low strategic priority for the TVN role in relation to research and education (Stephen-Haynes and Greenwood 2011; Ousey et al. 2013b; Ousey et al. 2015); they were considered to hold considerable power and influence in relation to knowledge development where it most occurred: at practice level (Madden 2012).

On the whole, generalists more explicitly demonstrated an ability to consider and integrate wider holistic factors in wound management; however; this ability was attributed to DN/CSN expertise rather than to either wound management specifically or to generalist practice in the wider sense. It may reflect the unique knowing and skill set of the DN (Kennedy 2004; Longstaff 2013; Heaslip 2014; Bain 2015). Specialists with experience working in a community setting articulated this ability to a comparable degree as generalists, but those working in an acute role often focused on the wound in the *here and now*. This supports the advanced consideration and integration of wider holistic factors as being inherent to the skill set of the community practitioner rather being specific to either specialist or generalist wound management practice and suggests that certain clinical roles may also dictate strengths and weaknesses of different patterns. For example, the provision of care in a patient's home rather than in an institutionalised setting may facilitate the development of closer relationships leading to different power dynamics between service users and service providers; findings that have been supported by existing literature (Kennedy 2004; Bain 2015). Given that the majority of wounds in the UK are managed in the community setting (Vowden and Vowden 2009; Moore 2010; Logan 2015), this should be recognised as a key strength of wound management knowledge.

Specialists were more aware and appraising of specific associated shortfalls in the empiric evidence base; demonstrating a greater value placed on the importance of research evidence a more developed knowledge in this capacity. This was also supported in some literature reviewed (Madden 2012; Ashton and Price 2013). Generalists did not appraise the quality of the formal evidence base and did not remark on its efficacy in relation to methodological quality of research. The exception was in relation to the role of industry; for which all participants noted the potential impact on both evidence and education. Since all generalist participants were enrolled in a masters level programme to prepare them to become DNs at the time of recruitment and had reached similar levels of academic education frameworks as those from specialist backgrounds, it is safe to assume that their comprehension of the research process and formal evidence were of comparable ability. This may be due to the broader range of knowledge and practice required for DN/CSNs in

their roles as generalists; compared to specialist practice which is more confined. It would naturally follow that specialists would appraise the evidence base in their selected clinical speciality in greater depth and that the failure of generalists to do so in the context of wound management should not be conceived as a failure to understand and engage with research and evidence based practice in the wider sense. This is supported by further findings from the study demonstrating that despite negligible differences in levels of educational preparation between the two groups, specialists felt educationally prepared to deliver wound management in relation to their own knowledge base, whilst generalists largely expressed that they did not; citing time and shortfalls in wound management education as barriers. The length and specificity of experience in wound management practice should also be a consideration here; since most specialists had more experiential practice specific to wound management than generalists. This links back to constructs of competence, capability and clinical decision making, which were found in the literature to be of somewhat better quality in specialists in certain activities (Lamond and Farnell 1998; Edwards et al. 2005; Ashton and Price 2013; Thompson and Adderley 2014; Adderley and Thompson 2015). The finding that practice-based knowledge dominates wound management was therefore reinforced and should be acknowledged accordingly. A final notable difference pertaining to the empiric evidence base was that a number of specialists highlighted the need for more innovation in wound management (i.e. in the delivery of education and product development) and generalists did not consider this at all. However existing literature questions the quality and nature of innovation in this context, which specialists did not question or acknowledge (Madden 2012).

Although there were negligible differences in the perceived barriers to wound management knowledge development, one example attributed to generalists was the perception of time as a barrier. Very few specialists identified this and it was explicitly noted by some that time spent with individual patients was a luxury afforded to them. Generalists in contrast, identified the role of the DN/CSN itself to be a barrier and while this was commonly linked to time, it was also identified in relation to factors such as variety of role, competing demands, restricted access to education, provision of care in patients' homes and having less access to dressing supplies. These findings were also acknowledged in broader literature which revealed increasing professional challenges facing contemporary DN practice (Heaslip 2014; Dickson et al. 2016; King's Fund 2016; RCN 2016; McComiskey 2017). Specialists also noted role-specific barriers which included: low value of tissue viability as a specialty; lack of career progression and recognition and shortfalls associated with the formal evidence base; which were also identified in wider literature (Stephen-Haynes and Greenwood 2011; Maylor 2012; Ousey et al. 2013b; Ousey et al 2015).

A concluding point to note about distinctions between the two participant groups was in relation to the number of codes which were identified in each group during data analysis. An overall total of 133 initial codes were associated with specialist participants; and the number for generalists was considerably less at 100. Although prevalence is not routinely considered in qualitative studies (Pyett 2003), the relevance here should not be dismissed and may be regarded as an indicator of richness of data, depth of content and a more extensive interest in the subject matter from those practicing in specialist roles.

The wider context

Outcomes of this study determined novel findings pertaining to the origins and nature of wound management knowledge from the perspectives of wound management generalists and specialists. These can be summarised into three broad categories: those that were generic and reflective of the knowledge of the wider nursing profession; those that were generic to the wider nursing profession but been significantly affected by the current policy and practice context; and those that were considered specific and comparatively unique to wound management knowledge development.

Study outcomes generic to nursing

The ability to consider and integrate wider holistic factors was found to be an important component of wound management knowledge in all participants; however rather than being linked to specialist or generalist practice, the distinguishing factor that affected its development was working in a community role. This capacity, which has been commonly recognised to reflect the nature of knowledge in wider nursing profession and more specifically district nursing (Carper 1978; Benner 1982; Kennedy 2004; Longstaff 2013; Garrett and Cutting 2014; Heaslip 2014; Voldbjerg et al. 2014; Bain 2015; Chinn and Kramer 2015; Pahor et al. 2015; Williams and Burke 2015; Davis and Maisano 2016; Lockwood and Hopp 2016); was therefore not considered to be unique to the context of wound management. Aesthetic knowing, whilst clearly demonstrated, was not as explicitly recognised or valued by participants as other patterns; which mirrors the wider nursing profession's historic tendency to place less value on informal knowledge types (Cooke and Philbin 2008; Denny 2010; Green and Earle 2010; Ayala et al. 2014). This was echoed in Chinn and Kramer's (2015) proposal that empiric knowing has traditionally been a *pattern gone wild* in nursing. To exemplify this, Chinn and Kramer (2015) point to the origins of *evidence-based practice* (EBP) which was initially adopted from the medical profession as *evidence-based medicine* (EBM) but construed to leave gap in nursing due to its practice-based roots and nature. Chinn and Kramer (2015) therefore offer *practice-based evidence* (PBE) as a suitable alternative; since it acknowledges the importance of the practice context

in knowledge formation and places value on the knowledge that is generated there. PBE should therefore be considered more representative of the types of knowledge that have been identified as shaping wound management: bottom up, practice-based forms of evidence that are multidimensional and linked to experience.

Study outcomes generic to nursing but significantly shaped by the context of wound management

The suggestion that knowledge is individualised and contextualised and develops predominantly in the practice setting has been historically recognised to reflect nursing knowledge in the broader sense (Carper 1978; Benner 1982; Benner and Wrubel 1984; Pahor et al. 2015; Voldbjerg et al. 2016). Yet; the specific limitations in the empiric evidence base and education supporting wound management which have been highlighted in this study can be contended to significantly affect knowledge development in this area of practice. This also applies to the integration of patterns of knowing in wound management reflecting definitions of capability (Cowan et al. 2005; Calman 2006); and for intuition as an advanced form of decision making taking place at subconscious level (Shirley and Langan-Fox 1996; Price et al. 2017). Although these are also traditionally recognised as hallmarks of practice-based professions and therefore nursing in the generic sense, shortfalls in the formal evidence base should be considered to impact and lead to a greater dependency upon both this integration and a dependence upon less formal types of knowledge. This supports the study's findings that the empiric pattern of knowing is highly valued, but considerably underdeveloped. Although the quality and nature of the evidence base supporting nursing knowledge has been historically questioned (Aktar-Danesh et al. 2013; Ayala et al. 2014; Chinn and Kramer 2015; Kilpatrick et al. 2015; Pahor et al. 2015; Shearer 2015), it was found to impact upon wound management to such an extent, that it contributed to the personal pattern of knowing's position as a *pattern gone wild*; a finding that does not support Chinn and Kramer's (2015) previous conclusions that the empiric pattern has traditionally dominated nursing knowledge.

Ethical knowledge was found to be highly developed and reflective of wider nursing practice but not unique to wound management, except in relation to the dominant role of industry and the resulting ethical considerations specific to this. This was also true of the barriers to the development of wound management knowledge which were found to be linked to wider organisational factors out with individual clinician control. Whilst many of the identified barriers could also be regarded as generic to wider nursing practice, the multiple, contradictory barriers that participants attributed to industry (i.e. their impact on the production of evidence and associated issues of quality and bias; prevention from industry

engagement etc.) were important distinguishing factors specific to the wound management context.

Study outcomes specific to wound management

The main outcome of this study found to be unique and clearly attributable to the context of wound management knowledge was the dominant presence of industry. This was found to infiltrate through a number of themes and patterns of knowing to some degree but most predominantly included its influential role in shaping the formal evidence base through contribution to research evidence, consensus documents and the development and delivery of clinical education packages. Industry was also regarded as a key constituent in ethical knowing; in terms of potential issues of quality and ethical conflicts of interest relating to the production of evidence and interaction with clinicians during delivery of education. It was therefore perceived to hold a degree of power over the information itself and the education of the clinicians to whom it was marketed; findings that were supported in the literature (Ashmore et al. 2007; Dumville et al. 2009; Madden 2012). Individual wound management specialists were also identified as having a degree of power by participants in this capacity due to their close working relationships with companies, their involvement in the co-production of educational packages and materials including original research studies and consensus documents; and their role in the development and participation at educational conferences (Radcliffe 2000; Health Committee 2005; Madden 2012). Potential for conflict of interest and ethical concerns were raised here since specialists were proposed to receive monetary payment in certain cases; suggesting that participants had an understanding of potential influence. However; although literature supports that clinicians believe themselves to above influence; a largely uncritical attitude to industry engagement prevailed (Monaghan et al. 2003; Ashmore et al. 2007; Crigger et al. 2009; Madden 2012; one that was echoed in certain respects by participants here (i.e. failure to question or consider the quality of innovation). Nevertheless, despite identified ethical and quality concerns, participants valued the presence of industry and the perceived importance of their role in the contribution to knowledge and education. As such, restrictions from health board managers on industry engagement were alleged to restrict knowledge development in the context of wound management.

Although the pharmaceutical industry has been documented as having considerable power and influence in a number of areas of clinical practice within healthcare (Murray 1974; Guay 1988; Busfield 2006), these have been traditionally more confined to interaction with medically-led specialites; for example through marketing medicines and drugs or surgical supplies. Since medical professions are traditionally recognised to have greater clinical and

professional power than nursing (Aktar-Danesh et al. 2013; Ayala et al. 2014; Chinn and Kramer 2015; Pahor et al. 2015; Shearer 2015) the consequences of industry engagement may not have comparable implications. This finding was supported by Radcliffe (2000) who determined the power imbalances in decision-making between the two professions. As a historically nurse-led specialty (Cowman et al. 2011; Guest et al. 2015; Harding et al. 2015; Ousey et al. 2015; Vowden and Vowden 2016) with a growing clinical burden comprising a large amount of nursing time and resource (Guest et al. 2015; Guest et al. 2016; NHS England 2016; NHS 2016; Guest et al. 2017; NWCSP 2018; Atkin et al. 2019) the clinical speciality of wound management is therefore in a distinctive position in relation to its influence by industry. Since the quality and uniqueness of the evidence base underpinning nursing and associated power within the profession have been questioned (Aktar-Danesh et al. 2013; Ayala et al. 2014; Chinn and Kramer 2015; Pahor et al. 2015; Shearer 2015), industry should be highlighted as having unique power and influence in the development of wound management knowledge. Out of all the themes and sub-themes generated in this study, data relating to the influence of industry in wound management was found to be the most contradictory and diverse, with industry perceived as both a limitation and a unique asset in wound management knowledge formation by participants. **Figure 11** (p. 132) provides an illustrative overview of the unique role of industry in shaping wound management knowledge.

Despite its perceived important and unique role of industry in wound management knowledge formation, there was recognition from participants that guidance around ethical conduct and relationships between NHS and representatives from industry remained inconsistent and ambiguous. Whilst codes of conduct directing engagement from both bodies exist, information doesn't consistently or accurately filter down to practice level and clinicians, particularly those in generalist practice, continue to be left without clear guidance. Misinterpretation about roles and rules of engagement amongst clinicians and those in positions to impose restrictions (i.e senior NHS managers) around industry roles and engagement continue as a result. For example, although companies with products on national contract and formularies have contractual obligations to provide product education, several participants highlighted that they are routinely forbidden from doing so. The implications therefore vary significantly within and across health board regions in addition to the national differences that exist; for example those between Scotland and England. Aesthetic knowing was the only pattern for which the presence of industry was not explicitly articulated or cited by participants as having an influential role. However; the aesthetic expressions that were identified; for example use of creativity in relationships and creativity in dressing technique can be perceived to apply to industry in an indirect sense.

Figure 11: Industry in wound management

Chapter 7 Conclusions and recommendations for research and practice

The aim of this study was to gain a detailed and rich understanding of the origins and nature of knowledge in specialist and generalist nurses with a key role in the delivery of clinical or educational wound management. The research questions were:

- What are the patterns of knowing for specialist and generalist nurses with key roles in the delivery of clinical and/or educational wound management and how has this been affected by the current wound management context?
- Do any particular pattern(s) dominate and if so, what factors have contributed to this?
- What comparisons can be made between specialist and generalist nurses?
- What are implications of these findings for wound management practice and education?

Seven themes were constructed following a review of the literature and Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA) of the interview data: *The bigger, picture; the smaller picture; It all comes together at the bedside; Show me the evidence; Industry: a political football; Do good not harm; The power isn't ours; and I'm not that creative...but*. The results support that although the patterns of knowing in wound management are reflective of wider nursing practice in a number of areas, there are components which are significantly influenced by the specific context of wound management and those in which knowledge development in this area is largely unique.

Empiric knowing was found to be highly valued by all participants but largely underdeveloped, particularly in relation to the quality and availability of research evidence and structured education. Industry was also identified as having a particularly influential role on the development of the evidence base and therefore in shaping the empiric pattern of knowing; which impacted upon its perceived quality and legitimacy. It was the most frequently referred-to patterns by participants; but the least dominant in shaping knowledge in this context. This was in contrast to previous findings that empiric knowing has historically dominated nursing and may be perceived to represent value of knowledge rather than articulation.

Personal knowing revealed wound management knowledge to be individualised, contextualised and developing predominantly in the practice setting. It was found to be the most dominant of the *Patterns of Knowing* in the context of wound management; with

specific overemphases on experiential knowledge that developed over time and learning from colleagues in practice. The personal pattern was the most frequently and widely reported to be the key source of wound management knowledge in all participants; but most evidently amongst those working in a community role. It was found to be the only *pattern gone wild* in the context of this study

Ethical knowing was found to be highly developed and reflective of wider nursing practice but not notably distinguishable or unique to the field of wound management. Exceptions were in relation an understanding of the influential role of industry and associated ethical considerations. As an integral component of nursing knowledge that is firmly embedded within the ethos and shared values of the profession itself, it was found to reflect that of the nursing as a whole and a relatively dominant pattern overall. This was not in the theoretical or academic sense; but rather, in the day to day practice of wound management.

Aesthetic knowing was found to be the least recognised and valued of patterns in the context of wound management knowledge formation; yet, not the least developed. Although clearly demonstrated by participants, it was not as explicitly or contentedly recognised as a key component of knowledge. Despite participants largely expressing that they did not feel creative or regard themselves to be so, aesthetic knowing was articulated in three key areas: therapeutic approaches; the formation and maintenance of interpersonal and professional relationships; and with the consideration and integration of wider holistic factors in the context of wound management. It was also articulated in intuition.

Emancipatory knowing was one of the more broadly expressed patterns which ran through a number of themes. It reflected generic concepts associated with the wider nursing profession rather than being unique to wound management practice. An understanding of the perceived power held by industry in relation to empiric knowledge development, as well as the power exerted by external sources in controlling access to the knowledge provided by industry and an ability to consider wider holistic factors prior to making decisions also characterised forms of emancipatory knowing. The most recognisable expression of emancipatory knowing was in relation to the critical awareness of barriers to the development of wound management knowledge and participants' recognition that they were linked to wider organisational factors that were often out with their own control. This included a critical understanding of the role of social power in the context of wound management and it's relevance in shaping outcomes. However since action to overcome barriers was not consistently demonstrated, full praxis was not consistently achieved.

The relationships between all patterns in the context of wound management were found to be closely connected and integrated; however, the extent of overlap between them was not consistent; with some patterns more visibly demarkated and blended than others.

Outcomes relating to an ability to integrate patterns of knowing did not reveal notable differences between specialists and generalists. Whilst both groups clearly identified ethical engagement with companies as a presenting potential conflict of interest; there were notable differences in the relationships with industry, with specialists articulating both a more intricate understanding of their role in this capacity and enjoying more autonomy and power in industry relationships.

On the whole, generalists more explicitly demonstrated an ability to consider and integrate wider holistic factors in wound management; however, this was attributed to DN/CSN expertise rather than to wound management specifically or to generalist practice in the wider sense. Specialists with experience working in a community setting articulated this ability to a comparable degree as generalists, but those working in an acute role often demonstrated a tendency to focus on the wound in the *here and now*.

Specialists were more appraising of specific shortfalls associated in the formal evidence base, placed more value on the nature of research evidence supporting wound management and had a more developed knowledge in this capacity. A final notable difference was that whilst a number of specialists highlighted the need for more innovation in wound management (i.e. in the delivery of education and product development), generalists did not consider this.

Specialists felt educationally prepared to deliver wound management, whilst generalists did not; citing the lack of time and shortfalls in wound management education as key barriers. This was despite negligible educational differences between the two groups

There were few differences in the perceived barriers to wound management knowledge formation between specialists and generalists; however generalists perceived time as a barrier whilst specialists did not. Specific barriers for generalists were: the role of the DN/CSN, including: variety and competing demands, restricted access to education and supplies and provision of care in patients' homes. Specialists role-specific barriers included: the low placed on tissue viability as a specialty; lack of recognition and career progression and shortfalls associated with the formal evidence base. The data produced by specialists was notably richer and more developed; supporting a more developed and extensive interest and depth of knowledge in wound management.

Implications of findings on wound management practice and education

The findings of this study present implications for wound management practice and education; most notably in relation to the shortfalls and challenges associated with the formal evidence base and insufficient education for those delivering wound management. Wound management continues to reflect traditional multidimensional models of nursing knowledge which are shaped by practice and experiential learning. These continue to be underpinned by holism; for which interpersonal interactions remain core to assessment and to the creation of overall health and wholeness. In Scotland, this has left it at odds with contemporary frameworks for nursing careers and education, which increasingly focus upon medical systems models (CNOD 2017a). Tissue viability as a speciality has not transitioned to medical systems models and has therefore not been considered to be as technical and elite as other areas of practice (i.e., ANP roles); however contemporary competency and capability frameworks in some areas of the UK, have begun to address this gap and incorporate both traditional and advanced models.

Positive implications for practice have also been highlighted. These include an ability for utilisation and integration of a range of knowledge types; highly developed aptitudes for ethical knowledge and conduct; and most notably, the revelation of complex, sophisticated personal knowledge types which exemplify the adaptability and strengths of specialists and generalists practicing in a context that is inherent with challenges and shortfalls. This includes the prevalence of those with particular passion and dedication going above and beyond to propel wound management forward; often without strategic direction and remuneration. Views of medical and scientific models of knowledge being superior to holism and views of caring, emotional labour and practice-based knowledge as second rate should therefore be challenged; since these arguments are driven by power and elitism; rather than being true indicators of quality. As a profession, nursing should continue to recognise its own subordination and control in this respect. Rather than adopting characteristics of the professions it strives to emulate, nurses should take the lead in defining and articulating their own unique knowledge.

The failure of education curriculums to include sufficiently developed and standardised wound management competencies has been highlighted here; bringing attention to the need for key indicators, alignment to contemporary competency frameworks reflective of theoretical and wider capabilities, skills and behaviours and consideration of professional regulation. Negative implications include the prevalence of localised, inconsistent practice which is marked by regional variation and challenges; ritualistic practice at individual level and a lack of historic strategic development of wound management as a speciality.

In addition to implications arising from wider shortfalls in evidence and education, are those inherent to the TVN and DN roles; both of which were identified by study participants. For specialists, this has resulted in a feeling of low strategic priority and lack of standardisation of TVN role. Challenges inherent to the DN role have also compounded generalists' ability to carry out wound management to a sufficient capacity. In summary, wound management should be regarded as having had to adapt in response to both shortfalls in the empiric evidence base and strategic direction in relation to professional roles which have had implications at practice level.

The influence of industry on practice and education can be viewed to some degree, as filling an opportunistic gap which has led to its dominant role in shaping the current evidence base underpinning wound management. Although participants established the importance of maintaining and developing industry partnerships, inconsistent protocols and variations in guidance around this means that challenges continue to present. The dominant influence of industry should therefore be recognised as having both positive and negative implications for the quality of evidence base.

Consideration of potential study limitations

Since the onset of this study in 2016, there have been noteworthy developments in the field of wound management. These have included the progress of national campaigns such as *Legs Matter* and the development of the *National Wound Care Strategy* which have gained considerable momentum and continued to raise the profile of wounds and tissue viability as a specialty. Although developments are ongoing and there is much work to be done, a number of the issues identified in the background chapter and literature review have begun to be addressed with the introduction of more strategic, systematic processes directed at the prevention and treatment of hard to heal wounds. As such, some of the identified problems may no longer present with as much precedence, which might be considered to limit some aspects of the strength of the background narrative. For example, the roles of TVNs and other specialist nurses are being reviewed and placed more strategically in national career frameworks and trajectories which has led to clearer alignment with more advanced career roles such as the ANP. In addition, the introduction of the NMC 's *Future Nurse: Standards of Proficiency for Registered Nurses* (2018) has introduced specific, albeit superficial, indicators of competence in wound management. Finally, despite recognised challenges associated with the DN role annual reports on DN education from the Queen's Nursing Institute (QNI) and Queen's Nursing Institute Scotland (QNIS) (QNIS 2020) revealed a 4% increase in numbers of students undertaking the SPQDN qualification in the UK from the previous year.

Although generalisability was not a particular aim of this study, it took place and recruited only participants from Scotland and was therefore representative of a localised context (i.e., NWCSP is an English collaborative which does not have comparable and consistent alternatives across all areas of the UK). Although many of the findings are transferable to the national and global context; others may therefore present as more localised; for example, wound management education which may vary in accordance with global pre-registration nursing curriculums. However; since the preliminary literature review identified comparable shortfalls in a number of international studies, it is reasonable to assume shortfalls in wound management education pervade globally and their impact upon knowledge development transcends the Scottish context. A second consideration is the impact of the role of industry in shaping wound management knowledge, particularly in relation to ethical inferences and perceived conflicts of interest surrounding industry engagement. Since the NHS in the UK is a public body, this may have particular national implications which are less relevant in countries with private health care systems such the United States (US). Within the UK, there are additional regional variations between Scotland, Northern Ireland, Wales and England and it cannot be assumed that the matter of industry, although significant and problematic in Scotland, will have the same degree of consequence in other areas nationally. For example, since 2013, localised clinical commissioning groups (CCGs) in England have commissioned many healthcare services to the private sector, an approach which differs from the publicly funded NHS in Scotland. However, regardless of differences in models of health care delivery, the influential role of industry should be of relevance in any context where it plays a substantial role in the co-production, dissemination and delivery of wound management research and education.

Identified issues relating to particular clinical roles such as the TVN and DN may also vary to some extent with region and significantly between countries. This was found to be the case for the US and Canada, in which roles were found to vary (i.e., in the US, the specialist role often incorporates wider aspects of practice such continence and ostomy care). Unlike the UK setting, specific training and accreditation is also obligatory for all clinicians practicing as wound management specialists in North America. TVNs and DNs working within inner city environments may have different clinical experiences due to demographic variations; as well as different opportunities for education and CPD from clinicians working in remote and rural areas which may theoretically impact upon knowledge development. Although recruits for this study ranged across four health board areas, these were in populated regions and any potentially unique challenges for those working rurally were not represented. However, recent advances in higher education and the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic have

contributed to the development of more innovative approaches and the resulting move towards curriculums that are increasingly delivered online may reduce variation.

Although RTA aligned to the ontological and epistemological approach of the study; it has been criticised for its subjectivity and lack of coherence which should be considered in relation to the transferability of findings of the study (Holloway and Todres 2003; Nowell et al. al. 2017). However, RTA is not concerned with generalisability and instead, seeks to explore and co-create themes that suitably represent contextual forms of knowledge as expressions of unique being. It was therefore a sound methodological fit for the aims of this study.

It is also important to reflect upon the efficacy of the conceptual models of knowledge selected for the study; Chinn and Kramer's *Patterns of Knowing* (2015); and Carper's (1978) model on which is has been based. Critique of the models arise from two main camps: those appraising them from the positivist perspective and those evaluating their failure to sufficiently explore the relationships and interactions between patterns. Garrett and Cutting (2014) highlighted that pattern such as aesthetic and personal knowing were subjective and difficult to define since they vary with individual and context; whilst Porter (2010) argued that formal knowledge associated with original research and evidence should be embedded in all patterns rather than being identified as a type in itself. As the first theoretical framework to explore knowledge within the confines of nursing, Garrett and Cutting (2014) question the currency of Carper's (1978) model; pointing out that it should be examined within the social and political context in which it originated; namely a time in which nursing was attempting to establish itself as a profession distinct from medicine. As such, the recognition of multiple perspectives in knowledge construction was proposed to prevail over an empiric concept of universal objective truth; with an emphasis upon practical forms of knowledge over scientific and empiric knowledge types. From this perspective, it might be questioned whether *Patterns of Knowing* is out dated as a conceptual framework of knowledge in contemporary nursing practice. Yet, other authors have defended Carper's (1978) model; arguing that it continues to identify the importance of empirical knowledge; but rather than regarding it as a distinct entity reflecting Aristotle's *episteme*, it focuses upon its practical application and links to outcomes (Pahor et al. 2015).. As previously identified in the findings of this study, the conceptualisation of knowledge as forming a range of contextual components and types may therefore be proposed to align appropriately with nursing as a profession rooted in practice. *Patterns of Knowing* has therefore been an appropriate framework in the development of the themes here.

With the continued academisation of nursing, has come a growing emphasis upon evidence-based practice (EBP) and practice-based evidence (PBE) which reflect Barnett's (1997) views of criticality and recognise three main components of knowledge: empirical evidence, experiential knowledge and patient preference (Voldbjerg et al. 2016). Chinn & Kramer (2015) propose that the traditional development of knowledge in academic settings is a reflection of the historical dominance of positivism and empiric forms of knowledge, a view that is supported by critical theorists such as Giroux (2017). Whilst the importance of less formal and experiential knowledge types has been long recognised as carrying as much weight as more formal types by nursing theorists (Carper 1978; Benner 1982; Benner and Wrubel 1984; Kennedy 2004; Cioffi 2012; Bain 2015; Lockwood and Hopp 2015; Pahor et al. 2015; Voldbjerg et al. 2016); positivist critics from out with the profession have continued to de-value and question its integrity (Denny 2010; Johnson 2010; Ayala et al 2014). Positivist critique of Chinn and Kramer's (2015) and Carper's (1978) models should as such, continue to be challenged.

Finally, Kennedy (2004) adds that Carper's model fails to sufficiently explore the relationships between patterns, which may not capture the mix of *how* and *that* intrinsic to DN knowledge; however, within the context of this study, Chinn and Kramer's adapted version (2015) was found to sufficiently capture the relationships and perceived overlap between patterns; which was articulated in all themes here, most notably theme 2: *It all comes together at the bedside*. Since it has been recognised that aspects of theoretical knowledge in nursing are not always reflective of that which occurs in practice and there is considerably more to knowledge than can be expressed in findings (Cioffi 2012; Chinn and Kramer 2015; Kilpatrick et al. 2015; Nickitas and Friedrickson 2015; Svavarsdottir et al. 2015; Kitson and Harvey 2016; Lockwood and Hopp 2016) only a multidimensional model could have fully captured the outcomes and addressed the aims of this study.

Although it is assumed the semi structured interview schedule used in this study demonstrated validity as a data collection tool; given that the findings have revealed the presence of industry as a unique contributing factor to wound management knowledge development, it has been questioned with hindsight whether the inclusion of representatives from industry as an additional participant group would have added a further dimension and contributed to answering the research questions.

Recommendations for Research and Practice

Five recommendations for research, policy and practice have been identified from the findings of this study as means to ensure the ongoing development of wound management knowledge.

Recommendation One: Research

There should be strategic priority at health board and higher educational institution levels for the development of the formal evidence base and research agenda supporting wound management. This should focus upon a commitment to the facilitation of independent studies of high methodological quality; including those placed high on the traditional hierarchy of evidence and equally those of a qualitative nature which have been highlighted in this study as being particularly applicable in the context of nursing practice.

Recommendation Two: Education

There should be a strategic priority at professional regulatory body, health board and higher educational institutional levels for more structured, innovative evidence-based education focusing on wound management as a core component of nursing practice. This should include sufficient and targeted content and competencies in the pre-registration nursing curriculum; structured, accessible CPD aligned to key quality indicators, competency and capability frameworks and professional strategy. Since wound management comprises a key component of DN workload, Specialist Practitioner District Nurse (SPQDN) programmes should have sufficient and standardised levels of competence in this area of practice using set educational hours on the SPQDN curriculum.

Recommendation Three: Industry

There should be strategic priority at health board and private industry levels to secure more systematic and standardised processes for relationships and partnerships with industry; including clearer guidance and governance supporting engagement with clinicians. The accurate and consistent interpretation and application of published codes of conduct relating to ethical practice between the parties should be facilitated by management at various levels of hierarchal organisation. Explicit and detailed outlines of roles and responsibilities should maximise potential for partnership working between the two sectors.

Since this study has highlighted that knowledge development in wound management largely occurs in the practice setting, a recommended method of fulfilling this is through the establishment of NHS-employed industry link role facilitators with responsibilities for maximising ethical partnerships and governance in education and research between the two sectors.

Recommendation 4: Knowledge

There should be increasing formal recognition and articulation of experiential, personal and contextual knowledge types as legitimate alternatives to objective, scientific and technical

knowledge in wound management by professional regulatory bodies, policy makers, healthcare service delivery managers and higher educational institutions. This should be facilitated through an ongoing development of evidence, research and policy which align clearly to competency and capability frameworks; and the establishment of stronger theory-practice links within academic and clinical settings and more consistent models for clinical educator roles between the NHS and higher education institutions.

Recommendation 5: TVN Roles

There should be a strategic commitment to more structured career trajectories, pathways and key indicators for specialist roles in wound management which align to contemporary career frameworks and advancing roles whilst continuing to support traditional models of nursing knowledge across all areas of the UK. This should include more standardised educational pre-requisites to fulfil roles nationally and mandatory professional regulation of wound management specialists such as the TVN on professional regulatory bodies.

Conclusion

The knowledge that specialist and generalist nurses apply in wound management practice is multidimensional and highly integrated. It is individualised, contextualised and develops mainly through experience in the practice setting; most commonly at the bedside in the direct presence of a wound. This is in contrast to previous claims that empiric knowing has dominated nursing, revealing nurses' overall knowledge in the context of wound management to have components that are distinct from nursing knowledge in the wider sense.

The consideration and integration of wider holistic factors plays a significant role in the development of wound management knowledge, most notably for those working in a community setting. Although the *Patterns of Knowing* in wound management are well integrated, they are not equally represented and the types of knowledge that nurses demonstrate is not consistently aligned with those they hold in high value or vice-versa.

Industry plays an influential role in shaping wound management knowledge development and impacts upon all *Patterns of Knowing* directly or indirectly. This is most notably, the empiric pattern through its influential role in shaping the formal evidence base and education in wound management. Although this presents considerations and concerns in relation to quality and ethical conduct, its role is highly valued in relation to education and wound management knowledge development. Industry is therefore an influential key factor contributing to its uniqueness.

What this study adds

The main scholarly feature of this study is that it creates a new understanding of an existing issue, the nature of knowledge in specialist and generalist nurses delivering wound management. Although previous studies have identified a number of generic and specific gaps in nurses' knowledge in wound management, the majority have adopted a post-positivist approach. This study is the first to examine the nature and quality of this knowledge and the link between existing shortfalls in wound management education and evidence and knowledge development using a qualitative theoretical framework.

This study is the first to make in-depth qualitative comparisons between the nature of knowledge of specialists and generalist nurses. While previous studies have included both specialist and generalist nurses working in wound management as participants, this study is the first to move beyond the identification and comparison of specific shortfalls and aspects of knowledge (i.e., venous leg ulcers, wound assessment) and provide a comprehensive exploration of the quality and nature of this knowledge.

The study is the first to provide a comprehensive exploration of the relationships between profession-specific challenges and the nature of knowledge development in this context. While a number of studies have previously explored community nurses' knowledge in various aspects of wound management, this has also primarily been in relation to specific identified knowledge shortfalls and deficits. This study moves beyond a focus on specified gaps and presents detailed findings on the nature of these links.

This study is the first to examine knowledge in wound management within a formal theoretical framework of knowledge (i.e., *Patterns of Knowing*).

Although the impact of industry on evidence formation and practice has been previously discussed, this study is the first to sufficiently and comprehensively explore its impact on the qualitative nature of wound management knowledge development from an insiders' view.

This new knowledge could add to the current policy and practice context in wound management by steering approaches to future education curriculums and training packages to ensure they sufficiently inform sub-specialties within the nursing profession; for example, those within pre-registration and SPQDN curriculums and those delivered in-house as wound management CPD. The findings should also support the development of approaches which effectively facilitate and strengthen links between academic and practice contexts in this area of practice; for example, the commitment to clinical educator and link nurse roles. The new knowledge from this study could also be applied to define and shape ethical

processes and relationships between health service providers, HEIs and industry which maximise learning.

References

- Adderley, U. Thompson, C. (2015) Community nurses' judgement for the management of venous leg ulceration: a judgement analysis. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*. 52, pp. 345-54.
- Aktar-Danesh, N., Bauman, A., Kolotylo, C., Lawlor, Y. Tompkins, C., Lee, R. (2013) Perceptions of professionalism among nursing faculty and nursing students. *Western Journal of Nursing Research*. 35(2), pp. 248–271.
- Allison, J. (1995) The effect of continuing education on practical wound management. *Journal of Wound Care*. 4(1), pp 29-31.
- Anfara, V.A., Mertz, N.T. (2015) *Theoretical frameworks in Qualitative Research*. 2nd edn. Thousand Oaks: Sage.
- Anfara, V.A. (2008) 'Theoretical Frameworks' in *The SAGE Encyclopaedia of Qualitative Research Methods*. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications Ltd.
- Apelqvist, J., Lazaro-Martinez, J.L., Van Acker, K. (2018) Delayed referral of patients with diabetic foot ulcers across Europe: patterns between primary care and specialised units. *Journal of Wound Care*. 27(3), pp. 186-192.
- Appleton, J.V. and Cowley, S. (2003) Valuing professional judgement in health visiting practice. *Community Practice*. 76, pp. 215-220.
- Argyrous, G. (2011) *Statistics for Research*. London: Sage.
- Ashmore R., Carver N. & Banks D. (2007) Mental health nursing students' relationships with the pharmaceutical industry. *Nurse Education Today*. 27, pp. 551–560.
- Ashton, J., Price, P. (2013) Survey comparing clinicians' wound healing knowledge and practice. *British Journal of Nursing*. 15(4). Avail at: <https://doi.org/10.12968/bjon.2006.15.Sup4.22114> {Accessed 11 May 2019}.
- Ashwin, P. Boud, D. Caulkins, S., Coate, K. Hallett, F., Light, G., Lockett, K. ,McArthur, J., Maclaren, I., McLean, M., , McCune, V., Martensson, K. ,Tooher, M. (2015) *Reflective Teaching in Higher Education*. London: Bloomsbury Press.
- Association of British Healthcare Industries (2018) *ABHI Code of Ethical Business Practice*. Avail at: <http://www.abhicodeofpractice.org.uk/cobp-documents.aspx> {Accessed 22nd June 2020}.
- Association of British Pharmaceutical Industries (2019) *Code of Practice for the Pharmaceutical Industry*. Avail at: <https://www.abpi.org.uk/media/6655/abpi-code-of-practice-2019.pdf> {Accessed 22nd February 2020}.
- Atkin, L., Bućko, Z., Conde Montero, E., Cutting, K., Moffatt, C., Probst, A., Romanelli, M., Schultz, G.S., Tettelbach, W. (2019). Implementing TIMERS: the race against hard-to-heal wounds. *Journal of Wound Care*. 28(3) (Suppl 3); pp. S1–S49.
- Augustin, M., Carville, K., Clark, M., Curran, J., Flour, M., Lindholm, C., MacDonald, J., Matsuzaki, K., Moffatt, C., Pattison, M., Price, P., Trueman, P., White, W., Young, T. (2012) *Optimising Wellbeing in People Living with a Wound: an expert working review group*. London: Wounds International.

- Aveyard, H. (2019) *Doing a Literature Review in Health and Social Care*. 4th edn. Maidenhead: Open University Press.
- Avis, M. (2003) Do we need methodological theory to do qualitative research? *Qualitative Health Research*. 13(7); pp. 995-1004.
- Ayala, R., Fealy, G.M., Vanderstraeten, R., Bracke, P. (2014) Academisation of nursing: an ethnography of social transformations in Chile. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*. 51, pp. 603-611.
- Ayres, L. (2008) 'Thematic coding and analysis' in: Given, L.M (eds) *The SAGE Encyclopaedia of Qualitative Research Methods*. Thousand Oaks: Sage.
- Bailin, S., Case, R., Coombs, J. R., & Daniels, L. B. (1999). Conceptualizing critical thinking. *Journal of Curriculum Studies*. 31 (3), pp. 285-302.
- Bain, H. (2015) *The Unique Knowing of District Nurses in Practice*. Doctor of Education Thesis. University of Stirling.
- Bansal, P., Corley, K. (2012) Publishing in AMJ-Part 7: What is different about qualitative research? *Academy of Management Journal*. 55, pp. 509-513.
- Barnett, R. (1997) *Higher Education: a critical business*. Buckingham: The Society for Research into Higher Education and Open University Press.
- Barratt, S., Cassidy, I., Graham, M.M. (2009) National survey of Irish community nurses' leg ulcer management practices and knowledge. *Journal of Wound Care*. 18 (5), pp. 181-190
- Bass, B.M. (1998) *Transformational Leadership*. Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum.
- Batkin, M.M. (1986) 'Speech genres and other late essays' in: Holquist, M., Emerson, C.(eds.) Austin: University of Texas Press.
- Batkin, M.M. (1981) 'The dialogic imagination: four essays' in: Emerson, C., Holquist, M. (eds.) Austin: University of Texas Press.
- Beauchamp, T.L., Childress, J.F. (2012) *Principles of Biomedical Ethics*. 6th edn. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Beeckman, D, Defloor, T, Schoonhoven, L, Vanderwee, K (2011) Knowledge and Attitudes of Nurses on Pressure Ulcer Prevention: A Cross-Sectional Multicenter Study in Belgian Hospitals. *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing*. 8(3), pp. 166-176
- Benner, P., Wrubel, J. (1984) *The Primacy of Caring*. Menlo Park: Addison and Wesley.
- Benner P (1982). From novice to expert. *American Journal of Nursing*. 82, pp. 402–407.
- Benner, P. and Tanner, C. (1987) Clinical judgment: how expert nurses use intuition. *The American Journal of Nursing*. 87, pp. 23-31.
- Biesta, G., Allan, J., Edwards, R. (2011) The theory question in research capacity building in education: towards an agenda for research and practice. *British Journal of Educational Studies*. 59(3), pp. 225-39.
- Birdin, H., Glass, N., Wilson, I., Harrison, M., Usherwood, T., Nass, D. (2014) Defining professionalism in medical education: A systematic review. *Medical Teacher*. 36, pp. 47-61.

- Bowers, B., Pellet, C. (2010) Measuring the clinical effectiveness of district nurses. *British Journal of Community Nursing*.18(7), pp. 332-337.
- Bradshaw, A., Merriman, C. (2008). Nursing competence 10 years on: fit for practice and purpose yet? *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 17(10), pp. 1263–1269.
- Brambilla, R., Hurlow, J., Landis, S., Wolcott, R. (2016) *World Union of Wound Healing Societies Clinical Report: innovations in hard-to-heal wounds*. Italy: WUWHS.
- Braun, V., Clarke, V. (2013). *Successful Qualitative Research: a practical guide for beginners*. London: Sage.
- Braun, V., Clarke, V. (2006) Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*. 3(6), pp. 77-101.
- Brooks, R., Maguire, M., te Riele, K. (2016) *Ethics and Education Research*. London: Sage.
- Burke, M. (2014) Modelling district nurse expertise. *British Journal of Community Nursing*. 19(12), pp. 608-611.
- Burrell, G., Morgan, G. (1979) *Sociological Paradigms and Organisational Analysis*. London: Routledge.
- Busfield, J. (2006) Pills, power, people: sociological understandings of the pharmaceutical industry. *Sociology*. 40(2). Avail at: <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F0038038506062034> {Accessed 30th September 20}.
- Calman, L. (2006). Patients' views of nurses' competence. *Nurse Education Today*. 26, pp. 719–725.
- Cannell, C.F., Kahn, R.L. (1968) 'Interviewing', in: Lindsay, G., Aronson, A. (eds.) *The Handbook of Social Psychology. vol. 2: Research Methods*. New York: Addison Wesley.
- Cardoso, D.S., Carvalho, F.M.O., Rocha G.B., Mendes, J.R., Cardoso, S.D.B., Rocha, F.C. V. (2019) The nurses' knowledge with regards to both classification and prevention of pressure injury. *Rev Fund Care Online*. 11(3), pp.560-566.
- Carper B.A. (1978) Fundamental patterns of knowing in nursing. *Advancing Nursing Science*.1, pp. 13–24.
- Centre of Research Dissemination (2009) *Systematic Reviews: CRD's guidance for undertaking reviews in health care*. York: University of York.
- Chief Nursing Officer's Department (2018) *Transforming nursing, midwifery and health professions' (NMaHP) Roles: pushing the boundaries to meet health and social care needs in Scotland: Paper 5: Transforming education and career development in nursing*. Edinburgh: Scottish Government
- Chief Nursing Officer's Department (2017a) *Transforming nursing, midwifery and health professions' (NMaHP) Roles: pushing the boundaries to meet health and social care needs in Scotland: Paper 1: Introduction*. Edinburgh: Scottish Government
- Chief Nursing Officer's Department (2017b) *Transforming Nursing, Midwifery and Health Professions' (NMaHP) Roles: pushing the boundaries to meet health and social care needs in Scotland: Paper 2 Advanced nursing practice: Introduction*. Edinburgh: Scottish Government.

- Chinn, P.L., Kramer, M.K. (2015) *Knowledge Development in Nursing: theory and process* 9th edn. St Louis: Elsevier Mosby.
- Cioffi, M.C. (2012) Loss of clinical nursing expertise: a discussion paper. *International Journal of Nursing Practice*.18, pp. 423–428.
- Clarke, V., Braun, V., Terry, G., Hayfield, N. (2019). 'Thematic analysis', in: Liamputtong, P. (eds.) *Handbook of Research Methods in Health and Social Sciences*. Springer
- Cohen, L., Manion, L., Morrison, K. (2018) *Research Methods in Education*. 8th edn. London: Routledge.
- Cook, L. (2011) Wound Assessment: exploring competency and current practice. *British Journal of Community Nursing*.16; (Suppl. 12), pp. S34-S40.
- Cooke, H. Phelpin, S. (2008) *Sociology in Nursing and Health Care*. London: Bailliere Tindall
- Cowan, D., Norman, I., Coopamah, V. (2005). Competence in nursing practice: A controversial concept: A focused review of literature. *Nurse Education Today*. 25, pp. 355–362.
- Cowman, S., Gethin, G., Clarke, E., Moore. Z., Craig, G. Jordan-O'Brien, J., McLain, N., Strapp, H. (2011) An international Delphi study identifying the research and education priorities in wound management and tissue repair. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*. 21, pp. 344-353.
- Crenshaw, K. (1989) *Demarginalising the intersection of race and sex: a black feminist critique of antidiscrimination doctrine, feminist theory and antiracist politics*. University of Chicago Legal Forum. May 13.
- Crigger, N., Barnes K., Junko A., Rahal, S., Sheek, C. (2009) Nurse practitioners' perceptions and participation in pharmaceutical marketing. *Journal of Advanced Nursing* 65(3), pp. 525–533.
- Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (2018) *CASP Cohort Study Checklist*. Available at: <https://casp-uk.net/casp-tools-checklists/> {Accessed 11th November 2018}.
- Croxon, L., Maginnis, C. (2009) Evaluation of clinical teaching models for nursing practice. *Nurse Education in Practice*. 9(4), pp. 236-243.
- Cullen, G., Moore, Z. (2013) An exploration of fourth-year undergraduate nurses' knowledge of and attitude towards pressure ulcer prevention. *Journal of Wound Care*. 22 (11). Avail at: <https://doi.org/10.12968/jowc.2013.22.11.618> {Accessed 22nd May 2019}.
- Cunningham, C.J.L., Weathington, B.L., Pittenger, D.J. (2013) *Understanding and Conducting Research in the Health Sciences*.1st edn. Chichester: John Wiley and Sons.
- Dall'Alba, G., Sandberg, J. (2006) Unveiling professional development: a critical review of stage models. *Review of Educational Research*. 76(3), pp. 383-412.
- Davidson, D. (1984) *Inquiries into truth and interpretation*. Oxford UK: Oxford University Press.
- Davies C, Lawrence S., Moore C. (1999) Research application: wound care in community practice. *Journal of Wound Care*. 3(7), pp. 330-333.

- Davis, A., Maisano, P. (2016) Patricia Benner: novice to expert – a concept whose time has come (again) *The Oklahoma Nurse*. September, October, November; pp. 13-15.
- Deeth, M. Grothier, L. (2016) Wound bed preparation: a survey of general nurses' understanding. *British Journal of Nursing*. 25 (12) Tissue Viability Supplement, pp. S66-S70.
- Denny, E. (2010) 'Nursing as an occupation' in: Denny, E., Earle, S. (eds.) *Sociology for Nurses*. 2nd edn. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Denscombe, M. (2014) *The Good Research Guide*. 4th edn. Maidenhead. UK: Open University Press.
- Dickson, C., Gough, H., Bain, H. (2016) Meeting the policy agenda, part 2: is a 'Cinderella service' sufficient? *British Journal of Community Nursing*. 16(11), pp.540-545.
- Digital Curation Centre (DCC) (2013) *Checklist for a Data Management Plan. v.4.0*. Edinburgh: Digital Curation Centre. Available online: <http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/data-management-plans> {Accessed 4th July 2019}.
- Dimond, B. (2015) *Legal Aspects of Nursing*. 7th edn. Edinburgh: Churchill Livingstone.
- Donomeyer, R. (2014) What if educational inquiry were neither a social science nor a humanities field? Revisiting Joseph Schwab's "The practical" in the aftermath of the science wars. *Education Policy Analysis Archives*. 22 (8). Avail at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.14507/epaa.v22n8.2014>. {Accessed 1st July 2018}.
- Dowsett, C. (2015) Breaking the cycle of hard-to-heal wounds. *Wounds International*. 6(2), pp.17-21.
- Drew, D. (2011) Professional identity and the culture of community nursing. *British Journal of Community Nursing*. 16(3), pp.-126-131.
- Dugdall, H., Watson, R. (2009) What is the relationship between nurses' attitude to evidence-based practice and the selection of wound care procedures? *Journal of Clinical Nursing*. 18, pp.1442–1450.
- Dumville, J. C., Petherick, E. S., O'Meara, S., Raynor, P., Cullum, N. (2009). How is research evidence used to support claims made in advertisements for wound care products? *Journal of Clinical Nursing*. 18(10), pp.1422-1429.
- Dumville, J. C., Petherick, E. S., Cullum, N. (2008). When will I see you again? The fate of research findings from international wound care conferences. *International Wound Journal*. 5(1), pp. 26-32.
- Dutton, M., Chiarella, M., Curtis, K. (2014) The role of the wound care nurse: an integrative review. *British Journal of Community Nursing*. 19(Supp 3). Avail at: <https://doi.org/10.12968/bjcn.2014.19.Supp3.S39> {Accessed 7th May 2019}.
- Eagleton, T. (1991) *Ideology*. London: Verso.
- Ecker, E., Skelly, A. (2010) Conducting a winning literature review. *Evidence-Based Spine-Care Journal*. 1(1), pp.9-14.
- Edwards, J., Mitchell, A., Bayat, A., Dunn, K. (2005) A comparative study of nurses' wound management knowledge in two areas. *Journal of Community Nursing*. 19(2), pp 4-12
- Eisner, E. W. (2002) From episteme to phronesis to artistry in the study and improvement of teaching. *Teaching and Teacher Education*. 18, pp.375-385.

- Eraut, M (2007) Learning from other people in the workplace. *Oxford Review of Education*. 33(4), pp.403-422.
- Eraut, M. (2004). Informal learning in the workplace. *Studies in Continuing Education*. 26 (2), pp. 247-273.
- Eraut, M. (2000) Non-formal learning and tacit knowledge in professional work. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*. 70, pp.113–136.
- Etafa, W., Argaw, Z., Gemechu, E., Melese, B. (2018) Nurses' attitude and perceived barriers to pressure ulcer prevention. *BioMed Central Nursing*. 17(4), pp. 3-8.
- Fantahun, A., Demessie, A., Gebrekirstos, K., Zemene, A., Yetayeh, Gebre, A. (2014) A cross sectional study on factors influencing professionalism in nursing among nurses in Mekelle Public Hospitals, North Ethiopia. *BMC Nursing*. 13(10). Avail at: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1186/1472-6955-13-10> {Accessed 11th May 2017}.
- Fawcett, J., DeSanto-Madeya, S. (2013) *Contemporary Nursing Knowledge: analysis and evaluation of nursing models and theories*. 3rd edn. Philadelphia: F.A. Davis Company.
- Ferreira, A., Rigotti, M., Barcelos, L., Simão, C., Ferreira, D., Gonçalves, R. (2014). Knowledge and practice of nurses about care for patients with wounds. *Revista de Pesquisa: Cuidado É Fundamental Online*. Avail at: [file:///C:/Users/m_wel/Downloads/3113-20205-1-PB%20\(1\).pdf](file:///C:/Users/m_wel/Downloads/3113-20205-1-PB%20(1).pdf). {Accessed 5th November 2017}.
- Finnie, A., Wilson, A. (2003) Development of a tissue viability nursing competency framework. *British Journal of Nursing*. 12(6) (Suppl); pp.S38–44.
- Finnie, A. (2001) Role definition and structured progress for tissue viability nurses. *British Journal of Nursing*. (Supp) 10(11); pp. S6-7
- Flanagan, M. (1998a) The impact of change on the tissue viability nurse specialist: 1. *British Journal of Nursing*. 7(11). Avail at: <https://doi.org/10.12968/bjon.1998.7.11.5671> {Accessed 27th April 2019}.
- Flanagan, M. (1998b) Factors influencing tissue viability nurse specialists in the UK: 2. *British Journal of Nursing*. 7(12), pp. 690-701.
- Fletcher, J., Fumarola, S., Haycocks, S., King, B., Powell, G., Vowden, K., Young, T. (2018) *Wounds UK: Best Practice Statement: improving holistic assessment of chronic wounds*. London: Wounds UK. Avail at: www.wounds-uk.com {Accessed 5th December 2019}.
- Fletcher, J. (2010) Education provision in wound care-does it make a difference? *International Wound Journal*. 7(2); pp.73-74.
- Fox, C. (2001) Perceptions of tissue viability nurses of their current roles. *British Journal of Nursing*. 10(Supp 2). Avail at: <https://doi.org/10.12968/bjon.2001.10.Supp2.12341> {Accessed 19th Dec 2019}.
- French, J.R.P., Raven, B. (1959) 'The Bases of Social Power'. in: Cartwright, D. (eds.) *Studies in Social Power*. Ann Arbor: Institute for Social Research.
- Freshwater, D. (2007) Reading mixed methods research: contexts for criticism. *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*. 1(2), pp. 134-146.
- Freire, P. (1973) *The Pedagogy of the Oppressed*. New York: Seabury Press
- Friedson, E. (1970) *Profession of Medicine*. New York: Dodd.

- Friman, A., Klang, B., Ebbskog, B. (2011) Wound care by district nurses at primary healthcare centres: a challenging task without authority or resources. *Scandinavian Journal of Caring Sciences*. 25, pp. 426-434.
- Frykeberg, R.G., Banks, J. (2015) Challenges in the treatment of chronic wounds. *Advances in Wound Care*. 4(9), pp. 560-582.
- Garrett, B.M., Cutting, R.L. (2014) Ways of knowing: realism, non-realism, nominalism and a typology revisited with a counter perspective for nursing science. *Nursing Inquiry*. 22(2), pp. 95–105.
- Gillespie, B., Chaboyer, W., Winsomes, S.J., Morely, N., Nieuwenhoven, P. (2015) Health professionals' decision-making in wound management: a grounded theory. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*. 71(6), pp. 1238-1248.
- Gillespie, B. M., Chaboyer, W., Allen, P., Morely, N., Nieuwenhoven, P. (2014). Wound care practices: a survey of acute care nurses. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*. Avail at: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/jocn.12479>. {Accessed 11th May 2017}.
- Ghobadifar, M.A., Mosalanejad, L. (2013) Evaluation of staff adherence to professionalism in Jahrom University of Medical Sciences. *Journal of Education and Ethics in Nursing*. 2 (2), pp. 1–7
- Giroux, H. (2017) *On Critical Pedagogy*. New York: Bloomsbury Academic.
- Glaser, B., Strauss, A. (1967) *The Discovery of Grounded Theory*. Chicago, IL: Aldine.
- Glasgow City Integrated Joint Board (2019) *Glasgow City Primary Care Improvement Plan (PCIP 2) 2019-21*. Glasgow: Glasgow City IJB.
- Gobo, G. (2011) 'Ethnography' in: Silverman, D. (2011) (eds) *Qualitative Research*. 3rd edn. London: Sage.
- Gonzaga de Faria G.B., Nascimento do Prado, T., Lima A, de Fátima, E., Brunet Rogenski N.M., Tomazini Borghardt, A., Massaroni, L. (2016) Knowledge and practice of nurses on the care of wounds. *J Nurs UFPE*. 10, pp. 4532–4538.
- Gray, T.A., Wilson, P., Dumville, J.C., Cullum, N. (2019). What factors influence community wound care in the UK? A focus group study using the Theoretical Domains Framework. *BMJ Open* 2019. 9:e024859. Avail at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2018-024859> {Accessed 30th September 2020}.
- Gray, T.A, Rhodes, S., Atkinson, R.A., Rothwell, K., Wilson, P. Dumville, J., Cullum, N. (2018) Opportunities for better value wound care: a multiservice, cross-sectional survey of complex wounds and their care in a UK community population. *British Medical Journal Open*. Avail at: <https://bmjopen.bmj.com/content/bmjopen/8/3/e019440.full.pdf>. {Accessed 11th July 2020}
- Gray, D. (2014) *Doing Research in the Real World*. London: Sage.
- Green, B., Earle, S. (2010) 'Why should nurses study sociology?' in: Denny, E., Earle, S. (2010) (eds) *Sociology for Nurses*. 2nd edn. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Greene, J.C. (2007) *Mixed-methods in social inquiry*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.

- Guay, Y. (1988) Internationalization of industrial research: the pharmaceutical industry; 1965–1979. *Scientometrics*.13, pp.189–213. Avail at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02019958> {Accessed 30th September 2020}.
- Guba, E. G., Lincoln, Y. (1989). *Fourth Generation Evaluation*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage.
- Guest, J., Fuller G.W., Vowden, P. (2018a) Venous leg ulcer management in clinical practice in the UK: costs and outcomes. *International Wound Journal*. 15(1), pp. 29-37.
- Guest, J., Fuller G.W., Vowden, P. (2018b) Diabetic foot ulcer management in clinical practice in the UK: costs and outcomes. *International Wound Journal*. 15(1), pp. 43-52.
- Guest, J.F., Gerrish, A., Vowden, P., Vowden, K. (2015) Health economic burden that wounds impose on the National Health Service in the UK. *BMJ Open*.5. <https://bmjopen.bmj.com/content/bmjopen/5/12/e009283.full.pdf>. {Accessed 20th February 2017}.
- Guest, J., Vowden, K., Vowden, P. (2017). The health economic burden that acute and chronic wounds impose on an average clinical commissioning group/health board in the UK. *Journal of Wound Care*. 26(6), pp. 292-303.
- Guest, J.F, Gerrish, A., Vowden, P, Vowden, K. (2016) Clinical outcomes and cost-effectiveness of three alternative compression systems used in the management of venous leg ulcers. *Journal of Wound Care*. 24(7), pp. 300-310.
- Habermas, J. (1972) *Knowledge and Human Interests*. London: Heinmann.
- Hallett, C., Austin, L., Caress, A., Luker, K. (2000) Wound care in the community setting: clinical decision making in context. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*. 31(4), pp. 783-793.
- Hammersley, M. (2013) *What is Qualitative Research?* London: Bloomsbury Academic.
- Hammersley, M. (2012) Troubling theory in case study research. *Higher Education Research and Development*. 31(3), pp. 393-405.
- Hampton, S., Lindsay, E. (2005) Empowering patients to take control of leg ulcer treatment through individualised management. *Journal of Wound Care*. 14, pp. 238-240.
- Haram, R., Ribu, E., Rustøen, T. (2003) The views of district nurses on their level of knowledge about the treatment of leg and foot ulcers. *Journal of Wound Ostomy and Continence Nursing*. 30(1), pp. 25-32.
- Harding, K. Dowsett, C., Fias, L., Jelnes, R., Mosti, G., Ojen, R., Partsch, H., Reeder, S., Senet, P., Soriano, J., Vnaschedit, W. (2015) Simplifying venous leg ulcer management. Consensus recommendations. *Wounds International*. Avail at: www.woundsinternational.com. {Accessed 11th November 2018}.
- Hart, C. (2001) *Doing a Literature Search*. London: Sage.
- Health Committee. (2005). *The influence of the pharmaceutical company*. HC 42-I [Incorporating HC 1030-i-iii]. London: The Stationery Office Limited
- Heaslip, V. (2013) District nursing: the hidden giant of the NHS? *British Journal of Community Nursing*.18, pp. 404-6.
- Hjelm, K., Rolfe, M., Bryar, R., Andersson, B.L. Fletcher, M. (2003) Holism in community leg ulcer management: a comparison of nurses in Sweden and the UK. *British Journal of*

Community Nursing. 8(8), Avail at: <https://doi.org/10.12968/bjcn.2003.8.8.11565> {Accessed 4th June 2019}.

Hjort, A, Gottrup, F. (2010) Cost of wound treatment to increase significantly in Denmark over the next decade. *Journal of Wound Care*. 19, pp.173–184.

Holloway, I., Todres, L. (2003). The status of method: flexibility, consistency and coherence. *Qualitative Research*. 3, pp. 345–357.

Holloway, S. (2019) Revisiting the role and responsibilities of the Tissue Viability Nurse. *Wounds UK*. 15(5); pp.16-23.

Holloway, S. (2017) The impact of postgraduate studies in wound healing on professional practice and personal development. *Wounds UK*, 13 (3), pp. 44-51.

Holm, A.L., Severinsson, E. (2016) A systematic review of intuition—a way of knowing in clinical nursing? *Open Journal of Nursing*. 6(5), pp.412-425.

Hosseini, R., Hosseini, M., Mohammad, E.A., Tayebeh M. (2015) Pressure ulcers: how much do nursing students really know? *British Journal of Nursing (Tissue Viability Supplement)*. 24 (6); pp. S12-S17.

Huff, A.S. (2009) *Designing Research for Publication*. Thousand Oaks: Sage

Hughes, M. (2016) Wound infection: a knowledge deficit that needs addressing. *British Journal of Nursing*. 25(6), pp. S46–S51.

Hugh-Jones, S. (2010) 'The interview in qualitative research'. in: Forrester, M.A. (2010) (eds.) *Doing qualitative research in psychology: a practical guide*. London: Sage, pp.78-97.

Innes-Walker, K., Edwards, H. (2013) A wound management education and training needs analysis of health consumers and the relevant health workforce and stocktake of available education and training activities and resources. *Wound Practice and Research*. 21(3), pp.104-109.

Jacobs, S. (2018) An analysis of the evolution of mentorship in nursing. *International Journal of Mentoring and Coaching*. 7(2), pp. 155-176.

Jarbrink, K., Ni G, Sonnergren, H., Schmidtchen, A., Pang, C., Bajpai, R., Car, J. (2017) The humanistic and economic burden of chronic wounds: a protocol for a systematic review. *Systematic Reviews*. 6 (15). Avail at: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1186/s13643-016-0400-8>. {Accessed 5th June 2020}.

Jayasekara, R., Smith, C., Hall, C., Rankin, E., Smith, M., Visvanathan, V., Friebe, T.R. (2018) The effectiveness of clinical education models for undergraduate nursing programs: A systematic review. *Nurse Education in Practice*. 29, pp. 116-126

Joffe, H. (2011) 'Thematic analysis' in Harper, D., Thompson, A. R. (eds). *Qualitative Methods in Mental Health and Psychotherapy: a guide for students and practitioners.*, pp. 209-223. Chichester: Wiley.

Johnson, M. (2008) 'Power and communication' in: Cooke, H. Phelpin, S. (eds) *Sociology in Nursing and Health Care*. London: Baillierre Tindall.

Jorgenson, S.F., Nygaard, J. Posnett, J. (2010) Meeting the challenges of wound care in Danish home care. *Journal of Wound Care*. 22(10). Avail at: <https://doi.org/10.12968/jowc.2013.22.10.540> {Accessed 11th November 2017}.

- Keeling, J., Templeman, J. (2013) Nurse Education in Practice An exploratory study: Student nurses' perceptions of professionalism. *Nurse Education in Practice*.13, pp.1318-1322.
- Kennedy, C. (2004) A typology of knowledge for district nursing assessment practice. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*. 45 (4), pp. 401-409.
- Kennedy, C., Arundel, D. (1998a) District nurses' knowledge and practice of wound assessment: 1. *British Journal of Nursing*. 7(7). Avail at: <https://doi.org/10.12968/bjon.1998.7.7.380> {Accessed on 14th Feb 2019}.
- Kennedy, C., Arundel, D. (1998b) District nurses' knowledge and practice of wound assessment: 2. *British Journal of Nursing*. 7(7). Avail at: <https://doi.org/10.12968/bjon.1998.7.8.5709> {Accessed 14th Feb 2019}.
- Kerlinger, F.N. (1970) *Foundations of Behavioural Research*. New York: Holt, Rinehart and Winston.
- Kessenich, C.R., Westbrook, M.H. (1999) Pharmaceutical companies and the prescriptive practices of nurse practitioners. *Journal of the American Academy of Nurse Practitioners*. 11(12), pp. 533– 538.
- Khalili, H., Hall, S., Daluca, S. (2014) Historical analysis of professionalism in western societies: Implications for interprofessional education and collaborative practice. *Journal of Interprofessional Care*. 28(2), pp. 92-97.
- Kielo, E., Suhonen, R., Salminen, L., Stolt, M. (2019a) Competence areas for registered nurses and podiatrists in chronic wound care, and their role in wound care practice. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*. 28(21-22), pp. 4021-4034.
- Kielo E., Salminen L., Suhonen R., Puukka, P., Stolt, M. (2019a) Graduating student nurses' and student podiatrists' wound care competence: a cross-sectional study. *Journal of Wound Care*. 28(3), pp.136-145.
- Kielo, E., Salminen, L., Stolt, M. (2019c) Graduating student nurses' and student podiatrists' wound care competence - An integrative literature review. *Nurse Education and Practice*. 29, pp. 1-7.
- Kitzinger, J. (1995) Qualitative research: introducing focus groups. *British Medical Journal*. 311, pp. 299-302.
- Kitzinger, J. (1994) The methodology of focus groups: the importance of interaction between research participants. *Sociology of Health and Illness*. 16(1), pp.103-121.
- Kilpatrick, K., Carter, N., Bryant-Lukosius, D Charbonneau-Smith, R., DiCenso, A., (2015) The development of evidence briefs to transfer knowledge about advanced practice nursing roles to providers, policymakers and administrators. *Nursing Leadership*. 28(1), pp.11-23.
- The King's Fund (2016) *Understanding quality in district nursing services. Learning from patients, carers and staff*. London: The King's Fund.
- Kitson, A.L., Harvey, G. (2014) Methods to succeed in effective knowledge translation in clinical practice. *Journal of Nursing Scholarship*. 48(3), pp.294-302.
- Kuhn, T.S. (1962) *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Kvale, S. (1996) *Interviews*. London: Sage.

- Lamond, D., Farnell, S. (1998) The treatment of pressure sores: a comparison of novice and expert nurses' knowledge, information use and decision accuracy. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*. 27, pp. 280-286.
- Lamond, D., Thompson, C. (2000). Intuition and analysis in decision making and choice. *Journal of Nursing Scholarship*. 32(4), pp.411–414.
- Langley, C., Parkinson, S. (2009) Science and the corporate agenda: The detrimental effects of commercial influence on science and technology. *Radical Statistics*. 104, pp. 5-12.
- Lemon, J.D., Munsif, M., Sinha, S. (2013) Role of wound clinic teaching in the undergraduate medical curriculum. *Wound Practice and Research*. 21(3), pp.112-115.
- Letherby, G. (2010) Gender. In: Denny, E., Earle, S. (eds.) *Sociology for Nurses*. 2nd edn. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Lincoln, Y., Guba, E. G. (1985). *Naturalistic Inquiry*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage.
- Lockwood, C., Hopp, L. (2016) Knowledge translation: what it is and the relevance to evidence-based healthcare and nursing. *International Journal of Nursing Practice*. 22, pp. 319–321.
- Logan, G. (2015) Clinical judgment and decision-making in wound assessment and management: is experience enough? *British Journal of Community Nursing*. Avail at: <https://doi.org/10.12968/bjcn.2015.20.Sup3.S21> {Accessed 22nd Jan 2019}.
- Longstaff, F. (2013) The case for renewed investment in the district nursing specialist practitioner qualification. *British Journal of Community Nursing*. 18(9), pp. 446-449.
- Lusher, J, Murray, E., Chapman-Jones, D. (2017) Changing the way we think about wounds: A challenge for 21st century medical practice. *International Wound Journal*. Avail at: <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/227578287.pdf>. {Accessed 11th September 2020}.
- McCluskey, P., McCarthy, G. (2012) Nurses' knowledge and competence in wound management. *Wounds UK*. 2(2), pp. 37-47.
- McComiskey, F. (2017) The fundamental managerial challenges in the role of a contemporary district nurse: a discussion. *British Journal of Community Nursing*. 22 (10), pp. 489-494.
- McInnes, A., Lawson-Brown, V. (2007) 'God' and other 'do-gooders': a comparison of the regulation of services provided by General Practitioners and Social Workers in England. *Journal of Social Work*. 7(3), pp. 341–354.
- Madden, M. (2012) Alienating evidence-based medicine vs. innovative medical device marketing: A report on the evidence debate at a Wounds conference. *Social Science and Medicine*. 74, pp. 2046-2052.
- Mahony, K. (2014) Understanding the basics of wound care in the community setting. *Journal of Community Nursing*. 28(3), pp. 66-75.
- Marshall, C., Rossman, G. (2016) *Designing Qualitative Research*. 6th edn. Thousand Oaks: Sage.
- Martimianakis, M., Maniate, J., Hodges B. (2009) Sociological interpretations of professionalism. *Medical Education*. 43, pp. 829-837.

- Martin, F. (2014) Educational challenges and requirements for managing leg ulcers in the community. *British Journal of Community Nursing*. 19; (Supp. 6). Avail at: <https://doi.org/10.12968/bjcn.2014.19.Supp6>. {Accessed 11th October 2018}.
- Masturzo, A., Beltz, W. R., Cook, R., Bates-Jensen, B., Stechmiller, J., Korzendorfer, H., Gould, L. J. (2013). Wound care certification: the grin without a cat. *Wound Repair and Regeneration*. Avail at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/wrr.12067>. {Accessed 19th August 2017}.
- Maylor, M. I. (2012). A curriculum to ensure nursing staff competency. *British Journal of Nursing*. Tissue Viability Supplement. 21(15), pp. S10-S17.
- Milne J. (2016) The challenge of providing cost-effective wound care. *Wounds UK*.12 (52), pp. 52-57.
- Miyazaki, M., Caliri, M., Santos, C. (2010) Knowledge on pressure ulcer prevention among nursing professionals. *Revista Latino-Americana Enfermagem*. 18(6), pp. 1203-1211.
- Moat, K.A., Lavis, J.N, Abelson, J. (2013) How contexts and issues influence the use of policy-relevant research syntheses: a critical interpretative synthesis. *The Millbank Quarterly*. 91(3), pp. 604-648.
- Momennasab, M., Koshkaki, A. R., Torabizadeh, C.,Tabei, S. Z. (2016). Nurses' adherence to ethical codes: The viewpoints of patients, nurses, and managers. *Nursing Ethics*. 23 (7), pp. 794-803. Avail at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0969733015583927> {Accessed 11th October 2019}.
- Monagan M.S., Galt K.A., Turner P.D., Houghton B.L., Rich E.C., Markert R.J., Bergman-Evans B. (2003) Student understanding of the relationship between the health professions and the pharmaceutical industry. *Teaching and Learning in Medicine*. 15(1), pp.14–20.
- Moore, Z., Clarke, E. (2011) A survey of the provision of education in wound management to undergraduate nursing students. *EWMA Journal*.11(1), pp. 35-38,
- Moore, Z. (2010) Bridging the theory-practice gap in pressure ulcer prevention. *British Journal of Nursing*. 19(15), (Suppl), pp. S15-18.
- Morgan, D.L. (2008) 'Sampling' in *The SAGE Encyclopaedia of Qualitative Research Methods*. pp.800-802. Thousand Oaks: Sage.
- Mulkeen, J. Abdou, H.A., Leigh., J, Ward, P. (2019) Degree and Higher-Level Apprenticeships: an empirical investigation of stakeholder perceptions of challenges and opportunities. *Studies in Higher Education*. 44(2), pp. 333-346.
- Murphy, C., Atkin, L., Swanson, T., Tachi, M., Tan, Y.K., Vega de Ceniga, M., Weir, D., Wolcott, R. (2020) International consensus document: Defying hard-to-heal wounds with an early anti-biofilm intervention strategy: wound hygiene. *Journal of Wound Care*. 29 (Suppl 3b), pp. S1–28.
- Murray, M.J. (1974) The Pharmaceutical Industry: A Study in Corporate Power. *International Journal of Health Services*. 4(4); pp. 625-640. Avail at: <https://doi.org/10.2190%2FM6YT-72J9-6LVV-FWG9> {Accessed 30th September 2020}.
- NHS England (2016) *Leading change adding value*. Avail at: <https://www.england.nhs.uk/wp-content/uploads/2016/05/nursing-framework.pdf>. {Accessed 11th July 2020}.
- NHS Greater Glasgow and Clyde (2016) *Code of Conduct for Staff*. Glasgow: NHSGGC.

- NHS Improvement (2016) *Stop the Pressure*. Avail at: <https://nhs.stopthepressure.co.uk/> {Accessed 11th June 2020}
- National Wound Care Strategy Programme (2021) *National Wound Care and Skills for Health Core Capabilities Framework for England*. NWCSP and Skills for Health
- National Wound Care Strategy Programme (2019) *National Wound Care Strategy programme progress report 2018-19*. Avail at: <https://www.ahsnnetwork.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/NWCSP-Progress-Report-November-2019-Final-.pdf> [Accessed 26th June 2020].
- Neuman, B. (1996) 'The Neuman system model: application to nursing education and practice.' 3rd edn. in: McEwen, M., Wills, E. (eds). *Theoretical Basis for Nursing*. USA: Lippincott Williams and Wilkins.
- Nickitas, D.M., Friedrichson, K. (2015) Nursing knowledge and theory: where is the economic value? *Nursing Economics*. 33(4), pp. 239-240.
- Nonaka, I., Toyama, R. (2007). Strategic management as distributed practical wisdom (phronesis) *Industrial and Corporate Change*.16 (3), pp. 371-394.
- Nonaka, I., Takeuchi, H. (1995) *The Knowledge Creating Company*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Nowell, L.S., Norris, J.M., White, D.E., Moules, N.J. (2017) Thematic analysis: striving to meet the trustworthiness criteria. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*.16, pp. 1-13.
- Nursing and Midwifery Council (2018) *Future Nurse: standards of proficiency for registered nurses*. Avail at: <https://www.nmc.org.uk/globalassets/sitedocuments/standards-of-proficiency/nurses/future-nurse-proficiencies.pdf>. {Accessed 26th June 2020}.
- Nursing and Midwifery Council (2018) *Realising professionalism: standards for education and training: Part 3: standards for pre-registration nursing programmes*. London: NMC.
- Nussbaum, S.R., Carter, M.J., Fife, C.E., DaVanzo, J., Haught, R., Nusgart, M., Cartwright, D. (2018) An economic evaluation of the impact, cost and medicare policy implications of chronic non-healing wounds. *Value in Health*. 21 (1), pp: 27–32.
- Nygaard, C., Belluigi, D.Z. (2011) A proposed methodology for contextualised evaluation in higher education. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*. 36(6), pp. 657-671.
- Olsson, M., Jarbrink, K., Divakar, U., Bajpai, R., Upton, Z., Schmidtchen, A., Car, J. (2019) The humanistic and economic burden of chronic wounds: A systematic review. *Wound Repair and Regeneration*. 27 (1), pp.114–125.
- Onwuegbuzie, A.J., Johnson, R.B. (2006) The validity issues in mixed research. *Research in the Schools*. 13(1), pp. 48-63.
- Oppenheim, N. (1992) *Questionnaire Design: interviewing and attitude measurement*. London: Pinter Publishers Ltd.
- Orem, D.E. (2001) *Nursing: concepts of practice*. 6th edn. New York: Mosby.
- Orsted, H.L., Woodbury, M.G., Stevenson, K. (2012) The Wound CARE instrument: the process for developing standards for wound management education and programming. *International Wound Journal*. 9, pp. 264-270.

- Ousey, K., Lindsay, C. (2019) Preparing tissue viability clinicians to understand business planning. *Wounds UK*. 15(4); pp. 44-47.
- Ousey, K. (2017) Protecting our education training and professional development. *Wounds UK*. 13(1). Avail at: <https://www.wounds-uk.com/journals/issue/51/article-details/2017-protecting-our-education-training-and-professional-development>. {Accessed 27th April 2018}.
- Ousey, K., Rippon, M., Stephenson, J. (2016a) Barriers to wound debridement: results of an online survey. *Wounds UK*. 12(4); pp. 36-41.
- Ousey, K., Stephenson, J., Carter, B. (2016b) Tissue Viability Leading Change competency framework: preliminary analysis of use. *Wounds UK*. 12(30); pp. 30-35.
- Ousey, K., Milne, J., Atkin, L., Henderson, King, N., Stephenson, J. (2015) Exploring the role of the Tissue Viability Nurse. *Wounds UK EWMA Special*, pp. 36-45.
- Ousey, K., Atkinson, R., Fleming, L., Conway, B. (2013a) Academia and clinical practice - working together successfully to develop skin integrity knowledge and skills. *Journal of Community Nursing*. 27 (1), pp. 15-17.
- Ousey, K., Stephenson, J., Cook, L., Kinsey, L., Batt, S. (2013b). Final year student nurses' experiences of wound care: an evaluation. *British Journal of Nursing*. Vol 18 (Sup. 3). Avail at: <https://doi.org/10.12968/bjcn.2013.18.Sup3.S7>. {Accessed 7th May 2017}.
- Pahor, M., Domajnko, B., Lindahl, E. (2015) Nursing students' perceptions of knowledge: an international perspective. *Obzornik Zdravstvene Nege*. 49(1), pp. 18–25.
- Panksepp, J. (1998) Affective neuroscience. *The Foundations of Human and Animal Emotions*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Patton, M.Q. (1980) *Qualitative Evaluation Methods*. Beverly Hills: Sage.
- Perakyla, A. (2011) 'Validity in research on naturally occurring social interaction' in: Silverman, D. (eds) *Qualitative Research*. 3rd edn. London: Sage.
- Pieper, B. Keves-Foster, M.K., Ashare, J., Zugic, M., Albdour, M., Albdour, D. (2016) A cross-sectional, descriptive, quality improvement project to assess undergraduate nursing students' clinical exposure to patients with wounds in an introductory nursing course. *Ostomy/Wound Management*. 62(4), pp.20-29.
- Polit, D.F., Beck, C.T. (2017) *Essentials of Nursing Research: appraising evidence for nursing practice*. 8th edn. Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams and Wilkins.
- Pollock, A. M. (2004). *NHS The privatisation of our health care*. London: Verso
- Porter, S. (2010) Fundamental patterns of knowing in nursing: the challenge of evidence-based practice. *Advances in Nursing Science*. 33(1), pp. 3-14.
- Porter, S., O'Halloran, P. (2009) The post-modernist war on evidence-based practice. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*. 46(5), pp.740-748.
- Powers, J.G., Higham, C., Broussard, K., Phillips, T.J. (2016) Wound healing and treating wounds: Chronic wound care and management. *Journal of American Academy of Dermatology*. 74, pp. 607-625.
- Price, A., Zulkosky, K., White, K., Pretz, J. (2017) Accuracy of intuition in clinical decision-making among novice clinicians. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*. 73 (5), pp. 1147-1157

- Probst, S., Seppänen, S., Gerber, V., Gethin, G., Hopkins, A., Rimdeika, R. (2014) European Wound Management Association (EWMA) document: home care-wound care. *Journal of Wound Care*. 23(5), pp. S1-44.
- Purwins, S., Herberger, K., Debus, E.S., Rustenbach, S.J., Pelzer, P., Rabe, E., Stadler, R., Augustin, M. (2010) Cost-of-illness of chronic leg ulcers in Germany. *International Wound Journal*. 7, pp. 97–102.
- Pyett, P. M. (2003). Validation of qualitative research in the “real world”. *Qualitative Health Research*.13(8), pp.1170-1179.
- Qaddumi, J., Khawaldeh, A. (2014) Pressure ulcer prevention knowledge among Jordanian nurses: a cross- sectional study. *BioMed Central*. 13(6). Avail at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6955-13-6>. {Accessed 11th January 2017}.
- Quine, W.V.O. (1953) *From a logical point of view*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Radcliffe, M. (2000). Doctors and nurses: new game, same result. *British Medical Journal*. 320(7241), pp.1085.
- Richie, J., Lewis, J. (2009) *Qualitative Research Practice*. 2nd edn. London: Sage.
- Rivas, C. (2018). ‘Finding themes in qualitative data’ in C. Seale (eds.) *Researching Society and Culture*. 4th edn. pp. 429-453. London: Sage.
- Romero-Collado, A., Raurell-Torreda, M., Zabaleta-del-Olmo, E., Hons-Romero, E., Bertran-Noguer, C. (2014) Course Content Related to Chronic Wounds in Nursing Degree Programs in Spain. *Journal of Nursing Scholarship*. 47(1), pp. 51-61.
- Rorty, R. (1991) *Objectivity, relativism and truth*. Cambridge. Cambridge University Press.
- Roy, C. (2009) *The Roy Adaptation Model*. 3rd edn. Upper Saddle River: Pearson Education.
- Royal College of Nursing (2016) *The RCN Scotland contribution to the Chief Nursing Officer and send’s review of District Nursing*. Avail at: www.rcn.org.uk {Accessed 30th January 2018}.
- Roxå, T., Mårtensson, K. (2011) Improving university teaching through student feedback: a critical investigation. *Student Feedback*. pp. 61–79. Avail at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9781843345732500045> {Accessed 1/11/2017}.
- Ruzsa, G., Szeverenyi, C., Varga, K (2020) Person- and job-specific factors of intuitive decision-making in clinical practice: results of a sample survey among Hungarian physicians and nurses, *Health Psychology and Behavioural Medicine*. 8(1), pp.152-184, DOI: [10.1080/21642850.2020.1741372](https://doi.org/10.1080/21642850.2020.1741372)
- Samuirwi, R., Dowding, D. (2014) Nurses’ pressure ulcer related judgements and decisions in clinical practice: A systematic review. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*. 51, pp. 1667–1685.
- Samuirwi, R. (2010) Effects of education and experience on nurses’ value of ulcer prevention. *British Journal of Nursing (Tissue Viability Supplement)*. 19 (20), pp. S8-S18.
- Scala, E., Price, C., Day, J. (2016) An integrative review of engaging clinical nurses in nursing research. *Journal of Nurse Scholarship*. 48, pp. 423-430.

Scottish Government (2017) *The General Medical Services Contract in Scotland*. Edinburgh: Scottish Government.

Scottish Government (2016) *A National Clinical Strategy for Scotland*. Edinburgh: Scottish Government

Scottish Intercollegiate Guidelines Network (2010) *SIGN 120 Management of Chronic Venous Leg Ulcers*. Avail at: <https://www.nhstaysideadtc.scot.nhs.uk/wound%20Formulary/Pdf%20docs/sign120%202010.pdf> {Accessed 11th Nov. /2017}.

Seale, C. (1999) *The Quality of Qualitative Research*. Oxford: Blackwell

Sharp, K. (2010) 'What is Sociology?' in: Denny, E., Earle, S. (2010) (eds.) *Sociology for Nurses*. 2nd edn. Cambridge: Polity Press.

Shearer, J. (2015) Critique of nursing as caring theory aesthetic knowing and caring in online learning. *International Journal of Human Caring*.19(2), pp. 45-49.

Shepherd, C., Challenger, R. (2013) Revisiting paradigm(s) in management research: a rhetorical analysis of the paradigm wars. *International Journal of Management Reviews*. 15, pp. 225–244.

Shirley, D.A. Langan-Fox, J. (1996) Intuition: a review of the literature. *Psychological Reports*. 79, pp. 563-584.

Sibbald, R.G., Woo, K.Y., Krasner, D.L., Smart, H., Tariq, G., Ayello, E.A., Burrell, R.E., Keast, D.H., Mayer, D., Norton, L., Salicido, R. (2011) Special considerations in wound bed preparation 2011: an update. *Wound Healing Southern Africa*. 4 (2), pp. 55-72.

Simonetti, V., Comparcini, D., Flacco, M., Di Giovanni, P., Cicolini, G. (2015) Nursing students' knowledge on pressure ulcer prevention evidence-based guidelines: a multi-centre cross-sectional study. *Nurse Education Today*. 35(4), pp. 77-82.

Smith, S. (2012) Nurse Competence: A Concept Analysis. *International Journal of Nursing Knowledge*, 23(3), pp. 172-182.

Smith, J.A., Osborn, M. (2008) 'Interpretative phenomenological analysis' in: Smith, J. (eds) *Qualitative Psychology: a practical guide to research methods*. London: Sage.

Smith, A.J. (2006) Continued psychometric evaluation of an intuition instrument for nursing students. *Journal of Holistic Nursing*. 24; pp. 82-89.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0898010105280114>

Snape, D., Spencer, L. (2009) 'The foundations of qualitative research' in: Richie, J., Lewis, J. (eds.) (2009) *Qualitative Research Practice*. 2nd edn. London: Sage. pp.1-23.

Springer, R.A., Clinton, M.E. (2015) Doing Foucault: inquiring into nursing knowledge with Foucauldian discourse analysis. *Nursing Philosophy*. 16(2), pp. 87-97.

Sullivan, K. (2010) Theory and Methods in Qualitative Research. In: Forrester, M.A. (eds.) (2010) *Doing Qualitative Research in Psychology: a practical guide*. Sage: London. pp.-15-38.

Svavarsdottir, E., Signurdardottir, A.O., Konradsdottir, E., Stefansdottir, A., Sveinbjarnardottir, E.K, Ketilsdottir, A., Blondal, K., Jonsdottir, A. Bergs, D., Guðmundsdottir,

H. (2015) The process of translating family nursing knowledge into clinical practice. *Journal of Nursing Scholarship*. 47(1), pp. 5-15.

Stephen-Haynes, J. (2013) Preregistration nurses' views on the delivery of tissue viability. *British Journal of Nursing*. 22(Sup 20) Avail at: <https://doi.org/10.12968/bjon.2013.22.Sup20.S18> {Accessed 19th August 2019}/

Stephen-Haynes, J., Greenwood, M. (2011) Audit of tissue viability knowledge and practice among mental health nurses. *British Journal of Community Nursing*. 16 (Suppl 6). Avail at: <https://doi.org/10.12968/bjcn.2011.16.Sup6.S22>. {Accessed 1st November 2017}

Taylor, M., Flaherty, C. (2020) Nursing associate apprenticeship – a descriptive case study narrative of impact, innovation and quality improvement. *Higher Education and Work-Based Learning*. 10 (5), pp. 751-766.

Thompson, C. Adderley, U. (2014) Diagnostic and treatment decision making in community nurses faced with a patient with possible venous leg ulceration: A signal detection analysis *International Journal of Nursing Studies*. 52(1), pp. 325-333.

Tissue Viability Society (2018) *Legs Matter Coalition*. TVS

Tobin, G. A., Begley, C. M. (2004). Methodological rigour within a qualitative framework. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*. 48; pp. 388–396.

Trafford, V., Leshem, S. (2008) *Stepping Stones to Achieving your Doctorate*. Maidenhead: Open University Press.

Tubaishat, A., Aljezawi, M., Qadire, A. (2013) Nurses' attitudes and perceived barriers to pressure ulcer prevention in Jordan. *Journal of Wound Care*. 22(9). Avail at: <https://doi.org/10.12968/jowc.2013.22.9.490> {Accessed 22nd June 2019}.

Ullman, S. (2015) Knowledge Defined. *The Educated Brain*. Avail at: <https://theeducatedbrain.com/>. {Accessed 5th May 2017}.

United Kingdom Central Council (2001) *Standards for specialist education and practice*. London: UKCC.

University of the West of Scotland (2019) University Ethics Committee Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship. Avail at: <https://www.uws.ac.uk/media/5544/guidelines-for-ethical-practice-in-research-and-scholarship-refreshed-september-2019.pdf>. {Accessed 11th June 2021}.

Upton, D., Alexander R., Upton, P., Upton, R., Dunk A.M. (2015) The M-Strong APN Model as an effective framework for registered nurse training in tissue viability: An interpretative phenomenological analysis. *Wound Practice and Research*. 23(4), pp. 158-164.

Upton, D., Solowiej, K. (2010) Pain and stress as contributors to delayed wound healing. *Wound Practice and Research*. 18 (3), pp.114-122.

Voldbjerg, S.L., Gronkjaer, M.N.G., Sorensen, E.E., Hall, E.O.C. (2016) Newly graduated nurses' use of knowledge sources: a meta-ethnography. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*. 72(8), pp. 1751–1765.

Vowden, P., Vowden, K. (2016) The economic impact of hard-to-heal wounds: promoting practice change to address passivity in wound management. *Wounds International*. 7(2), 10-15.

- Wade, C. (2008). Perceived effects of specialty nurse certification: A review of the literature. *AORN Journal*. 89(1), pp.183–188, 190–192.
- White, R., Moore, Z., Ousey, K., Milne, J. (2015) Tissue viability nurses: discussing representation, education, medical, safety, legal and financial matters. *Wounds UK*. 11(2); pp. 14-18.
- White, R. (2008) Tissue viability in tomorrow's NHS. *Journal of Wound Care*. 17(30); pp. 97-99.
- Wilkinson, S. (2011) 'Analysing focus group data' n: Silverman, D. (eds.) *Qualitative Research*. 3rd edn. London: Sage.
- Williams, M., Burke, L. (2015) Doing learning knowing speaking: how beginning nursing students develop their identity as nurses. *Nursing Education Perspectives*. 36(1), pp.-50-52.
- Willis, S., Sutton. J. (2013) Managing complex palliative wounds: an interactive educational approach for district nurses. *International Journal of Palliative Nursing*. 19(9), pp. 457-462.
- Wooliams, M., Williams, K., Butcher, D., Pye. J. (2009) *Be More Critical! A Practical Guide for Health and Social Care Students*. Oxford: Oxford Brookes
- Yin, R. (2014) *Case Study Research, Design and Methods*. 5th edn. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Ylönen, M, Stolt, M, Leino-Kilpi, H, Suhonen, R. (2014) Nurses' knowledge about venous leg ulcer care: a literature review. *International Nursing Review*. 61(2), pp.194-202
- Zarachi, K., Latif, S., Haugaard, V.,B., Hjalager, I.R.C., Jemec, G.B.E (2014) Significant differences in nurses' knowledge of basic wound management - implications for treatment. *Acta Derm Venereol*. 94(4), pp. 403–407. Avail at: <http://docserver.ingentaconnect.com/deliver/connect/mjl/00015555/v94n4/s6.pdf?expires=1603721406&id=0000&titleid=75001721&checksum=8190EA0D8B97351846E58EDC1BD6BD A4> {Accessed 11th July 2019}
- Zhou, X., Hall, J.N. (2018) Mixed-methods papers in first person and third person: writing voices in dialogue. *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*. 12(3); pp. 344-357.

List of Appendices

Appendix 1: Table of Studies....	165
Appendix 2: UWS Research Approval Letter....	169
Appendix 3: Participant Information Sheet Specialist Nurses...	170
Appendix 4: Participant Information Sheet Generalist Nurses....	173
Appendix 5: Data Management Plan (DMP)...	176
Appendix 6: Data Management: Electronic Folder Pathways.....	180
Appendix 7: Risk Assessment....	181
Appendix 8: Participant Consent Form Specialist Nurses....	183
Appendix 9: Participant Consent Form Generalist Nurses....	185
Appendix 10: Semi Structured Interview Schedule....	187
Appendix 11: Sample Interview Transcript Specialist Nurse....	192
Appendix 12: Sample Interview Transcript Generalist Nurse....	206
Appendix 13: Sample Initial Participant Code Sweep Chart (Data Analysis) Specialist Nurse....	217
Appendix 14: Sample Initial Participant Code Sweep Chart (Data Analysis) Generalist Nurse....	273
Appendix 15: Sample Individual Code Chart (Data Analysis) Specialist Nurse...	304
Appendix 16: Sample Individual Code Chart (Data Analysis) Generalist Nurse....	307
Appendix 17: Collated Code Chart (Data Analysis) Specialist Nurses....	312
Appendix 18: Collated Code Chart (Data Analysis) Generalist Nurses...	315
Appendix 19: Example Mind Map (Data Analysis)....	317
Appendix 20: Braun and Clarke's (2006) 15-Point Checklist for Thematic Analysis...	318
Appendix 21: : Extracts from data- table of themes....	319
Appendix 22: Themes in the context of Chinn & Kramer's Patterns of Knowing....	323

Appendix 23: Dimensions for the development & utilisation of knowledge-examples from the context of wound management (adapted from Chinn & Kramer 2015)....327

Appendix 1: Table of Studies

Paper	Research
Wound Knowledge and Evidence	
1. Lamond and Farnell (1998)	The treatment of pressure sores: a comparison of novice and expert nurses' knowledge, information use and decision accuracy. <i>Journal of Advanced Nursing</i>
2. Edwards et al (2005)	A comparative study of nurses' wound management knowledge in two areas. <i>Journal of Community Nursing</i>
3. Dugdall and Watson (2009)	What is the relationship between nurses' attitude to evidence-based practice and the selection of wound care procedures? <i>Journal of Clinical Nursing</i>
4. Miyazaki et al. (2010)	Knowledge on pressure ulcer prevention among nursing professionals. <i>Revista Latino-Americana Enfermagem.</i>
5. Beeckman et al. (2011)	Knowledge and Attitudes of Nurses on Pressure Ulcer Prevention: A Cross-Sectional Multicenter Study in Belgian Hospitals. <i>Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing</i>
6. Stephen-Haynes and Greenwood (2011)	Audit of tissue viability knowledge and practice among mental health nurses. <i>British Journal of Community Nursing</i>
7. Cook (2011)	Wound assessment: exploring competency and current practice (UK) survey, 255 delegates
8. McClusky and McCarthy (2012)	Nurses' knowledge and competence in wound management. <i>Wounds UK.</i>
9. Cullen and Moore (2013)	An exploration of fourth-year undergraduate nurses' knowledge of and attitude towards pressure ulcer prevention. <i>Journal of Wound Care</i>
10. Ashton and Price (2013)	Survey comparing clinicians' wound healing knowledge and practice. <i>British Journal of Nursing.</i>
11. Tubaishat et al. (2013)	Nurses' attitudes and perceived barriers to pressure ulcer prevention in Jordan. <i>Journal of Wound Care</i>
12. Qaddumi and Khawaldeh (2014)	Pressure ulcer prevention knowledge among Jordanian nurses: a cross-sectional study. <i>BioMed Central</i>
13. Ferreira et al. (2014)	Knowledge and practice of nurses about care for patients with wounds. <i>Revista de Pesquisa: Cuidado É Fundamental Online</i>
14. Gillespie et al. (2014)	Wound care practices: a survey of acute care nurses. <i>Journal of Clinical Nursing</i>
15. Samuiriwo and Dowding (2014)	Nurses' pressure ulcer related judgements and decisions in clinical practice: A systematic review. <i>International Journal of Nursing Studies</i>
16. Thompson and Adderley (2014)	Diagnostic and treatment decision making in community nurses faced with a patient with possible venous leg ulceration: A signal detection analysis. <i>International Journal of Nursing Studies.</i>

17. Zarachi et al. (2014)	Significant differences in nurses' knowledge of basic wound management - implications for treatment. <i>Acta Derm Venereol</i>
18. Ylonen et al. (2014)	Nurses' knowledge about venous leg ulcer care: a literature review. <i>International Nursing Review</i> .
19. Simonetti et al. (2015)	Nursing students' knowledge on pressure ulcer prevention evidence-based guidelines: a multi-centre cross-sectional study. <i>Nurse Education Today</i>
20. Gillespie et al (2015)	Health professionals' decision-making in wound management: a grounded theory. <i>Journal of Advanced Nursing</i>
21. Gonzaga deFaria et al (2016)	Knowledge and practice of nurses on the care of wounds. <i>J Nurs UFPE</i>
22. Hughes (2016)	Wound infection: a knowledge deficit that needs addressing. <i>British Journal of Nursing</i>
23. Ousey Rippon and Stephenson (2016)	Barriers to wound debridement: results of an online survey. <i>Wounds UK</i> .
24. Deeth, and Grothier (2016)	Wound bed preparation: a survey of general nurses' understanding. <i>British Journal of Nursing</i> .
25. Etafa et al. (2018)	Nurses' attitude and perceived barriers to pressure ulcer prevention. <i>BioMed Central Nursing</i>
26. Cardoso et al. (2019)	The Nurses' Knowledge with Regards to Both Classification and Prevention of Pressure Injury. <i>Rev Fund Care Online</i>
27. Kielo et al (2019a)	Competence areas for registered nurses and podiatrists in chronic wound care, and their role in wound care practice. <i>Journal of Clinical Nursing</i>
28. Kielo et al (2019b)	Graduating student nurses' and student podiatrists' wound care competence: a cross-sectional study. <i>Journal of Wound Care</i>
29. Kielo et al. (2019c)	Graduating student nurses' and student podiatrists' wound care competence - An integrative literature review. <i>Nurse Education and Practice</i>
Wound Education	
1. Allison (1995)	The effect of continuing education on practical wound management. <i>Journal of Wound Care</i>
2. Samuiriwo (2010)	Effects of education and experience on nurses' value of ulcer prevention. <i>British Journal of Nursing</i>
3. Cowman et al. (2011)	An international eDeplhi study identifying the research and education priorities in wound management and tissue repair. <i>Journal of Clinical Nursing</i>
4. Moore and Clarke (2011)	A survey of the provision of education in wound management to undergraduate nursing students. <i>EWMA Journal</i>
5. Innes-Walker and Edwards (2013)	A wound management education and training needs analysis of health consumers and the relevant health workforce and stocktake of available education and training activities and resources. <i>Wound Practice and Research</i>
6. Ousey et al. (2013b)	Final year student nurses' experiences of wound care: an evaluation. <i>British Journal of Nursing</i>
7. Stephen-Haynes (2013)	Preregistration nurses' views on the delivery of tissue viability <i>British Journal of Nursing</i>

8. Romero-Collado et al. (2014)	Course Content Related to Chronic Wounds in Nursing Degree Programs in Spain. <i>Journal of Nursing Scholarship</i>
9. Hossein et al. (2015)	Pressure ulcers: how much do nursing students really know? <i>British Journal of Nursing</i>
10. Pieper et al. (2016)	A cross-sectional, descriptive, quality improvement project to assess undergraduate nursing students' clinical exposure to patients with wounds in an introductory nursing course. <i>Ostomy/Wound Management</i>
11. Holloway (2017)	The impact of postgraduate studies in wound healing on professional practice and personal development. <i>Wounds UK</i>
TVN/Specialist Role	
12. Flanagan (1998a)	The impact of change on the tissue viability nurse specialist: 1: <i>British Journal of Nursing</i>
13. Flanagan (1998b)	Factors influencing tissue viability nurse specialists in the UK: 2. <i>British Journal of Nursing</i>
14. Fox (2001)	Perceptions of tissue viability nurses of their current roles. <i>British Journal of Community Nursing</i>
15. Dutton et al. (2014)	The role of the wound care nurse: an integrative review (1980-2011) 37 papers not all research
16. Ousey et al. (2015)	Exploring the role of the Tissue Viability Nurse <i>Wounds UK</i>
17. Upton et al. (2015)	The M-Strong APN Model as an effective framework for registered nurse training in tissue viability: An interpretative phenomenological analysis. <i>Wound Practice and Research</i>
DN Wound Knowledge and Education	
18. Kennedy and Arundel (1998a & b)	District nurses' knowledge and practice of wound assessment: 1 & 2. <i>British Journal of Nursing</i>
19. Davies et al. (1999)	Research application: wound care in community practice. <i>Journal of Wound Care</i>
20. Haram et al. (2003)	The views of district nurses on their level of knowledge about the treatment of leg and foot ulcers. <i>Journal of Wound Ostomy and Continence Nursing</i>
21. Hjelm et al (2003)	Holism in community leg ulcer management: a comparison of nurses in Sweden and the UK. <i>British Journal of Community Nursing</i>
22. Barrett, Cassidy and Graham (2009)	National survey of Irish community nurses' leg ulcer management practices and knowledge. <i>Journal of Wound Care</i>
23. Friman Klang and Ebbskog (2011)	Wound care by district nurses at primary healthcare centres: a challenging task without authority or resources. <i>Scandinavian Journal of Caring Sciences</i>
24. Willis and Sutton (2013)	Managing complex palliative wounds: an interactive educational approach for district nurses. <i>International Journal of Palliative Nursing</i>
25. Adderley and Thompson (2014)	Community nurses' judgement for the management of venous leg ulceration: A judgement analysis. <i>International Journal of Nursing Studies</i>

26. Hallett et al. (2014)	Wound care in the community setting: clinical decision making in context. <i>Journal of Advanced Nursing</i>
27. Logan (2015)	Clinical judgment and decision-making in wound assessment and management: is experience enough? <i>British Journal of Community Nursing</i>
28. Gray et al 2019	What factors influence community wound care in the UK ? A focus group study using the Theoretical Domains Framework. <i>BMJ Open</i>
DN Role/Knowledge (Discussion)	
29. Kennedy (2004)	A typology of knowledge for district nursing assessment practice. <i>Journal of Advanced Nursing</i>
30. Bain (2015)	The Unique Knowing of District Nurses in Practice: Case Study
Industry	
31. Kessenich and Westbrook (1999)	Pharmaceutical companies and the prescriptive practices of nurse practitioners. <i>Journal of the American Academy of Nurse Practitioners</i>
32. Monaghan et al. (2003)	Student understanding of the relationship between the health professions and the pharmaceutical industry. <i>Teaching and Learning in Medicine</i>
33. Ashmore, Carver and Banks (2007).	Mental health nursing students' relationships with the pharmaceutical industry. <i>Nurse Education Today</i>
34. Crigger et al. (2009)	Nurse practitioners' perceptions and participation in pharmaceutical marketing. <i>Journal of Advanced Nursing</i>
35. Dumville Petherick and Cullum (2008)	When will I see you again? The fate of research findings from international wound care conferences. <i>International Wound Journal</i>
36. Dumville et al. (2009)	How is research evidence used to support claims made in advertisements for wound care products? <i>Journal of Clinical Nursing</i>
37. Madden (2012)	Alienating evidence-based medicine vs. innovative medical device marketing: A report on the evidence debate at a wounds conference. <i>Social Science and Medicine</i>

Appendix 2: UWS Research Ethic Approval

14/02/2019 (Dr Gordon Mackay, ethics co-chair)

Dear Lynn Welsh,

Your application 7846: A qualitative thematic analysis of patterns of knowing in the context of nurses' wound management practice: comparing TVNs (Tissue Viability Nurses) and District Nurses/ Community Staff Nurses (DNs/CS, submission reference 6259, has been approved, with conditions, by the Health and Life Sciences SEC. **You may proceed with your study provided you meet the conditions outlined below:**

Title	Comment
Where will the proposed research take place?	Change request: Please ensure that a fieldwork risk assessment is completed before the research begins. This is to cover any work completed off-campus.
Please explain/justify your intended sample size:	Change request: Please ensure that all access permissions are in place before your research begins.
Please upload a copy of the Questionnaire or Interview Schedule	Comment: This is a very comprehensive, well thought through interview schedule. Considering the number of questions, I would think there is a potential for the interview to well exceed an hour. Is there the opportunity for some of the descriptive questions to be provided in a written questionnaire or consider how to restructure your questions to reduce the number of question whilst enabling a rich discourse. Many of the questions are very descriptive which could potentially be included in a written questionnaire. I would also suggest that you consider using more open questions which may capture the same amount of rich data with a reduced number of questions.
Please upload a copy of the Questionnaire or Interview Schedule	Change request: A very comprehensive semi-structured interview plan. However, will this be achievable in a 45-60 minute interview- this could be very ambitious? would there be scope to reduce this to ensure quality or responses rather than quantity?
Please upload a copy of the Participant Information Sheet(s)	Change request: Please add 'No' to the start of the sentence for the statement- 'Do I have to take part' for both PIS.
Please upload a copy of your Consent Form(s)	Change request: Please instruct the participants to initial each box to consent rather than tick each box for both consent forms.
What measures will you put in place to ensure the confidentiality of personal data gathered during your study?	Please ensure that you have completed a privacy risk assessment before you begin your research. If you are a student then please work with your supervisory team to complete this. Guidance on completion of the privacy risk assessment can be found here: http://intranet.uws.ac.uk/department/CourtSenateOffice/foi/SitePages/PrivacyImpact.aspx If you have questions regarding completion of your privacy risk assessment please contact: dataprotection@uws.ac.uk

If you wish to make any significant changes to your study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr Gary Boyd

personal details withheld.

Appendix 3: Participant Information Sheet Specialist Nurses

Study Title

Patterns of Knowing in Wound Management: A Reflexive Thematic Analysis of Wound Management Specialists and Generalists

Researcher

Lynn Welsh [REDACTED]

personal details withheld.

Introduction

You are invited to participate in a research project that forms a part of the candidate's Professional Doctorate Programme. Please take time to read all information that has been provided carefully. If anything is unclear or you wish to ask any questions, please do not hesitate to contact the researcher at the email address listed above. You are under no obligation to take part. Should you agree to participate, you may withdraw at any time throughout the course of the study.

Thank you for your consideration to take part in this study. You have been approached because you are a member of NATVNS and currently employed as a Tissue Viability Nurse (TVN).

The purpose of this study

- To gain a deeper understanding of TVNs and DN/CSNs patterns of knowing within the context of wound management practice and make comparisons between the two groups;
- To determine whether any particular pattern(s) dominate and if so, what factors have contributed to this;
- To encourage participants to critically reflect upon their own knowledge and practice in the context of wound management
- To consider how patterns of knowing may link to outcomes and shape future wound management practice and education curriculums

What is involved in taking part?

You will be asked to participate in a one-off, semi-structured interview with a single researcher lasting approximately 45-60 minutes. The interview will take place at an agreed place and time immediately following a NATVNS meeting. During the interview, you will be asked to give open ended responses to questions and statements about your knowledge, education and use of evidence in everyday wound management practice. You will not be asked to provide any identifiable data and you will be allocated a participant code to ensure anonymity. The interview will be recorded using a hand-held audio recorder and hand written notes.

Benefits and Risks

There are no direct benefits involved in choosing to take part. The study has the potential benefit for participants to critically reflect and consider their own wound management knowledge and practice; thereby potentially improving wound management practice and education outcomes for TVNs and the wider nursing profession. It is hoped that findings will in turn, contribute to improved outcomes for patients living with a wound.

If you have any questions or concerns at any point throughout the duration of the study, please contact the researcher via email at the address at the top of the page.

If you do not wish to participate, there is no further action required. Thank you for taking the time to read this information sheet.

Appendix 4: Participant Information Sheet Generalist Nurses

Study Title

Patterns of Knowing in Wound Management: A Reflexive Thematic Analysis of Wound Management Specialists and Generalists

Researcher

Lynn Welsh

Personal details withheld.

Introduction

You are invited to participate in a research project that forms a part of the candidate's Professional Doctorate Programme. Please take time to read all information that has been provided carefully. If anything is unclear or you wish to ask any questions, please do not hesitate to contact the researcher at the email address listed above. You are under no obligation to take part. Should you agree to participate, you may withdraw at any time throughout the course of the study.

Thank you for your consideration to take part in this study. You have been approached because you are currently enrolled as a student on a DN SPQ Programme at UWS and are currently working as a Community Staff Nurse (CSN) in the community setting.

The purpose of this study

- To gain a deeper understanding of TVNs and DN/CSNs patterns of knowing within the context of wound management practice and make comparisons between the two groups;
- To determine whether any particular pattern(s) dominate and if so, what factors have contributed to this;
- To encourage participants to critically reflect upon their own knowledge and practice in the context of wound management
- To consider how patterns of knowing may link to outcomes and shape future wound management practice and education curriculums

What is involved in taking part?

You will be asked to participate in a one-off, semi-structured interview with a single researcher lasting approximately 45-60 minutes. The interview will take place at an agreed place and time at UWS Paisley Campus. During the interview, you will be asked to give open ended responses to questions and statements about your knowledge, education and use of evidence in everyday wound management practice. You will not be asked to provide any identifiable data and you will be allocated a participant code to ensure anonymity. The interview will be recorded using an encrypted hand-held audio recorder and hand written notes.

Benefits and Risks

There are no direct benefits involved in choosing to take part. The study has the potential benefit for participants to critically reflect and consider their own wound management knowledge and practice; thereby potentially improving wound management practice and education outcomes for DNs and Community Nurses and the wider nursing profession. It is hope that findings will in turn, contribute to improved outcomes for patients living with a wound.

If you do not wish to participate, there is no further action required. Thank you for taking the time to read this information sheet.

Appendix 5: Data Management Plan

Checklist	Guidance and questions to consider
ID	Student ID B00297630 IRAS Approval ID 262262
Funder	University of the West of Scotland
Project Name	Patterns of Knowing in Wound Management Amongst Specialist and Generalist Nurses: A Reflexive Thematic Analysis
Project Description	<p>A qualitative RTA examining nurses' wound management practice comparing specialist and generalist nurses. Wounds constitute a significant burden to service providers and users; yet the evidence base supporting practice and education is accepted to be weak. Given shortfalls in the formal evidence base, it would be of interest to determine nature of knowledge in generalist and specialist nurses. Research Questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the patterns of knowing for specialist and generalist nurses with key roles in the delivery of clinical and/or educational wound management and how has this been affected by the current wound management context? • Do any particular pattern(s) dominate and if so, what factors have contributed to this? • What comparisons can be made between specialist and generalist nurses? • What are implications of these findings for wound management practice and education? <p>The study will use semi-structured interviews (approx. 45-60 minutes) with 4-6 specialist nurses and 4-6 generalist nurses to explore wound management knowledge, using a well-known theoretical framework of nursing knowledge to structure questions. Generalist candidates will be recruited from the student body at the University of the West of Scotland and specialists will be recruited through membership of a relevant professional interest group. Interviews will take place at UWS and NHS health boards across Scotland. Themes from interviews will be generated and analysed using RTA.</p>
PI/Researcher	Lynn Welsh
Data Contact	AA
Related Policies	General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) 2018 UK Data Service Guidance Digital Curation Centre Checklist UWS Ethics Committee Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship NHS Health Research Authority (HRA) Qualitative Protocol Development Tool IRAS
Data Collection	
What data will you collect or create?	Recorded data from 10 x semi-structured interviews (45-90 minutes) with 5 x specialist and 5 x generalist nurses involved in wound management using hand held encrypted recorder. Recordings will be transferred to an encrypted electronic file program on the PI's computer so they can be repeatedly reviewed.

<p>How will the data be collected or created</p>	<p>All data will be transcribed verbatim by the PI. No data management software package or transcribing service will be utilised.</p> <p>Data transcription, collection, management and analysis will be simultaneous in line with RTA methodology and phases will overlap and merge.</p> <p>Electronic folders will be created headed <i>Data Collection</i> and <i>Data Analysis</i> and include further sub-folders headed <i>Specialists</i> and <i>Generalists</i>. Sub-folders for each participant within that group will then be created. Specific steps of collation and storage pathway as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recordings will be transferred to an encrypted electronic file software program and stored in a sub-folder headed <i>Interview Recordings</i> in the <i>Data Collection</i> folder • Transcription will occur as soon after interview as possible and stored in the individual participant's electronic sub-folder headed <i>Transcribed Interviews</i> in the <i>Data Collection</i> sub-folder • Each individual participant's transcribed interview will be populated into an <i>Initial Code Sweep Chart</i> electronic template framed by Chinn & Kramer's Patterns of Knowing where an initial code sweep will be completed. It will be stored in the individual participant's sub-folder within the <i>Data Analysis</i> sub-folder where it will be reviewed as many times as necessary to develop and finalise codes. • Codes will be collated in an <i>Individual Code Chart</i> electronic template framed by Chinn & Kramer's Patterns of Knowing. It will be stored in the individual participant's sub-folder within the <i>Data Analysis</i> folder where it will be reviewed as many times as necessary to develop and finalise codes. • Codes will be collated in a <i>Collated Generalist or Specialist Code Chart</i> electronic template framed by Chinn & Kramer's Patterns of Knowing. They will be stored in the <i>Data Analysis</i> folder where they will be reviewed as many times as necessary to develop and finalise codes and generate themes <p>Quality Assurance:</p> <p>All participants will be identified with codes to ensure anonymity. S=Specialist (i.e., S11, S12 etc.) and G=Generalist (i.e., G11, G12 etc.). Use of data from pilot interviews will be identified as SP or GP (i.e., SP11, GP11 etc.)</p> <p>Standardised semi-structured interview templates will be utilised for data collection to ensure consistency and reliability of approach; however, it is recognised in RTA that it is not necessary to ensure absolute consistency in approach. Version control of interview schedules will be initiated and recorded by the PI.</p> <p>Standardised templates for data analysis will be used to ensure consistency in sequence and approach (i.e., <i>Initial Code Table</i>, <i>Individual Code Table</i>, <i>Generalist or Specialist Code Table</i>).</p>
--	--

	<p>Version control of interview schedules will be initiated and recorded by the PI.</p> <p>A peer reviewer will review codes and themes prior to finalisation to ensure relevance and integrity and consistency of analytic claims</p>
Documentation	
What documentation will accompany the data?	Standardised templates for data analysis will be used to ensure consistency in sequence and approach (i.e., <i>Initial Code Table</i> , <i>Individual Code Table</i> , <i>Generalist</i> or <i>Specialist Code Table</i>). All data analysis tables will be kept to enable future interpretation and further study.
Ethics & Legal Compliance	
How will you manage any ethical issues?	<p>Ethical compliance in adherence with IRAS, NHS R& D and UWS Ethics Committee Guidelines. Full participant consent for participation was given including that for data preservation and sharing. A 2-x week cooling off period was provided and participants were advised they could withdraw at any point.</p> <p>All data was anonymised using codes to identify participants. All identifying information (i.e., employer, geographical location etc.) was removed from transcripts</p> <p>Although the study is unlikely to generate sensitive data, all data will be stored securely in encrypted electronic folders and transferred via secure email using encryption function accessed only by the PI and shared only with the supervisory team. All hard copies of data, documentation and information was stored in a folder in a locked cabinet accessible to and accessed by only the PI.</p>
How will you manage intellectual property rights (IPR) issues?	NA
Storage and Backup	
How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?	<p>All electronic data will be stored in duplicate on the PI's computer as back up. Hard copies will also be kept in files in a locked cabinet accessible only by the PI;</p> <p>The PI is responsible for all storage, back-up and recovery</p>
How will you manage access and security?	<p>Risks to data security low as it will be stored in electronic copy on the PI's encrypted computer with security software and accessed only by the PI. Hard copies will be stored in a locked cabinet accessible only to the PI</p> <p>Although the study is unlikely to generate sensitive data, all data was stored securely in encrypted electronic folders and transferred via secure email using encryption function accessed only by the PI and shared only with the supervisory team</p>
Selection and preservation	
Which data should be retained, shared and/or preserved?	<p>All data will be retained/destroyed for contractual, legal, or regulatory purposes for 3 years in accordance with UWS Ethics Committee Guidance</p> <p>If the data is used for future research, education and dissemination, specific requirements for data retention may be applied following consent</p> <p>All data will remain anonymised to ensure confidentiality</p>

What is the long-term preservation plan for the dataset?	All data will be stored in encrypted electronic folders in the PI's security-protected computer accessible only to the PI for 3 years If the data is used for future research, education and dissemination, specific requirements for data retention may be applied following consent
Data Sharing	
How will you share the data?	The data will not be shared with users out with the supervisory team. Sharing of data will be via UWS email using encryption function
Responsibilities and resources	
Who will be responsible for data management?	The PI is solely responsible for implementing the DMP, and ensuring it all activities are reviewed and revised
What resources will you require to deliver your plan?	Encrypted computer hard drive with security software Encrypted email function with secure account Locked cabinet and storage for hard copies

(Adapted from DCC. (2013). Checklist for a Data Management Plan. v.4.0. Edinburgh: Digital Curation Centre. {Available online: <http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/data-management-plans> }

Appendix 6: Data Management: Electronic Folder Pathways

Data Collection

Data Analysis

Appendix 7: Risk Assessment

Risk Assessment

Department/Unit Name: School of Health & Life Sciences	Department Risk Assessment No:
Assessed by: Lynn Welsh	Date of assessment: Dec 19 th 2018
Authorised by: Academic Supervisory Team	Date of reassessment: NA
<p>Description of work activity or process <i>including any equipment/methods/procedures put in place to control risk.</i></p> <p>The researcher will conduct semi-structured interviews with participants, both on UWS premises and on NHS premises. The researcher will let her academic supervisory team and/or named colleagues know where she is at all times and provide contact details should they need to make contact. This will include leaving UWS and arriving at external premises. A mobile phone will be carried at all times and any incidents reported in accordance with local protocol.</p> <p>As any interview settings out with UWS will be NHS premises, local risk protocol will be adhered to at all times. As all data collection will occur within office hours, there will be no lone working.</p>	

What are the individual hazards?	Who might be harmed and how?	What are you already doing?	Do you need to do anything else to manage this risk?	Risk Level? (See method)	Action by whom?	Action by when?	Done
Travel to and from interview venues	Interviewer/Researcher	Please see above.	Please see above	Low	Researcher/Interviewer	Before each interview	Yes

Give details of any significant residual risks identified above requiring controls and actions still required to reduce these risks. If no significant residual risks are identified, or if no reasonably practicable controls can be put in place, then this must be noted here.

For further information and to view example risk assessments go to <http://www.hse.gov.uk/risk/casestudies/>

Risk Assessment Method

In order to assess a risk associated to a hazard, two factors need to be considered:-

The possible severity of the outcome

Realistically, what is the worst likely outcome? This method defines three categories of severity:-

- **Slightly harmful**
- **Harmful**
- **Extremely harmful**

The likelihood of the outcome to occur

How likely is it that the severe outcome will occur? Three categories are defined:-

- **Highly unlikely**
- **Unlikely**
- **Likely**

Once those two factors are assessed, the matrix below can be used to determine the level of risk. This information can then be used to prioritise any control measures necessary to eliminate or reduce the risk to an acceptable level.

	Slightly Harmful	Harmful	Extremely Harmful
Likely	MEDIUM RISK	HIGH RISK	HIGH RISK
Unlikely	LOW RISK	MEDIUM RISK	HIGH RISK
Highly Unlikely	LOW RISK	LOW RISK	MEDIUM RISK

Appendix 8: Participant Consent Form Specialist Nurses

PATTERNS OF KNOWING IN WOUND MANAGEMENT
Participant Consent Form Group 1 TVNs Version 2.0 April 17th 2019

IRAS Project ID: 262262

Participant Consent Form Group 1: TVNs

Study Title

Patterns of knowing in the context of Nurses' wound management practice: a qualitative study comparing TVNs (Tissue Viability Nurses) and District Nurses/ Community Staff Nurses (DNs/CSNs)

Researcher

Lynn Welsh

Personal details withheld.

Please initial all boxes below if you wish to consent to take part in this study

I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet dated 01/02/19 for the above study and have been given the time and opportunity to ask questions about what is involved

I confirm that I have an understanding of what is expected during my participation in this study

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason.

I understand that any semi-structured interview I partake in will be recorded on an encrypted audio device

I confirm that I understand what will happen with the data from this study and that it may be shared in future educational sessions and in publication/conference proceedings

I confirm that that I understand that this study comprises part of the researcher's Professional Doctorate degree

I agree to take part in the above study

PATTERNS OF KNOWING IN WOUND MANAGEMENT
Participant Consent Form Group 1 TVNs Version 2.0 April 17th 2019

IRAS Project ID: 262262

Name of Participant

Date

Signature

Name of Researcher

Date

Signature

Thank for agreeing to take part in this study.

Participant Code (to be completed by the researcher)

Appendix 9: Participant Consent Form Generalist Nurses

PATTERNS OF KNOWING IN WOUND MANAGEMENT
Participant Consent Form Group 2 DNs/CSNs Version 2.0 April 17th 2019

IRAS Project ID: 262262

Participant Consent Form Group 2: DNs/CSNs

Study Title

Patterns of knowing in the context of Nurses' wound management practice: a qualitative study comparing TVNs (Tissue Viability Nurses) and District Nurses/ Community Staff Nurses (DNs/CSNs)

Researcher

Lynn Welsh

Personal details withheld.

Please initial all boxes below if you wish to consent to take part in this study

- I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet dated 01/02/19 for the above study and have been given the time and opportunity to ask questions about what is involved
- I confirm that I have an understanding of what is expected during my participation in this study
- I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason.
- I understand that any semi-structured interview I partake in will be recorded on an encrypted audio device
- I confirm that I understand what will happen with the data from this study and that it may be shared in future educational sessions and in publication/conference proceedings
- I confirm that that I understand that this study comprises part of the researcher's Professional Doctorate degree
- I agree to take part in the above study

PATTERNS OF KNOWING IN WOUND MANAGEMENT
Participant Consent Form Group 2 DNs/CSNs Version 2.0 April 17th 2019

IRAS Project ID: 262262

Name of Participant Date Signature

Name of Researcher Date Signature

Thank for agreeing to take part in this study.

Participant Code (to be completed by the researcher)

Appendix 10: Semi Structured Interview Schedule

PATTERNS OF KNOWING IN WOUND MANAGEMENT Version 1.0 20/02/2019

IRAS Project ID: 262262

Semi Structured Interview Schedule

Title: A qualitative thematic analysis of patterns of knowing in the context of nurses' wound management practice: comparing TVNs (Tissue Viability Nurses) and District Nurses/ Community Staff Nurses (DNs/CSNs).

Participant Code

Generic/Overview Questions

Can you describe where you think the knowledge you apply to wound management comes from?

Can you describe which types of knowledge you think are the most important in wound management practice?

Can you tell me about where or from whom have you have learned the most about what you know in wound management?

Can you describe what you feel about your own knowledge and educational preparation to carry out your current role in wound management?

Can tell me about what you think would improve current wound management practice?

Empiric Knowing

To what extent do you think your knowledge in wound management is scientific and evidence based? Can you give some examples about where it comes from? How important do you think this is? Do you encounter any challenges transferring this type of knowledge to practice?

To what extent do you bring any theoretical or conceptual knowledge to your wound management practice? Can you give me some examples about where it comes from? Do you encounter any challenges transferring this type of knowledge to practice?

Appendix 10: Semi Structured Interview Schedule, cont.

PATTERNS OF KNOWING IN WOUND MANAGEMENT Version 1.0 20/02/2019

Can you tell me about any formal or structured education you have had in wound management and who delivered it? Can you tell me if you about how sufficient you found it to be? Can you tell me about how strong you considered the evidence base supporting it to be?

Do you continue to access formal or structured wound management education? Who delivers it? Can you tell me about how strong you considered the evidence base supporting it to be?

Can you tell me about any guidelines or protocols you apply in wound management and where they come from? Can you tell me about how effective you consider them to be? Up to date? Visible? Utilised in practice?

Aesthetic Knowing

Can you describe any artistic skill or ability that you bring to your wound management practice?

Can you give some examples from practice where you take a creative approach to wound management?

Can you explain whether you consider wound management to be more of an art or more of a science?

Can you give some examples of how you might establish a meaningful connection with patients whilst carrying out wound management in practice? Can you give me some examples from experience?

Ethical Knowing

Can you tell me about how you try to ensure that your wound management practice is ethical? Can you give me some examples from your practice?

Appendix 10: Semi Structured Interview Schedule, cont.

PATTERNS OF KNOWING IN WOUND MANAGEMENT Version 1.0 20/02/2019

Can you explain how you know you are doing the right thing for the patient in wound management?

Can you tell me about any available guidance to support your ethical decision making in wound management (i.e. local policy?) How often would you refer to them? Can you give me some examples of situations where you might do so?

Can you tell about how you decide which treatments are best for particular patients and who gets what? In your experience, do some patients get more than others? Can you explain why you think this is? Can you tell me about how consider cost when you choose particular treatments/dressings?

Can you tell me about how ethical you think it is to engage with wound care industry (i.e. company reps) in wound management practice? Can you tell me about what role you see industry as having in wound management?

Can you describe a time when you experienced moral distress or value conflict whilst caring for a patient with a wound? How did you manage it?

Personal Knowing

Can you tell me about how much of your genuine "self" you feel you bring to your wound management practice? Can you give me some examples?

Can you describe ways in which your own personal experiences shape your wound management practice?

Can you explain how interaction and relationships with colleagues shape your wound management practice? Can you give some specific examples from practice?

*Can you describe your relationship with TVNs and other specialists in wound management practice? (for DNs/CSNs only).

Appendix 10: Semi Structured Interview Schedule, cont.

PATTERNS OF KNOWING IN WOUND MANAGEMENT Version 1.0 20/02/2019

*Can you describe your relationship with generalist nurses who you support in wound management practice? (for TVNs only)

Can you tell me about how much your intuition guides your wound management practice? Can you give some examples from practice? Can you tell me about how effective you think it has been?

Can you explain how much you consider deep personal reflection to be an important part of your wound management practice? Do you reflect regularly? If so how? (i.e. journal/diary)

Emancipatory Knowing

Can you describe anything you encounter in your clinical role that you think limits or restricts your ability to carry out wound management practice? In what way?

Can you explain how well organised you consider current wound management practice to be in the wider sense? How consistently resourced? How fair it is for all patients?

Can you explain which healthcare professionals you consider to have the most power and knowledge in current wound management practice? Can you tell me about why you think this is?

Can you tell me about any wider social, political or organisational factors that positively or negatively impact upon current wound management practice in the wider sense?

Can you tell me about any barriers you have encountered which have prevented you from undertaking appropriate wound management education? Can you tell me about why you think this is?

Summary Questions

Can you tell me about how well integrated you think the different types of knowledge you use in wound management practice are?

Appendix 10: Semi Structured Interview Schedule, cont.

PATTERNS OF KNOWING IN WOUND MANAGEMENT Version 1.0 20/02/2019

Can you tell me about what types of knowledge you consider to be of the most importance in wound management practice and why?

Appendix 11: Sample Interview Transcript Specialist Nurse

Transcription Interview Participant S11

I: Thank you so much for agreeing to participate and I'm just going to start off with a few wee generic questions before I get into the specific knowledge for each area; so, can you give me an overview of where you think the knowledge you apply to wound management actually comes from?

A11:....Right.....it comes from clinical experience based on years of looking at wounds; literature....um courses I've done in the past and modules and.....yeah.....and education I've had around it and post graduate and under graduate and I suppose comparing our more recent evidence with what we used to do 30 years ago when I started. So, I suppose you draw on all these....all these.....all these areas really I suppose but past experience is quite a big one for me as well as all the recent evidence because things go around in circles especially types of wounds because you look at it and think "I've seen that before" because it's all new

I: It's kind of typical of all nursing really isn't it?

A11: Yeah.....yeah....yeah

I: Ok so you've said a few places-experiential learning in practice, evidence and literature and formal education-they were the kind of 3 that you mentioned. Is there any one of those that you think is more important?

A11: Yeah. On reflection I think formal education is what has empowered me to be more confident and I think makes people respect you more than if you have a clinical qualification. Looking back, I think I can rationalise more since I've done my masters....you can rationalise better and you do think differently. And my colleagues have actually said to me "you do think differently XXXX" but it's the education, that's what helped I think

I: And do you think...when they you think differently is that critical? Or analytical?

A11: Yeah, I think I ask questions they might not have thought about. I don't know if it's me personally but I always come up with a question for the company or the person presenting and I have to go back and ask someone else to answer that question...so....um...I don't know if that's just me or what

I: And so, you've been fortunate enough that you've been able to access structured education in wound management education ...do you foresee any challenges; like was that a challenge for you or were you able and quite supported to do so?

A11: It was a big commitment but a personal commitment and I was lucky to get some financial help to fund my modules and my travels because I had to travel down to XXXX to do that but I don't think that's available for nurses now; it was only about 10 years ago or so but.....yeah. It helped but it was also a big personal commitment....study time and using your own hours to study....

I: Tell me about it

Appendix 11: Sample Interview Transcript Specialist Nurse, cont.

A11: (Laughs) but your kind of motivated to do it with your peers that you're studying with at the same time

I: And what about likes of not only you but other members of your team; is ongoing structured education or even CPD education easily accessible? Are there any challenges?

A11: Emmm.....(long pause) we're quite fortunate in that we're able to go to conferences and things like that...em.....we're not offered formal education by our employers...it's not really encouraged. I suppose if we were to ask then that might be different and I suppose we do our mandatory training but that might be about it. And that can be laborious enough to get through in itself and I don't know how good the learning is with that but I suppose conferences and study days from different sources would be what they could access

I: Yeah. Ok, so do you feel that you have been sufficiently educationally prepared to carry out your role in wound management?

A11: Yeah, but even now with all that experience you don't know all the answers but you know where to get them I suppose and you might know your limitations. You DO know your limitations (laughs)

I: Ok and would you say, with these different areas of knowledge and where you've built up knowledge, is there any one that you've learned more from than the others?

A11: Emmm....I suppose...do you mean like topics or science?

I: Well could be topics or could be just the sources themselves so it could be that your structured education is where you've got the most or it could be your colleagues....

A11: Ohhh..... you get a lot from essays and assignments but also from discussion groups with your peers which at universities can often happen....open discussions and learning from each other's experiences as well I suppose and comparisons

I: Ok and we'll go back into a wee bit more detail in learning from experience in colleagues but first I'm just going to on to talk about empiric knowing or scientific and technical or formal knowledge if you like...so to what extent do you think the wound management knowledge and that you apply in practice or access is scientific or evidence based?

A11: (Laughs) there's all a big debate about science and evidence base in wound care and having RCTs and everything else. But I suppose I have a passion for science and I love to learn about the micro circulation and micro science and biology and bacteria and organisms and linked with medicine as well, so that gives you the desire and motivation to look things up I suppose in different areas and learn from them

I: So, do you think a lot of nurses in wound management are like that? Or do you think that because you have a particular interest you go and look it up?

A11: I think nursing in general is linked to medical knowledge and science and I think a lot of people must have that passion and the more you learn the more you realise how little you know and the human body and medicine, it's just amazing and it motivates you to learn

Appendix 11: Sample Interview Transcript Specialist Nurse, cont.

because of how it regenerates and how the cells work and how the scientists identify all the different hormones and it's just all so incredibly amazing

I: I know as you said once you get in there you realise you could go in and learn about the microbiology and immunology or the physics; you know there is so much isn't there?

A11: Mmmhmm.

I: And what about the quality of the evidence that's available to us in wound management, how do you find that?

A11: Emmm. I think that's where you need critical thinking because most of the evidence that is supplied is industry based and biased and you've got to be able to critique it and ask the right questions and not just accept what you're given even if it might be an RCT but you need to be able to critique it and to ask those questions

I: Definitely. And you've mentioned RCTs a couple of times and I wonder how well suited do you think RCTs are in wound management as a form of evidence?

A11: Mmmm, yeah.....there's a lot of talk...a lot of discussions over that as well, I suppose in that a lot of wounds.....it's hard to do an RCT because a lot of the people we come across are complex, they've got complex medicines, they're not standard people...it's difficult to compare them because all wounds are unique

I: Hard to control?

A11: Hard to control yes, that's the word.

I: So, the contextual aspect of wound management makes it hard to do a proper RCT?

A11: Yeah, yeah. But I always like to know what's the science, what's the lab tests behind all these products and how they're thought to work. Linked to biology and everything else. Sometimes that isn't always so evident, how they actually work.

I: So, do you think there's room for both then? Like studies looking at more contextual knowledge? You know case studies, looking at individual patients

A11: Em proper independent studies, like my work at XXX (professional tissue viability association) and Prof XXXXX and her RCTs and working with surgeons, they're all working with the proper independent research and I think we need more of that. I think we need a bit of both and also your years of experience and qualitative as well

I: We'll take a bit more about engagement with industry further on in the ethical section but since we're talking about it do you think there's a role for industry in wound management?

A11: Definitely because I think....we wouldn't have a lot of things if it wasn't for wound management . There wouldn't be a lot of education; as long as we can keep the education and we can question it then I think we'd have a lot of.....well unfortunately we wouldn't have a lot of education if it wasn't for industry or training if it wasn't for industry. It's getting

Appendix 11: Sample Interview Transcript Specialist Nurse, cont.

that balance; you might be able to get some independent studies and XXX (professional tissue viability association) work

I: Ok and you mentioned structured education and the education that you have had : how good in general or how effective do you think structured education in wound management is for preparing you to fulfil your clinical role and the workforce if you like. Like at pre-reg level, do you think its efficient?

A11: I think you need to know anatomy and physiology and how that applies to wound care. I think we can't know how dressings work until you know the process of wound healing and how the different cells work at microcellular level; unless you know that then you don't know how the products work. You've got to know how wound healing takes places and you've got to know the basics and that's changing all the time

I: And in your experience, in your own experience if you can remember or in your experience with students do you find that the curriculum is sufficient?

A11: Its more exciting in education now, you've got more videos and...like when I was looking at bacteria we used to have a diagram but now you can actually see the bacteria, you can see the colour and the shape and from under an electron microscope and you can see it on the internet and its more accessible and all this wonderful science that we didn't have, we just had a textbook with some diagrams. Now we can actually see the cells and it's very exciting

I: So maybe technology has improved?

A11: Yeah and its really exciting and easier to understand.

I: That's a good point actually. I think you're the first person to mention it.

A11: I think it helps you to learn all the scientific stuff; cells growing and I actually just thought of that myself

I: Yeah, I suppose different people learn differently; so, some people are visual learners and they like to see a video so there's maybe more means

A11: Yeah when you see it you can see that it actually contracts the wound and the shape and you can see that that's what it does when you see the shape of the cell

I: Ok so we've talked a wee bit about formal evidence as in research evidence or literature and education. What are some of the other means of formal education; so, you know guidelines or protocols. How much do you access them or how accessible are they?

A11: I think we do need guidelines and...um....set criteria so we have standard practice and evidence-based practice. But I've got more experience and worked at national level; sometimes you can be quite disappointed with the production of national guidance. It's not quite as in depth as you might think. I don't necessarily agree with it but standards might be too lean if you like or not in depth enough

Appendix 11: Sample Interview Transcript Specialist Nurse, cont.

I: Yeah that's true. And sometimes they don't get the right people involved in developing them

A11: Well, I think for clinical practice guidance is quite important and we need clinicians on groups so that's quite important

I: So, do you see any barriers in the development of the barriers or do you see any barriers in their implementation? Like do you think staff use them?

A11: I think maybe that unless you embed them into education and unless you get down to their level then they're not going to access it they're just going to put it on the shelf and forget about it until they might have to refer to it and they're in a situation where they don't know and they use the wound and the SIGN Guidelines and you would refer to it. You need these things; you do need them.

I: What about tools, you know things like assessment tools or grading tools?

A11: (Interjects)...that can put the guidelines into practice and make it more accessible for the nurses but theres.....as long as they're valid and verified tools and not just bog standard or not verified. Not quantified or tested. That can often happen.

I: Ok, we'll move away from that. You said you like the science of things so you may not like this wee group of questions because this is more artistic, the aesthetics of what nurses bring to their practice. So, you think of any creativity or artistic skills that you bring to your wound management practice? Are they important?

A11: Yeah, I think liaison and rapport with staff and nurses and the MDT is important. I think delivery of education if you're delivering; how you deliver. Making it exciting and how you connect with your students or delegates. Trying to communicate with them so they can ask you questions

I: So, using creativity to build or enhance relationships?

A11: Yes. We should be good communicators anyway and we learn a lot from our patients when we actually communicate with our patients and gather their history, we get more experience and get them motivated in trying to change their.....the way they act with their lives sometimes . It's important that you know how to communicate. That you can listen and all that and be interesting (laughs).

I: Definitely. Anything else?

A11: I think communication is very important because our experience of doing e-clinic because the one person you cut out doing a wound assessment is the patient and you can learn so much from looking at your patient and their environment. You can walk in and see if they're distressed, if they're malnourished and if you've just got a wound, that doesn't tell me.....I can't palpate it, I can't smell it I can't know if it's painful

I: It's not very holistic is it?

A11: No. It's very frustrating (laughs)

Appendix 11: Sample Interview Transcript Specialist Nurse, cont.

I: I can imagine, I've never really been involved in e-clinics....

A11: (Interjects).....I mean the patient has a right to speak to a specialist.....also when I go out to assess rather than just looking at a photograph, I'm also critiquing the nurses and how they deliver the care and if I can help them improve that or learn about the environment that they're living in-if they can't get resources or dressing packs or whatever or if they're working in a particularly strong home environment I can't gather that from a photograph, it's really quite challenging

I: Is it all community you do? You're based in community?

A11: Yeah.

I: So, all the more important in your area because you're treating people in their own homes or environments

A11: Yeah. And you're relying on the 3rd person and you're not getting the patient's perspective. And they can learn a lot from me as well, and I from them, from ward sisters who've worked for years. You can learn a lot from them from looking and watching. We can't do that from a photograph.

I: I suppose the argument is that telehealth might be a good supplement but not replacement?

A11: Yeah.

I: Ok anything else creative that you would bring?

A11: Yeah well, you've got your personality. And probably if you're stressed or you're tired your artistic is going to be different isn't it? So, it depends on how you're feeling, how much workload. I don't know if that's the kind of thing you're looking for?

I: No, it's not what I'm looking for its what you give me (laughs). So, you mentioned communication and the importance of communication and maybe considering holistic factors and looking at more than the wound. They're all very good examples of what I'm asking but can you think of anything else you would do to ensure you establish a meaningful relationship with your patient?

A11: And to be honest with them and to act...if you say you're going to do something to act on it and do your best for them and be sure it pulls through.....(hesitates)

I: So, being reliable? Trustworthy?

A11: Yeah. And using your expertise to write reports to ensure they get the right mattress to make them comfortable, to get special purchase and rationalise the evidence before the patient and circumstances to help get the equipment they need. Having that specialist knowledge, you have what you need to articulate and communication skills written or otherwise to analyse

I: Almost negotiation?

Appendix 11: Sample Interview Transcript Specialist Nurse, cont.

A11: Yeah with the different services and different.....like community equipment storeyou know you need to be very diplomatic. To be the patient's advocate

I: Ok well we'll move away from aesthetic knowing onto ethical knowing now. So, can you give me any examples of how you know your wound management knowledge is ethical?

A11: Yeah, you have consent forms and photographs and your IT security and.....(long pause).....your NMC code of conduct and you always rely on those things. You look at the patient's holistic assessment which tells you their religion and beliefs and by talking to them you can find out what drives them and what motivates them and what their beliefs are.

I: What their needs are as an individual?

A11: Yeah. And what their goals are. And their goals are often very different than the practitioner's goals or my goals. But if you can get their goals you might be able to get the right treatment

I: So actually, you've kind of answered my next question which is how you assure your delivery of care is ethical or the patient has got the right thing they needed and that was a good example....finding out what their goal is.

A11: Yeah, my goal is often to make the wound smaller or heal it. But I had a man with a spinal injury a tetraplegic type condition and I asked "well what is *your* goal?" because he'd been on bed rest for months and months and months and he said "my goal is to see my 12-year-old son playing football in the park" and I said "well we can get you up for 2 hours on a Sunday to do that". Why should he have to stay in bed all that time for a wound that isn't properly going to heal anyway? You have to adapt things to their quality of life, don't you? My goal-the nurse's goal was to heal it or to prevent it from getting worse but his goal was to get up and go

I: To live his life

A11: Yeah and that's a human right. And sometimes you've got to be adaptive and weigh up.....and sometimes that decision has to be taken not by me but with the GP and everyone involved with the patient so that we can collectively make that decision because the onus and accountability isn't just on me because I don't know the patient that well when I come in but we as a team with the patient can decide what can sometimes help

I: And what about, you mentioned the NMC code; is there any other guidance, like ethical guidance that you are aware of to support you specifically in wound management

A11: Emmm.....European rights and.....(long pause) and.....religious.....(long pause)....I don't know.....there's probably.....there's lots of WHO, human rights policies, I don't know them by name

I: Universal rights to health care and all that stuff?

A11: Yeah

I: But maybe not specific to wound management, maybe more generic?

Appendix 11: Sample Interview Transcript Specialist Nurse, cont.

A11: Yeah, I'm not aware of any. Sometimes I read about wound products and what they're made of so that I'm aware of any religious products or.....say.....some hydrocolloids have pork, some have....or don't have animal derivatives so you can tell them that

I: Yeah or maybe people that are vegetarian or vegan and are quite strict about that kind of thing

A11: Yeah. They don't want to use an animal product to get the wound bed to heal.

I: Ok they're all really good examples, in fact they're good examples as well. How fair do you think wound management service delivery is? Do you think all patients get the same? Is it equitable do you think?

A11: If you compare it to other services.....no. I don't know if it's just me or what but it's often referred to as a Cinderella service. And it does seem.....I don't know if it's the culture or a particular health board or.....it doesn't seem to.....perhaps it's my fault for not pushing or maybe I'm not a leader but it's hard to get respect and be heard and to get resources

I: So, compared to other services you think maybe wound management is a bit disenfranchised?

A11: Definitely, yeah.

I: What about, do you think people get the same depending on where they come from?

A11: No, it's a bit of a postcode lottery I would say, its dependent on the clinician looking after you and their expertise. We have a formulary.....but then sometimes pharmacists will say "well you can't have this or you can't have that product because it's too expensive" even though it's on formulary. Distribution sometimes there's problems with distribution centres or products and it's not....it can't always be equitable. And sometimes there's limited resources because they can't access a specialist and sometimes, they don't know about products but you try and educate everybody

I: That's really helpful thanks. And you mentioned wound care industry before when we were talking about research or evidence and the potential for bias; but you also mentioned that you do think they have a role in wound management. So, I just wondered what your thoughts were on how ethical it is to engage with wound management industry?

A11: I think you can be ethical as long as you have strong guidance and rules and you teach nurses to be.....critical.....they're all very....nurses are very educated; they're very bright and a lot of them have been scientists or whatever nowadays so they can critique and they can ask questions so I think as long as you have standards of practice on what you can and can't do ethically

I: And do you think we do that well? Do you think we do have standards of practice?

A11: We do have standards and clinical guidance on industry and engagement with staff; that they only talk about products that are on formulary and they sign a contract.....(Pause)

I: So, we do really?

Appendix 11: Sample Interview Transcript Specialist Nurse, cont.

A11: Yeah. But nurses are professionals and they are educated people and they're responsible for their own practice and they can make decisions themselves. But I think it's good to have independent conferences because at the moment, there's a big drive towards industry-based education where industry used to put in money for a part or label individual conferences but now with the new APBI guidelines they're being driven to have their own study days or conferences which are biased and have product bias on their products and nurses are invited to go there free and it isn't what the ABPI guidelines intended, it's quite the opposite now and charities like the XXXX provide independent education and papers that are totally independent and unbiased are being penalised now because industry isn't supporting those charities but the guidelines weren't meant for that to happen

I: Yes, it's quite challenging now. Ok we're going to move away from ethical and we're going to look at personal knowing. So how much of your genuine self-do you think you bring to your wound management practice? Does that shape your knowledge in any way or is it you're a professional and that's it? So how much of you do *you* actually bring?

A11: Well, you're human and you will bring yourself to wound care. And even with the education and knowledge and experience and sometimes you get tired and you think "well I know my products really well" but you might think "oh, that's twice I've said that product today" So is it because it's in my mind or is it because I'm making a rationale judgement.....usually it is but.....I've said that quite a lot today (laughs).....is that me or is that my rational judgement or is it because I'm tired? So yeah you do bring yourself to it and you are influenced by people around you use rational reasons for your decisions

I: And do you bring any of your own experiences to wound management do you think?

A11: Ehhh....definitely. Your lifetime of experience and your different practice experience and who you've been taught by and who was in your career, who was influential and who was the type of person....it might be a doctor or it might be a sister on a ward or somebody in wound care or burns or.....so you learn from people who you think in high regard

I: Do you think you learn from people who you don't hold in high regard?

A11: Yes (laughs). You learn not what to do

I: Well, this actually leads me nicely to the next question. We talked about it earlier and you talked about how you do learn from colleagues in practice. How important do you think learning from colleagues and others is? Is that a big part of knowledge?

A11: I think it is. Yeah. I think we should do it more. I think in our group we don't really.....I think we should critique and talk and discuss each other's cases. Not just to critique but to learn from each other. Could we have done that better? Or even your notes or whatever, could they have been written better? There's always something you can learn from reflection isn't there? You can learn from each other because when you're....you're often making

Appendix 11: Sample Interview Transcript Specialist Nurse, cont.

those decisions on your own but it's not until maybe you can reflect those decisions with the team and get different perspective, the outcomes might have been different

I: So, is reflection something you would do in your practice?

A11: I think we should do it more and I think that's one way we do it is to look at our complex cases and discuss them and learn. Everybody learns. We can all learn from our history and our cases

I: And would you say that you do that with peers?

A11: No. No, I think that's where we could learn. But I think you do have to have a very open and private atmosphere. You know it has to be clear that we're here to learn and not to criticise or point the finger

I: What about self-reflection? Do you use any kinds of means looking at your practice?

A11: Yeah you tend to when you're coming up to revalidation (laughs). But in our mind and I'd love to sit down and do it in a journal every week and practically you don't do that but in your mind you think "well I did that but next time I'd do that differently" and I think it would be good if I did have the time to write it down but I think psychologically in your mind you do reflect on it. And now I'm mentoring a new member of staff and I'm calling on my experiences and relay them to her and you realise that you do reflect and you do that

I: So sometimes it's an ongoing thing but not structured?

A11: Yeah

I: Ok and just finally in the personal knowing section would you say that generally the colleagues that you share wound management practice, whether that be colleagues that go out to support or other TVNs or other specialists or medical colleagues would you say that your relationships are quite good?

A11: Yeah. My link nurse meetings are open to all so I'll say "can I bring my student?" and they'll say "yeah, yeah" because I've learned from students but we can all learn from one another and I always say that; we've all been students and we've all been there; we've all been newly qualified nurses, first job in the community, we've all done that so we can all learn from one another and that has quite an open feel about it. Because you can learn from the student. You can learn what background they've had and what challenges they've had. I had a student the other day who had a baby due during her placement and was putting her essays in ahead of time-her time management was fantastic. But you can learn from people, you can learn what's going on in universities and you can do that.

I: Ok so one more question in this section. Do you think intuition has a role in your wound management knowledge formation or do you use intuition at all in your practice?

A11: I think you do; I think as you become a more expert practitioner you do use a gut feeling; that's kind of novice to expert. You do have a gut feeling that that patient is not well you do know if this patient is septic just by looking at them or you often can tell something is

Appendix 11: Sample Interview Transcript Specialist Nurse, cont.

not quite right just looking at them and you often have a hypothesis you know “this hasn’t healed and it’s all bone and its really painful to touch and I know that could be osteomyelitis and we need to do a scan” and when they’ve done the scan they come back and say “oh XXXXX so you were right, that was osteomyelitis” so that was a gut....kind of a gut, you’ve

got all the evidence there and you put it together and so I think yeah it does play a part and I think that becomes more as you get more experienced

I: So, you think intuition is linked to experience?

A11: Yeah

I: Ok we’re going to move away from personal knowledge now and go to look at emancipatory knowledge which is all about the wider social cultural political and organisational factors and how they might impact on wound management knowledge. So, I think a good place to start is do you think there is anything in your practice that limits or restricts your ability to deliver wound management practice to the best that you would like?

A11: I think the motivation and support to learn in management maybe or your employer is lacking unless you’re really motivated or driven. And actually, the career structure within our organisations and limits.....it doesn’t encourage....there’s no career pathway for clinicians if you want to remain clinical and progress if you get to a Band 7. Particularly in Scotland, there’s nowhere that you can go, that’s you. So, there’s me with my masters as a Band 7 for 15 years and I’d love to do my independent prescriber ; that would be fantastic. I’d love to have done my PhD but there’s nothing to motivate you because there’s no career pathway, there’s no pay rise. I’ve got my masters; I’ve got my 7 and I haven’t had an increment in 15 years so for the first time in my career I’ve thought “what’s the point?” And I shouldn’t be thinking like that really but it’s the first time I’ve felt like that. And it’s not all about money but it’s about being valued. Being valued. It’s very hard talking about it. So, I’ve learned to cope with that, that it’s about job satisfaction. You get your job satisfaction and you get your positive feedback from you patients and staff and that’s what motivates you. I earn a living I can live on so that’s fine. At the end of the day in our organisation if I want to get promotion then I’d have to become a manager and leave clinical and that to me, I didn’t do all that education to become a manager in non-clinical. My education didn’t set me up for that anyway and it’s a shame because I think the 2030 vision is all about empowering nurses and they need a structure, they need a career pathway to be consultants or whatever but it isn’t there; they don’t exist in Scotland. They might down south but they don’t here

I: And a lot of them are also based on the ACP model , traditional medical model which is very different to how nursing has always been

A11: And I think I do work at consultant level ; because GPs, surgeons, they come to me for advice and I do operate at a high level and it is a consultant level because.....it is.

I: But you’re not valued or recognised at an organisational level for fulfilling that role?

A11: That is a culture as well, a local culture

Appendix 11: Sample Interview Transcript Specialist Nurse, cont.

I: I think it's actually quite widespread. Ok so you mentioned earlier about wound management being a postcode lottery and that it wasn't necessarily equitable; how well do you think we deliver wound management services at organisational level? Do you think it's well delivered or structured?

A11: No. I think it could be made a lot easier. There's lots of reasons of why it's not and I think to my service it is due to geographically; I means there's a lot of wounds but it's just because some staff don't want to change and they're influential and managers don't want to cause disruption so they pretend things aren't happening and they don't deal with things.....but.....yeah.....yeah we're not really valued. A high ranked nurse in our organisation basically said to me "XXXX you're masters means nothing . It means *nothing*" . And I thought "how can you say that?" I sweat blood to get it. You don't even know what my dissertation was about and this is somebody at the highest level. And I thought "you don't even want to know what you sent me on study leave for; you don't want to know what I learned", just totally dismissed. I think that culture would change as these people retire and new people, new lead nurses are coming along, they've got their masters, they've got their – they're educated, they've got rational thinking, they don't feel threatened. If they can survive long enough to get into managerial positions, I think they'd be better.

I: Yeah, I guess the way nursing is you've people sitting in senior management positions who don't have these qualifications and they feel threatened

A11: Yeah, they feel threatened.

I: Ok here's a wee bit of a loaded question for you. Which health care professionals, if any, do you think have the most power in wound management? And power can be interpreted any way you want.

A11: The most power is when you work collaboratively. When you work together. When I work with the physios and the OTs in posture management and we work together to relieve pressure to relieve pressure ulcers. So, when we work, I don't think one person has all the answers, one professional has all the answers. Our cases are so complex now we have to work collaboratively and that's when we're most powerful. It's the same with having organisations and societies; we're more powerful when we work collectively together.

I: Ok that's a really good answer, so you don't think even in the traditional sense, there's anyone clinician or one group that kind of has power?

A11: No because I think we can empower each other. For example, I have a link practice group and I have a podiatrist who has come forward and said "I want to learn to put compression on" so they're going to do the competencies and why not you know? I mean she goes to see the foot and then she says "I could put the compression on at the same time" and it saves the nurses coming back the next day or just a few minutes after

I: Makes sense

A11: Yeah! I mean we'd be in just as she'd gone out the door, wouldn't we? And it's about empowerment and teaching everybody how to do it

Appendix 11: Sample Interview Transcript Specialist Nurse, cont.

I: And can you think of any sort of wider social, political, organisational factors that have an impact on wound management? So, you mentioned the *Legs Matter* campaign and that might be a good example of an organisation recognising and raising awareness of the need to focus on the lower limb

A11: Yeah, my latest work with the tissue viability society as a trustee and volunteer, I've learned a lot about the power of media and the power of marketing and branding from our marketing people and it does make a big difference. And social media, the power of social media, you can connect with positions and have a personal touch on twitter and Facebook and that influences and draws people in and makes wound management more interesting and people kind of want to come and join you and so you can't beat marketing, although part of me thinks it's very superficial as well especially Facebook but it is a good way of communicating a message and its highly accessible to everybody and it brings professionals together

I: Yeah, I agree

A11: Yeah, it's good to tell people about things and students love it, young ones; tell them about study days and they whizz it around.

I: Yeah, I would agree; it's made quite a big impact. Ok and I suppose I've already asked you about your barriers in wound management education, I think we've kind of covered most things; so just a few wee summary questions then. You've talked about the different types of knowledge; so, we've gone through the whole model; how well integrated do you think all those types of knowledge are for you in your wound management practice? Do you think they kind of come together in a coherent fashion? Or do you still kind of think your evidence is separate from your personal knowledge or your ethical knowledge or does it just feel like one body of knowledge to you?

A11: It just feels like one body of knowledge because you're drawing on your experience all the time and.....yeah.....I shouldlooking back I should look up new knowledge more often and do more literature searches and things more than I have done recently and that could be something I could do better.....but you do tend to draw on your knowledge and access it and if you do want to know more

I: And when you mentioned earlier and you mentioned intuition and you mentioned that it was linked to experience; would that almost be a quick way of integrating knowledge and that forms your intuition because you're maybe subconsciously putting at the pieces together without even realising it

A11: Yeah....maybe I've done a similar case before or I've learned from that and that didn't work before but this did and I've learned this from education and it almost comes together before it reaches conscious reasoning. Yeah, I think that's true

I: Ok and just one final wee question; I'm sure you could give me a list of about a thousand things but if you could take one thing that would take precedence to change; what would you like to see change in wound management; if you could make a change that you think would

Appendix 11: Sample Interview Transcript Specialist Nurse, cont.

improve wound management knowledge and practice what would it be? Not necessarily you make the change but if you could see a change what would it be?

A11: Emm.....I think we should work more collaboratively; that's the way forward to work more collaboratively in teams and to pull our ideas and knowledge for the benefit of the patient really. I think for too long nursing has worked in silos and shut doors and "we work on our own" and I think we should open it up. We can influence it you know; wound care is so holistic....there's so many different factors, you need a team really, there's microbiologists, you need....I'd love to be able to work more with doctors and surgeons and yeah.....you could learn so much from one another

I: So maybe new inter-professional models of working? In *theory* I guess that's what we do but yeah in practice you're right I guess it doesn't always work like that

A11: As a specialist I work very much on my own and I call on the doctors when I need to but I don't work like I used to in hospital side by side and even a simple thing like an X-ray well they're fantastic nowadays but because I've been out of hospital for so long I don't get to see them so much and I could learn so much, so....yeah.....and scans.....we learn so much more than we do

I: So, more collaboration and inter-professional working? Which actually fits in very nicely to the agenda even at academic level we're encouraged that we should all be sharing. Ok well I don't have any more questions unless there's anything particular that you want to say

A11: It's been so interesting

I: Thanks so much I'm so glad. Thanks so much

Time: 55:57.48

Appendix 12: Sample Interview Transcript Generalist Nurse

Interview Transcription Participant B12

I: Ok so thank you for coming and I just want to start off with a few generic questions so the first thing I'd like to know is where do you think the knowledge you apply to wound management actually comes from?

B12:.....I.....think that its coming from....peers, learning on the job as you go, and also, TV sessions that we've provided in the community that builds up the of the new types of dressings that are available now.....as per specific wound management

I: Ok so are they like structured wound management education sessions that TV provide for you?

B12: They are, they're like....well they tend to be arranged through our team lead who will send us out a time, like a session that...uh....someone is coming in to teach us regarding....wound care

I: Ok, and a lot learning from peers then, in practice?

B12: Peers in practice yeah

I: And is that like other community nurses and DNs or is that people from other disciplines?

B12: No, it tends to be other community nurses, although I have done the leg ulcer course; so, leg ulcer management at the university

I: Ok so you've had structured education in wound management?

B12: Yes

I: Ok and see when you say "peers" are they maybe people that have done extra training? Or people that just have an interest in it?

B12: I think people that just have more of an interest in it or were able to share and reflect about what went well; what might have gone better for specific wounds and then what went better to see if that then works again

I: Ok so would you say that like learning from colleagues and experience is quite important in wound management?

B12: Yes definitely

I: Yeah?

B12: Yeah

I: Ok, brilliant thanks. And is there any particular type of knowledge in wound management that is more important than others? So that could mean a special area or it could mean something particular about wound management practice or it could mean the stuff you pick up from your colleagues as opposed to what you learn in education or vice versa?

Appendix 12: Sample Interview Transcript Generalist Nurse, cont.

B12: I think personally the leg ulcer management was a special interest that made me go and find out more to manage the leg wounds so that gave me more of an insight on inspection of the wound just sort of looking at it; at the time frame it's been over and then what to do next type of.....managementlike a leg ulcer care pathway, to follow that

I: Ok, good, good. And you've already mentioned your own educational preparation to carry out wound management; so, you've done a module in leg ulcer management at university; what about at pre-reg level; was there much in wound management

B12: Emm....no, I think that was definitely learning on the job; learning from colleagues and peers and....emmm...you mentor, whoever was taking you as a pre-reg student and what they taught you and what their wound management knowledge was as well....

I: Uh huh. Ok to what extent do you think your wound management practice is scientific or evidence based?

B12: I would like to think most of it....I would always look towards my guidelines and look towards the wound formulary for what's being used in practice for that wound....if I wasn't sure about a wound I would take further advice whether that would be via a TVN or I would do a referral to get more specialised advice.....I would also use...em....evidence-based practice and look up whatever....you know if I didn't know it I would try to find out

I: Ok, and like what kinds of sources would you go to for that?

B12: Probably the NICE Guidelines.....I would look online for any studies; if it was a particular surgical wound for example and I hadn't ...it wasn't healing, I'd be looking to see if there were any studies or research on what best would aid the healing in that; but probably I would think it would be the TVN, the nurse specialist that I would look towards

I: Right; ok so probably a mix between research evidence, guidelines and protocols and also maybe specialists that you would draw on their knowledge.

B12: Yep.

I: Ok that's good, that's interesting and um do you get much opportunity in your day-to-day job to do any CPD in wound management?

B12:.....Emmmm.....I guess not specifically wound management because we're so busy doing different tasks as you know you're a multi-tasker but eh....the only structured approach I would say is if the team lead has made a point of organising a session, a teaching session of some kind; otherwise it's through reflection and discussion with the team if you've come across a wound that's not healing you would run it by your colleagues and discuss it to see if they see it improving or getting worse or perhaps draw on what they think has worked for them in the past for a similar type of wound

I: So is that....do you think that's quite a good learning tool, learning from colleagues and running a day-to-day thing by day to day....

Appendix 12: Sample Interview Transcript Generalist Nurse, cont.

B12: Definitely yeah....that reflection aspect of it or looking at your wound assessment process on CNIS and looking back to see what your colleagues done before and looking at your wound chart and seeing if things are improving and if they're not improving *why* are they not improving and just sort of having a re-think about that

I: Mmm hmm, ok and so you've mentioned your structured wound assessment tools and you've mentioned your SIGN and NICE Guidelines; are there any other structured protocols or tools that you would use or are familiar with in practice for wounds?

B12: I'm just thinking of the tools that we use in the sense of TIME and you know, looking at the appearance of the wound...eh...I can't think of anything else specific in practice apart from the wound assessment charts....and eh.....leg ulcer care pathways.....I think they're the two main ones we'd look towards to see if something is improving or getting worse and you're looking at.....the appearance of the wound and how long have they had it and is the discharge getting worse, is the odour getting worse, is what we're using on it working or do we need to re-think. We tend to be going towards the two-week challenge as well and not just staying on the same dressing and looking to review that more regular than perhaps what's been happening before

I: Mmm hmm. So maybe trying to review in a more structured way?

B12: Yeah

I: And being more conscious of and re-evaluating and changing?

B12: Yep. I'd say that's definitely got better and that certainly seems to have filtered through from TV....and....we're putting that more into practice now

I: Good, no, that's really helpful, thanks. And emm, you'll probably think this is a kind of strange question but can you think of any artistic abilities that you would bring to wound management or do you use a creative approach at all?

B12: Emmm....I think it's looking at the holistic type approach where you're looking at all the other reasons why this wound isn't healing, what else is going on with the patient-their nutritional status; emm...their mobility all the different aspects of pressure that could be affecting as it as just opposed to it being a wound on its own

I: So, like putting all the pieces together?

B12: Yeah

I: And do you think there's a creative element to that?

BI12: It's like putting a puzzle together and trying to solve it if you like; perhaps trying to get to the root of why are we not improving this or what's caused it in the first place, can we not prevent that from happening again and try and promote the wound healing

I: Ok and do you think that a.....is that maybe a nursing in general thing that you would do in other areas or is that something you'd only do in wound management?B12: no, I think in all areas is to look holistically at what's contributing....factors to what you're presented with

Appendix 12: Sample Interview Transcript Generalist Nurse, cont.

I: Ok, that's interesting as well. And can you describe whether you think wound management is an art? Or a science? Or do you think its maybe.....both?

B12: Probably a bit of both; I would think more scientific in the sense of the actual tissue and the structure of the wound, the structure of the healing process would be more scientific...emmm. But I suppose it could be in the artistic sense is that you are looking at the whole puzzle you're looking at the whole picture of promoting wound care in some way

I: And what about like, do you think technical skill, do you ever have to be creative in the actual technical management of a wound do you think?

B12: Yeah I think so; particularly perhaps if you're taking sutures out or removing clips is the emm.....thinking to yourself how the wound appears and if you were going to remove intermittent clips is the wound going to stay sealed; are you going to cause de-hisence or...at any point so you have to just use that clinical knowledge and skill to determine whether all the clips can come out or perhaps you have to just do that intermittently or are you going to leave one in....so you're using your own ..emmm....clinical judgement

I: Ok good thanks. And you've sort of alluded to this but can you give me examples of how you would establish a meaningful relationship and connection with patients during wound management practice? So, you'd kind of mentioned like putting all the pieces together which sort of ties into it but emm....can you give examples of how you would maybe do that with a patient?

B12: Emmm....I'm think more of the sort of leg ulcer management...I think that re-occurrence can be an issue and its education for the patient on a...and trying to promote concordance with the whole pathway in a sense of....that we can't...if the ulcer has appeared we go down that whole pathway but we continue on the pathway and continue on the compression hosiery and the importance of it; I think it's just reiterating and...and.. patient education but also listening to the factors that they're telling you....why it keeps re-occurring because there could be a simple reason but there could be chronic reasons....why....the wound isn't going to heal or what's affecting the healing

I: So, kind of looking at the bigger picture for that person rather than just think of one size fits all?

B12: Yeah, and individual...approach to that one person...yeah

I: So, would you say you take an individualised approach then?

B12: Yes, definitely

I: Can you give me examples of how you try to ensure that your wound management is ethical?

B12: ...Well.....consent....emm...that the patient comes on board with the care plan and is involved with the care plan...with the wound if you're giving them enough information about the wound; why you're using the dressing that you're using...its perhaps that you can justify through evidence that this works then I think an informed approach

Appendix 12: Sample Interview Transcript Generalist Nurse, cont.

I: Yep, so getting informed consent?

B12: Yeah

I: Anything else that you think is important in terms of trying to ensure you're ethical in your wound management practice?

B12:....Emm....I think probably back to that...the individualised....although we look at repetition in some sense....em...in one sense...you could look at a wound and thing "I've seen that before and I know that I used whatever product on it and that that worked; but it's not just going ahead but it's not just using that again; its looking at the individual person and taking in all the other factors ...eh....I can't think of anything else

I: No that's fine, there no right or wrong answers. And can you explain how you decide which patients get which particular treatments and do you think where you work its equitable across the board and does everyone get more or less the same and do you find maybe some patients get more than others and if so, can you tell me any reasons why?

B12:...Emmm...I would like to say that in the area I work it is equitable; however I think it's just human nature that some patients do get more than others in the sense that some have.....a big pile of dressings, bandages.....that perhaps...I'm not saying that they don't need them....it's just that that cost for that person is required....whereas for someone else its perhaps...not required...you can make it more cost effective by using a lesser amount of product so I would like to say that I don't think there's any barriers to someone having a specific treatment, say for example an expensive treatment like a xxxx; if that patient needs it I would like to say that they could definitely have it

I: So, if there any deviations it's not based on any other reason than patient need?

B12: Yeah

I: Some people just need more than others?

B12: Yeah...I would say so. From my experience anyway....there's never been a time that I've thought that a patient needs it but they can't have it because there's a barrier of some kind

I: Ok can you tell me how ethical you think it is to engage with wound care industry in your wound management practice? Do you think they have a role?

B12: I think they do have a role and I certainly miss that we don't have that any more....I think that theytheir knowledge on their products is very good.....personally but also a lot of my colleagues and I feel we can make our own decision on the products; we wouldn't be unduly influenced by one particular rep who's nicer than the other....I'd like to think that we can make our clinical decision based on what that individual wound needs as opposed to what product we've been sold

I: So, if they had a role than you would be quite confident that you and your colleagues would behave ethically with them and vice versa?

Appendix 12: Sample Interview Transcript Generalist Nurse, cont.

B12: Yeah.....yes, I believe that we did for many years prior; I don't think that the sales aspect of their job is so strong that it would influence you hugely but I do think that they have got a lot to offer in their knowledge and for our knowledge of what is new on the market....what is coming to formulary; you know what alternatives have they got?

I: So, like with their products and maybe how to use some of their products?

B12: Yeah, sometimes just the simple application of a product can be demonstrated through the industry reps which can be...I'm everyone at some point can think " oh gosh, I didn't know that.....even if it's just a small piece of information

I: And is that just something that you're maybe not able to do now in your clinical area?

B12: Yeah, that's not encouraged now at all

I: Ok, that's good thanks. And again, you're going probably not like this question or you may find it a wee bit hard to answer but how much of your genuine self do you bring to wound management practice? Or do you bring any of your actual self to wound management practice do you think?

B12: Emmm...I think you bring your reflective knowledge that's in yourself to a particular wound....a bit like that slight repetition in the sense that you've seen something before or you look at a leg ulcer and you think "that looks venous or it looks arterial"...I think you bring that...that's in you, that's a part of yourself...emm....but I'd like to think that I also use all my professional skills and make it individual for that person for that time

I: So, when you said you bring yourself, did you mean, was that like your experience....so you bring your previous experience to the patient?

B12: Yeah, and also, I suppose that ...eh....that sort of special interest as well and that particular interest....in leg ulcers, that's a particular interest; you're going to bring that more than perhaps, someone who doesn't have that interest

I: Yeah, definitely. And do you think that any of your personal experiences have shaped any of your wound management practice?

B12: Yeah definitely, yeah...I think that if you go out to seek the knowledge then you've got that personal interest to seek that knowledge and I'm quite happy to talk about that with any...or share it with staff who come to ask if.....that knowledge that came through your professional experience but also through an academic module then you've gone and learned more about that particular area and.....I think that that's important that you've got to seek it out as well.....seek the knowledge out. But I think we've got to in community, I don't think there's an option not to because there's too many wounds that to have a level of knowledge is ...accepted.

I: Mmm hmm. So, you'll pull that from different sources?

B12: Yeah....yeah

Appendix 12: Sample Interview Transcript Generalist Nurse, cont.

I: Ok and you'd already talked a little bit about this earlier as well but can you describe how your relationship with colleagues influences your wound management practice or your interaction shapes your wound management practice? You mentioned earlier that you found it useful to chat about things or problem solve with colleagues or whatever; so even tell me a wee bit more about that or other ways like, do you think your relationships with colleagues are important in wound management?

B12: Yeah absolutely...we can document as much as we can in our own notes and on our clinical summaries and our wound management tools and leg ulcer pathways but the discussion aspect with perhaps the same team that are looking after that person brings up a whole different view point and for caseload management just to review that patient; we're not promoting that healing; if we're not getting there then why are we not; we can go back to the drawing board almost, with each other to say "well we've tried this; let's look back at the care plans; we tried...what's worked and then what's not worked and definitely....."

I: So, it might be moreand I don't want to put words in your mouth so tell me whether I am picking this up right...so reflecting in an individual patient's point of view might be more useful rather than in the more generic sense? Maybe less about Clinical Guidance and Care Summaries and more about the individual patient?

B12: Yeah, about the individual patient. What's contributing to that particular patient's circumstances that we're not...or we *are*...because things are going well so or things are not going well for that particular person for other reasons

I: Yeah because it's not always about what's going wrong is it? It's about talking about how things are going well

B12: Yeah, using that product and that's going really really well and we should continue with it

I: That's great; that's really good. Emm can you describe a wee bit more about your relationships with TVNs and other specialists that you might involve in patients care? Would you say your relationship is quite good?

B12: Yeah I would say particularly in the area I know the TVN personally and I can contact at any point; do a referral form if I have to and draw on their knowledge even if it's just a bit of advice; just to run something by them I'd say that that's quite accessible....I don't work with them every single day but I'd say that that point of contact is available

I: And would you say it's quite a good....it's quite a supportive relationship or good supportive service?

B12: Yeah, I would definitely

I: Ok good...and a couple of times you've mentioned reflection and the importance of reflection in your wound management; so, you kind of talked about reflecting with colleagues; emmm would you say reflection is a pretty big part of your wound management practice?

Appendix 12: Sample Interview Transcript Generalist Nurse, cont.

B12: Yes, I think definitely....you're going to your starting point and each time you see your patient you're going back to....compare.....what's...what's... improving, again whether that's time or size-wise or your diameters of your wound what...you're reflecting all the time; you're looking at your wound to see what's going well and what's not going well to make your onward decision

I: And would that be something you do either with colleagues as you just mentioned or in your own head or would you use any tools or do anything structured with reflection?

B12: I think both but I would use...you can use structured as well, I've used wound management in my own reflections for my re-validation and emm...focused on the good ones to be honest (laughs) but yeah...yeah because it just demonstrates that your knowledge is improving all the time

I: So that's good so you've actually used both informal reflection with colleagues but also structured reflection for your validation as well

B12: Yeah, yeah, I suppose it's such a big part of our role then it's always too good to know that what we're putting in practice is...is *working* and perhaps what's not. I think that over the years that I've been doing this with the TV, you're almost kind of pre-empting what you would be putting in place....so your planning and using your wound.....management and your wound formulary to use what they regularly use in the hope to try to get to that point sooner

I: That's really helpful, we don't have that much to go, so can you describe anything in your clinical practice that restricts or limits your ability to carry out wound management practice to the best of your ability? Is there anything you think is a barrier to good wound management practice?

B12: I think....well the formulary...you're restricted in your formulary but I wouldn't say overly or I wouldn't necessarily see it as a major barrier....em...I think if you can justify why you're going off formulary for that particular individual patient then I think if you've got a rationale for that then that's....that can...there no barriers in the sense of the management structure to say that you can't do that. I think if you have a good rationale and evidence base for why you do something then no one else can really argue that point....who's going to benefit? A patient

I: Ok what about like other factors, sort of wider or more generic factors that might impact on....

B12 (Interrupts)....I think that maybe with working in the community its people at home and they're in their own homes and I guess it's the environment that they live in.....it could be....personal care; they might be struggling with that-perhaps you need to address that. It could just be that their living environment could be causing the wound not to heal in whatever way and it could be that their diet and nutrition and so on all their other environmental and social factors can contribute and that is a barrier and I guess that's patient choice as well ...that if they choose not to continue with the treatment that you're recommending, then that's a barrier for consent, isn't it?

Appendix 12: Sample Interview Transcript Generalist Nurse, cont.

I: So sometimes maybe patient non-compliance then with treatment or not wanting to do something that you think might be best for them or whatever?

B12: Yeah and the classic of that is your leg ulcer management when you get to that healed end-point and then, non-concordance with the hosiery as a preventative measure and then you can perhaps go around in that cycle again

I: Ok what about barriers in the kind of wider organisational side of things; like maybe things more related to the clinical role?

B12: Emm....I guess time constraints...when you're out and you've got a lot of visits to get round you've only got so much time....emmm.....perhaps if someone is to get a pomegranate soak for example, like how long have you actually got to deal with all of that and then deal with bilateral legs and deal with wound care then time constraints can be difficult

I: And lots of visits to different patients and things. And again, this might sound like a bit of a strange question but can you think of any particular health care professional or professionals that have the most power in wound management practice? Do you think any particular clinician or type of clinician has the most power?

B12: Emmm.....

I: And it could be good power, bad power

B12: I think perhaps emm...good power would be the sense that the TVNs are very focused on that particular...skin, wound care issues and that's their main focus and therefore they have more time to spend on that whereas we're looking at all other aspects and we're dealing with a lot of other different skills I suppose you're...you're trying to hone all different types of skills whereas perhaps their whole job role...eh...position is to improve skin and wound care...I guess that gives them slightly the upper hand

I: Cos they have more time to learn about it or spend time on it where you're more kind of pulled in different directions?

B12: Yeah absolutely.

I: Ok and em is there anything in practice that has prevented you from undertaking any wound management education that you'd like to take or you mentioned that you've been able to do the leg ulcer course which is good but

B12: No, I've been able to do that and if anything, its encouraged to do that...emmm...as always it would be nice to have more sessions that we can go over things and learn from your colleagues in these group sessions...it's always good to recap in your knowledge, I would never be against that and I'm always keen to learn something new. There are always new products coming out so if we can get as much as we can then...offered knowledge on that then I would be keen.

Appendix 12: Sample Interview Transcript Generalist Nurse, cont.

I: Ok that's good...how well organised do you think wound management is in the kind of wider sense; like how well organised do you think wound management service are? Do you think they're well resourced? Consistently resourced across different areas? You know, accessible to all patients?

B12: It difficult to comment on other areas but in the two community areas I worked in I would say yes, there are time constraints if you're looking for the TVN to meet with you at a patient to do a combined assessment to assess a wound then that could be time constraints on that might delay...perhaps delay the provision of a specific treatment or someone else's viewpoint on the management of that wound ...emm.....I don't know if there's anything else I can think of or come across personally

I: Uh huh, so if you were a patient with a wound would you be quite confident with the services that were available to support you?

B12: Yeah I think so, certainly in the sense of within the teams I work in if there was a wound that was particularly concerning they would be there the next day; I don't think there would be any further delay on that, there's even a 24-hour service; if there was something particularly bad, you always have access to the 24-hour service if need be

I: So, it sounds as though it's quite good; a good service

B12: Yeah, I would say so

I: Ok just a couple of wee summary questions then and that's us finished. You've talked a lot today about different types of knowledge that you've used so you talked about evidence and protocols and policies in practice and things like that, experience that you learn. What about, do you think intuition plays a role at all?

B12: I think it *does*; I think perhaps subconsciously it's there; I don't know that I'd draw on it all the time but I think....yeah there will be some ..."I know why that is" or "I know why that's happened" or "I've got a feeling that that's going to get worse and we need to do something". Do you mean in that sense?

I: Yeah basically. I suppose that is what I mean. I suppose what I'm trying to say is that it might not always be the type of knowledge you can explain in a kind of structured way but just you like you said, you sometimes just know or have a feeling

B12: Yeah and I think that does then come from your clinical judgement in the sense that if you were looking for a more specialised assessment of that, whether it be TV or dermatology or whatever then you know it's got to be a more urgent referral ; you know you've a feeling with the whole patient it's something that's going to go not so well for them then you'd want something more urgent; you'd be looking for that to be dealt with more urgently

I: I totally get that. And so, in talking about all these different types of knowledge how well integrated do you think these are for you; so, like how well integrated when you go to wound management-do you draw on your science, draw on your experience; things with colleagues, specialist support? Do you consider them all separate or do you think they all come together coherently?

Appendix 12: Sample Interview Transcript Generalist Nurse, cont.

B12: I think they all come together but I think they probably are ...separate in that you seek them out separately....em....yeah...I don't know that it's all drawn together, I'm trying to think of when I first became a community staff nurse; I don't think there was a package of "this is wound care and this is all of the aspects that you need to know about"

I: Wouldn't it be nice if there was?

B12: Wouldn't it be nice? But I would say that is probably something you learn as you go along when you draw them all together over a period of time

I: Ok good and just.....if there was one thing that you could maybe improve about wound management in general; what do you think you would want to focus on?

B12: Emmm.....perhaps something like that...a more sort of generic, integrated, all working from the same hymn sheet if you like that..emm....I....I guess it is there in some sense that we have got our wound assessment tool, we have our leg ulcer care pathway but how each professional uses it is slightly different...some in more depth and others just skim over the surface of it and that's perhaps a more individual staffing level thing

I: Yeah so maybe people not utilising the tools consistently rather than...the tools are available but maybe some people or some areas use them differently or ...

B12: Yeah and I know certainly in the team leads sense that is more streamlined and it's been audited that if you're not using wound assessment why are you not using it; you know why is there not a wound assessment for that patient and you would need to give a really good reason why not.

I: So, it is kind of monitored and audited and quality checked to improve services so that's good

B12: So, I suppose I would like to see that more, that we're all doing the same...emm...it's not one particular member of a team that's making sure all these things are in place, everyone has the same responsibilities

I: That's great that's really really helpful so unless there is anything else that you pressingly want to say that's us finished so thank you very much that was good.

Time: 37:08.720

Appendix 13: Sample Initial Coding Sweep Chart (Data Analysis) Specialist Nurse

Data Analysis S14 Free Text Analysis	Transcript	Codes
<p>Knowledge in General</p> <p>Wound management knowledge comes from multiple sources</p> <p>Experiential knowledge that develops over time</p> <p>RICH</p> <p>Range of clinical experience broadens knowledge</p> <p>Asking questions and individual seeking</p>	<p>I: Ok thank you very much for participating today and I'm just going to start off before I get into the framed questions by asking a few generic questions. So, my first is, can you describe loosely, where you think the knowledge that you apply to wound management comes from?</p> <p>A14: Ooooh. Big question actually....emm....I would say it's come from multiple sources; I would say it's come from years of experience in a range of different....um....settings I suppose....I mean I had 10 years in xxx...em...before I came into tissue viability and I'm xx odd years in tissue viability.....em....I also think that because I worked across community and hospital as well as in a specialist area it actually gives you a very broad range of wounds and experiences and different types of challenges that you come across. Em...I think that if you were in one particular ward or one particular area you may only see specific things so...em...I think that's probably one part of it; the other part is..em...I like to ask questions and find out answers so if I come across something that I don't know; I'll go look up an answer to find out. I might not keep it in my head immediately and I think that's one of the things I've learned about myself over time is that...emm...I did my degree in nursing because I wanted to ask</p>	<p>Wound management knowledge comes from multiple sources</p> <p>Experiential knowledge that develops over time</p> <p>Range of clinical experience broadens knowledge</p> <p>Seeking out knowledge individually</p>

Information overload	<p>questions and I thought I'd get more answers that way than when I was doing my nurse training...um...but I think that I'm not one of those people who retains everything in their head all the time....em....I think you probably get to the stage where you've got too much information to do that. So, the stuff you use every day or on a regular basis is there and you can pull on it regularly but if there's something you've come across before or it's been a while ago you have to go and find that information out. So, for instanceum...is this general enough for you?</p>	Information overload in wound management
Going away and searching oneself		Seeking out knowledge oneself
RICH	<p>I: Yes, yes, theres no right or wrong.</p>	
Going away and searching oneself	<p>A14: So, for instance I'm not paediatric trained or maternity trained but the role I had at XXXX before I had before I came into this job covering XXXX in XXXXX we covered paediatrics, special care baby and maternity and so I would come across a condition on a baby I'd never seen before so I would go online and I would Google it. You'd go online and find the little bits and you'd look for information and find answers and contact colleagues so I think that having the network is really good as well. When I first started there was XX of us across Scotland so having people there that have experience in different areas because we can't know it all so ..em...we've got paediatrics in our team which is fortunate so if its anything to do with children we go to XXXX...but....um...even within our team we've got</p>	Seeking out knowledge oneself
Learning from colleagues in practice		Learning from colleagues in practice
Learning from colleagues in practice		Learning from colleagues in practice

<p>Experiential learning that develops over time</p>	<p>people who are experts on....surgical wounds or.....more chronic pressure ulcers and leg ulcers because pf the environments they work in; so different people have developed different skills and knowledge or come across different conditions and so we share that and therefore you can go to those people to get more information so I think its...its....being aware that you can't have all the information yourself and building on it by linking with other colleagues, by reading journals...umm...I must admit, now a lot of stuff is via email and PDFs and things like that but going online to things like EWMA and Wounds UK and finding the up to date best practice....so...yeah that's probably where I'd say it's a combination of the years of experience and the sharing the knowledge with others as well as pulling information from various sources</p>	<p>Experiential learning that develops over time</p>
<p>Scientific evidence journals</p>		<p>Formal evidence (journals)</p>
<p>Learning online</p>		<p>Formal evidence (online)</p>
<p>Going away and learning oneself</p>		<p>Seeking out knowledge oneself</p>
<p>Experiential learning that develops over time</p>		
<p>Learning from colleagues in practice</p>		<p>Experiential learning that develops over time</p>
<p>Collaboration with colleagues in practice</p>		<p>Learning from colleagues in practice (collaboration)</p>
<p>Wound management knowledge comes from multiple sources</p>		<p>Learning from colleagues in practice (collaboration)</p>
	<p>I: Ok, good, good that's really interesting. And so, you've mentioned several different sources and the fact that it is a multiple knowledge source. Is there any one, do you think anyone precedes the others or has more importance or do you think they're all equally important?</p>	<p>Wound management knowledge comes from multiple sources</p>
<p>Experiential learning that develops over time</p>	<p>A14: Em. It's a good question I suppose because I came into tissue viability before there were any courses around or anything like that so my experience and development has been purely through....em....reading, attending study days I</p>	<p>Experiential learning in practice that develops over time</p>

<p>No structured education but I do my own reading</p>	<p>both and I think it is a balance of both definitely.</p> <p>I: Yeah definitely. And would you say, in your case you mentioned that you haven't undergone any formal degree qualification in tissue viability the people are now and that's probably because back then nurse training looked very different; but you've said in your own time you've done your own reading and theoretical development; would you say that you feel quite confident or do you feel quite happy with your own level of educational preparation to fulfil the role?</p>	<p>Seeking knowledge, oneself (no structured education)</p>
<p>Changes in educational structure make it hard to evidence knowledge</p>	<p>A14: I do yes, I think that the challenge now would be that if you were going to go for another role and you haven't got a qualification at a certain level, you would have to evidence that you haven't got that qualification but you've got the other knowledge and evidence from your experience and I think that would be harder because people often tick the box that you've got a particular level of education in that speciality so I think yeah em.....(long pause).....that you can evidence it and you can show that you've developed even if you haven't got the qualifications but I think theres the expectation there that you've got the qualifications. Does that answer your question?</p>	<p>Changes in educational structure make it hard to evidence knowledge</p> <p>Seeking knowledge, oneself (no structured education)</p>
<p>I have first degree but not post grad</p>	<p>I: Yeah it totally does and I think that you underwent nurse training at a time when many people-and I don't like to put an age on it but many people at certain stages of</p>	<p>First degree but no post grad</p>
<p>More practical training courses</p>	<p>I: Yeah it totally does and I think that you underwent nurse training at a time when many people-and I don't like to put an age on it but many people at certain stages of</p>	<p>More practical based training</p>

<p>Tissue viability has become a speciality over time</p>	<p>their careers, the expectations and opportunities were different. Pre-reg students come out with a degree now...</p> <p>.</p> <p>A14: Well, I did come out with a degree when I trained, I was the second year at XXXX and I suppose looking back I did do a course, it was a post registration course in XXXXX so I suppose that was the only technical course that I did, you know before Project 2000 and all these courses; it was a very specific course on <i>this</i> topic, so you did your 6 months training and then you had your certificate. So yeah, I guess there are little snippets but not what someone would look at and go "well that's wound education or that's specific to tissue viability" which I think now it maybe is more focused that that is a speciality</p>	<p>TV has become more of a speciality over time</p>
<p>Empiric</p> <p>My wound management knowledge is evidence based</p> <p>Overwhelming amount of information out there; it's difficult to keep up</p>	<p>I: Ok that's really helpful so I'm going to move away from the generic and move on specifically to empiric and scientific knowledge. To what extent would you say that your knowledge you apply in wound management practice is scientific or evidence based?</p> <p>A14: Em I would like to think that majority of it is scientific and evidence based ; I like to keep up to date with....em....I suppose best practice for what's out there. There is so much out there now that it's very difficult to keep up with what's out there today and I suppose that's why people tend to focus on one type of wound that they're interested in because</p>	<p>My wound management knowledge is evidence based</p> <p>Too much information (overwhelming)</p>

<p>Most tissue viability nurses have a particular specialty</p>	<p>there so much, theres so many journals that theres no way that you can physically keep up to date with it but I would say, yeah, its....I would not like to think that I was not using evidence and I think that's where if you've got a team or you've got a collection of people who can communicate or may all be working together you can look at different bits of evidence and bring it back in. So if you've got different interests, so I may have an interest in maybe sort of atypical wounds and maybe not sort of the ones that are like normal leg ulcers or pressure ulcers because they're the ones that I think maybe if you've got a bit more experience you've looked at the evidence for the standard leg ulcers, pressure ulcer management etc and the ones that are outside that, how do we look at that; what are the therapies that we can look at that are not just dressings ; so I think...I would like to think that I look at the evidence and then pull the relevant evidence for what's required...em.....but I would also say I'd like to think that not just myself but maybe the people on the team as well we maybe go out on a limb if that makes sense and go "you know actually this is quite new and innovative; not a lot of evidence yet but it sounds promising; theres evidence in the labs, let's give it a go". So, I think it's not just looking at the evidence that's out there but building your own evidence as well....so yeah a bit of both of those I would say...so yeah so we tried out things like XXXX when it first</p>	<p>TVNs have a particular interest due to too much information</p>
<p>Learning from colleagues in practice</p>		<p>Learning from colleagues in practice</p>
<p>Importance of collaboration in forming knowledge</p>		<p>Learning from colleagues in practice (collaboration)</p>
<p>Tissue viability nurses have particular specialities</p>		<p>Overwhelming information-TVNs have particular specialities</p>
<p>RICH</p>		
<p>Importance of formal evidence but also forming new evidence and being innovative</p>		<p>Forming new evidence and innovation</p>
<p>Building own evidence and being innovative</p>		<p>Forming new evidence and being innovative</p>

<p>Importance of linking formal evidence with experience</p>	<p>came out and did some case studies because the theories were there but we didn't have much practical so you have to build the evidence. So yeah, I would like to think that we do, we take the evidence and try it in practice</p> <p>I: Ok so you've talked a bit about your application of evidence in practice but what about the evidence itself that's available to you...what do you think about it? Do you think theres a good scope of evidence? Do you feel it's of a good standard?</p>	<p>Formal evidence and experience are equally important & complimentary</p>
<p>Quality of evidence ranges from good to not so good</p>	<p>A14: Ok, ok. I think that there a range of evidence out there and I think that some of it is at a very good level...some of it I find hard to understand because it's incredibly detailed and scientific. I mean even stuff that's sometimes in the XXX journal is very detailed and if you don't have that knowledge about...I mean I can look at...theres certain statistical things I can look at and I know, I can understand them but you can come up with a whole range of other ones that I tend to just skim because it's not one that I understand the process; I'll look to see "well what did they find? Was it statistically significant and what was the evidence around that? I may not understand the process but I'll still look at the</p>	<p>Range in quality of evidence</p>
<p>Some wound care evidence is too scientific and technical for nurses</p>	<p>outcomes...so I must admit, if something is too scientific or too detailed, I switch off. So I think that for generalist nurses and even for specialists I think you need to have something that's in a format that you can actually understand and utilise because em...that has the</p>	<p>Some wound care evidence is too scientific and technical for nurses</p>
<p>Some wound care evidence is too scientific and technical for nurses</p>	<p>because em...that has the</p>	<p>Some care evidence is too scientific and technical for nurses</p>

<p>Some wound care evidence is too scientific for nurses</p>	<p>level of evidence that you need but that as a nurse you don't necessarily need but maybe as a scientist you would need so I think some people do deal with that; they'll publish in a scientific journal and take bits of it and publish it in maybe a nursing journal or a specialist journal for June and that's generally in a format that's more accessible and I think that's maybe sometimes when you're looking for references sometimes you may come across the scientific, really detailed stuff and you can get lost in it. So, I do think for nurses; not everyone has a scientific mind and a statistical mind and I think figures are not always the top of our priority so I think understanding that side of it can be challenging</p>	<p>Some evidence is too scientific and technical for nurses</p>
<p>Some wound care evidence is too scientific for nurses</p>	<p>I: No, I would totally agree, I'm the same I'm not really scientific and quantitative type research it's not really my bag either and I'm more inclined to look at things that are applicable to nursing and to my practice and I think that maybe most of the people who write these papers are scientists, not nurses and they're not really interested in the contextual stuff but you're right, we do need their evidence</p> <p>A14: So if you're looking at,.....I remember I was reading the XXXX journal in the last few months and it was looking at pressures and tissues when you were sittingyou know <i>masses</i> of information but you know at the end you're thinking what does this mean for me in practice and I think sometimes that's where the</p>	<p>Some wound care evidence is too scientific for nurses</p>

<p>Some evidence is too scientific to be transferable to nursing</p>	<p>scientific stuff shows us the information but it doesn't...it isn't necessarily transferrable and I think that the other thing I find quite difficult...well quite annoying actually, is when they're done some work, there was 30 patients, they've done some good work, come out with good outcomes and it's like "well we'd recommend further research and it's like well has anything been done since then? And you know, actually what level of research and how many people before we can actually use this and can we just go with this 30-patient study and I think that's when it's just...well sometimes you just say "let's give it a go. There's a bit of evidence; somebody's tried it; it's not going to do any harm; it's licenced; let's try it in practice" And other times you come across research and it's got a lot of evidence behind it and I suppose in wounds...em....I suppose it's also the level of evidence, people talking about RCTs and actually there's not many and it's well is that our standard, is that what should we be looking at? Or are we looking at more comparative studies or, you know so it understanding its different in wounds it's not like a drug that you can do that really clear yes or no answer to something. So, um I think that's where it's difficult...and you know some people will only look at the top-level research, they won't consider anything below that and even within our team you've got that variation with people who will go "well let's give it a try" where other will</p>	<p>Some wound care evidence is too scientific for nurses</p>
<p>RICH</p> <p>Importance of trying new things and innovation and creating new evidence</p>		<p>Creating new evidence and innovation</p>
<p>RCTs too de-contextualised for nursing</p>		<p>Some evidence is too scientific for nurses RCTs too de-contextualised</p>
<p>RCTs too de-contextualised for nursing</p>		<p>Some evidence is too scientific for nurses RCTs too de-contextualised</p>
<p>Scientific snobbery in evidence</p>		<p>Scientific snobbery in evidence formation</p>
<p>RCTS too de-contextualised for nursing</p>		<p>Some evidence is too scientific for nurses RCTs too de-contextualised</p>

<p>Coase study evidence can be challenging to analyse and compare</p>	<p>go “well theres nothing at this level so we’re not going to look at it” and I think that’s where again, theres a difficulty, like what level of evidence or treatment would be acceptable?</p>	<p>Case study evidence can be challenging to analyse</p>
<p>RICH</p>	<p>I: No, I totally agree and I think there is a kind of scientific snobbery around quantitative evidence where they think the qualitative evidence doesn’t hold as much clout but as I’m reading more about this, I’m realising that a lot of this is more about snobbery and power than the quality of the evidence. So, what do you think about the availability of evidence that is more contextualised or qualitative like comparative or case studies?</p>	
<p>Comparative and multi-centre studies are useful in wound management</p>	<p>A14: I think theres a lot of it out there and I think the challenge is its difficult to see the wood for the trees if that makes sense. So actually, several different people have all done case studies or case analysis or case reviews on a different product but they’ve all done it differently; so, you can’t actually compare and I think that’s where it’s difficult. Em....I was involved with a piece of work and it was....it was with a company but what they were doing was doing it with a university and doing a Delphi process, looking at studies and trying to pull out information and if we start treatment here and we put information and we start to look at the product made and we start to see the outcomes what they were trying to do is they were trying to....see what was the bit before, what were we comparing for a</p>	<p>Comparative and multi-centre studies are useful in wound management</p>

<p>Comparative and multi-centre studies are useful in wound management</p>	<p>while and going back and thinking what was standard practice and that was really quite an interesting.....you know if we want to make a comparison then we have to know what standards there are....are these processes that everyone uses and what is the standard and we can compare to that; rather than everyone having a different pre and post so I think.....yeah.....and I think one of the things that's really good is when people have taken a load of studies on the same product or the same therapy and they've pulled them all together and done a multi-centre because to me a multi-centre study gives you a much bigger body of evidence because if everyone is using the same process on the same kind of wounds then if the outcomes are all showing as positive then that's great because we've got a big body of evidence. So, I would say that the single case studies are useful locally for testing something but actually from an evidence point of view they're not as good; but actually, when you pull them together in a sort of multi-centre or multi-site where it's all pulled then I think that's where it's much more useful to a clinician because you've often have got your patient experience in there; pain management as well as the product rather than just the theory which is at the far end if that makes sense? If you think of the spectrum of evidence you've got your sort of high level in-vitro scientific, in the lab, really really highly controlled where you can do all your controls and then you've got more of</p>	<p>Comparative & multi-centre studies are useful in wound management</p>
<p>Single case studies good locally but not as good</p>	<p>think.....yeah.....and I think one of the things that's really good is when people have taken a load of studies on the same product or the same therapy and they've pulled them all together and done a multi-centre because to me a multi-centre study gives you a much bigger body of evidence because if everyone is using the same process on the same kind of wounds then if the outcomes are all showing as positive then that's great because we've got a big body of evidence. So, I would say that the single case studies are useful locally for testing something but actually from an evidence point of view they're not as good; but actually, when you pull them together in a sort of multi-centre or multi-site where it's all pulled then I think that's where it's much more useful to a clinician because you've often have got your patient experience in there; pain management as well as the product rather than just the theory which is at the far end if that makes sense? If you think of the spectrum of evidence you've got your sort of high level in-vitro scientific, in the lab, really really highly controlled where you can do all your controls and then you've got more of</p>	<p>Single case studies are useful locally</p>
<p>Comparative and multi-site studies good for wound management</p>	<p>think.....yeah.....and I think one of the things that's really good is when people have taken a load of studies on the same product or the same therapy and they've pulled them all together and done a multi-centre because to me a multi-centre study gives you a much bigger body of evidence because if everyone is using the same process on the same kind of wounds then if the outcomes are all showing as positive then that's great because we've got a big body of evidence. So, I would say that the single case studies are useful locally for testing something but actually from an evidence point of view they're not as good; but actually, when you pull them together in a sort of multi-centre or multi-site where it's all pulled then I think that's where it's much more useful to a clinician because you've often have got your patient experience in there; pain management as well as the product rather than just the theory which is at the far end if that makes sense? If you think of the spectrum of evidence you've got your sort of high level in-vitro scientific, in the lab, really really highly controlled where you can do all your controls and then you've got more of</p>	<p>Comparative & multi-centre studies are useful in wound management</p>
<p>Comparative and multi-site studies are most useful in wound management. Some context</p>	<p>think.....yeah.....and I think one of the things that's really good is when people have taken a load of studies on the same product or the same therapy and they've pulled them all together and done a multi-centre because to me a multi-centre study gives you a much bigger body of evidence because if everyone is using the same process on the same kind of wounds then if the outcomes are all showing as positive then that's great because we've got a big body of evidence. So, I would say that the single case studies are useful locally for testing something but actually from an evidence point of view they're not as good; but actually, when you pull them together in a sort of multi-centre or multi-site where it's all pulled then I think that's where it's much more useful to a clinician because you've often have got your patient experience in there; pain management as well as the product rather than just the theory which is at the far end if that makes sense? If you think of the spectrum of evidence you've got your sort of high level in-vitro scientific, in the lab, really really highly controlled where you can do all your controls and then you've got more of</p>	<p>Comparative & multi-site studies are useful in wound management</p>
<p>Visual evidence is good</p>	<p>think.....yeah.....and I think one of the things that's really good is when people have taken a load of studies on the same product or the same therapy and they've pulled them all together and done a multi-centre because to me a multi-centre study gives you a much bigger body of evidence because if everyone is using the same process on the same kind of wounds then if the outcomes are all showing as positive then that's great because we've got a big body of evidence. So, I would say that the single case studies are useful locally for testing something but actually from an evidence point of view they're not as good; but actually, when you pull them together in a sort of multi-centre or multi-site where it's all pulled then I think that's where it's much more useful to a clinician because you've often have got your patient experience in there; pain management as well as the product rather than just the theory which is at the far end if that makes sense? If you think of the spectrum of evidence you've got your sort of high level in-vitro scientific, in the lab, really really highly controlled where you can do all your controls and then you've got more of</p>	<p>Visual evidence is useful</p>

<p>Contextualised studies are good</p>	<p>your control studies; they're not necessarily randomised control but they're maybe there is some control over them so em....I think theres a place for them as well; you might not be able to do a double blinded randomised because the products look completely different but you might be able to do a controlled study. So, I think there may be a spectrum of things and I think if you're looking at a control study or multi centre I think maybe that's the level of evidence maybe that's most suitable. A lot of them go to the case studies; they go to them because they understand because that's what they see. It relatable yeah, so if you put pictures in some people find that easier and I think that's where, having it in a format that people can visualise and understand. I mean I'm a very visual person I like pictures and I like graphs; you know diagrams to try and explain things so if it's all just words sometimes it's difficult to get the message across as well...quotes are really good as well if you're doing patient studies and things; so, if you've got patient experience and things like that that really adds to it because I think if a patients got something to say that also impacts</p>	<p>Single case studies are limited but contextualised element is good</p> <p>CPD is challenging to access</p>
<p>We provide CPD but have challenges accessing it</p>		<p>CPD is challenging to access</p>
<p>Funding as a barrier</p>	<p>I: I think that's a really good point because as you said about the multi-site studies because you can put the same dressing on different patients but they aren't all the same and you can't control things. And what about are you able or is your team able to access sort of</p>	<p>Funding as a barrier</p> <p>CPD is challenging to access</p> <p>Funding as a barrier</p>

Lack of availability of specialist CPD	CPD or ongoing training, you're probably involved in delivering it....	
Funding as a barrier	<p>A14: Yeah, as a team we deliver it locally for nurses and AHPs we deliver a range of things; but actually accessing it ourselves, yes we can access it, the challenge is getting funding, and I think that's always a challenge in the NHS is just getting funding for things...there usually isn't an issue for getting study time off but if theres any costs that's where there may be issue with it so you know, applying for education grants and things like that, we do have to look at that kind of thing for people to be able to attend. So yeah it can be a bit of a challenge, I think for specialists as well, if you want to try to get a debridement course, or leg ulcer course or specialist-type courses there isn't always that available. I mean I know there are some people who are happy to fund them themselves if they're able to get the time off so sometimes there are that, but yeah I think its....there are the resources out there; there seems to be more free ones becoming available as well and I don't know quite how that works whether they're funding them through the exhibitions because I know in the UK whether they're providing education for wounds but you're having to pay to get there so I'm not sure they're being funded because they seem to have reasonable speakers at these things so you know if people can get to these things then I suppose....so there is stuff</p>	Funding as a barrier
Funding as a barrier		Protocols, guidelines, formularies & policy (not always utilised)
Protocols, guidelines, formularies & policy (not always utilised)		Usefulness of online resources
Online resources		

RICH	out there but sometimes its accessing it from a financial point of view I would say	
	I: So that might be a barrier? A14: Absolutely because I think with all these changes in how to get educational grants and things. So, we managed it this year but yeah it is....it's a lot more complex	
Professional organisational guidelines	I: Ok so we've talked a bit about structured education and we've talked a bit about research evidence and original research. What about guidelines and protocols and formal evidence that way?	Protocols, guidelines, tools & formularies (professional organisation guidelines)
Professional organisational guidelines	Obviously, they're there; do you think they are well utilised? Do you think they are accessible? Do you see any issues with them being implemented?	Protocols, guidelines, tools & formularies (professional organisation guidelines)
Industry sponsored guidelines bias	A14: Ok, well I think it depends on what the guidelines are and I think it depends where you are...we have a website, we have our own tissue viability website and we try to put all the ones that we think are relevant on there for staff to access. Whether they actually access them or not is another issue. So, if theres specific ones we have them under headings, so like we have leg ulcer and surgical wounds and things like that and we try to put links in for when they come across. For a team point of view or my point of view, I use a lot of EWMA, I think the EWMA are excellent and they bring a lot of different documents so we have used quite a lot of those and referred to them....em.....XXXXX and XXXXX have produced quite	Protocols, guidelines, tools & formularies (professional organisation guidelines bias)
Professional organisational guidelines		Protocols, guidelines, tools & formularies (professional organisation guidelines)
Guidelines, protocols formularies & tools		Protocols, guidelines, tools & formularies

Industry guidelines (bias)	a lot of best practice statements and I think NICE have also come out with ones but one of things we've noticed as a team recently is that quite a lot of them seem to be company or product focused rather than general guidelines and that's a bit concerning in the sense of, actually is this what we're looking for or are we looking for something more generic and actually will people be influenced by the fact that they are industry sponsor. I think that the EWMA ones seem to be much more independent and objective. I think that some of the other ones that are coming out of other areas are seem to be less and there this spin put on them because they're advertised by companies. So for example the NICE ones recently were talking about a specific product-XXXXX I think it was and how effective it was but what actually came out of that is that there was only type of wound that was proven and although it was beneficial to others, there wasn't enough types of evidence to say it was or wasn't ; however the spin from the company was that there was more information than there actually was and I think that can actually be confusing for staff because I think staff see that and go "oh well wonder product, a NICE guideline or another guideline says that it is and I think a lot of people actually look to those. I think as a specialist you're more wary, I think if you were a generalist you may not pick up on that just the same. The guidelines that come out from HIS, I know that they're very robust having been	Protocols, guidelines, tools & formularies (professional organisation guidelines bias)
Industry guidelines (bias)		Protocols, guidelines, tools & formularies (professional organisation guidelines bias)
HIS Guidelines		Protocols, guidelines, tools & formularies (professional organisation guidelines HIS)
SIGN Guidelines		Protocols, guidelines, tools & formularies (SIGN guidelines)
Too many sources of information (overwhelming)		Protocols, guidelines, tools & formularies (overwhelming information)
Too much information (overwhelming) Protocols & Guidelines		Protocols, guidelines, tools & formularies (overwhelming information)

<p>Industry Guidelines (bias)</p> <p>Too much information (overwhelming)</p> <p>Too much information (overwhelming)</p> <p>Too much information (overwhelming) guidelines & protocols</p>	<p>involved in some of those as well I think that they're very useful, they're very robust...the pressure ulcers and the infected wounds and things like that. You know their processes as well; I think that it's very clear. I think the ones in Scotland, the SIGN guidelines, theres not industry involvement at all, so it's very much, this is the evidence this is the clinicians. Theres ones that may have education grants but I think that they're more specific and more acceptable. So yeah, I think that theres a lot of evidence out there but I almost think theres too many coming out; theres one coming out every month on a different topic, and it's quite hard to keep up with. I don't know if theres a competition going on as well and that's just a personal observation.....I was looking at an atypical wound one from XXXX today and there was another one coming out from XXXX and I thought it was quite interesting because obviously XXXXX have a best practice statement and I was like "why have you got two organisations looking at the same thing? Why can they not combine? Why can they not link together? Emmm...but I can see from an outside perspective that XXXXX is a company whereas XXXXX is an organisation and I think that the difference is that when you've got a company, they're looking at making money out of it in the long term as well as providing evidence and with XXXX it's much more about the evidence and the clinicians and the patient information</p>	<p>Protocols, guidelines, tools & formularies (professional organisation guidelines bias)</p> <p>Protocols, guidelines, tools & formularies (overwhelming)</p>
---	---	--

	<p>and making sure its accurate evidence so I think that's where I think the challenge is at the minute you've got evidence coming out from different sources and actually if I don't know about the XXXX ones, I'm going to go for the ones that say XXXX on them. And actually, if I'm in the UK do I go for UK rather than European because is that what I should be looking at and that's where I think it can actually be confusing for clinicians; the number and the fact that they're coming out from different places</p> <p>I: Yeah, I would agree with that; there does seem to be an overwhelming amount</p> <p>A14: I mean I feel that and I'm in the speciality. I mean if you were a District Nurse or a staff nurse somewhere and that was only part of your job and you were looking at all the evidence that was coming out for all the other things to do with your patients, you know you could see why people only pick up on one or two things</p> <p>I: Yeah, you can't do everything</p> <p>A14: no.</p>	<p>Protocols, guidelines, tools & formularies (overwhelming)</p> <p>Protocols, guidelines, tools & formularies (overwhelming)</p>
<p>Aesthetic</p>	<p>I: Ok thank you very much that's very interesting. We're going to move away from empiric knowledge now and we're going to look at aesthetic type knowledge. Can you describe any artistic or creative ability that you think is part of your wound management practice?</p> <p>A14: Ok. Yes. I think that you need to be able to visualise</p>	

<p>Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors in wound management</p>	<p>things. I think you need to be able to visualise.....you need to be able to put yourself in the patient's shoes if you want to put it that way as well; so, you need to be able to put it in their perspective so if you think about what their treatment options are ; how it will impact upon them. Because we can have the ideal patient but the patient in front of you may not be the ideal patient...they may have mobility issues, health issues dietary issues-whatever. So, I think thinking outside your nurse and specialist brain to be able to put yourself into the position of the patient or the family is really important. Um...creative....other thing creatively....you need to be a Blue Peter presenter. You need to be able to adapt and try things and change things and you know, get your pair of scissors out and just give it a go. And say "Ok right, this isn't going to work this way so let's try it this way....so I think.....is that the kind of thing you're looking for?</p>	<p>Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors in wound management</p>
<p>Creativity in building relationships</p>		<p>Creativity in forming relationships</p>
<p>Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors</p>		<p>Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors</p>
<p>Creative technical skill & dressing technique</p>	<p>I: Yeah, I'm looking for anything that you think is creative and they're two very good examples</p> <p>A14: Interjects. Yeah because I think, I think....one of the things I think is that if you've learned to do things and you've followed the instructions to the letter and you're presented with something that doesn't fit then actually then you're thrown. Um I think nurses in general are quite creative really, I think is something we learn. Um, it's part of us, we can be scientific but we</p>	<p>Creative skill dressing technique</p> <p>Creative skill dressing technique</p>

<p>Creative technical skill & use of dressings</p>	<p>can also be um...creative as well. And I think because you always have to think about solutionsmaybe not the standard solutions that makes you more creative in your approach....emmm.....I think discussing with colleagues can also be really useful because they might have thought of an approach that's different than yours...but yeah I suppose an example would be you've got a patient, you've got a range of sizes of dressings for different parts of the body and none of those dressings are the right shape or size for that part of the body so what do you do? And that's where you have to come up with different solutions to manage that and then you need to be able to teach that to other members of staff so they can manage that because if you don't explain.....and it can be simple things like having a square dressing and putting it on like a diamond because it fits into a shape or crease better and some people.....they can't actually do that in their head...they can't process so if its square it just goes on square and I think even just in your mind going "well if I do it that way, if I cut it, if I do this then that's going to do that" so that's where I think....I would say that's where creativity can come into it.</p>	<p>Creative skill dressing technique</p>
<p>Creative technical skill & dressing technique</p>	<p></p>	<p></p>
<p>Creative teaching skills</p>	<p></p>	<p>Creative skill teaching</p>
<p>Creative technical skill & dressing technique</p>	<p>I: So technical skill and creative skill and working with different parts of the body?</p> <p>A14: Yes. Yes.</p>	<p>Creative skill dressing technique</p>

<p>Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors</p>	<p>I: And also, the consideration of the individual factors for the patient?</p>	
<p>Creative therapeutic approaches</p>	<p>A14: Yes, yes. And also, different ways of looking at the wound or maybe seeing the wound because you go to see them and they're sitting at home; they're not going to go to bed because bed is upstairs and they only go there in the evening and the ulcers on the back of their leg and its quite a dark room. What are you going to do? So, you know there are challenges but you know things like mirrors and now we've got torches and things like that on our phones and you can use things to try and illuminate areas</p>	<p>Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors in wound management</p> <p>Creative therapeutic approaches</p>
<p>Creative therapeutic approaches</p>	<p>and.....yeah.....its.....I suppose.....(long pause).....other ways of.....(long pause).....thinking outside the box I suppose it's like "well this patient is not lying on the bed and we can't actually see the wound so what else can we do?" You know simple things like how can the patient stand up to see a wound on their back or bottom rather than lying in their bed because they can't get upstairs and probably we do these things but at first I was probably a bit shocked that someone should have to stand up to see their wound and get their dressing change. Because it was</p>	<p>Creative therapeutic approaches</p>
<p>RICH</p> <p>Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors</p>	<p>"surely they should be lying down somewhere so we can see their wound?" But it's like "well no actually this works" so I think you learn that maybe actually this is what the patient prefers; you know what do they want in how we manage their wound and how can they help? You</p>	<p>Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors</p>

<p>Creative therapeutic approaches</p>	<p>know I think one of the things we used to do and probably most people do it was treatment rooms you know they have limited time to actually see the wound and it's like "ok well how can we.....well it was when XXXXX first came out and you're meant to give it a 20-minute soak and it was like well how can we do this when we don't have time? So, we told them to have a shower, soak it at home before they come and wrap it in cling film so that it's had its 20 minutes by the time they get here and it's like...so it's not a standard approach but it's a creative way of ensuring that the patient can still get the treatment and then not hold up the treatment room nurse. Yeah so, it's looking at ways that you can manage that rather than just saying "we can't do it" you know it's trying to manage it.</p>	<p>Creative therapeutic approaches</p>
<p>Creative therapeutic approaches</p>	<p>I: Its interesting because even the way you're saying this, it's as if this is an add on knowledge that sits outside of our main knowledge base but actually all that stuff is really complex, skilled unspoken knowledge that we don't talk about or see it for what it is. It's actually one of our things as nurses that we do really really what but we don't sell it or articulate it or see it for what it is</p>	<p>Creative therapeutic approaches</p>
<p>Lack of recognition that aesthetic knowledge is a higher form of knowledge "just something that we do"</p>	<p>A14: I think because it's not scientific or its not....we do it to find out if it works and we just do it. We don't actually think that it's a skill that we've learned or you've used your knowledge to do that and actually you could pass</p>	<p>Aesthetic knowledge is a higher skill</p>
<p>RICH</p>		
<p>Experiential learning that develops over time</p>		<p>Experiential knowledge that develops over time</p>
<p>Learning from colleagues in practice (passing on aesthetic knowledge)</p>		<p>Learning from colleagues in practice (passing on aesthetic knowledge)</p>

<p>Wound management is both an art and a science</p> <p>Mutually dependent</p> <p>RICH</p> <p>Wound management is both an art and a science (mutually dependent)</p> <p>Wound management is individualised & contextualised</p>	<p>that on to other people. I suppose there are skills that are creative that you pass on for example if there are people there with you then you pass on those skills from that environment or team or whatever but yes, it's probably very localised that sort of level of knowledge or skill</p> <p>I: Ok thanks and moving on from that would you that wound management is more of a science or an art?</p> <p>A14: Oh, that's an interesting one. Well, its interesting because people talk about whether nursing is a science or an art and interestingly my degree was a BA not a BSc, I think now they do BSc but mine was a BA and we did 3 years of psychology and sociology in ours and I think that it's both; I don't think you can have one without the other. Emmm....I think that you have to have the science and you have to have the art side of it; you have to understand the psychology of the patient and the sociology, you know the family dynamics, the lifestyle issues, the work-life balance side of things and that not...its science but it's not anything you can actually put down to figures and I think wounds are the same. I don't think you can say....yes we need the science, we absolutely need the science of why wounds heal, why they break down, the different aetiologies, we need that information but actually we can have all that information and we can address them and we can have a wound that's still not healing and that actually</p>	<p>Wound management is an art and a science</p> <p>Wound management is an art and a science</p> <p>Wound management is both an art and a science</p> <p>Wound management is individualised & contextualised</p> <p>Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors</p>
---	--	--

<p>Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors</p>	<p>where I think the bigger picture bit comes in and the art bit of it comes in and it's like "right I've looked at all the sciency bits of it but actually the patient has got religious reasons why they take the dressings off or why they wash that part of the body with that particular product. Have I looked at the family reasons why that patient doesn't do anything because actually the family wait on them hand and foot because that's their culture? Have I looked at they're smoking and can't give it up because they've got mental health issues and that's their way of dealing with their mental health but actually it affecting their wound? So, I think that's where the psychology sociology art bit of it comes in and I don't think you can separate and they have to be considered together because you could be really science focused and you've missed all that bit. You could be totally focused on the psychology and sociology and managing the everything bits. Are we looking at quality of life are we looking at pain management but actually if you've not got an understanding of the wound and you've missed that bit out so you could actually not looking at the underlying aetiology that needs to be addressed? So, I would say it's like a set of scales and it needs to be...you need to have them evenly balanced.</p> <p>I: Ok that was a great answer. You mentioned relationships with the patient and families and carers; do you think you ever use creativity to establish</p>	<p>Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors</p> <p>Creativity in forming relationships</p> <p>Wound management is individualised & contextualised</p> <p>Wound management is an art and a science</p> <p>Creativity in forming relationships</p>
<p>Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors</p>		
<p>Creativity in forming relationships</p>		
<p>Wound management is individualised & contextualised</p>		
<p>Wound management is an art and a science (mutually dependent)</p>		
<p>Creativity in forming relationships</p>		

Creativity in forming relationships	<p>meaningful relationships with your patients? Do you think that's part of that process?</p> <p>A14: Yeah, I think it probably is actually. Some patients are really resistant; some people it's really easy actually to develop a relationship with them; you go in you develop a rapport really quickly they trust you you can explain things and they understand you. Other people are more reserved or have maybe had bad experiences so are actually cautious about developing a relationship so I suppose the creative ways you develop relationships is actually finding things in common so something they have an interest in that you can maybe talk about. You may have some knowledge about it; you may not have an interest yourself but you have some knowledge so noticing maybe a photograph or a book about something so asking them about it and actually showing an interest and if you show an interest in them they're actually more likely to listen to you and there's a quote I don't know if I can remember it accurately but there's a quote about people are not interested in what you have to say until you have shown an interest in them and that's not the right quote but that's the gist of it and basically they need to know you care before they'll come into that relationship with you and sometimes I think it takes a bit of time to develop that if they've had bad experiences before. Sometimes they can just be quiet people and they really don't want to and I think you have to respect</p>	Creativity in forming relationships
Creativity in forming relationships patient empowerment		Creativity in forming relationships (patient empowerment)
RICH		Creativity in forming relationships (patient empowerment)
Professionalism in wound management		Professionalism in wound management
Creativity in forming relationships		Creativity in forming relationships

<p>Creativity in forming relationships</p>	<p>that if someone doesn't want to discuss family or personal things and would rather keep it professional and is like "fine, tell me about it, do it and then go away" I think that makes it harder when they have issues they need to address and that makes it harder and you may have to go deeper into things and it's like, ok.....do we need a conversation or do we need to bring someone else in who maybe they're comfortable with? You know would they like to have a family member or a friend with them so that they can then feel that they're.....emm.....what's the word(long pause).....not talked to or talked at but made to feel that they are being made to do something but sometimes I think the balance is out between the professional and patient relationship that they feel they have to do what you're telling them and they maybe don't want to but they're not allowed to so I think having someone else there with them to say this is reason I'm telling them this and if you don't do this this is what might happen so that they then have the information and knowledge to actually make the decision themselves . Yeah I think having that third person on their side can make a difference because otherwise they could feel a bit pushed into a corner so yeah theres a lot of people who are quite happy to let you do things and not ask questions and trust you because you're the professional but theres others who are much more</p>	<p>Creativity in forming relationships</p>
<p>Professionalism in nursing</p>	<p>I think the balance is out between the professional and patient relationship that they feel they have to do what you're telling them and they maybe don't want to but they're not allowed to so I think having someone else there with them to say this is reason I'm telling them this and if you don't do this this is what might happen so that they then have the information and knowledge to actually make the decision themselves . Yeah I think having that third person on their side can make a difference because otherwise they could feel a bit pushed into a corner so yeah theres a lot of people who are quite happy to let you do things and not ask questions and trust you because you're the professional but theres others who are much more</p>	<p>Professionalism in wound management</p>

	resistant and take a bit of time	
<p>Ethical</p> <p>Ethical practice in wound management research & processes</p> <p>Guidelines, protocols, tools & policies</p> <p>Ethical engagement with companies</p> <p>Partnership with industry is important</p>	<p>I: Ok thank you. We're going to move away from aesthetic and we're going to move on to ethical knowing. How do you ensure your knowledge in wound management is ethical?</p> <p>A14: What exactly do you mean by ethical?</p> <p>I: Really anything you interpret it to mean. So, it could be with regards to ethical guidance or engagement with companies. It could be doing the right thing for the patient . Just anything that you think would apply ethical theory or knowledge in wound management.</p> <p>A14: Ok. I suppose there could be a number of things. So obviously you've got the high level ethical when you're involved in a study so going through the ethical process and approvals and things like that, so in a sense that's dealt with by the committee and process and its very clear and you've got very strict guidelines of when people are included and that's a very clear one, I would say. And then you've things like working with companies and working with companies to me has to be absolutely ethical and above board and I think theres guidelines from an NHS point of view and theres guidelines from an industry point of view. I think that we need to work in partnership with companies and I think we need to do that in a very open way and I think</p>	<p>Ethical practice in wound management research processes</p> <p>Protocols, guidelines, tools & formularies</p> <p>Ethical engagement with companies</p> <p>Partnership with industry</p>

Ethical engagement with industry	that.....(long pause) we would never take anything on that we're not comfortable with or that felt like it was in the patient's best interest and was more of a "if you do this we'll give you money" rather than "this is a study we'd like you to be involved in or this is an evaluation". I think with evaluations the ethics is do you accept free products and that its one of these ones that depends on the situation and what the rules are for the health boards and things and for some things its ok as long as it comes through an identified process and procurement are aware of it and you've got lot numbers and things and if theres an adverse event you can deal with it and come back to the company so I think theres that side of things where you're doing everything above board. I think when you've got an evaluation of a product where all that has been dealt with, you've not got the ethical issue of "is this product okay to use on a patient and could there be a negative effect on the patient because that's already been dealt with. But you may have the ethical issue of "do I accept free product or not and if I do it would be for a set time and then what would happen after that. So, I think that's where the ethical decisions would come in. If we're going to do it then we're going to do it for a set time and then we'd go on to purchase the products ourselves. Other ethical things I suppose is treatment options for patients and em.....you know....what things can be offered to them , what are appropriate, what	Ethical engagement with industry
RICH		
Partnership with industry is important		Partnership with industry
Ethical engagement with industry		Ethical engagement with industry
Do good not harm (fairness of resources)		Do god not harm (equity of resources)

<p>Do good not harm (fairness of resources)</p>	<p>are available. Because sometimes patients can come to requesting things because it's amazing what Google can tell them so they maybe come requesting particular treatments and its maybe not something that's available on the NHS or that's not actually licensed for wounds and that's where it becomes a bit of a challenge so I suppose that's where we have to look at "well what alternative can I offer you?" and one thing that comes to mind is honey,</p>	<p>Do good not harm (equity of resources)</p>
<p>Do good not harm</p>	<p>when honey first came into use for medical marketing purposes and patients would come requesting it and it was making them aware of the risks and that this is maybe not medical grade and if they do that in their own environment well we can maybe give them advice but it's up to them whether they choose to take that advice or not but if they're under the care of the nurses they have to make use of the product that's available so I think that's where it's a difficult one; I know that there was a case years ago in the burns unit we had a plastic surgeon who wanted to use XXXX on an open wound so that they could use it as a local anaesthetic so they could then shave the graft and as nurses we looked at the license and we saw that it wasn't licensed but the consultant said "I want you to use it" and we said "well that's fine; if you want it used; you can use it because you are accountable for your practice we are accountable for our practice and we as nurses are not going to be using it" and he was very annoyed and he went off and</p>	<p>Do good not harm</p>
<p>Do good not harm (accountability)</p>	<p></p>	<p>Do good not harm (accountability)</p>
<p>Do good not harm (accountability)</p>	<p></p>	<p>Do good not harm (accountability)</p>

<p>Do good not harm (information giving)</p>	<p>he used it and it was fine; that was his decision and as a medic he can make that decision for himself but we felt as nurses that we couldn't because if there was an issue ; one there could have been patient harm and two we could be putting our own registration at risk and so I think it's those things: are we going to harm the patient; is the patient aware of the risks and challenges around that because actually patients often aren't; you know if we don't give them the information; very few patients read the instructions on things and many nurses don't actually read to see actually do I need to check; does this patient have an allergy so I think that having that understanding that certain hydrocolloids have an alginate and if you have an allergy you can't use it or some products maybe have an animal product and maybe "well I can't use that because it's got collagen and its come from an animal" so I have to check if my patient is a vegetarian or vegan and so they're maybe the situations where people aren't really aware of the sort of more minor issues as opposed to the bigger, can somebody be in a study or not; just whether the product is suitable for use</p>	<p>Do good not harm (information giving)</p>
<p>Do good not harm (product selection & safety)</p>	<p></p>	<p>Do good not harm (product selection)</p>
<p>Do good not harm (cultural sensitivity)</p>	<p></p>	<p>Do good not harm (cultural sensitivity)</p>
<p>Ethical research</p>	<p></p>	<p>Ethical practice in wound management research processes</p>
<p>Do good not harm Information giving</p>	<p></p>	<p>Do good not harm Information giving</p>
<p>Do good not harm (consent and documentation)</p>	<p>I: So just the more day to day; so theres the research thing but also the bedside thing? A14: Yes. Doing the right thing or not doing any harm. And also helping them make the right decisions as well because they may actually choose not to go with what</p>	<p>Do good not harm (consent and documentation)</p>

<p>Do good not harm (autonomy)</p>	<p>you have advised they may choose to take a risk in something and choose something that's actually it may do them good and it may not and I suppose it's giving them the ability to make that decision with the right level of information and also making sure that it is documented that this isn't what's being advised but the patient is making the decision so that its very clear what has been discussed and what has been agreed and what hasn't</p> <p>I: So just ensuring their autonomy?</p> <p>A14: Yeah. Absolutely. Because if someone makes a decision that actually "I've read up about this; well, that's their decision and they have the right to make that decision but we obviously can't endorse that if it's something that hasn't gone through the processes or we can't see the evidence</p>	<p>Do good not harm (autonomy)</p>
<p>No ethical specific guidelines</p>	<p>I: And do you think that there is any ethical guidance available that you're aware of to help guide you in these types of decisions? So, it could be when you come into a value conflict with a patient as you have described or with a member of surgical staff. Do you think there is anything there to support you?</p> <p>A14: I must admit, I don't think I've actually looked, apart from the one which is the guidelines for working with industry from a health board point of view I don't think I've actually looked but I think I would check with EWMA first in the first</p>	<p>No specific ethical guidelines</p> <p>Partnership with industry</p>

<p>Importance of partnership with industry</p>	<p>instance or I'd Google but I'd use Google Scholar because somebody told me about that and then you get proper research but no I don't think I've gone and actually looked at specific ethical information</p>	<p>Scientific integrity of industry</p>
<p>Scientific integrity of industry</p>	<p>I: And you mentioned industry and that you think we should have partnerships with them; albeit ethical partnerships; so, you do see a role for industry in wound management?</p>	
<p>Ethical engagement with industry</p>	<p>A14: Oh absolutely. Absolutely. I don't see any way that wound care can evolve without them. They have huge resource; they have huge R&D departments and yes, some of their work will be very product focused but they are world renowned scientists these people; I mean people like XXXX and XXXX who have worked with companies are actually scientists in their own right and they are working in labs with companies but I would imagine would have to work to scientific standards and industry standards from a scientific point of view so yes the actual way something is written up may be focused on the product but the process behind it has been robust and I think absolutely we have to work in partnership with industry because I think that the NHS does not have the resources to do what I would consider to be a simple study for example do we use mattress a or mattress b-is one or the other better at preventing pressure ulcers; I mean is quite a simple study but it took 3 years over different sites to get patients and at the end of it they didn't</p>	<p>Ethical engagement with industry</p>
<p>Resources (cost) as a barrier</p>		<p>Cost as a barrier</p>
<p>Scientific integrity of industry</p>		<p>Scientific integrity of industry</p>
<p>Partnership with industry</p>		<p>Partnership with industry</p>
<p>Cost as a barrier</p>		<p>Cost as a barrier</p>
		<p>Ethical engagement with industry</p>

<p>Ethical engagement with industry</p> <p>Partnership with industry</p>	<p>actually have enough results; that has actually been a non-industry sponsored study and that took up masses of amounts of time of staff so if you look at it from a wound point of view the NHS doesn't have the resources so I think we have to work in partnership and I think we have to be clear about what we will and won't do because I think there are some people who don't want to work with industry at all because they see them as the baddies but I think that's wrong because yes they're industry and a business and they have to make money but they have to be ethical and they have guidelines that they have to go by and if they harm a patient they have to stand up in court and be very very clear about things so yeah, absolutely we have to work in partnership</p> <p>I: It is a bit of a hot potato isn't it?</p> <p>A14: Yes it is.</p>	<p>Partnership with industry</p>
<p>Personal</p> <p>I bring myself to wound management practice</p> <p>I bring more of myself as I get more experienced</p>	<p>I: Ok well we're going to move away from ethical knowledge and move on to personal knowledge. Can you tell me how much of your genuine self you bring to wound management practice? Is that part of your knowledge base?</p> <p>A14: Mmmm. That's an interesting one. Em...I do think I bring some of my genuine self; I think since I've been in tissue viability, I bring more of my self than I did at the beginning but I think that I do still have my professional face. Yes I do talk to patients and staff and engage and you do share a</p>	<p>I bring myself to wound management</p> <p>I bring myself to wound management (more as I get more experienced)</p>

<p>Creativity in forming relationships</p>	<p>bit about yourself; you find out about your families and things like that so people know if you're married and have children and things like that and I think that.....yeah I think that if you care about something and genuinely want people to improve their lives then I think that comes from me as a person; that's not.....you can't make that up I don't think.....</p>	<p>Creativity in forming relationships</p>
<p>Genuine caring for people</p>	<p>I: You can't fake?</p>	<p>Genuine relationships with people</p>
<p>Genuine caring for people</p>	<p>A14: No, I don't think you can fake that. So, I think yeah, I've always been a person who's cared for other people and I think I've always wanted to be involved in something like that in some shape or form so yes, I do think that I bring that of myself. I do think there are parts of me that I keep separate and I think that's healthy but I think you have to be careful because some things definitely are for work and for professional and there are some that aren't.....does that....is that the sort of thing you're looking for?</p>	<p>Genuine relationships with people</p>
<p>Professionalism in wound management</p>	<p>I: Yeah, that's perfect. So, would you say that any of your personal experience shapes your wound management practice?</p>	<p>Professionalism in wound management</p>
<p>My personal experiences have shaped wound management practice</p>	<p>A14: Yes. And I would say, actually as you have different personal experiences through life, they actually change and shape how you see things. So if you think back over your life...you know, when you had family then you maybe didn't consider that an issue if patient didn't have family ,</p>	<p>My personal experience shapes wound management</p>
<p>RICH</p>	<p></p>	<p></p>

<p>I bring my personal experiences to wound management</p>	<p>you know people to do things....I mean like I had xxxx a number of years back and I think that then gave me a different perspective in the mental health side of things and how that can affect people and how people can often hide it and how that can have an impact on things and actually a couple of years ago I had xxxx and actually you see things from the inside and I very much put myself into patient mode because I need to be...you know I'm the patient here so I completely ignored that what they putting on in A & E wasn't what I would have put on because that was their decision and you know I went through the inside and it gives the very different perspective of being the patient and you do see things; you see the environment that patients are in and if you're in a ward environment the challenge of that. And things like, how do you manage when you get home and wash your hair and have a shower if you've got a big bandage on and suddenly...you've been aware of that and given patients advice about it but suddenly it's much more real and you can share that from experience. And more recently when I had my xxx I became aware of why people who've had xxx say they can't lie on their side and I used to think "your operation was 10 years ago, surely that can't still be an issue" and I think sometimes we don't actually listen to the patient; we think we listen to them but we think they don't tell the whole truth and I think that your experience whether they're from you or</p>	<p>I bring my personal experiences to wound management</p>
<p>I bring my personal experiences to wound management practice</p>		<p>I bring personal experiences to wound management</p>
<p>Consideration and integration of wider holistic factors in wound management</p>		<p>Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors</p>
<p>I bring myself to wound management</p>		<p>I bring myself to wound management practice</p>
<p>Personal experiences shape wound management practice</p>		<p>My personal experiences shape wound management practice</p>
<p>Creativity in forming relationships</p>		<p>Creativity in forming relationships</p>
<p>Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors</p>		<p>Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors</p>

<p>Wound management is individualised & contextualised</p>	<p>from family and friends they can shape how you respond and how you react and how you shape your practice and how you relate to people because I think you can actually come up with solutions because you can relate rather than “well you need to do it” and I don’t think I would ever actually say that but sometimes it’s a challenging environment as a nurse and you have a lot to deal with and I don’t have time to think about this so just do it. And that’s the reality sometimes. So, I’d say, yes definitely, as I’ve gone through my career and I’ve experience of different things and different situations myself or with family members it does change how you deal with things and how you respond or consider things</p>	<p>Wound management is individualised & contextualised</p>
<p>Time is a barrier</p>		<p>Time is a barrier</p>
<p>Personal experiences shape wound management practice</p>		<p>Personal experiences shape wound management practice</p>
<p>Learning from colleagues in practice</p>	<p>I: Yeah, I totally agree. And what about, you mentioned earlier on I think in the generic questions about the knowledge you’d gleaned and how some of that maybe came from others and being with others and watching others; how much do you think your relationships with colleagues, whether they’re in other disciplines or within your team or just anyone you would consider a colleague shapes your wound management knowledge?</p>	<p>Learning from colleagues in practice</p>
	<p>A14: Oh absolutely, I think very much. Because you can’t develop and learn without seeing other people’s skills as well. I mean I learned sharp debridement by watching plastic surgeons in theatre and watching the skills they had and the techniques and that before</p>	<p>Learning from colleagues in practice</p>

Learning from colleagues in practice	there were courses in that.	Seeking out knowledge oneself
Finding out by oneself	You know, there weren't any courses so you did it and	
	were watched by a plastic surgeon and they said "yeah you can do it" and that was you.	
	So, you learn your skills by watching and observing	
	and by asking questions; you know sometimes I think we can observe and understand	
	and not necessarily take on those skills but know that that person is who we refer on to.	Learning from colleagues in practice
Learning from colleagues in practice	So, for example diabetic podiatrists, that is a skill in its own right you know	
Experiential learning that develops over time	the sharp debridement and the assessments they do.	Experiential learning that develops over time
	But to actually see those skills and understand makes you see "well that's where we need to send people"	
Learning from colleagues in practice	because although the guidelines say it actually you've seen it and you can't do that	Learning from colleagues in practice
	and that's not a skill anyone can do. I think even things like being shown how to do certain bandaging techniques ; you know I remember as a student nurse I worked in an orthopaedic ward or somewhere where they had orthopaedic patients and learned bandage skills and wounds and then being surprised other people didn't know them.	
	You know like I remember we had a hip spiker bandage and it was before we had all these fancy dressings or stump dressings or things like that, if somebody's never seen it, they don't know how to do that or have that knowledge.	
RICH	Even saying to somebody to put a figure of eight bandage on a leg, they look at you like "what's a figure of eight bandage?" and I think they're the sorts of skills you learn off people and then you have	
Learning from colleagues in practice		Learning from colleagues in practice
As important as theoretical knowledge		Experience is as important as theoretical knowledge

<p>Learning from colleagues in practice (other disciplines)</p>	<p>to pass them on because you don't necessarily learn those when you're training or you may not have been in a particular area where you've had that opportunity so I think that's where you do learn a lot of skills from other people and not necessarily in your discipline either...it can be a staff nurse in a ward, it can be a clinical support worker, it can be anybody who has that skill that actually passes it on to you and then you develop it and take it on to the next person.</p>	<p>Learning from colleagues on practice</p>
<p>Good relationships with colleagues</p>	<p>I: And what about your relationships with other colleagues in wound management. So that could be generalists to whom you provide specialist support or other specialists that you're working with, other disciplines; do you find that you work well together or have mutually supportive relationships?</p>	<p>Good relationships with colleagues</p>
<p>Individual clashes rather than professional ones</p>		<p>Individual clashes not professional ones</p>
<p>Inter-professional relationships</p>		<p>Interprofessionalism</p>
<p>Creativity in forming relationships</p>	<p>A14: Yes, I would say for the majority of people absolutely yes. There's always going to be the occasional person that you clash with things. It might be that you only clash with certain things, not everything or it might be that you clash because of personalities or it might be that you clash over a particular process or a particular treatment and I think as professionals it's about being able to have that disagreement but being able to differ and accept that as we said, it's an art and sometimes we don't have all the answers because we can't. So, I think in general yes, I get on with most people and don't really have an issue. I think sometimes</p>	<p>Creativity in forming relationships</p>
<p>Individual clashes rather than personal ones</p>		<p>Individual clashes not professional ones</p>
<p>Learning from colleagues in practice</p>		<p>Learning from colleagues in practice</p>
		<p>Experiential learning that develops over time</p>

<p>Experiential learning that develops over time and knowing limitations</p>	<p>people can misinterpret things or take something the wrong way and I think that's where its most likely to be a challenge but I think in general I would go to anyone and be able to ask for things. And I think that's the other thing-just because you're experience or been trained for a certain number of years doesn't mean you can't go to someone to ask something and I think it's always being able to admit you don't know everything and I used to say that at one of the training things "the day you think you know everything about wound management; that's the day you need to stop". Because if you think you know it all, then you start to be dangerous. So, I think having that open mind and being able to go and ask your colleagues whether they're local colleagues or more distant, I think absolutely, I would always do that.</p>	<p>Knowing limitations</p>
<p>Learning from colleagues in practice</p>	<p></p>	<p>Learning from colleagues in practice</p>
<p>Knowing ones limitations is a part of knowledge</p>	<p></p>	<p>Knowing one's limitations</p>
<p>Learning from colleagues in practice</p>	<p>I: I would agree.</p>	<p>Learning from colleagues in practice</p>
<p>Reflection with colleagues</p>	<p>A14: Absolutely and there was someone who asked a question in our wound management introduction days and they asked "does this particular drug affect wound healing?" And I said "Oh, I have not come across that before but I will go away and try to find out" and somebody in the room was actually able to answer because they were on that type of drug and they were able to share their experience which was very good but I actually went back to the team and said "has anybody ever come across this?" and somebody said "oh yes, here's some</p>	<p>Reflection with colleagues</p>
<p></p>	<p></p>	<p>Intuition is important in knowledge but it is complex and advanced</p>

<p>Intuition is important in knowledge but it is complex and advanced</p>	<p>information” but I actually just hadn’t come across them and I think actually that’s where you have to share the information and say “ I don’t know but I’ll find out”</p> <p>I: Ok well we’re just about finished with the personal section but before we move on I have just one more question. How much do you think intuition has a role in your knowledge or does it? Do you think that’s something that is important or have ever used or used routinely?</p>	<p>Intuition is important in knowledge but it is complex and advanced</p>
<p>Intuition is complex and advanced</p>	<p>A14: I think intuition, yes, absolutely but I think that intuition is actually based on.....a lot of things. So, it’s based on the knowledge and skills you’ve gotten over the years, so you sometimes do get a gut feeling or what I call a gut feeling about something. But I think that that gut feeling is actually based on what you’re picking up and the more experienced you are the more you pick up and the more easily you will go on intuition if you want to call it that. So yeah you may go to a patient and you may look at their wound and do an assessment and you may find out what’s going on with them and you may think “well actually I would normally do A but I’m maybe going to give B a go because I think there something else going on here and I can’t see any evidence but given the history they’ve given me I’m going to go with this. So, I think intuition absolutely yes, but I don’t think intuition is a thing on its own. Is not a magical force out there; it’s a</p>	<p>Intuition is important in knowledge but it is complex and advanced</p>
<p>Intuition is complex and advanced</p>	<p>Intuition is important in knowledge but it is complex and advanced</p>	<p>Intuition is important in knowledge but it is complex and advanced</p>
<p>Importance of collaboration</p>	<p>Collaboration with colleagues</p>	<p>Collaboration with colleagues</p>

<p>Intuition is complex and advanced</p>	<p>combination of the knowledge and skills and experience and things you've read and things you've seen all pulled together and it's the way your brain has processed them. So, it will be different to everybody so I may go in and see a wound and my gut reaction is to do this and someone else may go in and they may do that. And that's fine because their experience and skills are different. So actually, in a sense that why you need different people looking after someone because different people and going to bring different skills and pieces to the jigsaw. So yes, it does exist; it does exist but different people bring different things that are out there</p>	<p>Intuition is important in knowledge but it is complex and advanced</p>
<p>Intuition is complex and advanced</p>	<p>I: So, do you think it is linked to your knowledge and experience?</p>	<p>Intuition is important in knowledge but it is complex and advanced</p>
<p>Experiential learning that develops over time</p>	<p>A14: I think its linked to your knowledge and experience absolutely to what you've read but not necessarily put into practice but you've noted it and filed it away and you think "that's interesting" and then you go away and you see another patient and you go "oooh! I wonder if that's the same thing; right. I wonder if we could use the same thing; let's give it a go". So, to me you've not got the experience of it yet; you've not got the knowledge; you've got a bit of understanding maybe; you know what some of the options are; your intuition is probably "let's give it a go, let's try this"; you go away and read up on it and sometimes I think we use our intuition and we play safe</p>	<p>Experiential learning that develops over time</p>
<p>Knowledge from different sources processed at subconscious level</p>	<p>Do good not harm</p>	<p>Intuition is important in knowledge but it is complex and advanced (subconscious level)</p>
<p>Do good not harm</p>	<p>Do good not harm</p>	<p>Do good not harm</p>

<p>Unstructured reflection (alone)</p>	<p>until we go and find out some more. So, it might be “I think this is the treatment that I’m going to go for but for now I’m going to put this back on, it’s not going to do any harm and then I’m going to go and do some research and I’m going to come back”. So, I think your intuition and gut can give you that and make you go away and look at something but sometimes I think you go “mmmm... actually I’m not going to do that; I’m going to do the other thing”</p>	<p>Unstructured reflection (alone)</p> <p>Reflection with colleagues (unstructured)</p>
<p>Reflection with colleagues (unstructured)</p>	<p>I: Yep, ok, good. What about reflection? Do you use reflection much in your wound management practice?</p>	
<p>Unstructured reflection (individual)</p>	<p>A14: Em I would say that reflection is something that I wasn’t taught; reflection is something that I found quite difficult when people started talking about it as student nurses “oh we’ve got journals and we do this and this and this”. I think it’s probably something we did without being taught it if that makes sense. I think it was something you went away and thought about after you’d been with patients and we weren’t taught it and it wasn’t called reflection but I think yes, you process things afterwards and reflection is the word that’s used and has been used for a few years now but I think yeah, you do reflect by bouncing ideas off other people as well so you may have used your intuition and you may go back to your team and say “I’ve done this, I’ve had a think about this; anyone else got any other ideas and do you think I’ve got the right thing?”</p>	<p>Unstructured reflection (individual)</p> <p>Reflection (validation)</p>

<p>Reflection at revalidation</p> <p>Reflection following new learning</p>	<p>I: So, you maybe don't do structured reflection in the form of journals but you reflect with peers or you would reflect on your own afterwards?</p>	<p>Individual reflection (new learning)</p>
<p>Reflection with colleagues</p>	<p>A14: Yes. Very definitely. I mean I think if I was in a situation where there were more complex issues that's where I'd do some more reflection...if it's something simple then you probably do less. You deal with it, write it up and that's the end of that but if it's a bit more complex or if "theres two options there and I've gone for this one or should I have gone for the other one or".....yeah so I think it's a part of normal processing but I don't reflect clinically or reflect professionally by writing it down anywhere....it's not something I do. I suppose having to revalidate with the reflection, that's probably the first place where I've done any written reflection so that's probably the only formal reflection I've done. I suppose I've done it when I've attended training events; I've usually written</p>	<p>Reflection with colleagues</p>
<p>Reflection with colleagues</p>	<p>something done and taken notes so I've done it with training or something like that</p> <p>I: It funny because a lot of people tell you they don't do structured reflection but then when they think or talk about it, they say "actually yes I do"</p> <p>A14: Yeah well after we have meetings we have a sort of catch up and a time for people to bring up any challenges or reflect or bring things to the group so we do have a sort of time there</p>	<p>Reflection with colleagues</p>

	<p>when people can bring thoughts like “well I had this or tried this” and people can say “well yes I had the same and did you try this” and I think that’s where we try to do it as a team and I think we did this before revalidation when some of us had not done reflection before and we wondered what did it mean and what did it mean in true life? So, we thought if we add it into our monthly meeting and the actual process then hopefully people will see that we’re actually doing it so yes, we do it in that shape or form probably</p>	
<p>Emancipatory</p>	<p>I: Ok we’re going to move on now to some of the wider organisational factors that shape wound management. So, do you ever encounter anything in practice that you think restricts or limits your ability to carry out wound management to the best of your ability?</p> <p>A14: Ok well I suppose.....there are structures in place and I think they’re helpful for instance formularies. So, I think formularies.....we’re on the formulary committee...well not the committee but the sub-group for wounds so I think that having that input and having all the specialists on the group to have that input makes us feel we’re being listened to and actually have a choice with the products that are going to be there. So that is a part of the structures that are going to be there. I think things that can limit it....sometimes the people who are clinicians who use the formulary don’t really</p>	

<p>Protocols, formularies, guidelines & tools (restrictive)</p>	<p>realise they can come off formulary and they sometimes think they have to stick with it; people who are prescribers do realise they can come off but they tend to have a rationale for it; in the hospital its harder to come off formulary but you still can and I think the challenge with getting a contract is that.....theres so much products out there that its sometimes deciding which ones you're going to put on formularyI think that the contract process does you give choices but I think because it has to be a very legal structured process it actually can miss some of the clinical side of things so up until now we've not had any issues about having to go with the first ranked and we've been able to choose and look at the product locally and that hasn't been challenged so that's made it easier for us and I think as specialists theres never an issue if we want to get thing non-stock so we have a very good relationship with procurement here and with the clinical service supply manager; if we want to try new things they are made available so the specialists have access to things. So I think we've probably got very good working relationships with formulary pharmacists and procurement that allows changes to be made and ability to get access to therapies and things....emm...I think.....(long pause).....they do change the rules from time to time and that can be a bit challenging...so I think that's actually where it can get a bit challenging is making sure</p>	<p>Protocols, formularies, guidelines & tools (restrictive)</p>
<p>Too many products (overwhelming)</p>	<p>that.....theres so much products out there that its sometimes deciding which ones you're going to put on formularyI think that the contract process does you give choices but I think because it has to be a very legal structured process it actually can miss some of the clinical side of things so up until now we've not had any issues about having to go with the first ranked and we've been able to choose and look at the product locally and that hasn't been challenged so that's made it easier for us and I think as specialists theres never an issue if we want to get thing non-stock so we have a very good relationship with procurement here and with the clinical service supply manager; if we want to try new things they are made available so the specialists have access to things. So I think we've probably got very good working relationships with formulary pharmacists and procurement that allows changes to be made and ability to get access to therapies and things....emm...I think.....(long pause).....they do change the rules from time to time and that can be a bit challenging...so I think that's actually where it can get a bit challenging is making sure</p>	<p>Too much information (products, overwhelming)</p>
<p>RICH</p>	<p>that.....theres so much products out there that its sometimes deciding which ones you're going to put on formularyI think that the contract process does you give choices but I think because it has to be a very legal structured process it actually can miss some of the clinical side of things so up until now we've not had any issues about having to go with the first ranked and we've been able to choose and look at the product locally and that hasn't been challenged so that's made it easier for us and I think as specialists theres never an issue if we want to get thing non-stock so we have a very good relationship with procurement here and with the clinical service supply manager; if we want to try new things they are made available so the specialists have access to things. So I think we've probably got very good working relationships with formulary pharmacists and procurement that allows changes to be made and ability to get access to therapies and things....emm...I think.....(long pause).....they do change the rules from time to time and that can be a bit challenging...so I think that's actually where it can get a bit challenging is making sure</p>	<p>Too much information (products, overwhelming)</p>
<p>Protocols, guidelines, formularies & tools (mdt relationships)</p>	<p>that.....theres so much products out there that its sometimes deciding which ones you're going to put on formularyI think that the contract process does you give choices but I think because it has to be a very legal structured process it actually can miss some of the clinical side of things so up until now we've not had any issues about having to go with the first ranked and we've been able to choose and look at the product locally and that hasn't been challenged so that's made it easier for us and I think as specialists theres never an issue if we want to get thing non-stock so we have a very good relationship with procurement here and with the clinical service supply manager; if we want to try new things they are made available so the specialists have access to things. So I think we've probably got very good working relationships with formulary pharmacists and procurement that allows changes to be made and ability to get access to therapies and things....emm...I think.....(long pause).....they do change the rules from time to time and that can be a bit challenging...so I think that's actually where it can get a bit challenging is making sure</p>	<p>Protocols, guidelines, formularies & tools (mdt relationships)</p>
<p>Overwhelming choice & information (barrier)</p>	<p>that.....theres so much products out there that its sometimes deciding which ones you're going to put on formularyI think that the contract process does you give choices but I think because it has to be a very legal structured process it actually can miss some of the clinical side of things so up until now we've not had any issues about having to go with the first ranked and we've been able to choose and look at the product locally and that hasn't been challenged so that's made it easier for us and I think as specialists theres never an issue if we want to get thing non-stock so we have a very good relationship with procurement here and with the clinical service supply manager; if we want to try new things they are made available so the specialists have access to things. So I think we've probably got very good working relationships with formulary pharmacists and procurement that allows changes to be made and ability to get access to therapies and things....emm...I think.....(long pause).....they do change the rules from time to time and that can be a bit challenging...so I think that's actually where it can get a bit challenging is making sure</p>	<p>Overwhelming choice & information (barrier)</p>
<p>Protocols, guideline, formularies & tools (access issues) barrier</p>	<p>that.....theres so much products out there that its sometimes deciding which ones you're going to put on formularyI think that the contract process does you give choices but I think because it has to be a very legal structured process it actually can miss some of the clinical side of things so up until now we've not had any issues about having to go with the first ranked and we've been able to choose and look at the product locally and that hasn't been challenged so that's made it easier for us and I think as specialists theres never an issue if we want to get thing non-stock so we have a very good relationship with procurement here and with the clinical service supply manager; if we want to try new things they are made available so the specialists have access to things. So I think we've probably got very good working relationships with formulary pharmacists and procurement that allows changes to be made and ability to get access to therapies and things....emm...I think.....(long pause).....they do change the rules from time to time and that can be a bit challenging...so I think that's actually where it can get a bit challenging is making sure</p>	<p>Protocols, guidelines, formularies & tools (access issues/barriers)</p>

<p>Protocols, guideline, formularies & tools (access issues)barrier</p>	<p>that the patients can get the products.....that's slightly harder in hospital than it is in community I would say, if it's in community you can get it on prescription as long as somebody can write the prescription and theres a reason for it; care homes it can be a real challenge because GPs will question everything and it's about having everything in place and getting advice from a specialist makes it easier to get access so I think there can be barriers and different areas have different barriers...yeah....so....does that answer your question?</p>	<p>Protocols, guidelines, formularies & tools (access issues/barriers)</p>
<p>Different areas have different barriers</p>	<p>I: Yeah, absolutely and how well organised do you think wound management practice is on a bigger scale? So, is it consistently resourced, is it equitable to most patients depending on where they live or....do you think it's quite well delivered?</p>	<p>Different areas have different barriers</p>
<p>Wound management services are fair and consistent</p>	<p>A14: Yeah, I don't think there is a postcode lottery in our health board, so in NHSXXX the formulary is across all areas; if they can only access things on prescription then the majority of people have access to that so I would say that maybe across Scotland different health boards do different things and so some of them will have gone for first choice or first ranked on contract and not looked at anything else and so if theres issues with that then patients may feel that they're not getting the best dressing or the best treatment and "how's my auntie getting this treatment and I'm not?" so I think that's where there might be an inequity although that might</p>	<p>Wound management services are fair & consistent</p>
<p>Different areas do things differently (national level)</p>	<p>Different access to resources nationally</p>	<p>Inconsistent services national level</p>
<p>Different access to resources nationally</p>	<p>Difficulty to product access</p>	<p>Inconsistent services national level</p>

<p>Organisational factors (barriers)</p> <p>Patients get service they need</p>	<p>just be a perception of an inequity because if the product is doing the same thing its maybe just looking slightly different and the patient may not quite understand that. So, I don't think that there issues getting products but I think the issues are the processes behind that so if your health board doesn't say "I want that product" and stock it in the big shed, you're not going to get that product but I think that would apply to everywhere. So sometimes I think processes within health boards can stop staff from getting access to something but sometimes it's not picked up because if its only one person here and one person there; unless somebody links that up as being a multiple problem and actually the big issue is up here; so actually, I don't think theres an issue with people getting what they need</p>	<p>Inconsistent services national level (product access)</p> <p>Organisational factors barriers</p> <p>Services provision is fair</p>
<p>Certain wound organisations have power</p>	<p>I: Ok that good, and is there any particular group or health care professional within wound care that you think has power in comparison to other ones? Or do you think that there are any wound care clinicians that carry more power than others? Now that could be good power, I don't necessarily mean that in a negative sense</p>	<p>Wound organisations have power</p>
<p>RICH</p>	<p>A14: Well, the first thing that pops into my head is the XXXX in XXXX...that's the one that pops into my head and I know they've changed their name over the years and I think that's one that had a lot of good work come out of over the years....I do wonder if.....some people</p>	<p>Specialist individual power</p>
<p>Leaders in wound management tissue viability have power</p>		
<p>Specialist individual power</p>		

<p>Those in power can be supported by industry (potential bias)</p>	<p>can be very positive and have influence that..... I do wonder if it's the best influence, if that makes sense....not from a wound management point of view. I think that XXXX has got a lot of clout. I don't know her personally but I know she's very vocal and she's very.....she's got a route into NHSXXX and things like that and I know she has a lot of influence there but one thing I'm not sure about is how much she is influenced by companies because there a lot of things that she does where she seems to be supported or.....and speaking on behalf of. And I find that difficult to separate out; a clinician who's got an ethical and moral "that's my speciality and I'm going to push it forward" but I'm not sure how much it is supported by industry. And I think that's where there does need to be a partnership but I think it's difficult from the outside to separate the two and one thing I've noticed there is a tissue viability Facebook page...I think it's a great idea, a closed Facebook group where people can just share so you have to answer so many questions and the admin decide if you can get on it; you have to be a tissue viability nurse in a tissue viability role to get in this group and the idea is to share challenges, give some advice and get ideas; so I think it is a really good idea but the people who run it are becoming quite big names and I don't know if it's through XXXX but I think a lot of these things are linked through wounds and again that's a company and it's just</p>	<p>Specialist individual power</p>
<p>Ethical engagement with industry</p>		<p>Specialist individual power (industry support & bias)</p>
<p>Specialist power through social media groups</p>		<p>Ethical engagement with industry</p>
<p>Specialist power groups</p>		<p>Specialist power through social media</p>
<p>Industry bias (power)</p>		<p>Specialist group power</p>
<p>Specialist power groups</p>		<p>Specialist power (industry support & bias)</p>
<p>Specialist power groups</p>	<p>Specialist group power</p>	

<p>Specialist individual power</p>	<p>that.....I don't have any issues at all, they are just clinicians who are very happy to speak out on behalf of tissue viability and try to get the best for their patients so I think there are people who have got influence and have got a voice and are young and coming up and have a lot of oomph and ideas which is great and I think they can make a difference so yeah, theres a lot of people out there who vie for that position but I don't think theres a lot of people who actually are in it and have influence at that level. And there are some people who are actually really quiet and influential.....emm...I discovered quite recently...like XXXX, she's involved in the XXX and the XXXX but she's a very quiet, very reflective person but she's got involved with the XXXX and the work nationally so she's a very quiet person and she's not pushing herself but she's in there and I think there can be people who are quietly influencing and making a difference but they've not got a big name for themselves so.....were you talking about people who were maybe more clearly recognised?</p>	<p>Specialist individual power</p>
<p>Specialist Individual Power</p>	<p>I: Well yeah maybe not even tissue viability nurses, it can be other disciplines</p>	<p>Specialist individual power</p>
<p>Specialist individual power</p>	<p>A14: Yeah you know theres other people like XXXX with the diabetic foot; I mean he's very very influential and I think he pushes for his speciality and he's very much up there and he's very, you know his patients come</p>	<p>Specialist individual power</p>

<p>Increased awareness of wounds at national level</p>	<p>first and his people skills maybe need a bit of work...not with the patients but with the staff but if you get on with him he is fine and there are people who were influential in the past who seemed to have dropped off the radar...people like xxxx who is still there but under the radar and...so.....yeah</p>	
<p>Increased awareness of wounds at national level</p>	<p>I: Ok just one more question in this section; what about and wider or social or political or organisational factors....you kind of mentioned the whole formulary process and you know, procurement and things like that...access to products but what about wider social and political factors? Does anything pop into your mind about how they might impact-either positively or negatively?</p>	<p>Increased awareness of wounds at national level</p>
<p>Increased awareness of chronic wounds at national level</p>	<p>A14: Yeah I suppose theres the big discussions that are going on in government about leg ulcers and lower limb and Legs Matter and that and I think that's really positive because it comes not just from clinicians but from a whole group of organisations and I think the fact that they're all working together and its interesting someone showed us a link to an MP's experience with having a leg ulcer and she was sharing that to the group to the committee and I thought that that was really powerful that people are actually sharing their experiences and what it means and the challenges and things so its...I think that's really good that Legs Matter has become really high profile and I think wounds for a long time has</p>	<p>Increased awareness of wounds at national level</p>

<p>Increased awareness of chronic wounds at national level</p>	<p>been quite low profile and I think you know cancer and heart disease and all these things have been really up there but I think they've realise-especially chronic wounds, I think they've realised the impact that chronic wounds have on patients and life and budgets is huge. So, I think that's where work has come out of as well, prevention and leg ulcer work has come from that so I think it's good that it has been recognised and I hope that it does develop and they continue to do something about it. But yeah, I think it has to be recognised at quite a high level for things to change and happen</p> <p>I: Yeah, I agree and I think that pressure ulcers came first and that was a big thing for the past few years and I'm actually quite glad that finally legs and lower limb ulcers are getting the recognition because it's been a long time coming</p> <p>A14: Yes, and I think they'll probably be other things that will come afterwards but they're the big ones that we see anyway; they're the burdens on health care on people on families, on costs for everything, so yeah, I think.....yeah.....it's good that its actually finally happening</p>	<p>Increased awareness of wounds at national level</p>
<p>Summary</p>	<p>I: Ok just one or two summary questions and that's us done. We've talked about a lot of different types and sources of wound management knowledge; how well integrated do you think these are for you? Do</p>	

<p>Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors</p> <p>My knowledge gets more integrated over time</p> <p>RICH</p> <p>Intuition is the integration of different knowledge types at subconscious level</p> <p>Intuition is the integration of different knowledge types</p>	<p>you think they're separate entities, do you think any are dominant and do you think you are able to integrate them? And you've probably already answered this without answering the question directly</p> <p>A14: I would agree, it's not just about the wound and you have to consider other factors because people want to know about the dressings they put on and that's where they start but actually that's the last thing you think about because if you don't assess your patient and look at the underlying aetiologies then you're not going to-it doesn't matter what dressing you put on its not going to make a difference or very little chance of it....no I would say.....and it's probably become more integrated over time...you know I think it's something that over time you do more of, so you link everything together better so....</p> <p>I: I think when you mentioned intuition that was a really powerful answer because you said that intuition is not just intuition; it actually is the integration of all these things at a kind of subconscious level maybe</p> <p>A14: Yeah, I think that's actually what it is; it's actually the subconscious, the fact that you're processing it without actually thinking about it and probably when you're newer doing it you're probably doing that processing in your head in live time. So you're looking at the patient and you're thinking "I wonder what that's like, I wonder</p>	<p>Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors</p> <p>My knowledge integration increases over time</p> <p>Intuition is the integration of different knowledge types at subconscious level</p> <p>Intuition is the integration of different knowledge types at</p>
---	--	---

<p>at subconscious level. Comes with experience</p>	<p>what is going on, has it got signs of infection” and you’re actually thinking it in real time whereas I think when you get to the stage when you have a lot more knowledge and experience in your head you look at it and you go “well actually theres this this this and this” and you have to do that not having to think it through its come out as something I have to do and I’ve only spent 5 minutes looking at it or less than because you’ve done that integration of everything so it becomes almost a subconscious process and that’s something that you step back from when you’re teaching somebody else you do that “right what have I thought through before I’ve come to that conclusion” so what do I need to do to ask that question to that student or staff nurse to say “well right what are you looking for?” What are we looking for or what are my processes? Because I think it does, it becomes a kind of subconscious process like that</p> <p>I: Ok good and finally if you could change something about current wound management practice, what would it be?</p> <p>A14:EH.....(pause) if I could change one thing? Or more than one thing?</p> <p>I: You could say more than one thing</p> <p>A14: I think something that could assess the wound bed itself for things like.....and I’ve no idea whether there are things out there like this</p>	<p>subconscious level. Comes with experience</p>
---	--	--

<p>RICH</p> <p>More innovative diagnostic tools would improve wound management</p> <p>More innovative diagnostic tools (cost is barrier)</p>	<p>for.....has it got bacterial biofilm and levels of.....are the cells actually multiplying and dividing, have we got dead cells that are not doing anything, have we got MMPs that are.....have we got growth factors....you know information about the wound in an easy format so that you could then go “right our thing is this one therefore we need to address the MMP levels or our issue is dead cells so we need to look at debriding the wound or actually its bacteria that’s the issue but they’re in a biofilm so we need to do this. To me it’s looking at the cellular level and what’s actually going on in a wound because I could look at a wound and with all my knowledge and experience, I could go “right this is what we need to do at the moment, we’ll do A, B and C. And four weeks down the line we stalled again and then we need to go back and look at it again because we can’t physically see anything so we then have to go with our intuition of whatever else could be the issues here. I’m not seeing signs of infection so it’s not that so maybe it’s the growth factors and MMP so let’s go with a product that will do that so let’s try that for a few weeks so if you could narrow down what’s going on at a cellular level then I think you could make a more informed decision and actually target your treatment better so that you’re not just thinking about a dressing. And you’re not just going we’ll go A first and then B and then C. And that’s the way we have to go in wounds right now...you know it is its pick and choose what kind of dressing am I</p>	<p>More innovative diagnostic tools would improve wound management</p> <p>More innovative diagnostic tools would improve wound management</p> <p>Cost as a barrier</p>
--	---	--

	<p>going to choose, which products am I going to choose to do this. The thing is theres things that the companies have brought out, theres one at the moment that...theres various things that you can dip in your wound...I mean the other day we were talking about PH in wounds and I said "maybe we should go back to litmus paper" and we talk about changing the PH balance and how that can change healing. Yeah so theres a product out just now that's meant to pick up if there is bacteria in the wound form an image of a wound but you have to be in complete darkness to use this thing and its meant to be able to pick up thermal imaging or something so there are things out there that companies are trying to develop and look at but I'm not sure that they're looking at them in quite the way that...like if I was looking at a wound as a nurse hoe am I going to black a room to look at their wound? So, I think the ideas and things are starting to come out but they're not practical enough and that's just my thought that it needs to be at that level for wounds that are not progressing, if you're looking at chronic wounds. Because I think general wounds, we put a dressing on , they heal and its ok but I think it's the wounds that we know are going to become chronic because of the underlying aetiologies or the ones that become chronic that's the ones that we need to have more focused information on what's actually happening</p>	
--	--	--

	<p>I: So, some kind of more advanced assessment?</p> <p>A14: Yeah absolutely. And something that's also usable by staff and can be done at the bedside and that is affordable because I think that's important because it is a challenge in the NHS and that may be the challenge, we can't actually do it because the costs are too high and if something could do all those things then that would be great rather than having a half a dozen different things</p> <p>I: Thank you so much. I think unless there is something else you need to say we can end the interview 1:11</p>	
--	--	--

Appendix 14: Sample Initial Coding Sweep (Data Analysis) Generalist Nurse

Data Analysis G11 Free text analysis	Transcript	Codes
<p>Knowledge in General</p> <p>Learning from colleagues in practice CPD & learning from TVNs practice Reading textbooks Learning from reps Bias of company information</p> <p>Pictures in textbooks and literature</p> <p>Learning from reps Bias of company information</p> <p>Learning from students</p> <p>RICH</p>	<p>I: Thank you for coming. I'm just going to start off asking you a couple of generic questions about wound management. And the first thing I'd like to ask is where you think the knowledge you apply to wound management comes from?</p> <p>B11: I suppose in the beginning I came from a background of acute medical to the community; at lot of my knowledge at first came from peers...emmm....and the knowledge they had passed down but after a while you think "oooh! Is what they're doing quite right?" so you would be looking further afield like going to tissue viability days, emmm....looking in books....I like pictures so pictures for me are something I quite like to look at....emmm. no so much...we used to get...but they've stopped reps coming in and we used to get some of the knowledge from them and then I know they say it's a bit biased but some of the knowledge they had was quite good; you wouldn't always take it as first hand ; you'd go away and kind of analyse it because obviously you've got a bit of bias because they want to sell you their products.....emmm... Sometimes we get knowledge from students if they've been in an area like dermatology or with the vascular nurse or....I think there a wide range of places you get knowledge from....emmm (pause)</p> <p>I: Good, I think you're the first person who has mentioned students so that's really interesting and true because</p>	<p>Learning from colleagues in practice Importance of structured education Learning from formal Evidence & literature Learning from companies Bias of company information</p> <p>Learning from formal evidence and literature</p> <p>Learning from companies Bias of company information</p> <p>Learning from colleagues in practice</p>

<p>Learning from students Experiential learning</p>	<p>depending on where they've been or what their interests are</p> <p>B11: Some of them are mature students and have maybe been an auxiliary or worked in TV or vascular so they've seen things that you might not have thought of actually</p> <p>I: Yeah that's very true. And you mentioned reps and that you found some of their education quite useful; so, do you think there is a role for reps? Or do you think wound care industry has a role?</p>	<p>Learning from colleagues in practice Experiential learning that develops over time</p>
<p>Evidence from companies Company information has a role</p>	<p>B11: I think so because there was a book given to us by reps and we've still got it and we give it to students and it had all the different types of wounds and products you may use on them and its quite a good book for students because you've got all the different brand names but this one was quite specific like alginates, hydrogels, emmm.....foams-although we're kind of getting away from using foams but the information from that book alone was quite good; it wasn't just company focused; although at the back it had all their products at the kind of start of the book it broke it all down and it was useful</p> <p>I; And that was useful? Good, ok. And do you think, so you've described a couple of different sources of knowledge or types of knowledge; do you think anyone is more important? Do you think there is one that's maybe more important than others or do you think that they all have their place?</p>	<p>Learning from companies Usefulness of company I information</p>
<p>Bias of company information Company information is useful Autonomous practitioners can make decisions about companies</p>	<p>B11: I think they all have their place but I think you need to make your own mind up as an autonomous practitioner. Like what I find is, I work with different</p>	<p>Important role of wound care industry Bias of company Information Autonomy to see company bias</p>

<p>Learning from colleagues in practice but making own decisions</p>	<p>nurses and not that their knowledge or what they were saying is wrong; but.....I suppose I like to find out my own way; like, what they were saying.....I don't know how to explain it.....so two of them could go to the patient and do totally different things and not that any one of them is wrong but I like to look and see which well which one might have been slightly better and why did they do it that way because it's more of a kind of holistic thing so.....although you learned from your peers it was probably going to like study days and doing your own thing and increasing your knowledge but at a personal.....at a personal level</p>	<p>Learning from colleagues in practice Would management knowledge is integrated and contextual</p>
<p>Consideration of holistic factors in wound management knowledge</p>	<p>so.....although you learned from your peers it was probably going to like study days and doing your own thing and increasing your knowledge but at a personal.....at a personal level</p>	<p>Consideration and Integration of wider holistic factors in Wound Management</p>
<p>Learning from CPD Learning from colleagues in practice Putting own slant on it</p>	<p>I: Uh huh, so a kind of personal source of knowledge? B11: Mmm hmmm.</p>	<p>Learning from structured education</p>
<p>Personal nature of wound management knowledge</p>	<p>I: yeah that's really interesting, and is there any one person or type of source that you think you've learned most of your knowledge in wound management?</p>	<p>Wound management knowledge is Integrated and contextual</p>
<p>Prescribing knowledge improved my wound management knowledge</p>	<p>B11:I think when I became a nurse prescriberthat.....I learned more knowledge because if I was prescribing I would need to look at a certain product and if it was effective, how long was it going to last before I changed it; so, I think becoming a nurse prescriber and doing that course <i>made</i> me look for more knowledge myself; but there are certain peers that I go to that I know are very knowledgeable; if I don't know, they'll point me in the right direction</p>	<p>Prescribing improved my wound management knowledge</p>
<p>Learning from colleagues in practice</p>	<p>I: Ok and they like other DN or Community colleagues? B11: Yeah</p>	<p>Learning from colleagues in practice Those with passion take on wound management</p>
<p>Other DN colleagues</p>	<p>I: Ok and they like other DN or Community colleagues? B11: Yeah</p>	<p>Learning from colleagues in practice Those with passion take on wound management</p>

<p>DN colleagues with a particular interest in wound management</p>	<p>I: So, within your own profession?</p> <p>B11: Mmm hmm.</p> <p>I: And are they maybe folk who just have an interest in wound management or have done extra training or are known in the area as being someone with a particular interest?</p>	<p>Learning from colleagues in practice Those with a passion take on wound management</p>
<p>Learning from colleagues in practice Reflection with colleagues in practice</p>	<p>B11: Just a particular interest really. Some people are more knowledgeable than others...or like, the more you work in an area you know where you can turn basically if you were like "oh I've got this problem, I know who can solve it or help me with it" so you kind of reach out with all your peers but that's getting to know everybody and being in the job for a wee while</p>	<p>Learning from colleagues in practice Learning from colleagues in practice Reflection with colleagues in practice</p>
<p>TVN was good source of knowledge</p> <p>Learning from colleagues in practice</p>	<p>I: So, kind of picking all the knowledge from experience and kind of putting it all together?</p> <p>B11: I think.....see when the pressure safety cross came in and we had to contact the TVN? Well, I was kind of new in post then and I feel she was quite a good source of knowledge. When you met up to assess the patient you could ask her "why you doing that?" and "what do you think about this?" and.....kind of.....could get a wee bit of knowledge at that point in time</p>	<p>Learning from colleagues in practice Power of TVN role</p>
<p>Not a lot of education in pre-reg</p>	<p>I: Good, excellent. And how good, do you think you've been given the right educational preparation to carry out wound management? So that could either be a pre-reg level; or a CPD level; do you feel you've been given enough education in wound management?</p> <p>B11: I think.....naw.....naw..like at pre-reg I trained and qualified</p>	<p>Lack of structured education in pre-reg</p> <p>Lack of contextualised wound management education in pre-reg</p>

<p>In pre-reg colleagues didn't explain wound management knowledge in context</p> <p>Informal learning in practice not structured</p> <p>No structured formal wound management education</p>	<p>over ten years ago now and I don't remember at pre-reg there being-there may well have been but I don't remember-maybe that not what I was focused on at the time but I don't remember lots of wounds.....and a lot of the time, even being in placement nobody really properly explained thing to you, like why they were using specific dressings and things, it was just what was available in their cupboard if it was on the board. There was no rationale as to why they were doing something; like what they were doing and why they were doing it....emmm...I've not done any official courses it's been like in the DN course, that's been a refresher...emmm.....my own study, form peers, but I've never done an official TV course or anything</p>	<p>Experiential knowledge that developed over time</p> <p>Unstructured informal learning in practice</p> <p>Lack of structured education in pre-reg</p>
<p>Empiric</p> <p>Evidence comes from CPD and refreshers</p> <p>Evidence comes from peers</p>	<p>I: Ok, no that's good. And to what extent would you say that your wound management is evidence based and scientific?</p> <p>B11:.....Well I suppose when you assess anythingyou've got to assess like, what the wound is, the type of wound it is....and I suppose how do you know all this? But you know it from like, peers, form getting refresher courses; we attended.....ehh....a seminaryou were at it in fact, what was it called? The one at xxxx.....</p> <p>I: Oh, uh huh, the xxxxxx.....were you there?</p> <p>B11: Aye. So, I went to that, so things like that; this all refreshes your knowledge</p> <p>I: So, kind of CPD, updates; what about, do you get anything in-house? Like you know in the NHS? Like in your health board do you get any wound</p>	<p>Evidence comes from structured education</p> <p>Learning from colleagues in practice (evidence comes from peers)</p> <p>No structured wound management education</p>

<p>No structured NHS wound management education Online learning</p>	<p>management education or CPD?</p> <p>B11: Not really, you've got like Learn Pros but they're more like aseptic technique andtheres nothing on wound management</p> <p>I: Nothing on wound management?</p>	<p>No structured wound management education</p>
<p>Missing from wound management</p>	<p>B11: That's something that's missing actually</p> <p>I: Ok, I know in xxx there was one on PUP because I was involved in that at the time but that just might be xxx so I'm not really sure. Ok thanks that's really helpful so just moving on, are there any guidelines or protocols that you are aware of or would routinely use or refer t in your wound management practice?</p>	<p>Formularies, protocols & tools</p>
<p>Assessment tools and guidance</p>	<p>B11: I know I'm saying this is recent but it's probably not; it's probably been awhile because you lose track of time but there was one on skin tears in the elderly; not to put like, put adhesives on that, just to use like a contact layer and maybe bandage that up....emm....and maybe leave it a bit longer to let it heal up; that was one because we were finding, especially if they went to casualty people were coming home with steri-strips on elderly skin and you were like "oh no! how am I going to get like, get that off?" or they were sticking like a xxxx on and just the same you were</p>	<p>Formularies, protocols & tools</p>
<p>National and local protocols and guidelines</p> <p>RICH</p> <p>Consideration of holistic factors in wound management</p>	<p>damaging the tissue trying to get the dressing off so.....and you've got all your PU safety cross and you're thinking more of a holistic thing, like the pressure, the diet, the surfaces, the incontinence....emmmm....and there is.....when you're a nurse prescriber....like I'm NHSXXX , theres quite a lot on leg ulcers; before you prescribe anything it</p>	<p>Prescribing has improved my wound management knowledge Consideration and Integration of wider holistic factors in wound management</p> <p>Formularies, protocols & tools</p>

<p>Practical policies rather than national theoretical guidelines</p> <p>Practical policies rather than national theoretical guidelines</p>	<p>B11:.....Just your aseptic technique.....emmm.....thinking obviously you're limited to your aseptic technique and how you carry out something because it's not going to be perfectly sterile in community.....and you've got your antimicrobials.....your polices regarding them and their overuse.....you tend not to use antimicrobials in practice now....kind of shying away from that...so</p>	<p>Formularies, Protocols & Tools (Local Protocols)</p> <p>Formularies, protocols & tools (local protocols)</p>
<p>Aesthetic</p> <p>Creative dressing technique in hard-to-reach wounds</p> <p>Creative dressing technique when supplies aren't readily available</p> <p>Creative dressing technique in hard-to-reach wounds</p>	<p>I: Ok, excellent that really helpful....and this might sound like a kind of funny question but do you bring any artistic skills or creative skills to wound management?</p> <p>B11: I suppose if you're gonny dress an elbow or a toe or any kind of hard to dress area you've got to be creative because sometimes, especially in the community if it's just referral that's come in from a carer or something and you're going to assess the situation you might not have the size of dressing in your bag because most things are patient prescriptions now; so sometimes you've got to be a wee bit artistic or creative on how you dress something to the best of what you've got....so you can order up what you need</p> <p>I: Ok so would you say that's a kind of technical skill or technique, like to put dressings on or trying to do the best with what you can?</p> <p>B11: Probably a bit of both....ehh... a bit of both I would say because you learn from your peers as well like if they've had a hard to dress area; like we work weekends so sometimes you're covering other people's practices so I know that you're going in to such and such a patient and it's a hard area to</p>	<p>Dressing technique & utilisation of supplies</p> <p>Dressing technique & utilisation of supplies</p> <p>Dressing technique & utilisation of supplies</p>

<p>Creative dressing technique when supplies are limited</p>	<p>dress but what we've found is that if you do it this way, it's easier or the dressing will stay on better so it's probably a bit of both</p>	<p>Dressing technique & Utilisation of Supplies</p>
<p>Learning from colleagues in practice Experiential learning in practice</p>	<p>I: Well, I guess that sort of answers my question which is can you give me some examples from practice where you would take a creative approach to wound management? So, do you consider wound management to be more of a science or an art?</p>	<p>Learning from colleagues in practice</p>
<p>Wound management is both a science and an art</p>	<p>B11: Have I got to pick one or the other? (laughs)</p>	<p>Experiential learning over time</p>
<p>Science of tissue healing is scientific</p>	<p>I: No, you're free to answer however you like</p>	<p>Science and an art</p>
<p>Science of tissue healing is scientific</p>	<p>B11: I suppose they could be both because scientifically a wound is going to heal the same but you're going to have variations and you're going to have wound beds that are all different; so you need to know the scientific way of how to treat these things; for example if you've got a cavity it's got to be packed for it to heal from the inside out but the artistic side of things could be you have got to get a wee bit creative especially in somebody's house with space, even positioning and.....time to get a dressing in a hard to reach area that's gonny fit and be comfortable for the patients so it probably could fit into both</p>	<p>Evidence of tissue repair</p>
<p>Creative technique in difficult to manage wounds Creative technique when supplies are limited Being creative so dressings stay in place and are comfortable</p>	<p>I: And can you give me some examples of how you might establish meaningful relationships or connections with your patients when you're carrying out wound management in practice? I suppose you could apply the question to any area of nursing but is there anything you do or any way you encourage relationships with your patients?</p>	<p>Dressing technique & utilisation of supplies</p>
<p>Being creative so dressings stay in place and are comfortable</p>	<p>I: And can you give me some examples of how you might establish meaningful relationships or connections with your patients when you're carrying out wound management in practice? I suppose you could apply the question to any area of nursing but is there anything you do or any way you encourage relationships with your patients?</p>	<p>Dressing technique & utilisation of supplies</p>

<p>Consideration of wider holistic factors in wound management</p> <p>Building relationships and finding out what is important out them</p> <p>Communication</p> <p>Person-centredness</p> <p>Wound management is individualised</p>	<p>B11: I suppose one of the most things I think is like....not be like...like “ this is what you’ve got to do and why you’ve got to do it”</p> <p>If you can build a....a kind of a.....if you can ask questions to see.....I suppose you gather a lot of information form even a patient’s surroundings and how their lifestyle is and...I mean especially with maybe younger physically disabled people; their wound healing maybe sometimes isn’t their first focus; they could have children, their social life might be more important so I think you need to establish, maybe what’s important to them before you even try to look at the wound and how you’re gonny heal it because you might have to come to some compromises; like, well, if you’re not gonny go on bed rest if it’s a PU you might need to sit up for short periods of time, go back to bed but.....I think you build that up by <i>not</i> telling somebody what to do; well it’s like they understand what my feelings and thoughts and what I want my life to be then they’ll take on board what you say <i>also</i>. It’s not....I don’t think it’s a simple thing, it’s quite a complex thing actually...to come to an agreement with the patient ...of....sorry have I distracted from that question?</p>	<p>Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors in wound Management</p> <p>Creativity in forming relationships</p> <p>Creativity in forming relationships</p> <p>Wound management is individualised & contextualised</p>
<p>Consideration of wider holistic factors in wound management</p> <p>Persona centredness and fitting needs to meet patient</p>	<p>I: No, no on the contrary that’s a really good answer because what I’m trying to do is capture nursing knowledge and I think what you’ve done is really sum up what makes nursing knowledge distinct</p>	<p>Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors in wound management</p> <p>Creativity in forming relationships</p> <p>Wound management is individualised & contextualised</p>
<p>RICH</p> <p>Complexity of coming to an agreement with patient</p>	<p>B11: See cos I came from acute; you’ve got more control in the acute side in that what you can expect the patient to do and they’re mostly following your kind of lead; whereas in the community I think you’ve got to</p>	<p>Creativity in forming relationships</p>

<p>Person centredness Distinction of community</p> <p>Consideration of wider holistic factors of wound management</p> <p>Person centredness Consideration of wider holistic factors in wound management Distinction of community</p> <p>Importance of building relationships with patients</p> <p>Creativity in building relationships and communication</p>	<p>follow the patient's lead to a certain extent; because that's their home, that's their life and they're letting you in.....</p> <p>I: yeah in and they're not really in a controlled institutionalised environment, you're in their home as a guest?</p> <p>B11: And I think you've got to build that relationship up where, if they're going to do something and you're thinking "why is that wound breaking down?" you've to let that..... "If you're sitting up for four hours, just tell me because we need to know why the wound is breaking down because if it's not that, it could be something else, it could be infection blah blah blah so I think you've got to build those relationships up and sort of trust and if they do something and you're thinking "oh gosh, why did they do that?" but you're not really derogatory to that, like "(scolding) you shouldn't have done that!", you're like "right, never mind, let's get on track again"</p> <p>I: So, a lot of that is probably like communication and how you learn to communicate with different people and not get their back up?</p> <p>B11: Mmm hmm.</p>	<p>Distinction of community Wound management is individualised & contextualised</p> <p>Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors in wound management</p> <p>Wound Management is individualised & contextualised</p> <p>Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors in wound management Distinction of community</p> <p>Creativity in forming relationships</p> <p>Creativity in forming relationships</p>
<p>Ethical</p> <p>Do good not harm</p>	<p>I: That's really helpful. Ok, can you give me some examples of how you try to make your wound management ethical?</p> <p>B11: So ethical meaning you're going to do no harm to the patient.....so obviously you wouldn't.....like probably.....like that with the steri-strips, you</p>	<p>Do good not harm</p>

Adhesive dressings and comfort and skin injury	wouldn't (motions pulling off a plaster).....like the frail skin you wouldn't do harm but I suppose	Do good not harm
Unintentional harm due to lack of knowledge and education	sometimes people don't mean to do harm as in if their education isn't up to scratch, that's kind of like harm to the patient.	Do good not harm Unintentional harm
Consent	Obviously you're always going to ask for their consent and eh.....get them to.....eh.....what do you call it?.....involve them	Do good not harm
Autonomy and person-centredness	in the decision about what kind of wound products, what's comfy, they may want a shower every day so you're going to think about something that's maybe water tight....emm....and obviously confidentiality is a big thing...you're not going to tell their neighbour or you'd only tell who needs to	Do good not harm Wound management is individualised & contextualised
Consideration of wider holistic factors in nursing	know...emm....about what you're doing in their house.....and even if theres other people in the house they might not want them to know....we had a girl that had maggots and she didn't want anybody else in the house to know that that's what we were doing so it can even be quite.....close confidentiality	Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors in wound management
Confidentiality	I: Yeah, excellent..umm can you tell me how you'd decide what the best treatments are for each individual patient.....and in your experience in your area of practice is it fairly accessible for everybody ordo some patients get more than others and if they do....why would you think that is? So how do you ensure fairness and equity?	Do good not harm
Wound management is individualised	B11: I would say everyone....I would say we try to be fair and equitable...I suppose....I have seen on other teams theres been a certain person and he has got a position in the community and he does just want everything at the drop of a hat and they sometimes respond but its due to like, he's wrote letters of complaint.....but I suppose that	Wound management is individualised & contextualised
Confidentiality		Do good not harm
RICH		
Try to be fair equitable with service Some patients get more than others if they are recognised members of the community		

Wound management is individualised	isn't fair on the other hand but.....(long pause)....mmm.....but I suppose if.....if anybody needs any wound management you would go and you would assess and you would....not everything works the same for everybody so you would ...certain wounds you <i>would</i> treat differently just so that person's lifestyle....if you're going to get them in, if....eh.....they might have a bit of a chaotic lifestyle so if....some things you would think a bit differently....you might to visit more often.....but it would tend to be quite fair and equitable to everybody.....I would say	Wound management is individualised & contextualised
Fear of complaints		Wound management is individualised & contextualised
Try to ensure fairness and equity of resources		Wound management is individualised & contextualised
Different patients' behaviours sometimes trigger different patient needs	I: so, if you do make any changes in treatment it's because you need to suit the needs or behaviours and it's not because you're being fairer to one person or another?	Wound management is individualised & contextualised Responsible use of resources
Fairness and equity of patients' needs	B11: No and I think when you're a prescriber as well you're aware of the prices, so you're not going to prescribe something or someone you prefer something a wee bit more expensive, you're not going....you're going...you always try to stick to the same.....(pause)	Wound management is individualised & contextualised
Prescribing has made me more awareness of fairness of resources	I: Dressing? B11: Dressings. I: well actually that was going to be my next question; how much cost comes into it; how much do you consider cost in your day to day wound management practice? Is it quite a big consideration for you or do you think it's someone else's job to worry about cost?	Wound management is individualised & contextualised Prescribing has improved my wound management knowledge
	B11: I think we do consider it because obviously we've got to document it in nursing notes and we've got access to the GP	Wound management is individualised & contextualised

<p>Cost is an important consideration in wound management</p> <p>Individual spend is visible to others</p> <p>Formulary makes you more aware of spend</p> <p>Wound management is individualised</p> <p>Individual patients sometimes need more spend based on needs</p> <p>Prescribing has made me more aware of cost in wound management Individual spend is visible and accountable</p>	<p>notes so obviously you type anything in plus you've got the NHSXXX and its got all the sizes on itsometimes you've got to refer to that so when you're looking at it you might say "well actually, they might not need that; they can get away with that and it's a wee bit cheaper, it works just the same and its maybe better so you do look at cost because at the end of the day you're going to be audited as well; and theres no point in prescribing sometime that's not needed but if you do need it, I would prescribe it; for example I've got a patient who's allergic to quite a lot of different things so sometimes we do need to prescribe off-formulary for her and I think that's a good reason to do that; as long as you can justify</p> <p>I: And would you say that since you've done prescribing, you're more aware of case, has that kind of made you consider it more or do you feel you always did anyway?</p> <p>B11: I think it's made me more aware of considering it; before I was a prescriber you could maybe just ask maybe the GP if they could order up stuff – dressings and they would just do it; they would just take your word for it so I suppose they thought we were looking at those things as well but now we've got pharmacists attached to the GP surgery as well so sometimes she'll actually ask us such and such, like the girl with the allergies "does she need that cos its such and such a price" so I think there are other people looking at it even if you're not a prescriber, theres more people looking at if it is needed, which is probably a good thing actually</p>	<p>Cost consideration & monitoring</p> <p>Cost consideration & monitoring</p> <p>Cost consideration & monitoring</p> <p>Wound management is individualised & contextualised</p> <p>Wound management is individualised & contextualised</p> <p>Prescribing has improved my wound management knowledge</p> <p>Prescribing has improved my wound management knowledge</p>
---	---	--

<p>Resources are monitored</p> <p>Nurses are accountable and can make their own decisions with industry</p> <p>Company information is biased</p> <p>Nurses are accountable and can make their own decisions with wound management</p> <p>Nurses are accountable and can make own decisions about products and engagement with industry</p>	<p>I: yeah, yeah. And we talked a wee bit about wound care industry earlier on; but how-do you think its ethical to engage with wound management industry in practice?</p> <p>B11:.....(Pause).....I suppose if you're ethical as nurse, you're not going to be swayed; you are going to with what's best for your patient; not what someone else says; so, in that respect yes, but you could be argued that you might adjust your thoughts to become biased to certain products. But I think as nurses you know what products are good and bad and rubbish (laughs)...I don't think you can be swayed because at the end of the day; you're looking at your patients and at the end of the day you want these wounds to heal because you want these people off your caseload (laughs) because you've got enough so you're not going to use a product that doesn't work.</p> <p>I: So, it wouldn't really sway you what a rep said; you could make your own mind up you think?</p> <p>B11: Mmm hmm. I mean sometimes we've had reps before and they've said "right well this isn't on formulary but we have these other products we want to show you" and sometimes we've come out and went "that's rubbish. I don't see the point in that, we've got things that we could use and we don't need all that; that probably costs a fortune" so we do talk about it with peers as well, like not in front of the rep probably but like, when we've come out we'll say "I don't think that's any good" or its maybe not necessary</p>	<p>Cost consideration & monitoring</p> <p>Cost consideration & monitoring</p> <p>Autonomy in own decisions Bias</p> <p>Company information Bias</p> <p>Nurses are autonomous Company bias</p> <p>Nurses are autonomous Company bias</p>
<p>Personal</p>	<p>I: Ok, good. And you'll probably think this is kind of strange question but how much of your</p>	

<p>I bring my true self to wound management practice Can't separate from professionalism</p> <p>Importance of communication in wound management practice</p> <p>Different types of knowledge merge</p> <p>Personal relationships important in wound management Importance of communication on wound management</p> <p>Consideration of wider holistic factors in nursing</p> <p>Do good not harm Confidentiality Consent</p>	<p>genuine self do you think you bring to your wound management practice?</p> <p>B11: Do you mean in like the way I approach things?</p> <p>I: It could be the way you approach things....or just....do you bring yourself to your nursing role in wound management? Or is it something that you maybe distance and think of as a professional job-do you think you bring your true self into your day-to-day practice?</p> <p>B11: You probably bring a bit of both because think if you don't bring your true self, like building relationships, seeing what makes people tick, I think that's a skill in itself so if you can't do that, then you're not going to treat the wound because you're not going to really know what the patient needs or wants or feels of thinks or.....and relate that back to your team members.....maybe?</p> <p>I: yeah, I mean theres no right or wrong; but can you give me any examples or is that too kind of difficult to answer?</p> <p>B11:.....I suppose.....we have a young MS patient and I do usually go because I've got quite a good rapport with her.....and she opens up to me because she's quite a.....private person.....I think the more you know somebody, the easier it is to.....treat them. You probably could argue on the other hand that the more you know you might not be able to treat them if you see what I mean?</p> <p>I: yeah, I see both sides, definitely</p> <p>B11: But as a nurse, you're always professional because you're always thinking about the patient and the ethics as well, you don't want to do no harm,</p>	<p>Personal experience shapes wound management Professionalism I bring myself to wound management</p> <p>Creativity in forming relationships</p> <p>Wound management Knowledge is integrated & contextualised</p> <p>Creativity in forming personal relationships</p> <p>Creativity in forming personal relationships</p> <p>Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors in wound management</p> <p>Do good not harm</p>
--	--	--

<p>Distinction of community</p> <p>Experiential learning in practice over time</p> <p>I had to take initiative to learn about wound management due to my own interest</p> <p>Personal reflection in wound management</p> <p>Experiential learning in practice over time</p> <p>Peer reflection in wound management practice</p>	<p>get your consent, maintain confidentiality, so I think you're a bit of both with that; I suppose you've got to give a bit of yourself because your self is your personality and your whole being and the way you act; so, I don't think you kind of..... have one hat and then another hat, I think they both kind of merge I: and this is kind of leading on from that but hopefully maybe a wee bit easier to answer....can you tell me how your personal experiences maybe shape your wound management practice? Or do you think they do?</p> <p>B11: I think they always learn from the experience because I came from the acute to the community and actually.....I'm going to admit I didn't know a lot about some of the wounds and I found it fascinating, like leg ulcers and all these surgical wounds because I never worked in surgical so I did learn on the job but a lot of that was me seeking information because I knew that I was lacking and I didn't want to be seen as incompetent or going to assess somebody and then having to ask somebody else to go if I didn't know what it was....so.....I do think you learn on the job but you do need to do your own reflection and.....learning as well</p> <p>I: Ok so learning from experience what you don't know and maybe need to brush up on and you kind of mentioned reflection; is reflection something you would use quite routinely in your practice?</p> <p>B11: We have a report every day and that's when we talk about any of the patients we been to, you'd reflect with your peers...emmm...like if something wasn't working or something was</p>	<p>Distinction of community</p> <p>Experiential learning in practice</p> <p>Those with a passion lead in wound management</p> <p>Personal reflection</p> <p>Experiential learning in practice</p> <p>Learning form colleagues in practice Reflecting with colleagues</p>
---	---	--

<p>Importance of relationships with colleagues in wound management practice</p>	<p>working really well, you'd reflect on that</p> <p>I: Ok and that's actually another one of my questions that ties in quite well with that is how important do you think your relationships with your colleagues is in wound management?</p>	<p>Learning from colleagues in practice Interprofessional learning</p>
<p>Importance of communication in wound management practice</p>	<p>B11: I think it's very important because.....you need....especially if you've changed something, you need to give it time to see if it's going to help....emm....and obviously, if you've not got good relationships, then everybody is going in and doing their own thing; that's not going to be any good for the patient, nobody is going to be giving any time to....and the patient is going to think "what's going on? Nobody knows what they're doing"</p>	<p>Creativity in forming relationships</p>
<p>Learning from colleagues in practice Peer reflection in practice Contextual</p>	<p>I: So, communicating is important then, but also you mentioned earlier that you quite often reflected as a team so to kind of share learning as well then?</p>	<p>Learning from colleagues in practice Reflecting with colleagues</p>
<p>Importance of communication and relationships in wound management practice</p>	<p>B11: And....agree that maybe this is the right thing to do or maybe go "oh no actually, maybe we should be doing this a bit differently". But we do have quite a close-knit team and our DN sister is quite trusting cos.....she knows us; so, she trusts our judgement on a lot of things but if she had a feeling that were doing something not right she would also say it...emmm....we wouldn't take that offence we would take that as a learning curve....."right ok, that might not be quite the right thing to do so what can we do next time</p> <p>I: Ok, good, ok that good. Eh, ok let's see; can you describe and I think you mentioned very briefly</p>	<p>Creativity in forming relationships</p>

<p>Relationships with TVNs generally good Sometimes problem of acute nurse and community nurse cause friction</p> <p>Distinction of community</p> <p>Acute formulary in community a problem</p> <p>TVN referral process is lengthy and too formal</p>	<p>earlier what your relationship kind of is with TVNs and other specialist that you might involve in wound management in your practice?</p> <p>B11: I think.....mostly in the beginning it was the pressure ulcers when we were doing the PU Safety Cross and we had to advise the TVN for every one that came on your case load or if it was case load acquired so you did get to know your TVN quite well...emm...the only thing recently I would say that we had to get a TVN out it was the one from the hospital andthe only comment that annoys me is.....that they prescribe from the acute formulary and not the community and then you've got a wee bit of friction with the patient as to what dressings you've to use and not to use and</p> <p>I: Yeah that was always a kind of issue....if someone came home from hospital with a dressing from the acute formulary it would always cause problems, but would you say generally speaking it's a supportive service and you work well together andits helpful?</p> <p>B11: Mmm hmm. The only thing is sometimes if you want a wee bit of quick information you've got to go through the whole referral process and that can be a bit time consuming; even if you just want somebody to phone you; you've got to go through the whole referrals and its often late whereas sometimes it would be quite good I suppose everybody is busy but if you could just lift the phone and ask the question I: have an informal chat?</p> <p>B11: Mmm hmm.</p> <p>I: But it's kind of harder to do that now with the processes so that's</p>	<p>Importance of TVN role Importance of interpersonal communication with colleagues Issues between acute & primary care</p> <p>Distinction of community</p> <p>Organisational barriers Issues between acute & primary care</p> <p>Problems with TV referrals</p>
---	---	--

<p>TVN referral process is lengthy and time consuming</p> <p>Good TVN relationships</p>	<p>maybe more to do with the actual structure of the service rather than the person at the end of it type-thing?</p> <p>B11: But they've always been quite helpful when you contact them....they'll come out and see a patient if you're concerned or worried about them</p>	<p>Problems with TV referrals</p> <p>Good TV relationships</p>
<p>Time to read and access materials is a barrier</p>	<p>I: Ok and what about education wise? Do they provide any education for you?</p> <p>B11: Do you know sometimes I get emails and I just delete them...(laughs)</p>	<p>Time a barrier to wound management</p>
<p>Time and resources are barriers to accessing education</p>	<p>I: I'm glad you didn't delete mine (laughs)</p> <p>B11: There is a lot of education and we get emails for them but sometimes its juggling, if you can't get away from....like we're short staffed just now so trying to get away from work to anything is a bit of a nightmare to be honest...emm...</p>	<p>Resources a barrier to wound management</p>
<p>Time and role challenges are barriers</p>	<p>I: So, time is a bit of a barrier?</p> <p>B11: Mmm hmm. I think it's the same all the time....sometimes your fire-fighting a wee bit</p> <p>I: so, it might be that you're offered it but you don't know or don't manage to attend or whatever?</p>	<p>Time a barrier to wound management</p> <p>Variation of role a barrier to wound management</p>
<p>CPD education from TVN and reps</p>	<p>B11: I have attended ones in the past and they've been quite good but that was a few years ago, where the TVN was there and different kind of reps and things, they were always quite good sessions; I think there was somebody there talking about leg ulcers and dopplers and when they put on sessions they are quite good but they're usually all day so sometimes it's getting the time to attend</p>	<p>CPD comes from reps & TVN</p>
<p>Time to access education is a barrier</p>		<p>Time a barrier to wound management</p>

<p>Distinction of community Intuition has a role in wound management</p>	<p>I: Right, and do you think intuition has a role to play in your wound management practice? Would you ever say you use intuition as a nurse in wound management practice decision making?</p>	<p>Distinction of community Intuition important in wound management</p>
<p>Intuition is related to experience</p>	<p>B11: ..Probably because the more you work in the community especially the more you can second guess when you meet somebody like if they're just giving you lip service ... "uh huh, uh huh, I'll do that" sometimes you can tell like.....or if they're going to...maybe they've unravalled their bandages or they don't like it or something is not comfy you can tell with different people sometimes just through experience</p>	<p>Intuition important in wound management Intuition is linked to experience Wound management is individualised & contextualised</p>
<p>Person centredness in wound management Consideration of wound management practice</p>	<p>I: So, you can kind of pick up sometimes if people don't tell you or by their behaviours or....</p>	<p>Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors in wound management</p>
<p>Intuition is important in wound management Consideration of wider holistic factors in wound management</p>	<p>B11: I think you can pick up on a lot just by looking at a person's appearance to be honest; like they might have quite swollen legs for example and they're saying they go to sleep in their bed but every time you go in in the morning the bed is freshly made up and they don't have the capacity to make the bed if you know what I mean but the carers haven't been in yet; so you can pick up on a lot of wee subtle cues like they say they might want to cut back on their diet or something and they've got like biscuits and sweetie wrappers you pick on a lot of really subtle cues in a patient's house I think</p>	<p>Intuition is important in wound management Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors in wound management</p>
<p>Distinction of community</p>	<p>Wound management is individualised</p>	<p>Distinction of community Wound management is individualised & contextualised</p>
<p>Distinction of community</p>	<p>I: So, do you think it's quite distinct from working in a hospital in that way?</p>	<p>Distinction of community</p>
<p>Distinction of community</p>	<p>B11: Mmm hmm. Because when I moved into community I actually met some of the people from hospital; they were regular</p>	<p>Distinction of community</p>

<p>Consideration of wider holistic factors in wound management</p> <p>Patient compliance and priority can be a barrier</p> <p>Wound management is individualised</p> <p>Consideration of wider holistic factors in wound management</p> <p>Patient compliance can be a barrier</p>	<p>I: So, supply issues and access issues and time you mentioned is a really big one....and do you think the time, is there anything maybe in particular to the community nurse or the DN role that makes wound management a bit of a challenge or a problem?</p> <p>B11: Probably just like what I was talking about earlier....patients sometimes their wound is not their main priority or main focus. If they've got a chaotic lifestyle it could be alcohol it could be drugs is the main focus so you really need to work hard with these people you know "if you can just kinda knuckle down a wee bit we can get this healed; we wouldn't need to come back to you; you could do what you like" and obviously your young physically disabled people; if they've got other commitments, like children; social things that are quite big, they're not going to maybe go onto bed rest or if they've got leg ulcers....the patient is sometimes.....I don't mean the patient is a barrier-I don't mean that-sometimes their wounds are not the focus unless they've got them there not the main thing to get them healed</p> <p>I: So, your priority as a nurse might be different than theirs are; so, you might want to get it healed but for them other things are more important?</p> <p>B11: Mmm hmm.</p> <p>I: So patient priority? Anything else?</p> <p>B11: I can't think if anything else.</p> <p>I: That's fine, no worries. Ok how well organised do think wound management practice is in the wider sense? In the bigger</p>	<p>Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors in wound management</p> <p>People as barriers in wound management</p> <p>Wound management in individualised & contextualised</p> <p>Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors in wound management</p> <p>People as barriers in wound management</p>
--	--	--

<p>Wound management service delivery could be better</p> <p>Inappropriate referrals from GPNs, weekend referrals, non-housebound patients</p> <p>Little out of hours and housebound services</p> <p>Too many patients not enough resources</p> <p>Lack of service priority for wounds</p>	<p>sense; so, in the kind of service delivery sense? Do you think it's quite well organised? Do patients that live in different areas get the same access to service/ Do you think it's quite a well delivered type of service, compared to other ones maybe?</p> <p>B11: It probably could be better to be honest; like I think.....some of the PNs would refer wounds to us rather than them doing it themselves or maybe they're not educated and I think sometimes maybe if you've got a leg ulcer or something and you're workingem...treatment room is only open from 8-6 or whatever time sometimes that doesn't always suit somebody if they've got to get their bandages changed; it could be better.....probably.....especially if you're younger and you're mobile rather than the more housebound patients because obviously we would visit them....and theres no service at the weekend, see if you're in NHSXXXX; we've got no service at the health centre; if they made an appointment they'd have to wait until we go to their house so if they needed a visit on a Monday, they couldn't make planes, they'd need to wait because as nurse you've to prioritise.....obviously sometimes wounds don't really come to the top of the priority, just with the nature of things</p> <p>I: Yeah you might have palliative care...</p> <p>B11: Basically, yeah, they would come first</p> <p>I: So that's a really good example....so maybe for mobile patients and in the out of ours there could be better service delivery?</p>	<p>Organisational & service barriers</p> <p>Time is a barrier to wound management</p> <p>Organisational & service barriers-lack of priority</p>
---	---	---

<p>Patient self-management improves wound management Teaching carers improves wound management</p>	<p>B11: Mmm hmm. I think we felt that...if the patient can change their own dressing ...or a family member, we have showed family members...eh...how to change it, say they were going on holiday...like that or they've got a day out planned, we can come to compromises, we can be there at a certain time</p>	<p>Self-management improves wound management Teaching carers improves wound management People as barriers</p>
<p>Shortfalls in community service delivery Have to be flexible</p>	<p>I: Ok and you did mention and I know this having been a DN, sometimes theres not services for mobile patients and DNs have to pick up; when really your caseload should be the housebound ...so I suppose that could be a gap as well</p>	<p>Organisational & Service delivery as barriers Community Flexibility in DN role</p>
<p>Weekend and out of hours service shortfalls are a barrier</p>	<p>B11: Especially at the weekend if their people that need to be on then that....theres a shortage of....theres less staff plus you've got the added extras so the normal treatment room patients so sometimes that can be a wee bit of a bind; it shouldn't be should it?</p>	<p>Organisational & service Barriers community</p>
<p>TVN has most power in wound management</p>	<p>I: No, it shouldn't be. Emm. ok can you think of healthcare professionals in particular who maybe have more power than others in wound management? Or do you think...yeah....who do you think has the most power clinically in wound management?.....Again maybe it's not something that you've ever considered which is fine as well</p>	<p>Power of TVN</p>
<p>Power is related to knowledge and specialism</p>	<p>B11:.....Pause.....I suppose maybe the TVN , you would say maybe they've got the most power because that's their.....I don't know if you would call it power, maybe more knowledge and specialised training because that's what they do day in and day out so you would expect them to have to the most knowledge and be able to trust what they recommend</p>	<p>Power is knowledge</p>

<p>Vascular specialist has power but leads to restrictions between acute and community formularies</p>	<p>really.....and vascular...you've got your leg ulcers although we've had the same kind of friction with the vascular nurse and what he sometimes prescribes compared to what we can access on the community formulary</p> <p>I: Ok what about medical staff?</p> <p>Do you find that they're quite involved in wound management?</p>	<p>Power of TVN Power is knowledge</p> <p>Organisational & service as barriers-acute and primary care</p> <p>Organisational & service barriers-resources</p>
<p>Limits to supplies are barriers</p>	<p>B11:Not really....well....GPs for example usually just go....."emm....well we don't really...like they'll admit that they don't really know about wound managementlike that's what you're good at so we trust you in knowledge and we'll take on board anything that you say".....sometimes, we had a young boy recently that had...eh.....overgranulation of his.....thingme drain....(motions to chest area)</p>	<p>GPs not involved in Wound Management</p> <p>GPs don't have knowledge</p>
<p>Medical staff (GPs) not involved in wound management</p>	<p>I: Chest drain?</p>	<p>Consultants don't have knowledge</p>
<p>GPs don't have knowledge</p>	<p>B11: Chest drain! Sorry! Chest drain recently and we were putting a wee bit of hydrocortisone....well he was putting it on himself and we were just checking on it but the consultant up there thought it was a pustule and squeezed it....so sometimes people aren't as knowledgeable ascos the boy said.....he was saying....."he thought that was a pustule"....."well it's definitely not, it's over granulated-google it" so he did google it and he's like "you're right" but.....maybe the plastics people, they quite like you to follow their policies and protocols but I don't mind that because sometimes I think they know best with plastics and if there any grafts or anything they've got all the kind of latest information.</p>	<p>Specialist Consultants have knowledge</p>
<p>Consultants don't all have knowledge Sometimes you think they have more than they do</p>	<p>I: Chest drain?</p>	<p>Consultants don't have knowledge</p>
<p>Plastic surgeons and staff have specialist</p>	<p>B11: Chest drain! Sorry! Chest drain recently and we were putting a wee bit of hydrocortisone....well he was putting it on himself and we were just checking on it but the consultant up there thought it was a pustule and squeezed it....so sometimes people aren't as knowledgeable ascos the boy said.....he was saying....."he thought that was a pustule"....."well it's definitely not, it's over granulated-google it" so he did google it and he's like "you're right" but.....maybe the plastics people, they quite like you to follow their policies and protocols but I don't mind that because sometimes I think they know best with plastics and if there any grafts or anything they've got all the kind of latest information.</p>	<p>Specialist Consultants have knowledge</p>

<p>knowledge and power in wound management</p>	<p>I: Right, ok and what any sort of...your kind of already talked about this but what about any wider political or social factors that might impact on wound management? Do you think there is anything at <i>that</i> level that could be better or isn't working or is working really well? It's not just all about the negative</p>	<p>Formularies & protocols</p>
<p>National strategy and protocols influence wound management positively</p>	<p>B11: I think when the PU Safety Cross came in I think that was quite good...cos I think that made you think...just more about the wound and PUs and what's causing it; it's not just about the pressure, it's like diet fluids, incontinence so it made you look at the wider aspects that you maybe wouldn't have if that policy was in place so that was quite a good thing.....the only negative was that you had to complete it all and it could be quite time consuming and the paperwork that goes with it.....but...emmm.....I suppose everything needs to be audited to look at how things are going if its workingsocial aspects.....what do you mean by that?....like...</p>	<p>Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors in wound management</p> <p>Organisational & service barriers- time, admin</p>
<p>Consideration of wider holistic factors in nursing</p>	<p>I: Well, more like is there anything at kind of big level that filters down that makes the nurse's job in carrying out bed side care difficult? So is there any...you know it could be money....it could be policy....it could be...changes in policy all the time; just anything that impacts. So, something that might make you think "if this weren't happening it would be better because I could do a, b or c". Or, that was a really good one that you raised about pressure ulcers because it raised the profile and now, we're much more aware and we look to prevent rather than catch up, you know?</p>	
<p>Paperwork and time are barriers to wound management</p>		

<p>Restrictions on formulary can be positive and negative</p> <p>To many decisions can be negative in wound management</p> <p>Prescribing has improved my wound management knowledge</p>	<p>B11: I can't think of any social things that's made it worse; I don't think there are any restrictions on what we can do....maybe the formulary but I think they've cut the formulary to make it more streamlined...and that you've only got a few choices so that.....its easier and not harder and if you needed to use anything out with it you can; you've got a good reason</p> <p>I: Ok so do you think that that's quite a good thing then? That its maybe cut down some of the unnecessary decision making that you had to make?</p> <p>B11: I think soI think when you've got students as well and you're talking about xxx(name of dressing) , you should really break it down "well that's an alginate" like what they are rather than the brand namesI always show them the prescribing because I mean anyone can access it...and eh show them what everything is and it sometimes makes a wee bit more sense</p>	<p>Formulary & protocols</p> <p>Role variation as a barrier to wound management</p> <p>Prescribing has improved my wound management</p>
<p>Summary</p>	<p>I: Yeah I mean that's a perfectly good example of how its helped so that's exactly the kind of thing I'm looking for...ok we're nearly done; just a couple of wee summary questions; you've talked a lot about the different types of knowledge you bring to wound management practice; so, you talked about the protocols and evidence and you've talked about learning from colleagues and experiential learning in practice;...learning from....emm...like intuition...do you think it's hard to integrate all of that? How well integrated-do you think you're good at</p>	

<p>I integrate different types of knowledge in wound management</p> <p>They are all equally important</p> <p>Consideration of holistic factors in wound management</p> <p>My wound management is well integrated</p> <p>Wound management is individualised</p> <p>I integrate different types of knowledge in wound management</p> <p>They all have equal importance</p> <p>Experiential learning practice that improves over time</p>	<p>integrating all the different types of knowledge in wound management or is there any one in particular or is there any one in particular that is your first port of call? Do you know what I mean?</p> <p>B11:I think when you....meet a patient and you're looking.....say they've got a wound ...you know "what type of wound is it; how am I going to treat this wound; how often am I going to visit; what kind of products am I going to use?" I think whenlike I don't think any one takes overI think you're always thinking.....like.....you're going to assess it; you're going to think what kind of wound it is; you're going to think what kind of products are you going to put on and you're thinking ...you want it to be cost effective; you want to free up your time but you want to make the patient happy as well so it's a kind of balance...I think, you need them all, I don't think theres any one that's more important than others....maybe that's just my perception of it but I think you need them all equally and its developed over time cos when I think when I just started compared to where I am now I think you're practising and learning new things and getting better and learning new things</p> <p>I: So, would you say that's something that has improved? For you as a nurse, as you've gotten more experienced have you gotten better at integrating the knowledge you get from everywhere?</p> <p>B11: (Nods). And I think it's good to pass knowledge down to new starts as well; to encourage them to reflect and you get good at finding sources of knowledge and passing that back and how to print it off or emailing and</p>	<p>Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors in wound management</p> <p>I integrate different types of knowledge</p> <p>I integrate different types of knowledge</p> <p>Wound management is integrated & contextualised</p> <p>I integrate different types of wound management knowledge</p> <p>I integrate different types of wound management knowledge</p> <p>Experiential learning that improves over time</p> <p>Experiential learning that improves over time</p>
--	---	---

<p>Integration of different knowledge types improves over time and comes with experience</p> <p>Sharing knowledge and passing down to colleagues</p> <p>Experiential knowledge in practice</p>	<p>people go “could you email me that?” you’re emailing it and kind of sharing it as well</p> <p>I: Yep, so sharing knowledge? Yep that’s a really good one. And finally, then, what do you think would make wound management better? You could probably give me a long list but just give me one or two things that you think areif you could change or improve what do you think it needs to make it a bit better?</p> <p>B11: Probably a bit more....I don’t know about the pre-reg education</p>	<p>Interprofessional learning learning from colleagues in practice</p>
<p>Education would wound management practice</p>	<p>I: Just for you. I don’t mean necessarily for you personally but in your experience and in your clinical role?</p>	<p>More education required</p>
<p>More time wound improve wound management practice</p>	<p>B11: Probably more time to go to free up and get to these things, these days and get refreshed on new things.....emm....sometimes even just the time to look at a policy for 10 or 15 minutes....to read through it instead of skimming though it all the time...to really get in-depth knowledge and so that I can get to appointments that at the weekends...just the number of hours, so I can free up some hours and obviously to make it a better for the patients.....to make it better from their point of view</p>	<p>Time as a barrier to wound management</p>
<p>Time would improve wound management practice</p>	<p>I: so probably time then, would be the common thing there; but time to do more specific things; time to access education and CPD, time to read things properly and maybe time to spend with the patients as well</p>	<p>Time as a barrier to wound management</p>
<p>Time to study, read and spend with patient</p>	<p>I: Good, ok well that’s all that I want to ask; is there anything that you want to ask or say</p>	<p>Time as a barrier to wound management</p>
<p>More CPD would improve wound management practice</p>	<p>B11: Mmm hmm. Yep.</p>	<p>Education would improve wound management</p>

	<p>B11: I hope I've been helpful....(laughs)</p> <p>I: You've been very helpful, thank you very much; I'm going to end the interview now; and that is 51 minutes and 33 seconds. Thank you for coming</p>	
--	---	--

Appendix 15: Sample Individual Code Chart (Data Analysis) Specialist Nurse

Code Chart Participant S13

Generic	Empiric	Aesthetic	Ethical	Personal	Emancipatory	Summary	Most Prevalent	RICH
Experiential learning in practice that develops over time 1	Lack of high quality evidence in wound management 1	Dressing technique and utilisation of supplies 1	Protocol, formularies, tools & guidelines 7	Communication & Creativity in forming relationships (humour) 6	Barriers in Service Provision (availability of products) 6	My wound management knowledge is well integrated	Experiential learning in practice that develops over time 12	Empiric 1 Ethical 2 Emancipatory 1 Summary 1
Learning from colleagues in practice 1	Empiric evidence comes from companies 1	Creativity in wider activities (newsletter) 1	Ethical dilemmas between disciplines 2	Communication & creativity in forming relationships 7	Patients as Barriers 2	Integration of knowledge is linked to experience	Barriers in Service Provision 11	
Learning from formal evidence and literature 1	Bias of company information 1	Dressing technique and utilisation of supplies 2	Protocol, formularies, tools & guidelines 8	Wound management is individualised & contextualised 8	Barriers in Service Provision 7	My wound management knowledge is well integrated	Wound management is individualised & contextualised 11	
Wound management knowledge comes from a combination of sources 1	Bias of company information 2	Communication & Creativity in forming relationships 1	Do good not harm 1	Communication & Creativity in forming relationships 8	Time as a Barrier 5	Integration of knowledge is linked to experience	Communication & Creativity in forming relationships 11	
Importance of formal evidence 1	Nurses are autonomous company bias 1	People as barriers (other specialists) 1	No ethics-specific guidelines or protocols 1	Wound management is individualised & contextualised	People as barriers (other clinicians) 3	Educational barriers to wound management 5	Importance of Reflection 10	
	Lack of high quality evidence in	Communication & Creativity in forming relationships 2	Ethical dilemmas between disciplines 3		Medical Dominance (power) 4		Protocols, formularies,	

Experiential learning in practice that develops over time 2	wound management 2	management is individualised & contextualised (involving patient) 1	Experiential learning in practice that develops over time 10	9	People as barriers 4	Importance of structured education 3	guidelines & tools 9	
Importance of formal evidence 2	Important role of wound management industry 1	Communication & Creativity in forming relationships (humour) 3	Dominance of medical profession (power) 1	Professionalism 1	People as Barriers (general nurses interest) 5	Critical appraisal skills	Wound management needs better education at pre & post reg levels 7	
Learning from colleagues in practice 2	Experiential learning in practice that develops over time 7	Communication & Creativity in forming relationships (humour) 4	Ethical dilemmas between disciplines 4	Personal experience shapes wound management practice 1	Distinction of Community 3	Critical appraisal skills	Community nurses have more knowledge than acute 6	
Wound management knowledge comes from a combination of sources 2	Evidence comes from specialists 1	Wound management is individualised & contextualised 2	Ethical dilemmas between disciplines 5	Wound management is individualised & contextualised 10	Community Nurses have more knowledge than acute 4	Importance of reflection (structured) 3	Learning from colleagues in Practice 5	
Learning from colleagues in practice 3	Wound management is increasingly regulated 1	Dominance of medical profession (power) 2	Dominance of medical profession (power) 2	Communication & Creativity in forming relationships (empathy) 9	Specialists have power 2	Importance of reflection (with colleagues) 4	People as barriers 5	
Experiential learning in practice that develops over time 3	Important role of wound management industry 2	Protocol, formularies, tools & guidelines 9	Protocol, formularies, tools & guidelines 9	Consideration & Integration of wider holistic factors in wound management 1	Barriers in service provision (inconsistent service delivery) 8	Importance of reflection (structured) 5	Ethical dilemmas between disciplines 5	
	Formularies,	I bring my complete self to wound	Do good not harm 3	Wound management is	Community have more knowledge and acute	Importance of reflection (with colleagues) 6	Wound management is increasingly regulated 5	

Appendix 15: Sample Individual Code Chart (Data Analysis) Specialist Nurse, cont.

Importance of structured education 1	protocols, guidelines and tools 1	management 1	Dominance of medical profession (power) 3	individualised 7 contextualised 11	Community have more knowledge than acute 5	Importance of reflection (structured) 7	Time as a barrier 5	
Insufficient structured education in pre and post reg 1	Cost consideration strategic 1	I bring my complete self to wound management 2	No ethics specific guidelines 3	Personal experiences shape wound management 2	Barriers to service provision (lack of consistency) 9	Importance of reflection (good and bad) 8	Learning from formal evidence & literature (over time) 5	
I have sufficient education 1	Cost consideration strategic 2	Wound management is individualised & contextualised 3	Distinction of Community 2	Communication & Creativity in Forming Relationships 10	Barriers in service provision 10	Learning from colleagues in practice 5	Dominance of medical profession (power) 4	
Insufficient structured education in pre and post reg 2	Formularies, guidelines, tools and protocols (not utilised) 2	Time as a barrier (generalists) 3	Community Nurses have better knowledge than Acute 3	Professionalism 2	Resources as barriers 1	Importance of reflection (with colleagues) 9	Do good not harm 4	
Experiential learning in practice that develops over time (students) 4	Formularies, guidelines, tools and protocols (not utilised acute) 3	I bring my complete self to wound management 3	Organisation & Service Barriers (Inconsistency) 2	Barriers in Service Provision (specialist teams) 5	Barriers in service provision 11	Creativity in forming relationships	No ethics-specific guidance 3	
Insufficient structured education in pre & post reg	Community nurses have more wound management knowledge than acute 1	Time as a barrier (generalists) 4	Organisation & Service Barriers 3	People as barriers 2	Resources as barrier 2	Experiential learning in practice that develops over time 12	Importance of structured education 3	
		Creativity in forming relationships 5	Organisation & Service Barriers 4	Learning from colleagues in practice 4		Importance of reflection (unstructured)	I bring myself to wound management practice 3	
		Wound management is		Experiential learning in			Those with passion take on wound	

(assessment tools) 3	Formularies, guidelines tools and protocols 4	individualised & contextualised 4	TV Service Provision is equitable 1	practice that develops over time 11	10	management 3		
Experiential learning in practice that develops over time (students) 5	Community nurses have more wound management knowledge than acute 2	Distinction of community 1	Wound management is individualised & contextualised 6	Importance of Intuition 2	Wound management needs better structured education at pre & post reg levels 6	Distinction of community 3		
Experiential learning in practice that develops over time (students) 6	Service provision as a barrier (lack of TVNs in community) 1	Wound management is an art & a science 1	TV Service Provision is equitable 2	Intuition is linked to Experience 1	Wound management needs better education at pre & post reg levels 7	Importance of intuition 3		
Insufficient structured education in pre & post reg 4	Formularies, guidelines, tools and protocols (not utilised acute) 5	Science becomes more important as you become more knowledgeable 1	Do good not harm 4	Importance of Intuition 3		Resources as barriers 2		
	Experiential learning in practice that develops over time 8	Wound management is becoming more scientific over time 1	Wound management is individualised & contextualised 7	Intuition is linked to experience 2		Intuition is linked to experience 2		
	Importance	Wound management is both an art and a science 2	Wound management is increasingly regulated (industry) 2			Specialists have power 2		
						Wound management knowledge comes from a combination of sources 2		
						TV Service is equitable 2		
						Personal experiences shape wound management 2		

Appendix 15: Sample Individual Code Chart (Data Analysis) Specialist Nurse, cont.

<p>of TV Link Nurses 1</p> <p>Importance of TV Link Nurse 2</p> <p>Those with passion take on wound management 1</p> <p>Time as a barrier 1</p> <p>Formularies, guidelines, tools and protocols (not utilised acute) 6</p> <p>Those with a passion take on wound management 2</p> <p>Experiential learning in practice that develops</p>	<p>Wound management is individualised & contextualised 5</p> <p>Wound management has become more scientific over time 2</p> <p>Science becomes more important as you become more knowledgeable 2</p>	<p>Wound management is increasingly regulated (industry) 4</p> <p>Wound management is increasingly regulated 5</p>				<p>Professionalism 2</p> <p>Patients as barriers 2</p> <p>Importance of TVN Role 2</p> <p>Wound management is an art & a science 2</p> <p>Lack of high quality evidence in wound management 2</p> <p>Dressing technique & utilisation of supplies 2</p> <p>Bias of company information 2</p> <p>Importance of wound management industry 2</p>
--	--	--	--	--	--	---

<p>over time 9</p> <p>Those with passion take on wound management (CAs) 3</p>						<p>Cost consideration (strategic) 2</p> <p>Nurses are autonomous (companies) 1</p> <p>Creativity in other areas (newsletter) 1</p> <p>Evidence comes from specialists 1 Empiric evidence comes from companies 1</p> <p>Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors 1</p>
---	--	--	--	--	--	--

Appendix 16: Sample Individual Code Chart (Data Analysis) Generalist Nurse

Code Chart Participant G14

Generic	Empiric	Aesthetic	Ethical	Personal	Emancipatory	Summary	Most Prevalent	RICH
Experiential learning in practice that develops over time 1	Product evaluation has shaped my wound management. 1	Creative dressing use- Using practical tricks of the trade to creatively manage wounds 1	Being ethical is acting in line with guidelines and evidence, not going against this to ensure safety (do good not harm) 1	I have a natural ability and gift that I bring to wound management 1	People as barriers in wound management ritualistic practice 1	My wound management knowledge is well integrated and comes together at the bedside without conscious effort 1	Experiential learning that develops over time 18	General 3
Experiential learning in practice that develops over time-dressing and bandage techniques 2	I participated in product trial research. Working in a centre of excellence 2	Creative dressing use Using practical tricks of the trade to creatively manage wounds 2	Using knowledge to stand up for the patient Not bowing to pressure from others 1	I have a natural gift and ability that I bring to wound management 2	People as barriers in wound management-service organisation 2	My wound management knowledge is well integrated and comes together at the bedside without conscious effort 2	Learning from colleagues in practice 14	Empiric 2 Aesthetic 1 Ethical 2 Emancipatory 2 Summary 1
Experiential learning in practice that develops over time 3	Product evaluation has shaped my wound management. 3	Using practical tricks of the trade to creatively manage wounds 3	Promoting safety, doing the right thing 1	My natural gift is my authentic self 3	People as barriers in wound management ritualistic practice 3	My wound management knowledge is well integrated and comes together at the bedside without conscious effort 2	Insufficient knowledge and education in wound management 10	
Learning from colleagues in practice 1	I participated in product trial research. Working in a centre of excellence 4	Do good not harm 2	Teaching	Experiential learning that develops over time 14	People as barriers in wound management -cost cutting	My wound management knowledge is	People as a barrier to wound management-	

develops over time-working in centres of excellence 4	Product evaluation has shaped my wound management. 5	Invention 3	others to do the right thing-students 1	learning that develops over time-learning from mistakes (episodic learning) 15	4	well integrated and comes together at the bedside without conscious effort 3	ritualistic practice 8	
Experiential learning in practice that develops over time-working in centres of excellence 5	I participated in product trial research. Working in a centre of excellence 6	Wound management is both an art and a science 1	Not trusting everything industry says is ethical 1	I bring my wound management knowledge to other areas of life 1	People as barriers-using too many products 5	People as barriers-lack of knowledge 6	I participated in product trial research.8	
Learning from colleagues in practice 2	Product evaluation has shaped my wound management. 7	Aesthetics of applying dressings (bandages). Beauty in a bandage 1	We used to engage with industry but it was ethical and new product trial or teaching only 2	My personal passion leads wound management 4	People as barriers-lack of knowledge 6	Wound management is equitable 3	My gift is a visual understanding of wound management 7	
Experiential learning in practice that develops over time-working in centres of excellence 6	I participated in product trial research.8	Science is why you're using and beauty of a well applied bandage is art 2	Disengagement with industry 3	My personal passion leads my wound management-5	People as barriers to wound management-ritualistic practice 7	People as barriers to wound management-knowledge to advocate for right product for patient 2	My personal passion has driven my wound management 8	Industry have a role-introduction of new products Industry have a role 7
Experiential learning in practice that develops over time-working in centres of excellence 7	Working in a centre of excellence-learning about adverse	Wound management is both an art and a science 2	Gradual disengagement with industry 4	I take my wound management knowledge outside to other areas 2	I use my wound management knowledge to advocate for right product for patient 2	Cost as a barrier to	My personal passion drives my wound management 9	Insufficient wound management education in pre-reg 7
		Creativity in forming relationships-using it to	Industry have a role-				My personal passion drives my wound management 10	People as barriers-lack of knowledge 6

Appendix 16: Sample Individual Code Chart (Data Analysis) Generalist Nurse, cont.

Learning from colleagues in practice 3	effects 1 I worked in a centre of excellence 2	get patient buy in, negotiation 1	negotiation 6 Industry have a role- introduction of new products Industry have a role 7	My personal passion leads my wound management 6 I take my wound management knowledge outside to other areas 3	wound management 1 Policy and service organisation as a barrier to wound management (cost) 2	My personal passion has driven my wound management knowledge 11 Wound management knowledge and education is insufficient 8	TVNs have the most power in wound management 5 People as barriers-using too many products 5	
Learning from colleagues in practice (specialists) 4	Learning from study days and conferences (industry) 1	Creativity in forming relationships-using it to get buy in, negotiation 2	Wound management is ethical in community but not specialist clinics 1	Learning from colleagues in practice (students) 10	Service delivery ad a barrier to wound management (being told what to use-cost) 3	Wound management knowledge and education is insufficient 9	Service delivery as a barrier to wound management (being told what to do and being limited-cost) 4	
Learning from colleagues in practice (brainstorming sessions) 5	Learning from colleagues in practice (specialists) Working through competencies 10	Using creativity to get patient buy in- negotiation 3	Simple tried and tested products are the best not fads 1	My personal passion drives wound management 7	Service delivery as a barrier to wound management (being told what to do and being limited-cost) 4	Organisational barriers-service delivery and provision and access to education 1	Service delivery as a barrier to wound management (being told what to do and being limited-cost) 4	
Learning from colleagues in practice (new products, bag of tricks) 6	Learning from study days and conferences (industry) 2		Wound management is equitable because we had a systematic approach 2	Experiential learning that develops over time-product knowledge 16	Insufficient knowledge and education in wound		Intuition is important and	
Learning from colleagues in practice collaboration 7	Experiential learning that develops over time 10		Tried and tested products are	Experiential learning that develops over	People as a			
No structured education 1	Personal							
Experiential learning that develops over								

time 8	passion drives wound management 3		the best, not fad 3 Wound management is fair and equitable 3	time-product knowledge 17 Knowledge of different innovative products 1	barrier to wound management- ritualistic practice 8 Service delivery as a barrier to wound management (being told what to do and being limited-cost) 4	management 10	has shaped my knowledge and decision making 4 Individual and group reflection 4 Wound management is equitable 4 My wound management knowledge is well integrated and comes together at the bedside without conscious effort 3 Using practical tricks of the trade to creatively manage wounds Invention 3	
My personal passion in wound management drives my knowledge 1	Learning from CPD 1			Learning from colleagues in practice 11	TVNs have the most power in wound management 3			
Experiential learning that develops over time 9	Poor transfer of evidence to practice in DNs 1			Learning from colleagues in practice-good relationships with TVNs 12	TVNs have the most power in wound management 4			
Learning from colleagues in practice 8	Lack of wound management education in DNs 1			Intuition is important and linked to experience 1	TVNs have the most power in wound management 3			
My personal passion in wound management drives my knowledge 2	Lack of wound management education and product knowledge in DNs 2			Intuition is important and linked to experience 2	TVNs have the most power in wound management 4			
Linking theory to practice by reading following patients 1	Lack of wound management education and knowledge in			I have a gift in wound management that was not taught 4	Service delivery as a			
Learning from colleagues in								

Appendix 16: Sample Individual Code Chart (Data Analysis) Generalist Nurse, cont.

practice 9	DNs 3			Intuition is linked to experience and may be learned behaviour 3	barrier to wound management (being told what to do and being limited-cost) 5		Using creativity to get patient buy in- negotiation 3
Linking theory to practice by reading following patients 2	Wound management knowledge and education and training is insufficient for DNs 4			Group reflection increases knowledge 1	TVNs have the most power in wound management 5		Tried and tested products are the best, not fad 3
	Wound management knowledge and education and training is insufficient for DNs 5			Formal and informal reflection forms my knowledge 2	Nurses using products should have more say and power 1		I take my wound management knowledge outside to other areas 3
	Insufficient wound management education in pre-reg 6			Learning from colleagues in practice 13			Protocols formularies guidelines and tools 3
	Insufficient wound management education in pre-reg 7			Individual reflection shapes wound management practice 3			I worked in a centre of excellence 2
	Experiential			Individual and group reflection 4			DNs have no power in wound management

	learning that develops over time (product knowledge) 11			Experiential learning that develops over time 18			2
	Experiential learning that develops over time (product knowledge) 12			Learning from colleagues in practice 14			Linking theory to practice by reading following patients 2
	Protocols, guidelines tools and formularies 1			Subconscious learning when I'm not trying 1			Learning from study days and conferences (industry) 2
	National guidelines as a way to justify approach and stand up to pressure from consultants 2			I have a gift in wound management- not learned 5			Science is why you're using and beauty of a well applied bandage is art 2
	Original research 1			My gift is a visual understanding of wound management 6			Wound management is both an art and a science 2
	Protocols			My gift is a visual understanding of wound management 7			Do good not harm 2
							I use my wound

Appendix 16: Sample Individual Code Chart (Data Analysis) Generalist Nurse, cont.

	<p>formularies guidelines and tools 3</p> <p>Experiential learning that develops over time-dressing products 13</p> <p>Research is demonstrated by correct product use 1</p> <p>Research is demonstrated by correct product use 2</p>			<p>Intuition is important and has shaped my knowledge and decision making 4</p> <p>My personal passion has shaped my wound management 8</p>			<p>management knowledge to advocate for right product for patient 2</p> <p>National guidelines as a way to justify approach and stand up to pressure from consultants 2</p> <p>Research is demonstrated by correct product use 2</p> <p>Teaching others to do the right thing- students 1</p> <p>Learning from CPD 1</p> <p>Poor transfer of evidence to practice in DNs 1</p>	
--	---	--	--	---	--	--	--	--

							<p>Lack of wound management education in DNs 1</p> <p>Cost as a barrier to wound management 1</p> <p>Wound management is ethical in community but not specialist clinics 1</p> <p>Original research 1</p> <p>Organisational barriers- service delivery and provision and access to education 1</p> <p>Nurses using products</p>	
--	--	--	--	--	--	--	---	--

Appendix 16: Sample Individual Code Chart (Data Analysis) Generalist Nurse, cont.

							should have more say and power 1 Subconscious learning when I'm not trying 1 Knowledge of different innovative products 1	
--	--	--	--	--	--	--	---	--

Appendix 17: Collated Code Chart (Data Analysis) Specialist Nurses

First Coding Sweep All Participants TVNs

Generic	Empiric	Aesthetic	Ethical	Personal	Emancipatory	Summary	Most Prevalent	RICH
1.Wound Management Knowledge is tripartite (read, experience, peers) (1,2,3,4,5)	Use of intuition (1,2,3,5) Challenges in formal evidence base, range in quality (1,2,3,4,5)	Creativity in teaching & education (1,4) Creativity at bedside (1,5) Creativity and skill in dressing technique (2,3,5)	Do good not harm- empowerment, equity, accountability, information giving, cultural sensitivity, animal products, consent (1,2,3,4,5)	I bring my complete self to wound management (1,2,3,4,5) Genuine relationships with patients (3,4)	Personal control a barrier to wound management (1) Time as a barrier to wound management (1,2,3) Skills as a barrier (1)	More structured education at pre-reg and post reg is biggest needed change (1,2) My wound management knowledge is well integrated (2,3,4,5) Integration of knowledge is linked to experience (2,3,4,5)	Creativity in forming relationships (1,2,3,4) Experiential learning in practice that develops over time (2) Learning from colleagues in practice (3)	Ethical (1) Ethical (2,5) Empiric & Personal (3,5) Ethical & Emancipatory (4) No aesthetic
2.Ritualistic practice is prevalent (1,5)	Lack of high quality evidence (2)	Creative therapeutic approaches (3,4,5)	Ethical dilemmas between disciplines (2)	Importance of professionalism (2,3,4)	Political and organisational barriers (management, referral pathways) (1,4,5)	Integration happens at bedside-consideration of wider factors (5)	Wound management is individualised & contextualised (2,4)	
3.Importance of structured education (1,2,4,5)	Wound management evidence is overwhelming (too much) (3) TVNs choose	Aesthetic knowledge is a higher skill (3) Creativity in wider activities	Standing up to senior colleagues traditional power of medical profession (Individual clashes, not professional ones (3) Knowing one's own limitations (3) Collaboration with	Organisational & service barriers inconsistency in service, career structures management, TVNs not valued, support for education (2,3,4,5)		Barriers in service provision,	

(1,2,3,4,5)	a specialist interest area due to too much information (3) Forming new evidence and being innovative (3,4,5) Evidence isn't always empiric (1,3)	(newsletter) (2) Creativity in forming relationships - communication, humour, buy-in, empowerment rapport with others, personality (1,2,3,4,5)	surgeons) (1,2,3) Wound management service is equitable (1,5) Wound management service is not equitable (2,3,4)	colleagues (1,2,3,4,5) Trying not to dictate to other colleagues (1,2) Strong MDT/interprofessional Relationships - increases power, but unclear roles (1,3,4,5) Intuition is linked to experience (1,2,3,4,5) Unstructured reflection both individually and with colleagues (1,2,3,4,5)	Political and organisational barriers (teams) (1,5) Political and organisational barriers (models of service delivery- formularies, TVNs contracts, not valued) (1,2,3,5) Too many products overwhelming (3) Consideration of cost (5) Different areas have different barriers (3) Lack of resources (access to supplies as a barrier- protocols) (1,2,3,4) Loss of power of TVN role (1) TVN has power	Critical appraisal skills with formal education (2,4) Intuition is the integration of different knowledge types at subconscious level (3) More sophisticated diagnostic tools would improve wound management (3) Interprofessional collaboration would improve wound management (4)	continuity (2,5) Power of TVN role (1) Inter-professional collaboration would improve wound management (4) Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors (5) Protocols formularies & tools (5)	
5.Experiential learning in practice that develops over time (1,2,3,4,5)	Traditional hierarchies of evidence don't represent wound management (RCTs)too de-contextualised (1,3,4,5)	Creativity in relationships limited by time and fatigue (4) Poetic language in wound management (1)	Ethical use of resources (1,5) No ethics- specific protocol or guidance (1,2,3,4,5)	Referral & lack of role clarity, teams (5) Person centredness (5)				
6.Challenging knowledge comes with experience (1)	Scientific knowledge is important (4,5)	Wound management is becoming more scientific over	Adherence to policy guidelines & protocols					
7.Challenging knowledge comes with education (4)								
8.Learning from colleagues in practice (1,2,3,4,5)								
9.Role of TVN in education (1)								
10.Importan								

Appendix 17: Collated Code Chart (Data Analysis) Specialist Nurses, cont.

ce of formal evidence (2)	Multi-centre and case studies are useful (1,3,5)	time (2)	(3,4,5)		individual specialists, key figures) (1,2,3,5)	would improve wound management (5)		
11. Insufficient education at pre-reg (2,5)	Case studies are hard to analyse but useful for context (3)	Science becomes more important as you become more knowledgeable (2)	Ethical engagement & partnership with industry (1,2,3,4,5)		Specialist power through social media (3,4)			
12. Poor use of assessment tools (2,5)	Visual evidence is useful (3)	Wound management is both an art and a science (2,3,5)	Lack of ethical preparation at basic level (1)		People as barriers (4,5) management			
13. Range of clinical experience broadens knowledge (3)	CPD is challenging to access (barrier) (3,4)	Distinction of community (more knowledge) (2,4,5)	Power of TVN role (1)		Specialist/organisation group power (industry bias)(3,5)			
14. Seeking out knowledge oneself (3,4,5)	Evidence from companies is biased-need independent studies (1,2,4,5)	I am more scientific and logical (1,2,4,5)	Resources as barriers (supplies) (1)		Medics have power (1,2,3)			
15. Scientific knowledge comes from journals (3,4,5)	Nurses are autonomous with companies (2,5)	Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors in	Strategic cost considerations (1,2,5)		Increasing awareness of wound management nationally (3)			
16. Structure			Inappropriate resource use (1)					
			Wound industry is increasingly					

d education and experience are equally important (3)	Wound management is increasingly regulated (2,3,5)	wound management (1,2,3,4,5)	regulated- difficult to access (1,2,4,5)					
17. Changes in educational structure make knowledge difficult to evidence (3)	Evidence comes from specialists (2)	People as barriers-other specialists (2,5)	Important role of wound care industry (1,2,3,4,5)					
18. Tissue Viability has become a speciality over time (3)	People as barriers- patients, other specialists (1,2,3,5)	Creativity limited in e-technology (4)	Ethical practice in research (3,5)					
19. Comparing past knowledge with new evidence (4)	Money/funding as a barrier (1,2,3,5)	Aesthetically pleasing for patient (5)	Wound management is not valued as speciality (4)					
20. Formal education changes how you think (critical) (4)	Guidelines, protocols, formularies & tools, SIGN, NICE, formularies, tools, not utilised, overwhelming, should be	Creative cost consideration (5)	Nurses are autonomous (industry bias) (4,5)					

Appendix 17: Collated Code Chart (Data Analysis) Specialist Nurses, cont.

<p>21. Formal education gives respect (4)</p>	<p>embedded in education (1,2,3,5)</p>							
<p>22. Barriers in accessing formal education (4)</p>	<p>Guidelines, protocols, formularies & tools, SIGN, NICE, formularies, tools</p>							
<p>23. Personal passion & motivation drives wound management (4,5)</p>	<p>as in-depth as could be, importance of clinician involvement (3,4)</p>							
<p>24. My wound management knowledge is sufficient (4,5)</p>	<p>Guidelines, protocols, formularies & tools, SIGN, NICE, formularies, tools (widely used) (1,2,3,5)</p>							
	<p>Community nurses have more wound management</p>							

	<p>knowledge than acute (2)</p>							
	<p>Importance of TV Link role (2,5)</p>							
	<p>Those with a personal passion take on wound management (2,3,4,5)</p>							
	<p>Innovation in technology has improved wound management education (4)</p>							
	<p>Wound management is individualised & contextualised (4,5)</p>							

Appendix 18: Collated Code Chart (Data Analysis) Generalist Nurses

Initial Coding Sweep Group B DNs

Generic	Empiric	Aesthetic	Ethical	Personal	Emancipatory	Summary	Most Prevalent	RICH
<p>Experiential learning that develops over time (11,12,13,14,15)</p> <p>Learning from colleagues in practice (11,12,13,14,15)</p> <p>Knowing how to prioritise what needs to be done (assessment) (11,12)</p> <p>Wound management knowledge is 3-part (CPD, experience, colleagues-often from</p>	<p>Generic empiric knowledge wasn't always sufficient but I knew about specific things (11)</p> <p>Empiric evidence comes from companies (11,12,13,14,15)</p> <p>Empiric evidence comes from research (12,13,)</p> <p>Insufficient time & content from TVNs (11,15)</p> <p>Hard to access TVN education (time) (14,15)</p>	<p>Creativity & skill in dressing techniques- difficult to dress invention, practical tricks of trade, complexity (11,12,13,15)</p> <p>Creative therapeutic approaches (15)</p> <p>Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors (11,12,13,14,15)</p> <p>Patience with patients (11,13)</p> <p>Creativity in</p>	<p>Do good not harm-pain, information, unintentional, advocacy, documentation, safety, empowerment, education, doing the right thing, teaching others to do the right thing (11,12,13,14,15)</p> <p>Adherence to guidelines, not bowing to pressure from others (15)</p> <p>No specific ethical guidelines (11)</p>	<p>Personal dressing preference (11)</p> <p>Intuition is important (11,12,13,14,15)</p> <p>My natural gift is my authentic self and I bring it wound management (15)</p> <p>Intuition linked to experience (12,14,15)</p> <p>Intuition in considering wider factors (community) (13,14)</p>	<p>Time as a barrier to wound management practice (11,12,13,14,15)</p> <p>Formularies as barriers (12,13,14)</p> <p>Variation of DN role as a barrier to wound management practice (11,12,13)</p> <p>Change is DN role as a barrier (ANP) (11)</p> <p>Patients as barriers to</p>	<p>More Education from TVNs would improve wound management (11,14)</p> <p>Lengthy & problematic TV referral processes (11,13,14)</p> <p>Good relationships with TVNs (11,12,13,14,15)</p> <p>Integration of wound management knowledge is linked to experience (12,15)</p>	<p>Experiential learning that develops over time (11,15)</p> <p>Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors (11)</p> <p>Wound management is individualised & contextualised (12,13)</p> <p>Learning from colleagues in practice (12,13,15)</p> <p>Patients as</p>	<p>Generic (15)</p> <p>Emancipatory (11,12,15)</p> <p>Empiric (12,13,14,15)</p> <p>Aesthetic (13,15)</p> <p>Ethical (13,15)</p> <p>No personal</p>

<p>industry (11,12,13,14,15)</p> <p>Education comes from TVNs (CPD) (12,13,14,15)</p> <p>Importance Of TVN role (12,14,15)</p> <p>Reflection with peers (12,14,15)</p> <p>Insufficient education at pre-reg (12,13,14,15)</p> <p>Learning from reading research, literature (13,14,15)</p> <p>Ritualistic practice (13,14,15)</p> <p>Lack of audit of</p>	<p>Distinction of community issues- time competing tasks, consideration of holistic factors (11,12,13,14)</p> <p>Formularies, guidelines, tools & protocols (11,12,13,14,15)-useful, restrictive, barrier, cost, acute/pc, justify standing up to pressure from senior colleagues</p> <p>Consideration & integration of wider holistic factors in wound management (11,12,13,14,15)</p>	<p>developing relationships (communication, buy-in, giving time & continuity, challenging ritualistic practice, building trust, negotiation (11,12,13,14,15)</p> <p>Wound management is an art & a science (12,13,15)</p> <p>Wound management is a science (14)</p> <p>Science of tissue repair (12,13)</p> <p>Aesthetics of dressings (beauty in a bandage) (15)</p>	<p>Bias of company information, not trusting everything they say (11,12,13,14,15)</p> <p>Usefulness of company information- education, teaching, research, importance of role, innovation (11,12,13,14,15)</p> <p>Cost consideration (formulary use and prescribing) (11,13,14,15)</p> <p>Responsible use of resources (inappropriate use and spend)</p>	<p>Professionalism in wound management (12,13,14)</p> <p>I start off professional and let patient guide me (14)</p> <p>Individual unstructured reflection (11,13,14,15)</p> <p>Reflection with colleagues (12,13,14,15)</p> <p>My personal experience shapes wound management knowledge (11,12,13,14,15)</p> <p>I take wound management skills to other areas of life (15)</p>	<p>wound management compliance (12,13,14,15)</p> <p>Variation & inconsistency in practice a barrier to wound management (11,12,13,14,15)</p> <p>Those with personal passion shape wound management (11,12,15)</p> <p>Wound management is nurse led but informal (11,15)</p> <p>Pressure from senior colleagues traditional power of medical</p>	<p>Intuition & integration comes together at bedside subconsciously (15)</p> <p>Integration is consideration of wider and individual factors (13,15)</p> <p>My wound management knowledge is well integrated (13,15)</p> <p>Interprofessional learning (13,15)</p> <p>Intuition & experience dominate research evidence (14,15)</p> <p>My practice is not as up to date as it</p>	<p>barriers (non-adherence) (14)</p> <p>Challenging ritualistic practice (14)</p>
---	---	--	--	--	---	---	---

Appendix 18: Collated Code Chart (Data Analysis) Generalist Nurses, cont.

<p>wound management practice (14)</p> <p>Wound management could be more critical (14)</p> <p>You need both theory & practice to develop knowledge (15)</p>	<p>Limitation of product availability as barrier (11,13,15)</p> <p>Wound management is individualised & contextualised (11,12,13,14,15)</p> <p>Seeking out knowledge oneself (only if time) (14)(11,12,13,15)</p> <p>TV Link Nurses (11,14)</p> <p>Evidence comes indirectly from TVN (14,15)</p> <p>Product evaluation & working in a centre of excellence, correct product</p>		<p>(12,13,15)</p> <p>Resources are fairly distributed (14,15)</p> <p>Nurses are autonomous (company bias) (12,13,15)</p> <p>Restrictions in wound management industry role; disengagement with industry (11,12,14,15)</p> <p>Formulary a barrier to wound management (product access, difference in acute/pc) (12,13,14)</p> <p>If some patients get more it is only</p>	<p>Challenging ritualistic practice (14,15)</p> <p>I bring my true self to wound management practice (11,12,13,14,15)</p> <p>Importance of formal education (12,13,14,15)</p>	<p>profession (11,15)</p> <p>Organisational & service barriers- resources, service design & delivery, lack of priority, acute vs pc, time, access to dressings, cost, access to education (12,13,14,15)</p> <p>People as barriers (14,15) management, pressure from above, ritualistic practice, being told what to do</p> <p>TVN has most power (12,13,14,15)</p> <p>Industry has power</p>	<p>should be (14)</p> <p>Wound management knowledge & education is insufficient for DNs (15)</p> <p>Wound management education insufficient at pre-reg (15)</p> <p>DNs have no power in wound management (15)</p>		
--	--	--	--	---	--	---	--	--

	<p>use (15)</p> <p>Poor transfer of knowledge for DNs (15)</p> <p>Insufficient DN education & knowledge (15)</p>		<p>because of need, generally fair (12,13,14,15)</p> <p>Not ethical to engage with industry (14)</p> <p>More ethical with DNs than specialist clinics (15)</p> <p>Simple tried and tested products are best, not fads (14)</p>		<p>(market) (14)</p> <p>Self-management improves wound management (13)</p> <p>Teaching carers improves wound management (13)</p> <p>Wound management has a high profile in community (14)</p> <p>Wound management services are equitable (15)</p> <p>Clinical staff should be involved in steering groups (15)</p>			
--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

Appendix 19: Example Mind Map

Appendix 20: Braun and Clarke's (2006) 15-Point Checklist for Thematic Analysis

Process	No.	Criteria
Transcription	1	The data have been transcribed to an appropriate level of detail, and the transcripts have been checked against the tapes for 'accuracy'.
Coding	2	Each data item has been given equal attention in the coding process.
	3	Themes have not been generated from a few vivid examples (an anecdotal approach), but instead the coding process has been thorough, inclusive and comprehensive.
	4	All relevant extracts for all each theme have been collated.
	5	Themes have been checked against each other and back to the original data set.
	6	Themes are internally coherent, consistent, and distinctive.
Analysis	7	Data have been analysed - interpreted, made sense of - rather than just paraphrased or described.
	8	Analysis and data match each other - the extracts illustrate the analytic claims.
	9	Analysis tells a convincing and well-organised story about the data and topic.
	10	A good balance between analytic narrative and illustrative extracts is provided.
Overall	11	Enough time has been allocated to complete all phases of the analysis adequately, without rushing a phase or giving it a once-over-lightly.
Written report	12	The assumptions about, and specific approach to, thematic analysis are clearly explicated.
	13	There is a good fit between what you claim you do, and what you show you have done - i.e., described method and reported analysis are consistent.
	14	The language and concepts used in the report are consistent with the epistemological position of the analysis.
	15	The researcher is positioned as <i>active</i> in the research process; themes do not just 'emerge'.

Braun, V., Clarke, V. (2006) Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*. 3(6), pp. 77-101. Reprinted by permission of Informa UK Limited, trading as Taylor & Taylor & Francis Group, <http://www.tandfonline.com>

Appendix 21: Extracts from data- table of themes

Theme	Sub-theme	Verbatim Extract	Link to <i>Patterns of Knowing</i> and themes from literature
<p>1.The bigger picture; the smaller picture</p>	<p>Wound management knowledge comes from multiple sources</p> <p>Consideration & integration if wider holistic factors</p> <p>Wound management is individualised & contextualised</p> <p>Personal motivation and passion drives wound management</p>	<p>“It comes from clinical experience based on years of looking at wounds; literature....um courses I’ve done in the past and modules....and education I’ve had around it and post graduate and under graduate and I suppose comparing our more recent evidence with what we used to do xx years ago when I started. So, I suppose you draw on all these” (S11)</p> <p>“I would say the knowledge that I had came from a number of sources to begin with..emm, experience as I went through...emm, different people that we met along the way we had got some study days from... sort of tissue viability.....emm, also other nurses like in our area of practice also came with emm... different information, learn on new products that came in, so just like a build up over the years but I’d say more so just a building knowledge as I went through (pause)...over my years” (GP11)</p>	<p>Personal Emancipatory</p> <p><i>Application of clinical evidence to practice</i></p> <p><i>Links between knowledge and competence</i></p> <p><i>Clinical decision making</i></p> <p><i>Wound management education and training</i></p> <p><i>Industry in wound management</i></p>
<p>2.It all comes together at the bedside</p>	<p>Wound management knowledge is well integrated</p> <p>Intuition is integrated knowledge at subconscious level that develops with experience</p>	<p>“I would say they’re integrated yeah.....yeah. But I think as well I’ve had the advantage of working in the same speciality for a long time and that kind of makes you...that kind of makes it integrated and its quite good as well to sometimes step out of that and go and do something else but no I think...but I think in terms of the knowledge I would say...I feel its integrated” (S13)</p> <p>“I think sometimes.....(long pause).....I think I probably do , yeah. And that’s maybe not just intuition; that’s maybe based on experience orI mean I know they talk about this gut feeling that nurses get on other things; do they get that about wounds? I’m not sure but I would maybe look at a wound and say “Mmm I think that might.....we could leave that; I don’t</p>	<p>Integration of Patterns</p> <p>Empiric Aesthetic Ethical Personal Emancipatory</p> <p><i>Application of clinical evidence to practice</i></p>

		think its infected” but how do I know? I think maybe just based on experience more than intuition. I would say probably the intuition part or the experience part dominates more than the scientific part” (G13)	<p><i>Links between knowledge and competence</i></p> <p><i>Clinical decision making</i></p> <p><i>Wound management education and training</i></p> <p><i>Industry in wound management</i></p>
3.Show me the evidence	<p>Limitations and barriers to the formal evidence and education in wound management</p> <p>Guidelines, formularies, tools and protocols are a key source of evidence</p>	<p>“No, no, no. Pre-reg, I remember getting nothing on wound management products. I remember having maybe 2 hours in an afternoon on bandaging which would be k-lite and a bit of wool. Emm....I don’t even know if we had tissue viability, we probably did but I don’t remember that much about it in the pre-reg class so em...even if we did it wasn’t that effective, it wasn’t enough. You need more. More days, a week, you know, a module” (G14)</p> <p>“I use for skin tear guidelines we use for NHSXX; we use the pressure ulcer standards; we are using the SIGN Guidelines for our leg ulcer management if we have leg ulcers;.....yeah so we do use guidelines but do I use those for education? Probably”. (S12)</p>	<p>Empiric</p> <p>Ethical</p> <p>Emancipatory</p> <p><i>Application of clinical evidence to practice</i></p> <p><i>Links between knowledge and competence</i></p> <p><i>Clinical decision making</i></p> <p><i>Wound management education and training</i></p> <p><i>Industry in wound management</i></p>
4.Industry: a political football	Importance of industry role	“Right.....it’s a bit of a political football.....now.....it wasn’t so much before.....we couldn’t have functioned without the wound care	<p>Empiric</p> <p>Ethical</p> <p>Emancipatory</p>

	Ethical engagement with industry & potential for bias	<p>companies.....and the wound care companies couldn't have functioned without us" (SP11)</p> <p>"Emmm. no so much...we used to get...but they've stopped reps coming in and we used to get some of the knowledge from them and then I know they say it's a bit biased but some of the knowledge they had was quite good; you wouldn't always take it as first hand ; you'd go away and kind of analyse it because obviously you've got a bit of bias because they want to sell you their products....." (G11)</p>	<p><i>Industry in wound management</i></p> <p><i>Clinical decision making</i></p> <p><i>Application of clinical evidence to practice</i></p> <p><i>Wound management education and training</i></p>
5.Do good not harm	<p>Doing the right thing</p> <p>Sound ethical practice but not widely considered in theory.</p>	<p>"Yes. Doing the right thing or not doing any harm. And also helping them make the right decisions as well because they may actually choose not to go with what you have advised they may choose to take a risk in something and choose something that's actually it may do them good and it may not and I suppose it's giving them the ability to make that decision with the right level of information" (S14)</p> <p>"I think that's maybe just in your own nursing NMC guidance just to treat your patient...emmm...that way; just to always be competent in what you're doing that you can justify to somebody what you've done; why you've done it . But no, I wouldn't say that there's a specific ethical guideline for wound care. Or it probably doesn't really get talked about that much to be honest". (GP11)</p>	<p>Ethical</p> <p>Personal</p> <p>Emancipatory</p> <p><i>Application of clinical evidence to practice</i></p> <p><i>Links between knowledge and competence</i></p> <p><i>Clinical decision making</i></p> <p><i>Industry in wound management</i></p>
6.The power isn't ours	Barriers to wound management knowledge development	"I think wounds for a long time has been quite low profile and I think you know cancer and heart disease and all these things have been really up there but I think they've realise-especially chronic wounds, I think they've realised the impact that chronic wounds have on patients and life and budgets is huge. So, I think that's where work has come out of as well, prevention and leg ulcer work has come from that so I think it's good that it	<p>Emancipatory</p> <p>Empiric</p> <p><i>Specialist nurses (TVNs)</i></p>

	<p>Power in wound management</p>	<p>has been recognised and I hope that it does develop and they continue to do something about it. But yeah I think it has to be recognised at quite a high level for things to change and happen” (S14)</p> <p>“I think that maybe with working in the community its people at home and they’re in their own homes and I guess it’s the environment that they live in.....it could be....personal care; they might be struggling with that-perhaps you need to address that. It could just be that their living environment could be causing the wound not to heal in whatever way and it could be that their diet and nutrition and so on all their other environmental and social factors can contribute and that is a barrier and I guess that’s patient choice as well ...that if they choose not to continue with the treatment that you’re recommending, then that’s a barrier for consent, isn’t it?” (G12)</p>	<p><i>Generalist Nurses (DNs and CSNs)</i></p> <p><i>Clinical decision making</i></p> <p><i>Application of clinical evidence to practice</i></p> <p><i>Wound management education and training</i></p>
<p>7. I’m not that creative... but</p>	<p>Creative therapeutic approaches</p> <p>Creative interaction with others</p> <p>Thinking about the bigger picture</p>	<p>“I think we always refer to blue peter when do things like complex VAC dressings and you’re having to compromise in some of the really complex wounds or not even complex wounds but ones that are in a difficult body part or..or..whatever so I suppose I’m not a creative person in my normal life. Emmm...but certainly in terms of wound care I would say myself and my colleagues can be quite creative...at times when we have to be. And that can be a challenge so I mean it can be awkward to dress areas-VACs are the main ones I can think of, when you’ve got quite a complex VAC dressing and we often finish by saying we should get a blue peter badge (laugh)” (S13)</p> <p>“Using a completely inappropriate on-the-surface dressing and cutting it to what you need to do a heel, to do a hand, to do a finger, to do a sacrum, to do a groin. And cutting things to shape. Inventing dressings I guess. And using something square and making it octagonal, like origami. And showing other people and students how to do these things and going “oohhh.....just very simple things and being artistic that way. Using something to do that job and making it work, because sometimes that’s all you’ve got” (G14)</p>	<p>Aesthetic Personal</p> <p><i>Application of clinical evidence to practice</i></p> <p><i>Links between knowledge and competence</i></p> <p><i>Clinical decision making</i></p>

Appendix 22: Themes in the context of Chinn & Kramer's patterns of knowing

Theme	Links to Pattern(s) of Knowing	Nature of Pattern in context of wound management	Differences/Similarities between Specialists & Generalists
<p>1. The bigger picture; the smaller picture</p>	<p>Core: personal knowing Additional: emancipatory knowing</p>	<p>Personal knowing: wound management knowledge is individualised and contextualised and develops predominantly in the practice setting</p> <p>Emancipatory knowing: participants consider wider holistic factors in the development of wound management knowledge and these have a significant role in shaping it (overlaps with Theme 6)</p>	<p>Specialists and generalists working in community consider wider integration of holistic factors more explicitly than those in acute.</p> <p>Experiential knowledge was dominant for all participants but more notably so for generalists</p>
<p>2. It all comes together at the bedside</p>	<p>Integration of all patterns (rather than focus on single particular theme)</p> <p>empiric</p> <p>aesthetic</p>	<p>Integration of patterns of knowing in wound management is linked to experience and occurs at the bedside. Intuition is an advanced form of decision making that takes place at subconscious level and improves with experience</p>	<p>Little difference between specialists & generalists</p> <p>Can vary where it is applied</p>

	<p>ethical</p> <p>personal</p> <p>emancipatory</p>		
<p>3. Show me the evidence</p>	<p>Core: empiric knowing</p> <p>Additional: ethical knowing; emancipatory knowing</p>	<p>Empiric knowing: is highly valued but underdeveloped in wound management</p> <p>Ethical knowing: the empiric evidence base is highly influenced and shaped by the presence of industry which raises ethical concerns (overlaps with Theme 4 & Theme 5)</p> <p>Emancipatory knowing (specialists only): awareness that positivist types of evidence don't always align to wound management</p>	<p>Specialists are more critically appraising and dependent upon the empiric evidence base than generalists;</p> <p>Specialists considered the importance of innovation in wound management; generalists did not;</p> <p>Specialists feel educationally prepared to deliver wound management and generalists do not despite little difference in educational preparation (means experience is also key in specialist?)</p>
<p>4. Industry: a political football</p>	<p>Core: empiric knowing</p>	<p>Empiric knowing: the influential presence of industry in the formation of formal wound management knowledge</p>	<p>Specialists are permitted to engage more freely with industry than generalists</p> <p>Specialists have significantly more power in relation to engagement with industry</p>

	Additional: ethical knowing; emancipatory knowing	Ethical Knowing: the influence of industry in knowledge formation raises ethical concerns (overlaps with Theme 3 & Theme 5) Emancipatory knowing: (overlaps with Theme 6)	(gatekeeper to access to NHS) than generalists
5. Do good not harm	Core: ethical knowing Additional: personal knowing; emancipatory knowing	Ethical knowing: is highly developed and reflective of wider nursing practice but not unique to wound management. The only exception, is the dominant role of industry in the wound management context and enhanced considerations relating to this Personal knowing: ethical conduct draws on personal values Emancipatory knowing: ethical conduct draws on an understanding of wider holistic factors (overlaps with Theme 1)	Little overall difference between specialists & generalists except in relation to engagement with industry and formulary adherence
6. The power isn't ours	Core: emancipatory knowing	Emancipatory knowing: understanding that barriers to the development of wound management knowledge are linked to wider political, social and organisational	Time and DN role more of a barrier for generalists

	<p>Additional: empiric knowing</p>	<p>factors and often out with individual clinician control</p> <p>Empiric knowing: the most significant overarching barrier shaping wound management knowledge is limitation in empiric evidence base (overlaps with Theme 3)</p>	<p>Career trajectory and value of wound management as a specialty and specialist role barriers for specialists</p> <p>Industry is the major power differential between the two groups</p>
<p>7. I'm not that creative but....</p>	<p>Core: aesthetic knowing</p> <p>Additional: personal knowing</p>	<p>Aesthetic knowing: is clearly demonstrated but not as explicitly recognised or valued as other patterns in wound management</p> <p>Personal knowing: ability to consider and integrate individualised and wider holistic factors highlighted as a particular creative skill</p>	<p>Little difference between specialists & generalists</p> <p>Generalists and specialists working in a community role considered integration of holistic factors more explicitly than those based in the acute setting.</p>

Appendix 23: Dimensions for the development & utilisation of knowledge-examples from the context of wound management (adapted from Chinn & Kramer 2015)

	Dimension	Emancipatory	Ethics	Personal	Aesthetics	Empirics
Generation & development of knowledge	Critical questions	<p>Who benefits?</p> <p>What is wrong with this picture?</p> <p>What are the barriers to freedom?</p> <p>What changes are needed?</p> <p><i>“I think if you’ve got a rationale for that then there are no barriers in the sense of the management structure to say that you can’t do that. I think if you have a good rationale and evidence base for why you do something then no one else can really argue that point...because who</i></p>	<p>Is this right?</p> <p>Is this responsible?</p> <p><i>“That product was on contracts and everyone was putting complaints against it and it got back on there-how does that happen?”</i></p>	<p>Do I know what I do?</p> <p>Do I do what I know?</p> <p><i>“I have been fortunate in all the operations I’ve had...my wounds have always healed but I often think what would happened if I had a complication with that? How would I feel? You know, how would I feel if I was relying on a specialist?”</i></p>	<p>What does this mean?</p> <p>How is this significant?</p> <p><i>“I think you’ve got to build that relationship up where, if they’re going to do something and you’re thinking “why is that wound breaking down?” If they do something and you’re thinking “oh gosh, why did they do that?”</i></p>	<p>What is this?</p> <p>How does it work?</p> <p><i>“I’ll look to see “well what did they find? Was it statistically significant and what was the evidence around that? I may not understand the process but I’ll still look at the outcomes...”.</i></p>

		<i>is going to benefit? A patient"</i>				
	Creative processes	<p>Critiquing</p> <p>Imagining</p> <p><i>"So sometimes I think processes within health boards can stop staff from getting access to something but sometimes it's not picked up because if its only one person here and one person there; unless somebody links that up as being a multiple problem and actually the big issue is up here"</i></p>	<p>Clarifying</p> <p>Exploring</p> <p><i>"They're telling me its £(cost) per sachet of XXXX so I think they might try to be restrictive. This is local contract for NHSXXXX and its on contract. I'm not breaching contract., I might be incurring cost for them but am I convinced I am doing the best for the patient? Yeah I am"</i></p>	<p>Opening</p> <p>Centring</p> <p><i>"I think sometimes we don't actually listen to the patient; we think we listen to them but we think they don't tell the whole truth and I think that your experience whether they're from you or from family and friends they can shape how you respond and how you react and how you shape your practice and how you relate to people. Because I think you can actually come up with solutions because you can relate rather than "well you need to do it"</i></p>	<p>Envisioning</p> <p>Rehearsing</p> <p><i>"I think you need to establish, maybe what's important to them before you even try to look at the wound and how you're gonny heal it because you might have to come to some compromises; like, well, if you're not gonny go on bed rest if it's a pressure ulcer you might need to sit up for short periods of time, go back to bed but.....I think you build that up by not telling somebody what to do; it's like they understand what my feelings and thoughts and what I want my life to be then they'll take on board what you say""</i></p>	<p>Conceptualising</p> <p>Structuring</p> <p><i>"I remember I was reading the XXXX journal in the last few months and it was looking at pressures and tissues when you were sittingyou know masses of information. But you know at the end you're thinking what does this mean for me in practice? I think sometimes that's where the scientific stuff shows us the information but it doesn't....it isn't necessarily transferrable"</i></p>

Examination & improvement of knowledge	Formal expressions in wound management	Healthcare policy (i.e., person-centred care); equality of wound management service provision & resources; awareness of limitations & barriers; awareness of power of industry, management & specialists; awareness of challenges integral to TVN & DN roles;	NMC Code of Conduct; Health Board Code of Conduct for Engagement with Industry; National Guidelines (SIGN & NICE); wound-specific Guidelines (i.e., consensus documents; wound assessment charts); local guidelines (i.e., local formulary);	Knowing when to be professional; bringing oneself to practice; experiential learning that improves over time; learning from colleagues in practice; personal passion;	Creativity in relationships; creative dressing technique; consideration and integration of wider holistic factors; intuition & integration of patterns of knowing;	Research evidence; consensus documents; industry-supported research and education; guidelines, tools & formularies; formal education/CPD; evidence shared through others (i.e., specialists, link nurses);
	Authentication processes in wound management	Example of social equity (i.e., sustainability) <i>"I would like to say that in the area I work it is equitable; however, I think it's just human nature that some patients do get more than others in the sense that some have.....a big</i>	Example of dialogue Justification <i>"My job also came into being the budget holder for dressing clinic and every month they would come to me for the bill and go "explain that to me because that's a lot of money" and I would have to rationalise</i>	Example of reflection (individual & group reflection) <i>"The only structured approach (to reflection) I would say is if the team lead has made a point of organising a session, a teaching session of some kind; otherwise, it's through</i>	Example of inspiration <i>"I loved this attitude- you're so sly wound but so am I. And I'll use my bag of tricks to heal you.... you non-healing wound"</i>	Example of confirmation and validation of knowledge <i>"Probably the NICE Guidelines.....I would look online for any studies; if it was a particular surgical wound for example and I hadn't ...it wasn't</i>

		<p><i>pile of dressings, bandages.....that perhaps...I'm not saying that they don't need them....it's just that that cost for that person is required....whereas for someone else its perhaps...not required...you can make it more cost effective by using a lesser amount of product. So, I would like to say that I don't think there's any barriers to someone having a specific treatment, say for example, an expensive treatment like a xxxx; if that patient needs it I would like to say that they could definitely have it"</i></p>	<p><i>every product that I had used"</i></p>	<p><i>reflection and discussion with the team... if you've come across a wound that's not healing you would run it by your colleagues and discuss it to see if they see it improving or getting worse or perhaps draw on what they think has worked for them in the past for a similar type of wound"</i></p>		<p><i>healing, I'd be looking to see if there were any studies or research on what best would aid the healing in that; but probably I would think it would be the TVN, the nurse specialist that I would look towards"</i></p>
--	--	---	--	---	--	--

	<p>Integrated expressions in wound management practice</p>	<p>Example of praxis:</p> <p><i>"I think it had massive change in the last few years.....there is a loss of single-person practice and there are now teams and that has huge benefits....but I don't always see that the practice has improved or changed for the better for the patients.....the service may be very well organised; but if the patient is not on the receiving end of it, the benefit of having all these people attached to it.....I struggle. I think the less time spend in meetings and the more time doing your job, is better. And I think the more people you have the more</i></p>	<p>Example of moral and ethical comporment:</p> <p><i>"We had a situation recently where a surgeon wanted to use negative pressure on a wound that was actively bleeding which was of course against the clinical guidelines and they were quitethere were quite a few strong conversations between the surgical registrar and my colleagues and our stance was ...as nurses that we really have to follow the clinical guidelines and we don't really have the full anatomical knowledge that the surgical team had sowe.....weren't going to be re-applying the negative pressure for the right reasons. So that was quite a</i></p>	<p>Example of therapeutic use of the self:</p> <p><i>"I would say it was more of an interest and I think it was watching more DNs in placement healing people.... I think there's nothing like healing someone. And you know, us being involved in it; sometimes it's just so overwhelming for the patient that they actually cry. They're never been out of a bandage; they've never had a dressing and they've got a stocking on for the first time and they don't know what to do. And I just think it's just "wow". It was always just "wow" for me. And I had the knowledge and power to be able to do that</i></p>	<p>Example of transformative art/acts:</p> <p><i>"I suppose you gather a lot of information from even a patient's surroundings and how their lifestyle is... their wound healing maybe sometimes isn't their first focus; they could have children, their social life might be more important; so I think you need to establish, maybe what's important to them before you even try to look at the wound and how you're going to heal it because you might have to come to some compromises; like, well, if you're not going to go on bed rest if it's a PU you might need to sit up for short periods of time.....I think you build that up by not telling somebody what to do. It's like they</i></p>	<p>Example of scientific competence:</p> <p><i>"I think that me personally, there are some scientific papers and they're interesting to read but they're often brought to you by again, companies to support their products and that's fine.....its, difficult to .I think it's up to the individual how much they can understand the scientific stuff...but I think it is important to consider it, definitely. And wound management...we've spoken about that for years, there's not a huge amount of...sort of really solid evidence...a lot of it is...you know not.... RCTs and the big studies and things...."</i></p>
--	---	---	--	---	---	---

		<i>meetings you end up having and the less productive you tend to become"</i>	<i>difficult conversation but we do have an awareness of local protocols, guidelines."</i>	<i>and teach that to somebody...as time went on to teach that"</i>	<i>understand my feelings and thoughts and what I want my life to be, then they'll take on board what you say. It's not.... I don't think it's a simple thing, it's quite a complex thing actually...to come to an agreement with the patient"</i>	
--	--	---	--	--	--	--